

Andrew Robinson

**Opinion, Networks & Protest: The Emergence,
Mobilisation and Dynamics of Community Opposition to
the M77 Motorway**

**A thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the
requirements of the University of Paisley for the degree
of Doctor of Philosophy**

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Abstract

The 1990s witnessed the emergence of radical direct action against road-building. The anti-roads movement which developed at this time typically comprised two groups; the first are eco-warriors who are typically young and unemployed whilst the second are local groups and people who have often been involved in campaigning against the proposed road for many years. Media and academic analysis tends to focus only on the former group with little attention paid to the nature and dynamics of local opposition to these developments. This thesis aims to explore the emergence, mobilisation and dynamics of community opposition to the M77 motorway in Glasgow. The thesis explores concepts of public opinion and social movements and notes that notions of communication, leadership and networks are common across both theories. These concepts then form the basis for an analysis of the emergence, mobilisation and dynamics of the Corkerhill community and its opposition of the M77 motorway. Empirically the paper utilises the results of an opinion survey of 600 residents in three communities along the route of the M77 to explore notions of opinion leadership and networks of communication within the communities. Qualitative analysis of interviews with key actors and residents of Corkerhill allows an exploration of the processes of micro-mobilisation through examination of processes of 'framing'. The thesis concludes that a critical analysis of processes of communication can develop our understanding of how collective action of this nature emerges. Furthermore it indicates that theoretical concepts such as public opinion and social movements, previously considered as distinct, have common elements which, when brought together, can contribute to our knowledge of collective action.

Introduction

The 1990s witnessed the emergence of a new form of environmental protest in Britain. The nature of that protest was frequently radical and direct and the focus for these actions was the construction of new roads. The anti-roads movement developed in response to the Conservative government's 1989 paper *Roads to Prosperity* and the number of protests is testimony to the strength of the movement and its ability to unite disparate groups involved. These disparate groups characteristically fall into two categories. The first are Eco-warriors, who are typically young and unemployed and who have made a commitment towards pursuing a certain lifestyle, usually involving a rejection of materialism and industrialisation. Their ideology is concerned with protecting the environment and nature but also with attempting to redress the injustices of what they regard as an increasingly centralised undemocratic state. The second category of group involved is that of local groups who have campaigned against the road for many years without success. Academic and media analysis of this new form of protest has tended to concentrate only upon the first of these groups in an attempt to discover an explanation for the development of the anti-roads movement. Consequently there has been a paucity of research on the role played by local groups involved in anti-road protest, their association often being classified as a product of Not In My Backyard (NIMBY) parochialism.

Although the focus for the dissertation is collective-action against road-building, it is not uniquely an analysis of environmental protest. Environmental issues arise, as might be expected, but they do not dominate until the latter stages of the protest. Instead it seeks to analyse the nature of community protest and community concerns in protests of this type. A number of works emerged in the 70s that sought to explore the development of the anti-road protests which occurred at that time. These protests were largely community-led but the analysis tended to focus upon the planning procedures and barriers to participation faced by communities opposing road construction. Consequently, there was little exploration of the deeper motivations behind protests and the emergence and dynamics of these types of community opposition. In general

terms however there has been a great deal of work exploring community processes and community protest, much of it American (see Poplin 1979 for a review of theory and method) and this body of work offers insights into community conflict, action and leadership. Many of the themes discussed in these works, such as action and leadership, are explored in this dissertation. It does so by engaging with what at first may appear to be unrelated theoretical disciplines, namely public opinion and social movements.

Discussions of community protest tend not to discuss the process by which that protest emerges. This process must involve the shaping and formation of opinion such that people understand why they are protesting and what their goals are. As a result, it is necessary to understand this opinion shaping and mobilising process. Studies of social movements have recently begun to engage on some levels with this activity. It is rarely, however, referred to as 'opinion' formation. Instead social movement theorists refer to 'political consciousness' and discussions of opinion are often located within debates about mobilising collective identity.

It is within these contexts that this dissertation is presented. Firstly, it aims to more fully understand the role of community groups in protests of this nature. Secondly, it seeks to develop ideas of community action and leadership and lastly it attempts to explore the dual processes of opinion and movement mobilisation which these instances of collective action seem to display. This dissertation seeks to explore the emergence, mobilisation and dynamics of community opposition. It attempts to develop our understanding of the processes that lead to collective action of this nature and to explore the mechanisms and motivations which lead to community protest. It does so by examining a particular instance of community opposition to a contested development, namely the sustained opposition by the Glasgow community of Corkerhill against the construction of the M77 motorway.

The dissertation is comprised of six chapters collected into three parts. Part 1 is entitled Building Conceptual Bridges. Consisting only of Chapter 1 this sets out to develop the conceptual tools utilised later through a review of theoretical discussions of public opinion and social movements. As might be expected of concepts of such historical import, in both cases the literature is extensive and, as a result, any review could not hope to discuss every aspect. It is hoped, however, that by seeking to determine those features or ideas common to both concepts an original approach can be derived. The chapter begins by reviewing the concept of public opinion. It notes that the idea, whilst utilised extensively in contemporary societies, is still a contested area, despite the long history of writings on the topic. Notwithstanding this debate it is noted that two conceptual threads of public opinion have emerged from the numerous writings on the topic: an individual thread which stresses that public opinion is a collection of individual opinions and a collective thread which argues that public opinion emerges from collective processes and is indeed a collective phenomenon.

The chapter goes on to cover both notions by drawing on the works of enlightenment philosophers such as Hobbes, Locke, Rousseau, Bentham and Mill. This is followed by a discussion of the works of Tocqueville, Tonnies and Durkheim and leads into an engagement with the debate concerning the emergence of mass society which these writers sparked and later 20th century writers developed. Despite the emergence of the individualistic thread of public opinion to be found in these works, this section seeks to demonstrate that central to all of these theories was the idea of communication and that public opinion can be considered as a communication concept. This idea of public opinion as communication leads into a review of the idea of opinion leadership that emerged from the perception of media dominance of opinion formation in the 1940s. This covers the seminal work of Lazarsfeld, Berelson & Gaudet in the USA which suggested that opinion formation was often the result of 'opinion leaders' acting as intermediaries between media and people. A critique of this work is offered by an examination of Gitlin's *Media Sociology: The Dominant Paradigm* and later works which challenged the opinion

leader notion on both conceptual and methodological grounds. An exploration of the work of Weimann and his notion of 'influentials' follows. This seeks to update the opinion leader concept and introduces the idea of opinion 'influentials'. Three concepts emerge from this review of theories of public opinion. Firstly, that public opinion is essentially a communication process. Secondly, that leadership can play a crucial role in the formation and mobilisation of opinion. Thirdly, that communication often takes place within social networks of interaction within which leaders are centrally located. The chapter then goes on to cover theories of social movements and seeks to demonstrate that those concepts discussed above are also applicable.

The review of social movement theory covers the deprivation and mass society theories which emerged at the turn of the century. It goes on to discuss the work of Smelser (1962) with particular regard to his structural-strain theory as an explanation for the emergence of social movements and collective behaviour. This leads on to a discussion of Resource Mobilisation theory and in particular the work of Zald & McCarthy (1987). This is followed by a review of New Social Movement theory with particular attention given to European theorists in this field including Inglehart and Melucci. The chapter then seeks to identify the common ties amongst these different theories and it notes that, like public opinion, ideas of communication, leadership and networks are present throughout. The work of Gamson (1992) and the idea of collective action frames is introduced at this point in order to engage with a theoretical approach which seeks to explain movement mobilisation and introduce the reader to a crucial conceptual element explored at length later in the dissertation. Chapter 1 ends with a discussion of Habermas's (1962) writings on the emergence of a public sphere and Anderson's (1983) notion of 'Imagined Communities'. This serves to pull together some of the common elements of communication, leadership and networks developed throughout the chapter and offer useful insights into both concepts developed in later chapters.

Part 2 is entitled Historical Background and comprises chapters 2 & 3. These chapters establish both the general and specific historical framework of later analysis. Chapter 2 reviews the change in public opinion and the rise in public concern for the environment which has occurred in the post-war years. It offers evidence of changing public opinion and considers the works of Inglehart (1977) and Dalton (1988) as explanations for this change. A discussion of the historical development of the UK anti-road movement follows; this serves to make the connection between changing opinion and emergent social movements by considering a specific example of the latter. The growth of the anti-road movement is discussed alongside the development of road policy in Britain and it notes that protest has gradually expanded such that road protests in the 90s were as much protests against the prevailing social and economic systems as they were against particular road developments. Chapter 2 ends with a discussion of the potential for movements, like the anti-road movement, to have consciousness raising effects on those not directly involved. This is achieved through a critical engagement with the concept of NIMBYism and a theoretical analysis of writers such as Melucci and Habermas who contend that social movements have the potential to make connections between global and everyday issues.

Chapter 3 takes the discussion of anti-road protests developed in chapter 2 and narrows the focus. Concentrating initially on Glasgow's motorway plans the chapter then moves on to consider the M77 and introduces the three communities of Arden, Corkerhill and Thornliebank examined in detail later. There then follows an extensive review of the history of Corkerhill's opposition to the M77. This review sets the scene for later discussions and introduces some of the key events and issues which emerged from Corkerhill's opposition. It ends by raising a number of pertinent questions regarding protest of this nature. These are questions which later chapters will take up and seek to answer.

Part 3, entitled 'Opinion Mobilisation and Movement Dynamics' comprising chapter 4-6, begins to engage with and utilise the conceptual tools developed earlier. It does so through

analysis of the development of Corkerhill's protest against the M77. Chapter 4 empirically examines the shaping and mobilising of opinion which occurred within the community, noting the crucial role of 'opinion leaders' or 'influentials' in this process. It further notes the presence of social networks of communication and through comparison with other communities suggests that they were crucial for the emergence of sustained protest. Chapter 5 explores the interpretative and motivational factors influencing protest development. Here, extensive use is made of Gamson's concept of framing and collective action frames introduced in Chapter 1. The chapter demonstrates the importance of critically reflecting on these processes and the potential for such an approach to offer insights into protest mobilisation that others may not. Chapter 6 studies the dynamics of Corkerhill's protest. This chapter builds on the analysis of NIMBYism and social movement consciousness raising potential established in chapter 3 by exploring the consequences of the interaction between local protestor and Eco-warrior which occurred at the M77. The chapter notes that perceptions of identity can alter as a result of a re-evaluation of what is under threat and who is the enemy.

The conceptual and methodological focus for the thesis altered during the course of the study. This alteration was the result of a period of reflection and review by the author during the course of the research, following the realisation that the original approach would not enable the thesis to achieve its objectives of more fully understanding the nature of public protest against environmentally sensitive developments. This alteration resulted in a simultaneous narrowing and broadening of focus. The focus narrowed in the sense that one community was explored in detail rather than the three originally covered. It also broadened conceptually as a result of the fact that the original theoretical focus on public opinion was too narrow to offer a sufficient conceptual framework for analysis of the M77 protest. As a result, the study broadened to draw upon theories of collective action and social movements, which ultimately led to the development of a synthesis of public opinion and social movement theory being utilised as the main conceptual basis.

It is also worth noting that the process of writing the thesis and attempting to operationalise some of the concepts which emerged led to a review of their use. Concepts which may seem useful initially often do not integrate well within a broader thesis. This was indeed the case here. Concepts which were developed to explain the communicative nature of the three communities under examination led to them being classified as either 'media-dependent' or 'discursive'. These initially seem to be useful explanatory tools for assessing communication within areas. However, once in use it becomes clear that the classifications were used in too rigid a manner, leaving little room for specific explanation. The process of writing, reviewing, and re-writing the thesis however does lead to a review of their use and focuses attention on exploring the reasons why, for particular issues, communities appear to have different communicative responses. I am indebted to those who reviewed the thesis for their comments in this area.

A final point; as someone who was involved in the protest against the M77, albeit in a quite limited and temporary manner, there is also a personal motivation in seeking to understand the events and issues surrounding it. It is hoped that this analysis will not only shed light on the processes discussed above but will also prove useful in wider debates about the nature, emergence and life of community opposition.

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Part 1: Building Conceptual Bridges

Chapter One

Public Opinion and Social Movements: Enduring Features and Common Ground

Introduction

Perhaps because they are rooted in different branches of academic research the study of public opinion and social movements may not initially appear linked. Research into public opinion is typically an aspect of political science whilst examination of social movements is more usually a branch of sociology. Examination and analysis of the central premises and writings in each area does however highlight similarities. Arguably, the central premise of both theories is communication, respectively what influences public opinion, and how are grass-roots social movements mobilised? Communication is the link.

A number of theories have arisen that endeavour to account for collective action. Most of these seek to explain those activities undertaken by groups or movements in protest to or opposition against some form of societal institution or policy. Thus, for example, theorists have sought to explain the rise and development of trade unions and the labour movement and in post-war years the emergence of movements around such issues as civil rights and environmentalism. Those explanations for the emergence and development of these movements have given rise to a specific theoretical field, that of 'social movement theory'.

Studies of social movement behaviour adopt an approach to analysing collective action which, almost exclusively, focuses on the end result and not the process that leads to that. In other words, the act of protesting rather than the process which lies behind that act. Some theorists do discuss processes of movement mobilisation but do not actually go into detail about what that process of mobilisation entails. They argue for instance that movement leaders mobilise groups of people to engage in collective action, but do not explain how movement leaders do this. It conjures up an image of disparate people undertaking activities but not really understanding why they are doing so. The notion of mobilising action implies that action wells up spontaneously without thought or consideration of the reasons for doing so. I would argue however that this is not *collective* action - not in the sense that collective implies co-operation, unity and solidarity. For action to be truly collective it could be argued that it must emerge from collective processes of debate, consideration, argument and co-operation. People must know why they are engaging in a particular activity and they must understand the collective nature of

the action and the need for a collective response. In other words for collective action to emerge collective opinion must be mobilised.

Recently theorists have begun to incorporate some elements of this process within discussions of social movement development. Eyerman and Jamison (1991), for example, talk of movements mobilising the 'collective will' of their members, of them being involved in a process of knowledge production. Others such as Melucci (1996) talk of movements seeking to build a collective identity. Yet these processes of mobilisation and development missing from social movement theory are remarkably similar to those discussed by theorists investigating public opinion processes and it is possible to argue that an exploration of public opinion theory offers insight into those elements absent from sociological explanations of collective action. Namely for the end result to emerge opinion must be shaped, altered, influenced or mobilised. I use the term mobilised in this sense to refer to opinion being organised and prepared, made ready for action.

Studies of public opinion seek to examine, in many respects, similar dynamics to those of social movement theory - namely the development of public opinion, its mobilisation and the role it plays in society and politics. However, in much the same way that social movement theory tends to focus on the end result of collective action, investigations into the role of public opinion are inclined to examine it in relatively narrow terms. It is often assumed that altering or influencing public opinion is an end in itself and that once we have discovered what public opinion about a particular issue is, then we can stop analysing it. If changing public opinion is regarded as a means rather than an end, it is more often than not a means of influencing only one thing - voting behaviour. This is the result of the dominance of polling as a measurement of opinion. This connection between polling and voting inevitably results in an assumption that public opinion is concerned with a very narrow spectrum of political issues, in particular voting and voting behaviour. Studies of public opinion rarely examine other results of changing opinion, for example forms of collective behaviour such as protest groups and social movements. If studies of public opinion do consider these outcomes they are usually considered as being indicators of changing opinion and evidence that people's attitudes are altering. As such the actual end result, protest, is rarely examined in any detail.

Public opinion theory does explore those methods of opinion mobilisation which lead to the development of social movements and collective action. If processes of movement mobilisation initially involve some form of opinion mobilisation then to analyse collective behaviour adequately it is necessary to examine both of these components. It is necessary to examine the process of opinion mobilisation in terms of how it is altered and by whom. To do so

requires examining protest in light of theories of public opinion and social movements, concepts that initially appear disconnected.

The goal of this work is to demonstrate that a merger of public opinion and social movement theory can provide a holistic analysis of the emergence and development of collective action. It hopes to show that those aspects missing from social movement theory can be taken from public opinion theory and incorporated and utilised to present a new and distinct approach to explaining instances of collective action. At the beginning of the chapter I noted that concepts of public opinion and social movements share a common defining link: communication. It is possible to argue that both could be considered as communication concepts and that the central premise of both is communication. Furthermore, lesser, but nevertheless important, concepts also link the two areas: networks and leaders. In the following sections I aim to discuss the concepts of public opinion and social movements. By examining different theoretical approaches to each and, in the case of public opinion, the historical development of the concept, I hope to demonstrate how these three ideas of communication, networks, and leadership resonate throughout discussions of each. The first section will examine the concept of public opinion.

What is Public Opinion?

The first dilemma faced when examining the concept of public opinion is what is it? What kind of animal are we looking for in the jungle of political theories? Here perhaps we encounter the most enduring problem regarding public opinion. According to Berelson & Janowitz (1950, p.1); "There is no generally accepted theory of public opinion, nor even a generally recognised attempt at the formulation of such a theory."

A number of writers have tried to outline and classify the nature of public opinion and the role it plays in modern society and yet a conclusive definition still proves elusive. Consequently, rendering a precise meaning is problematic. In addition many common-sense meanings have developed which typically describe it as 'the will of the people, 'the majority opinion' or 'what the public wants'.

Notwithstanding these difficulties, it is possible to argue that two broad conceptual threads of public opinion have developed. These are, an individual thread, which suggests that public opinion can be considered as the aggregation of individual opinion, and a collective thread which contends that public opinion is a collective phenomenon emergent from collective

processes of debate. These threads have emerged as a consequence of the historical development and use of the term. Nevertheless throughout the history of discussions on public opinion a certain enduring feature occurs, namely, the close connection of public opinion to processes of discussion and debate. Consequently, I wish to argue that it is possible to consider public opinion as a collective communication concept. Here public opinion is viewed as emergent from collective processes of discussion and debate. This section seeks to examine this view. It begins with an examination of the work of enlightenment writers and their use of the term 'public opinion' and subsequently outlines the historical development of this notion through the work of Tocqueville, Tonnies and Durkheim. It will then examine later twentieth century writings on the concept which emphasise the importance of discussion and debate as their central feature. A discussion of the idea of differing publics will be used as a comparison of the ideas of mass society discussed in the earlier model. This will lead to an analysis of models which seek to explain the dynamics of opinion flow, and the importance of interpersonal communication for the development of public opinion.

Public Opinion as Communication

Initial formulations: The Enlightenment, Locke, Bentham, Rousseau and Mill

The notion of public opinion first emerges in the works of political philosophers writing at the time of the enlightenment. John Locke proposed the view that men judge their action in terms of three laws: divine law, civil law and the law of opinion or reputation. To the third Locke ascribed the greatest significance. He suggested that men seldom concern themselves with the penalties for breaking divine law and believe in impunity for breaking civil law. He states however;

nobody that has the least thought or sense of a man about him can live in society under the constant dislike and ill opinion of his familiars and those he converses with. This is a burden too heavy for human sufferance. (1924, p.203)

Thus, public opinion is a force and influence upon individual behaviour, an instrument of social control but not necessarily government control.

The first writer attributed with making the link between public opinion and government action and public affairs is Rousseau who first uses the term *public opinion* in 1750 in his *Discourse on the Arts and Sciences* when he declared that the growth of writers and pamphleteers questioning traditional beliefs and morals were 'the enemies of public opinion' (1973, p17). It is not clear in this however that he is referring to collective deliberation outwith government to which governments must take heed. It is in his notion of the 'general will' that the

concept of public opinion, as we understand it today, is first expressed. Rousseau is considered the first to synthesise notions of *opinion* and *public* into the idea of *public opinion*.

Etymologically the term is derived from the Latin *publicus*, which has its roots in the Old Latin *poplicus* or *populus*, meaning people. Usage of the term 'public' began to emerge in the 1600s and by the 1800s it was established as the common spelling. Initially the term was a reference to common access or open to general observation and only later came to be synonymous as referring to 'of the people' and matters of common concern, in particular to matters of state. *Opinion* also has its roots in Latin, the term being a derivation of *opinionem*, related to *opinari*, to think or judge. The term was used in this manner, in old French, before the 1300s, in reference to what one thinks or feels. Later use focused upon opinion being used to distinguish that which is known from that which is unsure and was typically used disparagingly as 'common opinion' or 'vulgar opinion' meaning the opinion of the mob. (Habermas, 1962: Price, 1992)

Rousseau is credited with combining the two terms *opinion* and *public*, or *l'opinion publique*, within his famous concept of the general will. (Nolle-Neumann, 1984) According to Rousseau, the general will is not the same as the will of all or the will of the majority, nor is it expressed through voting in elections. Only when the individual ceases to follow personal desires and subjects themselves to a general law is a decision considered to reflect the general will. (Park, 1995) Rousseau contended that majority will is comprised of the sum of the particular will of individuals and reflects private interest. He argues however that the general will transcends private interests and is concerned only with the common good. Furthermore society exists as a collective and is more than merely the aggregation of individuals. (Halebsky, 1976) Significantly, for Rousseau, the general will arises through participation and public debate and it alone can direct the state for the common good. Opinion has a legislative function as well as a control function, for Rousseau envisaged a form of direct democracy where the people gather in public places to voice their views. Government is established as an agent to bind together public opinion and put it to work under the direction of the general will. Thus, for Rousseau, public opinion is both a collective and a communication concept. Collective in that it transcends individual desires and communicative in that it is formed from processes of public discussion and debate.

By the end of the eighteenth century this view of public opinion as some sort of common or general will dominates approaches to the concept. Later eighteenth century writers attempted to move the discussion of public opinion on to new ground, in particular how public opinion influenced government action. (Price, 1992) Whilst Rousseau had argued that public opinion

was essentially communicative in nature it was still unclear at this time how opinion was communicated to government. Attempts to clarify this process were made by firstly Bentham and later Mill.

Bentham provides the first detailed analysis of public opinion in English. Initially he described it as an instrument of social control, whilst his later writings view it as a means of securing democratic control over government. Bentham's writings are heavily based upon his utilitarian view of human nature. That is; 'humans act to satisfy desire and avoid pain'. (Held, 1987, p.66) Society therefore consists of individuals seeking to maximise their utility and consequently individual interests often conflict with each other. In his early works Bentham was heavily influenced by the seventeenth century writings of John Locke, in particular by Locke's assertion, discussed above, that public opinion is a means of social control. Bentham also utilises the phrase in this manner, identifying four sanctions upon individual behaviour: the physical; the political; the moral or popular and the religious. It is the third, the moral or popular sanction, which is most closely related to public opinion. Indeed Bentham refers to it as 'the sanction of public opinion'. (Palmer, 1950) The notion of a critical public opinion as a means of control also arises from the need to control those who are elected to govern for they also act to maximise their individual utility. Therefore government must be directly accountable to the electorate to ensure that abuse of power does not occur. A mechanism is required to reconcile the competing wants of individuals. This mechanism is majority rule as determined by regular election. In this way Bentham linked the concept of the individual with that of wider society and in this respect public opinion is determined within a majoritarian framework whereby the aggregation of individual wills into a majority replaces notions of a common or general interest which exists independent from individuals. (Price, 1992)

In this sense therefore Bentham's work appears to be distinct from the definitions of public opinion outlined by writers such as Rousseau. In this respect public opinion appears to be moving from a collective concept to an individual concept where public opinion is not the outcome of collective debate but is instead the aggregation of individual opinions apparently formed in isolation. Despite this apparent shift in conceptual focus, Bentham does propose that discussion and debate do have a role to play. He outlined the link between public opinion and knowledge of government action through the workings of a free press. This would ensure the 'tribunal of public opinion' would prevent corruption for;

the greater the number of temptations to which the exercise of political power was exposed..the more it needed a permanent control by public opinion. (Bentham, 1816; in Habermas, 1962, p. 100)

This opinion, whilst it could sometimes make errors, was ultimately incorruptible because it was comprised of the wisdom and judgement of the entire nation. Furthermore, if this tribunal was to be effective information was required. Thus a free press would ensure publicity of government action and a reasoned public debate.

In similar vein J.S. Mill emphasises the importance of communication and debate if society is to progress. In his most famous work *On Liberty* he is concerned to protect the individual from what he referred to as the 'sanction of public opinion' arguing that free and open communication of new ideas is essential for society to progress. It is, however, in his lesser-known work *Representative Government* that Mill seeks to make connections between public opinion and government in much the same way that Bentham does. Mill stresses the importance of public opinion in guaranteeing the workability and success of government; in other words in order that government does not become subject to powerful groups in societies (ruling classes) it must strive to ensure that it is based on a genuinely all encompassing public opinion. This safeguard is established through universal suffrage and a balanced electoral system based on proportional representation. This, Mill argued, would ensure that no one group in society would be able to effectively dominate and government and policy would emerge from a process of discussion between majorities and minorities ensuring government rests upon a particular type of public opinion, one which emerges from debate. So once again the importance of communication, debate and the transfer of information are crucial to the development of public opinion. Indeed in the works of Rousseau, Bentham and Mill we can see that communication is a central component in each account of the development of public opinion. This central importance of communication, of conversation discussion and debate, as a defining characteristic of public opinion is a notion that is returned to in twentieth century writings.

Following these works Price (1992) notes that late nineteenth and early twentieth century works on public opinion tended to be sociological rather than philosophical in nature. This reflected two things: firstly, the rise of the new 'social' sciences and the subsequent empirical analysis of societal processes in particular the growth of opinion polling; secondly, the awareness of the changing nature of society at that time, a society which increasingly came to be referred to as 'mass society'. The concept of mass society has its roots in the works of Tocqueville.

Mass Society: Tocqueville, Tonnies, and Durkheim

In his work *Democracy in America*, De Tocqueville offers a critique of the majoritarian views of public opinion and democracy as espoused by Bentham. For Tocqueville equality and

democracy have combined to create a society where traditional authority and hereditary principles no longer govern, instead the opinion of the majority dominates. He states;

At periods of equality men have no faith in one another, by reason of their common resemblance, but this very resemblance gives them almost unbounded confidence in the judgement of the public; for it would seem probable that, as they are all endowed with equal means of judging, the greater truth should go with the greater number. (1948, p.10)

In line with Bentham Tocqueville proposed that the mechanism of majority rule would dominate and that individuals would follow their own will and desires when deciding upon which actions to pursue, although this is the result of increased equality and independence. He warned that in a society of equals the opinions of individuals in the minority would be overlooked and important viewpoints disregarded. For Tocqueville then public opinion became not a force for liberation in the way Bentham foresaw it but instead almost an oppressive force whereby the opinion of minorities were subjugated to what Price (1992) refers to as 'the lowest common-denominator' of opinion, in other words the tyranny of the majority.

Published in 1887 Ferdinand Tönnies' examination of the changing nature of 19th century society *Gemeinschaft und Gesellschaft* (Community and Association) echoed many of the themes covered by Tocqueville fifty years earlier. Tönnies' aim was to explore the extent to which the modernisation and urbanisation of society at that time was leading to a steady loss of *Gemeinschaft* (community). For Tönnies traditional pre-industrial societies were founded on a series of strong bonds and relationships between individuals. Typically these bonds are based on ties of kinship, neighbourhood and community. In terms of work, ties of common need united people and in small-scale agrarian communities, fostering collective values and sentiments. These bonds are both natural and organic for Tönnies, stemming from tradition and experience and as such a strong sense of social solidarity develops amongst these smaller communities.

The main thrust of Tönnies' work however is to show how *Gemeinschaft* was slowly being replaced by *Gesellschaft* (Association). Tönnies argued that increasing urbanisation and industrialisation brought on by the Industrial Revolution eroded the social solidarity of *Gemeinschaft* and fostered instead feelings of individualism. Tönnies highlights the paradox of *Gesellschaft*, namely that despite the fact urbanisation brings people geographically closer together, spiritually they are separated. In *Gesellschaft* Tönnies argued that people are motivated by individual desires to progress and accumulate rather than collective sentiments of improving overall well being. City dwellers have no sense of common identity and only see others in terms of what function they can perform for them (doctor, carpenter, etc.) rather than on the

neighbourly attachment that exists in *Gemeinschaft*. Rational ties of use value and commodity exchange replace natural ties of family, kinship and neighbour. (Tonnies, 1957) Thus, for Tonnies society progressively moves from having a basis in social solidarity to one based on individualism and aggregation.

Writing at the same time as Tonnies, although published five years after, Emile Durkheim's examination of the emerging division of labour in society was undoubtedly influenced by Tonnies' writings. Durkheim's goal was to examine the links between individuals and society and the bonds that connect people. (Morrison, 1995). Like Tonnies Durkheim developed two ideal types of society to explain the transition he believed was occurring, these being societies based on mechanical and organic solidarity.

Societies based on mechanical solidarity broadly conform to Tonnies' idea of *Gemeinschaft* in that people are strongly bound by bonds of tradition, family and community, common roots of identity and similarity. The division of labour in this type of society is based on co-operation such that each member of society contributes to the overall well being of the community and individuals are part of a broader collective. These social bonds are strongly rooted in shared collective sentiments and values which he referred to as the 'collective conscience' which exists independently of individual conscience and serves as a guide for behaviour. Furthermore the collective conscience also acts to evaluate and potentially sanction those whose behaviour threatens traditional ways of life.

Within societies based on organic solidarity individuals become increasingly reliant upon others performing specialised economic tasks. The nature of the bond between the two members of society changes from one based on tradition and kinship to one based on economic function. Durkheim argued that as urbanisation and industrialisation intensifies the division of labour the co-operative ties of mechanic solidarity are replaced with individualism and specialisation. Personal bonds become weaker and thus, as Tonnies also observed, people are geographically closer yet socially separate. Under these conditions the hold of the collective conscience on values and tradition weakens and exerts less constraint on behaviour.

Following this it can be suggested that the notions of public opinion that emerge from English liberalism place at the centre of their theoretical models of democracy the individual. The individual seeks happiness, attempts to maximise his/her utility and their decisions reflect this. However as these works are emerging an alternative argument is also developing. Bentham's works stress the mechanism of the election as a means of reconciling competing wants and as a barrier against misrule and despotism, as does Mill's. In the works of Tocqueville however this

individual viewpoint is criticised for producing the very situation which Bentham sought to prevent. Tyranny exists, but tyranny of the majority. A majority whose actions are geared towards fulfilling their narrow material interests. Tocqueville's works also provides the first instance of a theme that European writers were to return to towards the end of the century, namely the changing nature of society and its effect on social solidarity and integration. Although Tonnies does not make any comment on the nature of public opinion within *Gesellschaft* his writings no doubt influenced Durkheim who does make a reference, albeit slightly abstractly, to the idea of public opinion. Durkheim's concept of 'collective conscience' is not unlike Rousseau's idea of the general will. Both can be seen as collective sentiments or opinion that exist independently of individual conscience and can act as a force for directing behaviour. Durkheim's stress on the breakdown of the hold of the collective conscience over individual behaviour and the notion contained in both Tonnies and Durkheim's writings that societies were moving from being collective to individual in nature led to a growing awareness, at the turn of the century, of the development of 'mass society'.

Notions of mass society were developed at the turn of the 20th century, most notably by the Italian writers Pareto, Mosca and Michels. Michels, for example argued that liberal democracy did not work in the way suggested by its supporters. Instead the masses were dominated by elites who ruled in their own interests. These themes of growing individualism were developed more fully by sociologists writing after the second world war. In reviewing the concept of mass society Kornhauser (1959) describes masses as; 'people who are not integrated into broad social groups including social classes.' (P.14) Like Mill and Tocqueville before him Kornhauser suggests that a prerequisite of mass society is equality for only within a society of equals will mass opinion be dominant. The decline of community and the development of an atomised society distinguish mass society. The growth of a highly industrialised, urbanised society leads to a decline in traditional group and community relationships. Hence individuals become separated, isolated and atomised. They lack a sense of belonging to classes or groups, and a sense of common purpose with others only being connected by a common link to the mass media as a source of knowledge and a common authority in the shape of the state. (Halebsky, 1976) This development is summarised by Broom & Selznick;

Modern society is made up of masses in the sense that there has emerged a vast mass of segregated, isolated individuals, interdependent in all sorts of specialised ways yet lacking in any central unifying value or purpose. The weakening of traditional bonds, the growth of rationality, and the division of labor, have created societies made up of individuals who are only loosely bound together. In this sense the word 'mass' suggests something closer to an aggregate than to a tightly knit social group. (1959, p.38)

Clearly there are links back to Durkheim and Tonnies here. Participation in politics becomes mass participation in that it typically takes the form of passively following news and issues reported through the media. Public opinion therefore becomes a reaction to the content of the mass media and the public is a collectivity of individuals passively exposed to the mass media and susceptible to the messages and manipulations that flow from it. The importance of the media as a source of knowledge and power had been recognised by Mill (1859) who, foreshadowing ideas of mass society, stated;

The only power deserving the name is that of masses, and of governments whilst they make themselves the organ of the tendencies and instincts of masses....the mass do not now take their opinions from dignitaries in Church and State, from ostensible leaders, or from books. Their thinking is done for them by men much like themselves, addressing them or speaking in their name..through the newspapers (p.66)

Over sixty years after Mill's comment; the power of the mass media was again emphasised by Lippman's 1922 work *Public Opinion*. This took the analysis of public opinion in a different direction from that of Locke, Bentham and Mill. Lippmann was sceptical about the existence of a spontaneous public opinion welling up through collective debate and believed that enlightenment period writings on the workings of democracy were an ideal which did not match reality. He suggested that for the majority of ordinary citizens the world of politics was; 'out of reach, out of sight, out of mind.' (p.18) Furthermore the nature of modern society had become too complicated resulting in the public becoming reliant upon the media for information; a media that takes on the role as an organ of democracy whose task is to create public opinion. However it is a media which is not objective, he states;

the mass is constantly exposed to suggestion. It reads not the news, but the news with an aura of suggestion about it..It hears reports, not objective...,but already stereotyped to a certain pattern of behaviour. (p.155)

Thus the frames of reference upon which the public construct their opinions may be skewed. Subsequently, the idealised views of the democratic process, as expressed by earlier writers, could not match the reality of a citizenship who do not have the time or inclination to participate in political affairs and whose knowledge is limited. The influence of public opinion on public policy is limited therefore to elections and then only on broad and unsubstantive issues. For Lippmann, mass opinion and public opinion are one and the same.

Lippmann's claim that mass and public opinion are essentially the same reflect the early 20th century concerns about the emergence of mass societies. Later 20th century writers however do begin to move away from this perspective and distinguish between the two,

contending that only by doing so can we arrive at an understanding of public opinion processes. Blumer (1950) provides the most useful examination of these conceptual issues when he outlines the features that distinguish the public from the mass.

Masses and Publics: Blumer and Key

Blumer attempted to locate public opinion within the broader social processes of human social relations and social psychology and in doing so his work marked a return to those discursive views of public opinion promoted by Rousseau and discussed earlier (Price, 1992). He contended that the term public is used to refer to;

a group of people (a) who are confronted by an issue, (b) who are divided in their ideas as to how to meet the issue, and (c) who engage in discussion over the issue...The presence of an issue, of discussion, and of a collective opinion is the mark of the public. (p.46)

A public comes into existence in response to a specific situation or issue, its birth is spontaneous and because of this the public lacks traditional norms of action; the public has no specific organisation, no status roles or culture. Thus an issue forces collective action but collective action without established tradition or organisation. Instead, as Blumer suggests;

the public is an amorphous group whose size and membership varies with the issue; instead of having its activity prescribed, it is engaged in an effort to arrive at an act, and therefore forced to create its action. (p.46)

Crucially however Blumer places great importance on the communicative nature of the public that is epitomised by disagreement and discussion. Argument and counterargument are proposed and opposition rather than unanimity typify a public. (P.47) He proposes that for this debate to occur there must exist what he refers to as a 'universe of discourse', a common language and ability to agree on fundamental terms. Argument and counter-argument is impossible if those involved cannot understand each other. This differentiates the public from the mass for the mass is composed of anonymous individuals, physically separated and therefore not interacting. This lack of interaction results in the mass acting individually, seeking to meet individual rather than collective goals. Consequently mass and public opinion cannot be the same; a public can only be formed through discussion and argument, masses do not engage in this behaviour and opinion of this nature is mass opinion not public opinion.

As Price (1992) notes, the contrast between mass and public noted by Blumer has implications. Firstly discursive publics comprise only one part of the overall public and secondly

the size and composition of publics can vary across issues and time. It follows from this that the number of specific publics holding a collective opinion is potentially as great as the number of issues which could exist giving rise to the notion of issue publics, or what Key (1961) refers to as special publics. Special publics are those sections of society who are concerned with particular issues which for many others will hold no relevance or interest. The notion of differing publics has led to attempts to conceptualise the varying typologies of publics that may exist. These range from the general public, the voting public, the attentive public, and issue publics studied above.

The general public is generally deemed to be an all-inclusive category; Allport (1947) stated that notions of public opinion must include all the population of a given geographical, community or political limit. In practice this means inferring a public opinion from a smaller 'representative' sample. This approach does however move away from the collective notion of a public discussed above by Blumer (1950) and adopts an individualist conception of both public and opinion. By aggregating individual views it moves nearer Blumer's concept of mass opinion rather than public opinion. Interestingly, however, by suggesting that a general public be comprised of all the individuals within a given geographical or political area, Allport is suggesting that there could be many thousands of different general publics, for there may be many different geographical or political limits. For instance the individuals of one town would be a different public from the individuals in another. Likewise individuals affected by one area of policy would be a different public to those not affected. In many respects it could be regarded as similar to the 'special publics' discussed by Key (1961).

The voting public, unlike the general public, is comprised of only those eligible to vote. As such the science of opinion polling has come to be most closely aligned with this conception of the public. Opinion polls are generally concerned with political matters, in light of this they rarely sample those sections of society who have no influence over political decisions. Consequently when opinion polls proclaim that '60% of the public think.' they are almost always referring to 60% of those eligible to vote.

Key (1961) identified a distinction between attentive and inattentive publics. He suggested that there are some sections of society who will maintain an interest in political affairs generally whilst other sections may maintain a specific interest only to those issues which directly affect them. For example teachers would constitute an attentive public with regard to issues surrounding education, farmers to issues surrounding agriculture. In many respects this is similar to Blumer's notion that on any issue there will be a section of the public who are actively interested in it and another section who are merely spectators. Similar distinctions have been

made between active and inactive publics. For Key (1961) the term active can be equated with elite, he suggests that there exists a;

thin stratum of persons referred to variously as the political elite, the political activists, the leadership echelons, or the influential. (p.536)

The active public is a further substratum of the attentive public and Key proposes that it is comprised of political leaders, government functionaries, party activists and opinion makers. Significantly the active public is often perceived as having an important role in opinion formation. Key refers to the elite as being persuaders and talkers, mediating between the mass and the remote and complex world of government. The distinction between the various publics, from the general to the specific nature of active and issue publics corresponds to the distinctions between mass and public noted by Blumer. The general public raises once again the notion of 'masses' and mass society discussed earlier. Price (1992) notes that it is within the attentive public that we can see the blurring of the boundaries between mass and public predicted by Blumer.

These theorists would appear to support the view that public opinion can again be considered as deriving from processes of communication. Following Blumer, for public opinion to be truly *public* it must emerge from discursive processes. Later attempts to categorise particular publics tended to do so according to the extent to which they can be considered as communicative; from, for example, the active issue publics of Key and Blumer, which are communicative in nature to the general public that is characterised by isolation. This sociological view therefore, according to Price (1992), sees public opinion as part of larger social processes where societies adapt to change through processes of discussion and debate. Despite this, however, promotion of the discursive approach to public opinion has tended to be superseded by the one-person one-vote model that draws upon the classical liberal notion of public opinion as an aggregation of individual opinions rather than the outcome of collective processes. I noted above that two factors contributed to this: the rise to prominence of theories of mass society; and the emergence of opinion polling as a measurement of public opinion. Implicit in theories of mass society is the concept of the atomised individual. It is perhaps not surprising therefore that opinion polling, as a measurement of public opinion, emerged at a time when this idea tended to dominate.

Opinion Polling: Individual decisions from collective processes

The growth of opinion polling as a method of gathering opinion is almost certainly associated with the idea of mass societies. Polling, by its very nature presupposes that public

opinion is comprised of the aggregation of the opinions of isolated individuals. It ignores the view that opinions form as the result of discourse or communication and the concept of a general will which exists independently of individuals. Instead the utilitarian democratic model proposed by nineteenth century liberals is its basis. Twentieth century attempts to measure opinion by polling may therefore also reflect growing urbanisation, the emergence of a mass media and the growing acceptance of the atomisation of society. This was partly due to the fact that those collective processes suggested by earlier conceptions proved to be extremely difficult to empirically measure, theorists tended to adopt instead a one-person one-vote aggregation model. There can be no doubt however that the development of the social sciences also contributed to the development of increasingly systematic and empirical methods of measuring public opinion. This development is noted by Childs who states, "The study of public opinion is the study of collections of individual opinions." (1965, p. 13)

Price & Roberts (1987) however reassert the view that public opinion is a communication process. They recall pre-aggregation models that viewed opinion as the product of a dynamic process of communication. (P.782). For them this conception of public opinion places communication at the centre of the model, not necessarily communication between individuals but between individuals and groups, within groups, and from group to group. Public opinion is; 'a complex function of interactive communication at multiple levels' (p.785), individual opinions originate in discursive communication. Price & Roberts support this contention by suggesting that opinion measured by polling is often constrained by what is considered to be acceptable to wider social norms and are rarely formed in a process of isolation. Discussion with others helps us to rethink and formulate our own opinions. Discussion may also be intrapersonal as individuals embark upon an internal debate or reflection that seeks to weigh issues and clarify an opinion regarding the issue. Internal debate and discussion is fuelled by information gathered in the media or from external discussions. Furthermore opinions develop over time, from a process of discussion or debate. For Price & Roberts opinion processes are learning processes; people learn from discussion, from information in the media. This development is shaped by social interaction. By expressing an opinion an individual may be testing their views or seeking clarification to advance the opinion-formation process. (P.789)

Thus in the discursive model opinion is fluid and constantly changing as individuals compare and discuss issues. Page and Shapiro (1992) refer to changes in public opinion as being the result of a process of collective deliberation within an immensely complex social structure. Very few people live in a conversational vacuum avoiding contact and discourse with others. At home and work conversations take place and opinions are formed. By polling opinions it is possible to establish an individuals opinion on a particular topic, but this takes no account of

the collective processes that shaped this opinion. Collective deliberation occurs such that public opinion becomes more than the sum of its individual parts, similar to Rousseau's 'general will', more than merely individual opinions aggregated. Discourse and deliberation therefore leads to more informed and measured opinion and public opinion is essentially a communication process.

Thus, to briefly summarise what has preceded. Clearly two competing concepts of public opinion have developed since the enlightenment. The first, rooted in the classical liberalism of Bentham and Mill, emphasises the role of the individual and suggests that public opinion on any issue can be determined by aggregating the individual opinions of a given public. This model was given further credence with late nineteenth and early twentieth century models of mass society and has dominated the twentieth century due to the emergence of opinion polling as a scientific measurement of opinion. The second model is the discursive model and draws on the works of Rousseau and later twentieth century writers such as Blumer, Key and Price & Roberts. What is also clear however is, as Price (1992) notes; 'the close connection of public opinion with processes of discussion, debate and collective decision making.' (p. 91). The central role of communication has been traced through the development of public opinion. It was noted that whilst communication was a feature of both of the models of public opinion it was far more prominent in the second 'collective' model. The communicative nature of public opinion was traced through Rousseau's general will and the stress placed on communication by enlightenment writers such as Bentham and Mill was noted. These communicative processes were further traced in the discussion of later sociological views of public opinion that stressed the discursive nature of publics as compared to masses and noted the differing typologies of public distinguished by the extent to which they are characterised by internal communication. It is possible therefore to argue that public opinion could be considered as a communication concept.

This notion of public opinion as a communication concept is not a unique proposition. The link between the two has existed for many years but these links have, in many respects, been opaque or implicit. By demonstrating the close connection between the two through a review of the historical development of public opinion it is hoped that this opacity will lessen.

Opinion Leaders and Flows of Information

To fully understand this communication process however it is necessary to examine processes of opinion formation. I have noted above the suggestion that opinion forms from processes of discussion and debate. Alongside this communicative element must therefore be added an interpersonal element. In other words who is communicating with whom and how? In an attempt to determine the processes of opinion formation a number of studies were conducted

in America during the 1940s. These studies concluded that rather than information flowing from the media to an atomistic mass of readers or listeners (television was not widely available at the time of research) there existed networks of communication where those who were more exposed to the media, relayed information to those less exposed. They termed this effect the; 'two-step flow of communication' and christened those relaying information as 'opinion leaders'

These findings emerged from studies that sought to examine the influence of mass communication and the mass media. The effect of posters and propaganda during the first world war raised awareness of the power of the media to manipulate public opinion. The introduction and common use of radio in the 1920s lent further credence to the notion of media power as did the mass panic which followed Orson Welles' 1938 'War of the Worlds' broadcast. Media influence came to be considered as inevitable in societies which, as discussed above, late 19th and early 20th century theorists perceived as being 'mass society'. The theory of mass media influence over public opinion came to be termed the 'hypodermic' or the 'magic bullet' theory whereby the mass media inject ideas and opinions into passive, isolated individuals thus shaping their views. Of particular interest was the effect the media may have on voting intentions and a number of studies developed to examine this.(Gitlin, 1978)

The first systematic attempt to empirically determine the effect the mass media had on voting behaviour was conducted by Lazarsfeld, Berelson & Gaudet in the USA in 1940. In an effort to determine the factors that exerted the greatest influence upon voter election decisions they selected four groups of voters in Erie county Ohio and interviewed them every month for the six months prior to elections, then following the election. Their findings were published as *The Peoples Choice* (1948). They did not support the hypodermic theory of mass media influence however. Instead their findings proposed that media information was often less influential than personal influence and that many respondents who made their minds up or changed their minds during the campaign indicated that the source of this decision was often family, friends or neighbours. Furthermore a greater number of respondents reported discussing election issues with friends and families than hearing a campaign speech or reading a newspaper report. They concluded that interpersonal communication appeared to be a more significant contributory factor to individuals political decisions than the mass media. (Lazarsfeld, et al, 1948) In addition, Lazarsfeld et al also concluded that the flow of interpersonal influence could be traced from specific individuals to the wider community. These individuals were located at every level in society and had similar socio-economic characteristics to those they influenced. They were more interested in and informed about the election issues and were often regarded as experts in that field by the community, furthermore they were typically more interested in and exposed to the mass media. It became apparent that they did not merely relate media messages but interpreted

and shaped them when relaying them to others and consequently they were termed 'opinion leaders'. (DeFleur & Ball-Rokeach, 1989) Lazarsfeld et al concluded that media influence often occurs in two stages, firstly from the media to opinion leaders and, second, from opinion leaders to the community who consider them experts and ask their advice; this process was termed the 'two-step flow'.

The findings of *The Peoples Choice* were significant for the challenge they presented to those theories that stressed media dominance of individual choices and decisions. Yet the development of the two-step theory was the least well documented of the findings of the Erie study and further studies were conducted to confirm the findings. These studies, The Rovere Study, The Decatur Study and The Drug Study not only confirmed the presence of opinion leaders but also verified the leader's role as mediating variables between the media and the wider public, in other words they supported the two-step theory of opinion formation. They corroborated the suggestion made in *The Peoples Choice* that opinion leaders are more exposed to the mass media. This led to the following conclusion:

opinion leaders and the people whom they influence are very much alike and typically belong to the same primary group of family, friends and co-workers...Influentials and influenced may exchange roles in different spheres of influence. Most spheres focus the groups attention on some related part of the world outside the group and it is the leaders function to bring the group into touch..through whatever media are appropriate. In every case Influentials have been found to be more exposed to these points of contact with the outside world. (Katz, 1957, p.77)

The emergence of the two-step theory of opinion formation was significant in a number of ways. It challenged those theories of mass society which stressed the isolated nature of human existence at that time and questioned the notion that media influence upon the individual was direct, immediate and powerful. Furthermore the studies' findings led research in this field into new territories and highlighted the numerous factors influencing individual choice. Consequently the 'hypodermic theory' and its *stimulus-response* basis was replaced with one that emphasised the intervening variables between media and actor. As might be expected however, criticism of the two-step theory emerged on both theoretical and empirical grounds.

The most vigorous theoretical critique of the two-step theory has been advanced by Todd Gitlin in his 1978 paper *Media Sociology: The Dominant Paradigm*. According to Gitlin, following the Decatur studies the dominant approach in media sociology was what he referred to as the 'limited-effects paradigm'. This emphasised the limited effect of the media on opinion and stressed instead the intervening role of opinion leaders within the two-step flow theory of opinion change. Gitlin's' critique focused on what he considered as flawed theoretical assumptions

underpinning research into the two-step model. He identified five assumptions: (1) *Commensurability of the Modes of influence*. The impact of personal influence was assumed to be equivalent to the impact of the mass media; (2) *Power as Distinct Occasions*: whereby influence can be measured by studying incidents of influence exchange; 'as if power were a kind of freely flowing marketplace commodity in a situation of equality.' (P.214); (3) *The Commensurability of Buying and Politics*. Research focussed on opinion change in four areas: marketing; fashion; movie-going and politics, assuming that changes in consumer behaviour were equivalent to changes in attitudes and that each could be measured by a single theory and method; (4) *Change as the Dependent Variable*. Influence was assumed to occur if a change in attitude occurred; if respondents had not changed their attitude influence was discounted, in this way the research overlooked the power of the media to reinforce existing attitudes, a factor Gitlin identified as crucial in the crystallisation of attitude into ideology. (5) *Leaders as Followers*. The results of The Decatur Studies concluded that ideas flow from media to opinion leaders and then outwards to the wider community; but by focusing on opinion leaders Katz & Lazarsfeld ignored the primary importance of the media in leading the leaders. Gitlin concludes:

In what sense did an opinion leader actually lead?... (by) taking for granted the power of mass media to define news;....they were therefore discovering not 'the part played by people in the flow of communications' but the nature of the channels of that flow. (p.218)

Gitlin proceeded to criticise the Decatur and Columbia studies for the marketing oriented approach; he pointed to the fact that funding for these studies had originated from magazines and television networks amongst others as a source of bias, especially in their conclusion of the limited effect of media. He suggested that the development of the two-step flow theory was an attempt to mask the true extent of the mass media's power to shape opinion.

Empirical criticism has been no less searching. Critics have noted that opinions are often shared, rather than given, as the opinion leader theory contends. They have argued that opinion leaders do not only rely on the media for information but also receive information from others, both other leaders and opinion followers, a process of opinion sharing. (Troidahl & Van Dam, 1965). Further criticism has pointed to the direct-flow of media messages as sources of knowledge and influence particularly in the case of significant news events, concluding that two-step is often one-step. (Lin, 1971) Definitionally the theory is hindered by a black/white dichotomy between leaders and followers, and problematic use of the term 'mass media' which is used to refer both to newspapers and television and specialised forms of media such as journals and magazines. (Lin, 1971; Rogers & Shoemaker, 1971) In addition opinion leaders do not only rely upon the mass media for information as the theory implies, knowledge also originates within

interpersonal networks; thus the flow of information may not be restricted to two steps, longer chains of information flow may exist. (Weimann, 1994)

This final criticism has led to a revision of the original theory and the replacement of the two-step model with a multi-step theory. Here, in addition to the downward flow proposed by the two-step model, flows of information may be horizontal (among leaders or among followers)' direct (linking two individuals directly), indirect (through a third party or number of parties) and upward (leader to media and follower to leader). (Weimann, 1994)

This barrage of conceptual and methodological criticism had the consequence of prompting the development and use of more sophisticated and methodologically sound measurements of the opinion leadership concept. Weimann reports how the German news magazine *Der Spiegel* challenged German public opinion scholars to identify 'the active consumers who set standards in their community.' Researchers constructed questionnaires designed to test self-perceived personal influence and after numerous refinements 'The Strength of Personality Scale' was established. Four categories of Personality Strength (PS) were classified: strong; above average; moderate and weak. Studies indicated that those with strong ratings on the PS scale were generally centrally located within networks of communication and are more active communicators of news. The results of these studies led to a reassessment of the opinion leader concept and to the search to instead identify those termed as the 'influentials' or the 'people who influence people' amongst society. (Weimann, 1994, p. xiii)

Findings of the studies did suggest that there were indeed influentials in society who were similar in many ways to those opinion leaders identified in the early studies. However it was not simply a case of replacing one term with another; for despite the similarities there were notable differences. Firstly, the opinion leader theory was based on a clear distinction between leader and follower. The later studies of influentials suggested that influence is not so clear-cut and can instead be considered as a continuous variable. Secondly, in the original theory opinion leadership was a product of greater exposure to the mass media; later studies determined that personal sources of information were equally significant to influentials and whilst differences in media exposure did exist these were qualitative rather than quantitative. Thirdly, according to the original opinion leadership theories leaders were evenly distributed across the social classes, later studies on the other hand discovered that influentials tended to be concentrated in higher socio-economic strata. Influentials were found in all socio-economic strata but in higher numbers and greater concentration in higher ones. As a result the middle and upper classes tended to mobilise opposition more frequently than working class groups. Fourthly, opinion leaders were

said to be typically leaders in only one area with little overlap whilst influentials did overlap especially in closely related areas. (Weimann, 1994)

Thus, according to Weimann (1994), the concept of 'influentials' provides a more sensitive and balanced approach to the study of personal influence. At the same time as this reconceptualisation of opinion leadership was occurring other researchers were focusing not on *who* influences *who* but on the *channels* of influence, in other words how and where information flows from influentials to followers. This built on the concept of the multi-step flow of information and the results of the PS scale which indicated that influentials tend to be centrally located in communication networks of friends, neighbours etc. Their work highlighted the importance of social networks in disseminating information, as Sheingold notes;

Social networks constitute social structures which exist independent of the perceptions of discrete individuals. The information an individual receives may emanate from others with whom he is not in direct contact and of whom he may be unaware. (1973, p.714; in Weimann, 1994, p. 252)

Empirical studies examining social networks of communication established that influentials were crucial disseminators of knowledge sitting at the centre of an interlocking web of communication. (Weimann, 1991)

Merging these theories of opinion leadership and social networks leads to a picture of opinion mobilisation where information and influence flows through social networks of communication at the centre of which are located influentials. The notion of leadership and communication networks is also central to theories of social movements. It is to these I now wish to turn.

Social Movements: Networks and Leaders

The study of social movements shares one particular characteristic with that of public opinion, the contested nature of the debate. As studies of public opinion have tended to divide into two fields, those emphasising its individual nature and those stressing the collective, so too have theoretical approaches to the study of social movements. Further complications arise when attempting to define what is and is not a social movement and here also there are parallels with the debates on public opinion. In the same way that publics are often defined in terms of who they incorporate (issue publics, general publics etc.) movements are likewise categorised. For example Aberle (1966) identifies four types of social movements. The first are alternative movements that seek limited change for a small proportion of the population. The second are

redemptive movements, which are more radical in nature but still have a limited focus in population terms. The third he classifies as reformatory social movements that have limited aims but target the entire population. The fourth are revolutionary movements, which have extensive, transformative goals aimed at an entire society.

Thus we are once again faced with a dilemma. What is a social movement? It is possible to define social movements in terms of what they do and we can describe a social movement as a group or organisation of groups who engage in organised activity for the purpose of either promoting or resisting change. Despite knowing what social movements do it is still not clear what they are, and indeed there are numerous different interpretations of this. Some recent writings of social movements have endeavoured to bridge existing conceptual distinctions thus arriving at a synthesis containing elements common to all. Diani (1992) attempts to achieve this synthesis. He argues that within conceptual discussions of social movements common factors do arise. However before going on to discuss Diani's work in greater detail an overview of these differing conceptual approaches is required. Pakulski (1991) reviews five different theoretical models of social movements.

Social Movement Theories and Models

The first model discussed by Pakulski is the deprivation theory of social movements. This theory contends that social movements arise when individuals feel relatively deprived; this deprivation can be based on income, employment or political rights amongst others. Movements form as people engage in collective action to correct this relative deprivation. The second theory covered by Pakulski is mass society theory (a topic covered at length in the above discussion on public opinion). In relation to social movements, mass society theory, as proposed by Kornhauser, postulates that movements offer socially atomised individuals an opportunity to belong. People who are, or have a sense of being, socially integrated are not attracted to these movements and thus those who do join tend to be easily manipulated and the groups typically emerge at the radical ends of the political spectrum. Both theories, whilst offering useful explanations are subject to criticism. For example it has been noted that deprivation theory assumes that relative deprivation results in social movements. However the evidence of deprivation upon which the theory is based is the presence of social movements, thus it is guilty of what Jenkins and Perrow (1977) refer to as 'circular reasoning'. Furthermore, as Zald & McCarthy have stated deprivation exists in many forms and in many different societies but has not necessarily resulted in the formation of social movements. Both these theories have their origins in late nineteenth century discussions of social change and crowd behaviour and as such have been superseded by later theories.

The first of these, and the third to be discussed by Pakulski, is structural-strain theory, the most prominent proponent of this being Neil Smelser (1962). Smelser's work evolved from the earlier writings on collective behaviour produced by Blumer who argued that collective behaviour was a form of symbolic interaction and pointed to the problem-solving and learning element of some forms of collective behaviour. Blumer's focus on the social-psychological factors of social movements was further developed through the structural-functionalist account of Talcott Parsons. Parsons argued that the emergence of social movements could be explained in terms of 'strains'. These strains arise as a result of structural tensions within society brought about by uneven development and the uneven effects of rapid modernisation and industrialisation. Individuals were differently affected by these developments and social movements develop in order to either protest against or promote these changes. Smelser's work sought to bring both the symbolic-interactionism of Blumer and the structural-functionalism of Parsons together. For Smelser, like Parsons, the emergence of social movements and collective behaviour is a response to structural strains. Alongside this, Smelser further outlined six conditions which affect the development of social movements: *Structural conduciveness*. Movements arise when particular problems or conditions promote their development. For example the political system may be amenable to the mobilisation of groups or there may be little state regulation of particular areas, e.g. religion. *Structural strain*. Tensions in society produce conflict between those who believe themselves to be relatively deprived and either the state or those with conflicting interests. *The growth and spread of beliefs*. Ideologies or beliefs can crystallise grievances and offer explanations for them. Thus social movements offer explanations for, and organised solutions to, problems. *Precipitating factors*. Grievances and discontents often simmer slowly until a particular incident or policy leads to a surge of collective action in response.

These four factors increase the potential for movement development but for a social movement to develop requires what Smelser calls '*mobilisation for action*'. This process of mobilisation is facilitated by group or movement leaders who co-ordinate action. Communication from leaders to members and within members is essential for action to remain organised. The success or otherwise of the movement depends on Smelser's last condition, *the operation of social control*. If the state response to movement activities is swift and repressive the movement will quickly fade from view. If however the state responds in the opposite manner the movement may flourish and gain more members. Furthermore the state could intervene to control the conditions which led to the development of structural-strain initially, thus limiting the need for movement action. (Smelser, 1962, Eyerman & Jamison, 1992)

Smelser's theory is useful in that it points out the complexity of social movements and the numerous factors involved in their development. However it has been criticised for its assumption that discontent and shared grievances are important pre-conditions for movement emergence. Zald & McCarthy (1992), for instance, point to empirical studies that indicate little relationship between discontent and movement activity or outbreaks of collective action. They suggest instead that prominence should be given to the processes by which people become involved in social movement activity. This shift in emphasis to the processes and organisation of social movements forms the basis for the fourth of the social movement theories reviewed by Pakulski, Resource Mobilisation Theory.

Resource Mobilisation (RM) theory has its roots in the rational-actor model of collective action promoted by Mancur Olson in his seminal work *The Logic of Collective Action* which places the weighing of cost and benefits at the core of individual motivations to participate in collective action. Olson suggested that;

the rational self-interested individual will ordinarily not act to achieve collective benefits because such public goods cannot be withheld from members of the group according to whether or not they contribute. (1968, p. 124)

The significance of the theory lies in its assertion that social movements are a product of cost/benefit analysis by rational individuals in contrast to those theories that stress discontent as a base for movement development. Proponents of RM theory contend that there is always discontent in any society but this does not necessarily translate into social movement activity. Discontent is only expressed through social movements if the movement is effectively organised and can draw on resources such as finance, time and organisational skills. Groups lower the costs and increase the benefits of participation in order to mobilise effectively. Direct action is considered to be an efficient and cost-effective approach to achieving goals for groups with little or no resources and limited political power. They further contend that grievances need not be overtly present but can be created, defined or manipulated by movement entrepreneurs.

Although it parallels Olson's work, RM theory does not exactly match it. Because of this it does somewhat manage to avoid the paradox of Olson's work, namely that of the *free rider*. Critics of Olson have pointed out that rationally it is easier to do nothing and let others organise and demonstrate. By applying Olson's thoughts on rationally acting individuals to social movement organisations RM theory seeks to demonstrate that the same principles may apply to both, namely that successful social movements are as much a product of organisation and resource mobilisation than political grievances.

RM theory has developed through the works of many writers over a number of years (for example: Tilly, 1973; Oberschall, 1973; Gamson, 1975; Jenkins and Perrow, 1977; McCarthy & Zald, 1987) and some enduring characteristics emerge in most approaches. First, if resources are essential these resources must be aggregated if they are to be utilised efficiently. Secondly, this aggregation requires some form of organisation. Third, there is a recognition of the importance of the involvement of individuals and organisations from outside the social movement in explaining the success or otherwise of movements. Fourth, the flow of resources to and from the movement is often portrayed in terms of supply and demand models. Finally individual involvement can be explained in terms of costs and rewards. (Zald & McCarthy, 1989)

Zald & McCarthy emphasise the distinctiveness of the RM approach in comparison to the traditional structural-functionalist model by comparing the two in three areas. The first area of comparison is the support base of the social movement. Traditional models suggest that social movements are based upon discontented populations. RM theory on the other hand argues that social movements are not necessarily born out of grievance and that support can come from individuals, other organisations and even people with no specific commitment to the values of the movement. The second area RM theorists use as comparison is strategy and tactics. Traditional models emphasise movement leaders' use of bargaining, persuasion and violence in an effort to influence decision-makers. Tactics depend on the movement's history, ideology and the relative success of previous actions. RM theorists note the primary strategic tasks each social movement faces, namely the need to mobilise supporters and thus ensure movement survival and achieving goals. Tactics are pragmatic in nature, taking whichever form is deemed to be the most efficient and effective at that particular time. Thirdly, traditional models stress the effect the wider environment has on the success of the social movement and the way wider forces can shape or hinder the development of movements. RM theory contends that society provides the infrastructure which social movements utilise, this includes communication networks, media, finance and access to decision-making. (Zald & McCarthy, 1992) Thus the RM model stresses that social movements need resources to survive and, importantly, need entrepreneurial expertise in order to successfully mobilise these. The need to obtain sufficient resources means that social movements tend to adopt a hierarchical form with often a small group of movement entrepreneurs or leaders responsible for the overall strategy and well being of the movement. Furthermore movements forge alliances with other movements and organisations to ensure resources and gain access to decision-making centres. For RM theorists movements are embedded within networks of formal and informal relationships. (Dalton, 1994)

The importance of RM theory in advancing understanding of social movements and social movement behaviour cannot be underestimated. The stress on the organisational and entrepreneurial elements of social movements took research into previously unexplored areas. Nevertheless, as might be expected, it is not without its critics. Criticism of RM theory has tended to come from European social movement scholars. Given that the majority of American approaches to the topic do tend to have their base in RM theory this has led to claims that we can distinguish between European and American schools of social movement theory. Criticisms from European writers are influenced by the greater emphasis in European sociology and political science on issues of class and ideology. As such critics argue that the RM approach with its roots in the rational-actor approach of economics removes or ignores factors such as ideology and values in individual motivations to participate. Furthermore criticism has been levelled at the fact that RM theorists uniformly apply the theory to a myriad of different groups, from trade unions to small community groups. They argue that this effectively dilutes the definition of what is and is not a social movement, including groups which other authors argue do not fall within this definition. Finally it has been suggested that RM theory overlooks or discounts the many differences in behaviour and strategies adopted by social movements preferring instead to focus on overall strategies rather than issues such as tactical innovation.

European approaches to social movement theory are heavily influenced by post-modernist theories that emphasise the alteration of the political complexion of modern post-war societies. This alteration has rendered problematic the core assumption that buttressed post-war society until the 1960s, namely the class domination of politics. A major consequence of this change has been the decline in traditional class-based voting, a reduction in support for major class-based political parties and traditional social movements such as trade unions and the advent of 'new social movements' such as environmental, peace and feminist movements. (Crook et al, 1992)

New Social Movement (NSM) theorists contend that traditional categories of class, status and occupation have little or no meaning in a contemporary society which lacks homogeneity and structure. Crook et al (1992) explain the rise of NSMs by locating them within the broader historical context of a shift towards post-modernism. They emphasise two aspects of this shift. The first is progressive class decomposition resulting in the breakdown of traditional class-based voting patterns and party identifications. The second is that the specific form of politics and activities promoted by NSMs has to be seen as a response to established overly-bureaucratized politics, as an;

attempt to resolve the tension between increasingly diverse social groupings seeking social articulation and political recognition on the one hand, and the bureaucratic rigidity and corporatist bias inherent in the old system on the other. (p.142)

NSM structure and behaviour differs greatly from the organisational structure proposed by RM theorists. In this case there is a clear rejection, certainly in principle, of traditional hierarchical forms of organisation. NSMs tend to be segmented and diffuse with no firm membership base and are often comprised of loose networks of autonomous groups. Tactics also differ from those suggested as typical by RM theorists. NSMs strive to remain outside the existing decision-making process, they are anti-bureaucratic and anti-statist; actions are geared towards mobilising publics and are often highly symbolic in nature relying on mass media coverage. In contrast to the value free stress of RM theory NSM theorists emphasise factors such as collective identity, ideology and values as being crucial to motivations to participate.

Ronald Inglehart perhaps most vociferously stresses the importance of changing values to the emergence of new political groupings and areas of collective action. According to Inglehart (1981) structural changes in post-war society, particularly with regard to economic and political stability and the increase in educational attainment, have facilitated a generational shift in values from materialist to post-materialist. Increased affluence and access to education has resulted in a change in priorities for many; higher priority is now given to quality of life issues such as the environment and peace, freedom of speech and participation. This shift is most prevalent amongst the relatively affluent middle-classes that have benefited most from educational and employment opportunities, and it is amongst the middle-classes that calls for increased participation in decision making and challenges to existing policies and institutions first emerged. The radical notions and politics of the post-war generation were incompatible, however, with the inflexibility of post-war political processes based upon class and sectional interests. To relieve the tension caused by this and give an outlet to radical and marginalised views NSMs were formed. Thus NSMs are both a consequence of the stability, consensus and bureaucratisation of the post-war era and a challenge to these very factors which led to their emergence. (Crook et al, 1992)

Thus new social movement theory attempts to relate the growth of these new forms of collective behaviour to structural changes in advanced post-war economies. A central feature of this European approach to new social movements is the emphasis on collective identity as a major component in promoting collective behaviour. Perhaps the most forceful proponent of this is the Italian sociologist Alberto Melucci.

Melucci has outlined his theories of new social movements in a series of books and papers in English (Melucci, 1988; 1989; 1994; 1996). He argues that NSMs are characterised by three unique features. Firstly, movement activity is essentially symbolic in nature, challenging the administrative logic of society in symbolic terms. Secondly, movements are messages, social movements do not simply seek to achieve political goals but also practice the changes they seek to effect. Finally, movements are submerged within the social networks of everyday life. This last feature is one of the core concepts developed by Melucci. He argues that social movements exist within movement areas. These are networks of dispersed and diverse groups which, as stated, are submerged within everyday life. These groups act as 'cultural laboratories' for people to test new ways of living. Collective action therefore is a continuous process, not an event, which is only sporadically visible in response to specific issues and thus social movements are always present in society but only sometimes apparent. These networks serve as systems of exchange where contacts are made and individuals and information circulates.

In his later works Melucci contends that the most important role of NSMs is to offer alternatives to the dominant codes of everyday life. Movement activity, he argues;

is in itself a message broadcast to society conveying symbolic forms and relational patterns which cast light on the 'dark side of the moon' - a system of meanings which runs counter to the sense that the apparatuses (of state and media) seek to impose on individual and collective events. (1992, p.75)

He reiterates his idea that movements are essentially communicative in nature and that in both the issues around which movements mobilise and the activity they engage in movements endeavour to educate. Attempts to judge the relative success of movements in terms of their success in forcing political change or accommodation are, according to Melucci, misguided;

social movements are taken into consideration solely on account of their capacity to modernise institutions or produce political reform. But this is to forget, or to ignore that the reduction of contemporary social movements to their political dimensions alone is tantamount to...suppressing the message contained in their specifically communicative character. (1996, p.2)

Meuller (1997) endeavours to construct a bridge between NSM and RM theory by an analysis of the women's liberation movement in America utilising Melucci's concept of submerged networks. Her analysis concluded that Melucci's theory is extremely useful in explaining motivation and participation in the women's liberation movement, particularly with regard to his assertion that collective identity is built up within the submerged networks of face-

to-face interaction and that this is crucial in the construction of a collective identity. However Mueller does suggest that the theory of submerged networks is less useful when seeking to account for how a collective shared identity enters the public domain. She suggests that this occurs through the publication of pamphlets, manifestos etc., and only when a collective identity becomes public does it have the potential to shape policy. Importantly, she claims that this public identity need not necessarily be the same as the collective identity developed within submerged networks. Despite this caveat Muller's work clearly demonstrates the commonality of much of the RM and NSM approach to movement development and mobilisation and the important role networks have to play in both.

The purpose of this review of social movement theory is not to arrive at some definitive or best theoretical model. Rather it is to highlight the contested nature of the debate on the topic. As is apparent, social movement theorists differ in their interpretations of how and why social movements mobilise, the factors that lead to their development, and the relative success or otherwise which social movements have enjoyed. Perhaps more fundamentally however there is a disagreement about the nature of social movements, about what does, and by definition does not, constitute a social movement. As I noted at the beginning of this section however despite this plurality of views some writers in the field have attempted to identify underlying features characteristic of social movements. Mario Diani's 1992 paper *The Concept of Social Movement* is one such example of this.

Enduring Features of Social Movements

Diani concedes that theoretical discussions of social movements are marked by their diversity but suggests that they converge in four areas. Firstly he contends that social movements can be considered as networks of informal interaction. Secondly, social movements are based on shared beliefs and solidarity. Thirdly, social movements engage in collective action on conflictual issues. Finally, social movement activity is largely conducted outwith the formal institutional sphere of everyday life.

It is Diani's first assertion that is most illuminating to this overall discussion. Diani points to the work of RM theorists such as McCarthy & Zald who indicate that social movements need to form alliances with other organisations in order to obtain the necessary resources or access needed to achieve their goals. Thus they are contained within loose networks of movement areas. This accords with Melluci's concept of the social movement area and his claim that movements are located within the social networks of everyday life, only occasionally becoming visible. Despite this definition Diani does not indicate what type of network he is referring to,

simply that movements are themselves networks. However if social movements are indeed networks then it is possible to consider them as networks of communication. Within these loose informal networks social movements communicate with other movements in similar or related areas, with movement members or sympathisers and with the outside world which they are striving to change or influence. For example from a structural-functionalist perspective collective-action is intended to communicate to government the discontent of the particular group involved. RM theorists similarly stress the communicative nature of social movements. The concept of communication does not therefore only refer to interaction in verbal or written form; the activities of a social movement are also communicative in nature.

Jo Freeman (1983), writing primarily from a RM perspective, examines four prominent American social movements of the sixties and seventies: civil rights; the student movement; welfare rights and women's liberation. From her analysis she concludes that four factors are involved in the mobilisation of each. (1) The need for a pre-existing communications network or infrastructure within social structures which precipitates movement communication and mobilisation. (2) A co-optable communications network, a network alone is not sufficient, it must be composed of like-minded people; 'whose background, experience or location in the social structure make them receptive to the ideas of the social movement.' (p. 9) (3) A crisis which galvanises those involved in the network into action. Finally, (4) Leadership and organisation is required to either fully co-opt an existing network or function as a linkage between groups and people involved in protest.

Freeman's stress on crisis as a galvanising agent is directly comparable to structural-functionalist notions of precipitating factors. Furthermore the idea that leaders or organisers have crucial roles to play is common to all movement theories, although some stress its significance more than others. Significantly she highlights two aspects important to social movement theory: communication and networks. Indeed in her view the two are almost inseparable. Despite Melucci also making the connection between the two the link between network analysis and social movement theory has predominantly been established by American writers analysing movements from a RM perspective. In this they attempt to locate the recruitment and mobilisation networks within which movements operate. Cross-movement studies by Snow et al (1997), for example have demonstrated that movement recruits tend to be drawn into movements through networks of contacts with friends or relatives already participating. Morris (1981) in his study of the black sit-in movement of the sixties emphasises the role of local networks of churches as being crucial to the dissemination of information and the mobilisation of potential recruits.

Movement Leaders: communication, mobilisation and 'cognitive praxis'

Given that we could consider social movements to be essentially communication networks or certainly reliant on communication networks for their development the question that remains is what is being communicated, by whom, and to whom? In the earlier discussion of public opinion, it was noted that opinion is often communicated within communication networks and that often the flow of information is from opinion leaders to followers. The idea of movement leaders is also a central feature of social movement theory.

For example, mass society theorists stress charismatic leaders as being crucial to the formation of Fascist movements in 1930s Europe. Smelser's structural-functionalist account highlights the role of movement organisers in one of his six conditions of movement formation: *mobilisation for action*. Resource mobilisation theorists emphasise the organiser or movement entrepreneurs whose role it is to form strategies and tactics needed to achieve movement goals. Freeman contends that; 'social movements do not simply occur they must be organised.'(p.109) whilst Melucci notes;

processes of mobilisation and the organisational structure of a movement are fuelled by the actions of the movement's leaders. It is the leadership that promotes the pursuit of goals, develops strategies and tactics for action, and formulates an ideology. The penetration of the movement in the society, the loyalty and involvement of its members, and the consensus of different social groups all depend on the leaders' actions. (1996, p.332)

Leadership then, in whatever guise adopted, is a recurring element in theories of social movements and there is general agreement on the fact that leaders are important for developing strategies and mobilising followers. Eyerman and Jamison (1991) suggest that movement leaders, or intellectuals as they refer to them, are essential in the initial formative phases of the movement. Their role is to articulate the needs and interests of the movement and also to act as movement communicator, conveying the movement's message to broader society and movement developments to its' members. In these early phases Eyerman and Jamison contend that the most important part played by the movement leader is that of mobilising the collective will of the movement; through books, speeches, pamphlets etc. leaders shape the collective identity of the movement. Central to this is the identification of what Eyerman and Jamison refer to as 'the Other' against which the movement is opposed. This 'Other' is usually an authority, a government, institution or some other 'real social actor'.

Eyerman and Jamison's approach is based upon their view of social movements as 'cognitive praxis'. They review existing theories of social movements and conclude that one

fundamental aspect of social movements has been overlooked by all theories, namely their contribution to the social production of knowledge. Social movements, they contend, are essentially knowledge producers, they contribute to knowledge production by challenging existing process or ideas, by providing alternatives to these and by translating everyday knowledge (common sense) and locating it within the broader forces of society. Social movements are not simply one organisation but instead, in terms reminiscent of Diani's notion of movements as networks, they argue that movements are more akin to a cognitive territory filled by dynamic interaction between different groups and organisations. Cognitive praxis is the process of knowledge production whereby a movement identity is articulated and new thoughts and ideas formulated and thus it refers to those processes which transform groups of individuals into social movements. This process is collective in nature, it is;

the product of a series of social encounters, within movements, between movements, and even more importantly between movements and their opponents. (p.58)

Examples of cognitive praxis could be discussions that take place amongst movement leaders about new strategies or organisation, debates and interaction with opponents in the public sphere, and interaction with other movements. It is the particular character of a group's cognitive praxis which defines it and sets it apart from others. The generation of movement intellectuals is essential in the formation of a social movement for it is the intellectuals who facilitate the process of cognitive praxis.

Gamson and Collective Action Frames

Eyerman and Jamison's cognitivist approach to social movement mobilisation and their stress on the importance of leaders in this process is bolstered by recent works which deal with the concept of 'framing' in relation to the same topic. The leading writers in this field are Snow and Benford (1992) and Gamson (1992) and I wish to discuss the latter's work in more detail.

Although utilised by Gamson the work of Goffman represents the first significant sociological use of the concept of 'framing'. The common referent is that of frames as interpretative schemata that; 'simplifies and condenses the world out there by selectively punctuating and encoding objects, situations, events, experiences, and sequences of actions within one's present or past environment.'(Snow & Benford, 1992, p.137). Frames therefore are mechanisms through which individuals come to understand the problems facing them, identify the source of the problem and develop solutions or as Goffman states; 'locate, perceive, identify and label events within their life space' (in Snow & Benford, 1992, p. 137). In short frames define

problems, diagnose causes and suggest remedies. Consequently theories which seek to explain the emergence of social movements by recourse to structural or resource mobilisation theories have ignored the fact that people must interpret events, construct meanings for what is going on in the world around them and define themselves as part of a collective identity.

Frames serve a number of roles: focusing attention on and punctuating existing social conditions which are unjust or immoral; and as a means of attribution of both the causes and solutions to the perceived problem. The identification of these different roles allows Gamson (1992) to identify three components of collective action frames: an injustice frame, an agency frame and an identity frame. Let me elaborate on these beginning with Gamson's discussions of injustice frames.

The notion that collective action is born out of a sense of injustice is emphasised by many social movement theorists but perhaps most explicitly by Turner & Killian (1972) and Moore (1978). For example Turner & Killian state;

The common element in the norms of many, if not most movements, is the conviction that existing conditions are unjust. The rule or norm that gains in importance, that is imposed upon members of the movement, and that movements seek to impose on the larger society is a specification that what has heretofore been accepted as a necessary or desirable condition must be viewed as unjust. (p.259)

Three conclusions can be drawn from this. The first is that it suggests that social movements only emerge as a result of the perception that existing conditions are unjust and do not develop in response to an awareness that proposed developments will either further exacerbate existing injustices or create new ones. The second is that a sense of injustice does not spontaneously develop but instead is imposed upon movement members by movement leaders (although the use of the term 'imposed' is problematic as it implies coercion rather than persuasion or enlightenment). Thirdly the development of a sense of injustice happens within the framework of a moral discourse distinguished by notions of fairness and statements of moral outrage.

The development of an Injustice frame therefore requires, according to Gamson, a concrete target for moral outrage or what Eyerman & Jamison refer to as an 'other'. It is the moral element that produces the emotional 'hot cognition' of an injustice frame. These concrete targets must however bridge both abstract and concrete and link broader structural forces with motivated human agents, in this way the roots of the injustice can be tackled. The identification of a focus for opposition encourages the development of the second component of collective

action frames: identity. The apportioning of blame and the identification of a 'them' leads to the development of an oppositional 'we' and the emergence of a collective identity.

The suggestion that collective identity is a crucial component of collective action has been promoted by a number of authors (see e.g. Touraine, 1978). In his writings on the emergence of social movements Melucci (1989) recognises that concepts of identity have had little prominence in the majority of studies of collective action. He suggests however that it is only through the process of constructing a collective identity that actors are able to calculate cost and benefits and shape their expectations. Construction is a process through which; 'actors produce the common cognitive frameworks that enable them to assess their environment' (p.35). For Gamson a collective action frame must be adversarial. Identity develops within an identity frame where 'we' stand opposed to 'them'. The precise nature of the collective identity could be based upon culture, class, ethnicity, nationality, or locality amongst others.

The recognition of a common grievance or cause and the development of a collective identity contribute to the development of the third characteristic of collective action frames: the agency component. According to Gamson identification of a collective 'we' in opposition to a 'them' leads to the awareness that 'we' can do something about it. The development of a political consciousness empowers people, but only in a collective sense. Gamson recognises that overcoming feelings of political efficacy and apathy can be extremely difficult and cites writers who emphasise that political and cultural forces constantly reinforce these feelings by manipulating news media to ensure public support for existing conditions. (Gans, 1979; Bennet, 1975) The only time agency is encouraged is during elections but even then it is bounded by narrow formalised norms of what is and is not acceptable.

Thus these components of collective action frames enable groups of people to make sense of the world around them and the events which are impacting upon their daily lives. It is clear that the three components are mutually interrelated, and that the evolution of a collective action frame requires the development of all three. Nevertheless, the root out of which the others develop and collective action then emerges is the adversarial element of injustice. Clearly there can be injustice without the adversarial element and adversaries without the injustice element however as Gamson notes the link between the two should be expected because;

an injustice frame makes the injured party collective, not individual. What one has suffered personally is shared by some implied we. Righteous indignation without a 'they' at which to direct it is difficult to sustain. It is frustrating and confusing to be angry and not know whom to be angry at. An adversarial frame helps to resolve this tension by interpreting and directing the emotional component of an injustice frame. (1992, p.112)

Framing therefore is akin to Eyerman and Jamison's process of cognitive praxis in that through interaction between movement leaders and followers a process of cognitive mapping occurs. This enables people to construct meanings for events in the world around them and develop explanations. The construction of a dominant frame by movement leaders may be crucial in bringing together disparate groups who previously considered themselves separate. Whether movement leaders specifically develop the frame to attract new recruits or the frame develops as a result of interaction between movement participants it is clear that once again leaders have a crucial role to play.

Thus the role of leaders could be considered as twofold: Firstly, dealing with the day to day organisation of the movement and its activities and secondly, communication. Theorists across the spectrum of social movement theories highlight the role of leaders, entrepreneurs and intellectuals in defining the movement goals, shaping the collective identity or crystallising grievances into general beliefs. Communication appears to be at the heart of the leaders role within a movement. Whether that communication be symbolic, in terms of movement activities, or in developing and disseminating knowledge, as in Eyerman and Jamison's cognitive praxis concept. This process could be through face-to-face interaction between leaders and members. It could be through the publishing of leaflets, pamphlets or glossy magazines. It could involve utilising the mass media to spread movement messages or highlight the symbolic nature of movement activities. Regardless of the medium the communicative role of the leader does not alter.

Social Movements: The role of Leaders and Communication

What can be taken from this short overview of the myriad theoretical approaches to the study of social movements? It is possible to infer a number of conclusions from this. It is clear that communication is a central aspect of social movement theory. Communication is essential for mobilisation, for recruitment and for organisation. Furthermore movement activities are often symbolically communicative of movement goals or causes. Movements themselves can be considered as communicative networks wherein diverse ranges of groups interact. Internally, movements depend on communication, both from leaders to members and between members, to aid the construction of a collective identity, spread knowledge and disseminate information and strategies. Considered in this way it is possible to suggest that communication is at the core of social movement activities and organisation.

Furthermore, following Diani, it is clear that social movements are inextricably linked to discussions of networks and network analysis. Social movements can be thought of as communication networks, or networks of communicating groups and organisations. Internal communication networks are crucial to movement mobilisation whilst external networks are often essential for movement recruitment. Moreover, it is also clear that notions of leadership resonate throughout theoretical discussions of social movements. Whilst approaches such as RM and mass society theory stress the importance of leadership more than others it is nonetheless a regular feature. Melucci contends that movement organisation, goals and success are dependant on the actions of leaders whilst Eyerman and Jamison stress the role of movement intellectuals in the process of knowledge production, or cognitive praxis, which they claim is the unique feature of social movements.

Thus we can conclude that networks and leadership are characteristics which appear to flow throughout discussions of social movement activity. Consequently it is necessary, as Melucci notes, to move analysis of social movements away from their success in achieving goals, away from the organisation and structure they adopt to achieve this and the nature of the collective action they engage in.

Habermas & Anderson: the Public Sphere and Imagined Communities

Before endeavouring to construct some conceptual bridges between theories of public opinion and social movements I wish to explore the writings of Habermas and Benedict Anderson. Habermas's discussion on the development of a public sphere and Anderson's work on imagined communities offers useful insights into both concepts.

Habermas's writings on public opinion provide a useful bridge between the historical and the contemporary in that his is a contemporary theory examining historical processes. Furthermore in his major work on this topic, *The Structural Transformation of the Public Sphere* (1962), he develops an account of the social conditions required for the emergence of a critical public discourse around social issues such that *public* opinion becomes an force for influencing government. More specifically Habermas seeks to give an account of the conditions required for public discourse to become the basis for political action. (Calhoun, 1992)

Habermas argues that a bourgeois public sphere first emerges in Europe in the seventeenth century and in its earliest conceptions was composed of fairly narrow segments of the population, namely the educated and literate. Crucial to the development of this public sphere was the development of long-distance trade and capitalism. He argues that the growth of long-distance

trade required traffic in news in order that merchants remained abreast of foreign developments and prices. Newsletters carrying information about prices began to emerge to accommodate this and it was not long before they carried other news as well. These newsletters originally circulated only amongst merchants but public newsletters and journals of opinion soon emerged. These facilitated communication between educated and literate members of society. Also at this time literature became increasingly secular as the influence of the church over individual thoughts and actions waned. A broad reading public formed and during the eighteenth century institutions such as reading clubs, lending libraries and second-hand book stores were established to accommodate the increasing desire for reading and knowledge. Consequently, the 'public' of the public sphere was essentially those members of society who could read.

For Habermas the development of a 'public sphere' facilitates the evolution of public opinion. He attributes the growing importance of public opinion to the growth of institutions such as reading societies and the coffee-houses and salons of London and Paris where issues of state were discussed, information exchanged and conversation valued. Given that it comprised the educated bourgeoisie, small-businessmen and merchants directly effected by state decisions this newly emergent public soon believes that it should have some influence over public administration. What began to emerge therefore was a civil society counterposed to the state. Members of this critically reasoning sphere considered themselves to be in opposed to, or certainly extremely critical of, state activities. For Habermas, the bourgeois public sphere institutionalised the practice of rational-critical discourse on political matters. Public opinion is formed within a public sphere of discussion and debate. Sparked by newspapers and pamphlets debate occurs within the coffee-houses and salons and becomes a political force for challenging monarchical rule. Thus, echoing Rousseau, for Habermas public opinion emerges from collective processes of discussion.

This Habermasian discursive view of public opinion stands opposed to that identified with enlightenment liberalism, specifically public opinion as an aggregation of individual opinions. For Habermas public opinion refers to the views of those who enter into rational-critical debate. However, later developments of the public sphere move its function away from that which originally shaped its formation, with the consequence of eroding the influence of public opinion on public administration. These later developments undermine the public sphere and arise as a result of what Habermas refers to as the 'refeudalisation of society'. He argues that for the public sphere to exist there had to be the separation of the public and private realm of life. As society progresses however structural transformations occur such that private organisations begin to assume public power and the state increasingly penetrates the private sphere of life. He cites the introduction of compulsory education, military service and welfare provision as examples of this. In addition groups such as trade unions and employers begin to accrue political power. Consequently the function of the public

sphere shifts from critical debate to negotiation between groups competing to influence state decisions. Critical debate occurs between large groups and government, not between people.

This transformation of the public sphere results in an alteration in the nature of communication within society from a 'culture-debating to a culture-consuming public'. For Habermas the erosion of the public sphere means that individuals no longer engage in critical debate and consumption replaces discussion as the main function of the public sphere, thus;

When the laws of the market..also pervaded the sphere reserved for private people as a public, the rational-critical debate had a tendency to be replaced by consumption, and the web of public communication unravelled into acts of individuated reception, however uniform in mode. (1962, p.161)

Participation in public affairs is sporadic and a passive reception and reliance on the media as a means of communicating government activity replace the rational-critical debate of the earlier public sphere. For Habermas, the public sphere becomes an arena of advertising rather than a forum of critical debate. Unlike the public sphere of the 18th and early 19th centuries the public sphere of the 20th century is apolitical in nature. (Calhoun, 1992)

Habermas's account of the development and subsequent transformation of public sphere serves as a description of the historical process of the emergence, function and changing role of public opinion in Europe. His work encapsulates a number of themes of public opinion covered by many theorists on the topic. For example, Habermas's concept of public opinion clearly mirrors the discursive view established by Rousseau. Furthermore his discussion of the transformation of the public sphere from a forum for critical debate into a forum of consumption of mass media messages is also strikingly reminiscent of the works of Tonnies, Durkheim and writings on mass society. The idea that public opinion gradually moves from being born out of processes of collective discussion and becomes a function of atomised individuals reliant upon the media is also reflective of these earlier debates about the nature of mass society. Habermas does maintain however that the nature of opinion which exists within the later transformed public sphere is not the same as that which emerges from the rational-critical public sphere. It is 'popular opinion' not 'public opinion'. Public opinion can only emerge from critical debate and communication.

Social Movements in The Public Sphere

In response to Habermas critics have pointed to his omission of social movements as a possible motor for the development of a critical public sphere. For example, Calhoun (1994) notes that Habermas's notion of the public sphere conforms too loosely to an idea of the sphere

as simply a realm where individuals bring their critical ideas and enter debate. He argues that public debate and democratic politics are both influenced by the work of social movements in that movements may be crucial in bringing issues to wider attention and thus fostering critical discourse. In a similar manner, Eley (1994) argues that Habermas's conception of the public sphere excludes groups such as women, minorities and the lower classes and that those excluded gradually begin to challenge this exclusion and contest the male bourgeois conventions and logic of the public sphere, opening it to critical debate. Ryan (1994) particularly notes the perception amongst women that they were excluded from participation and the attempts by the feminist movement of the sixties to take their grievances into the public sphere through the media, academia and demonstrations. Calhoun further argues that we could consider public spheres as loose networks of discursive connections within which are contained clusters of relatively denser communicating movements.

Again therefore, notions of networks and communication surface within discussions of social movements. Nevertheless, alongside this criticism that Habermas neglects the role of social movements within the public sphere others have suggested, on the other hand, that the emergence of social movements may be dependant upon the existence of a public sphere. Boyte (1994), for example, suggests that the elements which Habermas identifies as being necessary for the development of a public sphere may also foster the developments of forms of association which operate within the sphere. For example, the emergence of social information institutions such as reading clubs and libraries developed alongside an urban culture where people gathered in public halls, museums and parks to debate. Furthermore the development of reading societies, the press, libraries and coffee salons led to a cultural change where existing principles of deference to established hierarchies began to give way to principles of critical discourse leading to voluntary associations and business groups asserting claims for a more democratic and public leadership. Arguably the development of a critical public sphere creates the conditions within which social movements can emerge and flourish.

It is possible to argue therefore that the developments of a critically reasoning and discursive public opinion may be dependent upon the activities of social movements bringing new issues to the fore and campaigning for critical debate on issues previously excluded. On the other hand, it can also be argued that social movement activity is reliant upon the existence of a critically reasoning public sphere and a culture of critical discourse, within which they can operate and relay their message. What must also be considered, however, is Habermas's contention that the critical public sphere of 17th and 18th centuries gradually erodes until a 'culture debating' public becomes a 'culture consuming' one. Thus the activities of the social movements of the 1960s, may arguably facilitate a shift *back* towards the debating public sphere of a previous era.

In this way social movement activity may influence public opinion by opening up new avenues of critical debate and encouraging the re-awakening of a critically debating public sphere around issues and topics previously either excluded (feminism, civil rights) or new (the environment).

The 'Imagined Community' of Public Opinion

Alongside these Habermasian discussions of public opinion as a form of communication, either between individuals or between individuals and governments, we must consider in slightly more abstract terms why it is that people feel that public opinion can be useful or effective in controlling government actions. In other words, given that it is possible to consider public opinion as a collective phenomenon, as discussed above, what kind of collective is it? In attempting to explore this I believe Benedict Anderson's notion of the 'Imagined Community' is a useful explanatory tool.

Anderson's most influential work *Imagined Communities* (1983) is neither a study of public opinion nor of social movements. It is instead an account of the historical development of nationalism. For Anderson nations are imagined communities;

because the members of even the smallest nation will never know most of their fellow members, meet them or even hear of them, yet in the minds of each lives the image of their communion. (p.6).

Thus the nation is an abstract concept and national identity is based in the imagination. For Anderson, national identity exists in the imagination of people and all communities larger than those characterised by face-to-face communication are considered as imagined. He goes on to say that nations can be considered as imagined in three senses. Firstly they are imagined as limited because even the largest nation has finite boundaries. Secondly they are also imagined as sovereign in that they are autonomous from other states. Finally the nation can be imagined as a community because feelings of nationalism are usually able to overcome any internal difference which may prevail within states. Thus

(the nation) is imagined as a community, because, regardless of the actual inequality and exploitation that may prevail in each, the nation is always conceived as a deep, horizontal comradeship. Ultimately it is this fraternity that makes it possible over the past two centuries, for so many millions of people, not so much to kill, as willingly to die for such limited imaginings. (p.7)

Anderson's exploration of the rise of nationalism shares much with Habermas's account of the development of a critically discursive public sphere. Like Habermas's public sphere, he contends that it is the product of the expansion of print capitalism. For Anderson, the growth of print

capitalism in the 17th and 18th centuries facilitates the growth of imagined communities of nationalism. In particular the two forms of imagining which develop at this time: the novel and the newspaper 'provided the technical means for re-presenting the *kind* of imagined community that is the nation' (p. 25). The role of novels and, more importantly, newspapers is crucial he contends.

Firstly they provide a fixed language as a 'national' language. This is so because initially books were published only in Latin and as a result the market for the printed word, namely those relatively few literate members of the populace who understood Latin, became quickly saturated. Consequently book sellers and publishers sought new markets in order to increase profits. These new markets lay within the mass of European populations and printing in the vernacular soon developed in order to exploit this. Secondly the impact of the Reformation and the desire of Protestantism to communicate in the vernacular rather than in the Latin favoured by Catholicism meant that, as a result of the propaganda war fought between the two churches, mass markets in the printed word were opened. Protestantism's use of the vernacular in the many thousands of booklets and pamphlets produced ensured that it was better able to transmit its message to the mass of the public who did not understand Latin. This rapid expansion of print capitalism has three consequences. Firstly it produces what Anderson refers to as 'unified fields of exchange' where speakers of the many varieties of English and French that existed at that time are able to understand each other through a common printed language and gradually become aware of the fellow thousands or millions to whom they are connected through language. Secondly, they give a 'fixity to language...central to the idea of the nation', establishing and embedding languages such that the initial languages and the relationship between particular languages have changed remarkably little since the 17th century. Thirdly, print capitalism creates 'languages of power' in that certain languages more resemble the vernacular adopted by print capitalism than others. Those languages not able to establish themselves in print form quickly faded from common usage, examples include Gaelic and Welsh. Anderson concludes by stating;

the convergence of capitalism and print technology on the fatal diversity of human language created the possibility of a new form of imagined community which in its basic morphology set the stage for the modern nation (p. 46)

Anderson's notion of the nation as imagined community is potentially useful in discussions of the nature of public opinion. As Anderson maintains, communities larger than face-to-face ones have to be imagined because not all members of that community can possibly know or be aware of every other member. If public opinion is considered as a collective phenomenon, as has been suggested above, then it is possible to argue that the 'public' to which we are referring is an imagined public. Although public opinion can emerge from collective processes of debate no member of the public communicates with every other. Statements therefore such as 'the public

expects' or 'public opinion favours...' utilise the concept of 'the public' in a manner consistent with Anderson's idea of imagined communities. Thus the public, in any general sense, can be considered as a particular kind of collective in that it is an imagined collective.

Anderson's notion of imagined communities, as noted above, shares much with Habermas's conclusions on the origin of the public sphere. Both attribute the emergence of critical publics/nations to the development of print capitalism and both suggest that this was responsible for bringing people together. It alerted people to their common bonds, be they bonds of language and nation or bonds based upon similar social characteristics and similar attitudes to state activities. Thus print capitalism arguably creates publics and creates the conditions for an emergent 'public' opinion.

Social Movements as Imagined Communities

Anderson's work may also illuminate discussions of social movements. I noted above that 'publics', in the sense in which they are connected to 'opinion' to make public opinion, can be considered as a form of imagined community. It is similarly possible to consider social movements as imagined communities.

Anderson suggests that communities are imagined because members will never know, meet or hear from most of their fellow members. The same can also be said of social movements. If a social movement is a network of communicating groups then it is unlikely that members of each group will know every member of every other group within the movement. Hence social movements endeavour to construct imagined communities and thus make their members feel part of a larger group, or public. Movements do this partly through high profile mediated activities. These are designed to raise consciousness and achieve results but also to send a message to those who sympathise with the movement's goals, a message saying 'you are not alone'. In this way movements can recruit new members and reassure existing ones. Another way of maintaining the notion of a movement as a community is through newsletters and campaigns. In this way disparate members, who may be scattered all over the world in the case of some movements, retain a connection to other members by learning what is occurring elsewhere. Furthermore, movements often encourage the establishment of smaller, local branches in order that their members can actively participate in achieving movement goals and thus, again, feel connected to the broader overall movement community.

In the same way, therefore, that the creation of print capitalism and unified fields of exchange allow the developments of imagined communities of nations, movement activity and

internal organisation allows for the development of an imagined community of movements. People come to view themselves as part of a broader community As a result members of Greenpeace, for example, not only see themselves as Greenpeace members but also as part of a broader environmental movement.

Conclusion: Building Conceptual Bridges

The purpose of this review of public opinion and social movement theories is not just to identify commonalities between theories of public opinion and social movements. It is instead to endeavour to isolate those concepts common to both that can be utilised in explaining collective action. From the literature I believe that it is possible to draw a number a number of conclusions regarding the commonalities between the two concepts.

Firstly, and perhaps the most significant, is the suggestion that each in their own way can be considered as communication concepts. By tracing the historical development of the public opinion concept through the works of Rousseau, Habermas, and Bentham to the contemporary works of Price the significance of communication was established. Likewise, discussions of social movements demonstrate the importance of communication within those theories that seek to account for movement emergence and development. Also important to both concepts were ideas of networks and leaders. Arguably, public opinion forms within social networks of communication comprised of family, friends and co-workers. The importance of the media for providing information, setting agendas and establishing frames of reference is not disputed but instead of regarding it as the most significant source of opinion it is viewed as contributing to processes of interpersonal communication existing within social networks. Likewise, social movements are considered as networks of smaller, disparate groups communicating with each other whilst internal communication networks ensure the flow of information throughout movement members.

Secondly, the idea of leadership is present across discussions of both concepts, opinion leaders and movement leaders. Opinion leaders appear to mobilise opinion within multi-step flows of information. Movement leaders are responsible for knowledge production and dissemination, developing strategies and even the ultimate success or otherwise of the movement. Thus concepts of communication, networks and leadership resonate throughout debates on both public opinion and social movements.

Eyerman and Jamison (1991) talk of movements being engaged in a process of cognitive praxis, or knowledge production, a process whereby movement intellectuals mobilise

groups by building a common identity or mobilising the 'collective will' of the movement. Mobilising the collective will implies a process of constructing meaning of everyday events, linking private concerns to public issues and articulating these around a developing identity. Concepts of opinion leaders tend to be utilised more mechanically than that, opinion leaders are sources of information or intervening variables between mass media and individuals. If, however, they are considered as sources of knowledge and not just information, if their role is to tell people what events mean, how they will impact on their lives and how they should respond to this then opinion leaders can also be said to be involved in a process of knowledge production. Thus the distinction between movement leader and opinion leader is blurred.

I also noted the importance the concept of a critically reasoning public sphere had for the development of public opinion and social movements. By disseminating information during meetings and in leaflets movement leaders contribute to the creation of a public sphere within which public opinion develops. Habermas noted the importance of communication to this process. Publics and movements are both imagined communities, bound by common ties of interest and identity.

Further links exist in Habermas's discussion of the public sphere and Anderson's notion of imagined communities. This paper will build on this by examining in detail a specific episode of community opposition to a contested development, specifically opposition to the construction of the M77 motorway in Glasgow. In later chapters I intend to demonstrate that opinion leaders working within networks of communication were crucial to the emergence of opposition and the development of critically reasoning public spheres. Furthermore I hope to show that the activities of social movements can help shape opinion and lead to the development of new imagined communities of protest.

Part 2: History & Context

Chapter 2 The Environment: Public Opinion, Social Movements & Protest

Introduction

The previous chapter set out to explore some of the theoretical issues around which the remainder of the discussion will revolve. Before proceeding to demonstrate the relevance of these theories to the development of community protest and collective action against the M77 I believe it is necessary to present the contextual background to this protest.

The following chapter will look more closely at the history of protest against the M77. This chapter however examines, broadly, the rise of environmentalism in the UK and the growth of environmental protest. Using Anthony Downs (1972) model of the Issue-attention cycle as a basis I will discuss the rise of public concern and changing public opinion about the environment. I hope to demonstrate that as environmental issues pass through this cycle a residue of concern is left behind which makes subsequent mobilisations of concern easier. I hope to demonstrate that this residue is drawn upon by groups seeking to capture public attention or gain sympathy from broader sections of society for specific environmental concerns. This leads to a discussion of the anti-roads movement in the UK. This will provide an overview of perhaps the most significant environmental protest movement of the 90s in Britain whilst laying the contextual foundations of later work. Finally, by examining the concept of NIMBYism I wish to reflect on the extent to which the concerns of radical environmental groups are as far removed from those of more conventional opponents of environmental developments as is typically suggested. Furthermore, I wish to discuss the potential for social movements to effect opinion change and raise consciousness amongst wider society and raise some questions which will be explored and hopefully answered in later chapters.

Public Opinion and The Environment: The Cyclical Nature of Public Concern

There can be no doubt that public concern for environmental issues has risen since the 1950s but that does not mean that environmental concern is a new phenomenon. There have been protests about environmental issues in Britain since Victorian times. This early environmental concern tended to focus upon three issues: preservation of the countryside, nature conservation and animal welfare. (Garner, 1996) The early environmental groups reflected these concerns, such as the Commons Open Spaces and Footpaths Preservation Society established in 1865, The National Trust in 1895, The Ramblers Association in 1935 and

The RSPB in 1899. Moreover, whilst these groups were largely comprised of middle class members who sought to protect the environment through lobbying, direct action to protect the environment was also a tactic used by early environmentalists. Perhaps the earliest example of environmental direct action was the Kinder Scout trespass in 1865. Organised by the Commons Preservation society this action saw a mass trespass by campaigners on land given over to aristocrats for the exclusive purpose of grouse shooting.

Although the foundations of Britain's environmental movement were established in the late 19th century it is not until the 1950s that the environment became an issue which really captured public attention. Since its emergence it is clear that environmental concern tends to develop in a relatively cyclical manner, with peaks and troughs of public anxiety for environmental issues. This cyclical nature is best summed up by Anthony Downs (1972) discussion of the issue-attention cycle.

Downs proposed a five-point model of the issue-attention cycle which describes the process whereby issues become the focus of public concern. Specifically these are: one, the pre-problem stage when the problem exists, interest groups and experts are aware of it, and may indeed be alarmed about it, but its existence is unbeknown to the general public; two, the alarmed discovery and euphoric enthusiasm stage, where specific stimuli such as environmental disasters bring the issue to the attention of a wider audience and enthusiastic support grows for tackling the problem; three, involves the realisation of the cost of progress, here public interest wanes as the gradual realisation of the cost, either fiscal or lifestyle, of solving the problem become apparent; four, declining public interest as other issues rise to the top of the agenda, the public become bored or discouraged with the previous issue so that stage five emerges. In this, the post-problem stage, the issue has been replaced as the main issue of public concern and enters into, as Downs puts it; 'a twilight realm of lesser attention or spasmodic recurrences of interest.' (pp.40) As a result of this process however the initial relation to public attention has altered. During stages 2 to 4 public interest centred on the particular issue. Consequently, policy may have been introduced or agencies established. Crucially, for Downs, the result is that the level of attention, understanding and concern for the issue is higher than before it entered the cycle and higher than issues which have not yet done so.

Downs went on to suggest that environmental issues were likely to maintain public interest for longer than other social problems for the following reasons: one, environmental problems are more noticeable and threatening than other problems; two, environmental problems are less politically divisive because they threaten everyone; three, blame for environmental problems is easily attributed to large organisations and big industry which many

people will support and relate to; four, that environmental problems can be solved by technology rather than by political or social change makes them more acceptable to many people; five, the cost of dealing with environmental problems can be passed on to the consumer rather than through higher taxes which is again more acceptable to many people; six, environmental issues may be prolonged because it may create large public or private organisations or pressure groups with an interest in maintaining the issue; seven, the ambiguity of environmental concerns allows virtually anyone to claim that their concern is part of the general environmental issue.

Downs' model is a useful explanatory tool for examination of public concern regarding the environment. As noted above environmental concern tends to be cyclical in nature, waxing and waning as issues rise and fall. By discussing this within Downs' model the rise in public concern for the environment can then be examined within a broader theoretical framework that seeks to explain the processes whereby issues enter and exit the public consciousness and the public policy arena. Of particular importance is Downs' notion that after each peak in environmental concern a 'residue' is left behind which sustains public interest, albeit at a lower general level, and which means that subsequent interest is more quickly generated and mobilised.

Despite the earlier manifestations of environmental concern discussed above it was arguably not until the 1950s that it became an issue of national political concern. The mobilising issue of that time was air pollution, specifically the 'London Smog' crisis. In December 1952 a thick fog descended over London. Lasting for four days and attributed to the burning of coal as household fuel the fog virtually eliminated visibility. Of greater concern however was the fact that almost 4000 deaths and countless respiratory complaints were attributed to the fog. In May of the following year the government established a committee of investigation. Reporting six months later The Beaver Committee concluded that;

Air pollution on the scale with which we are familiar in this country today is a social and economic evil which should no longer be tolerated (Ashby and Anderson, 1981 in Vogel, 1986, p. 38)

The recommendations made by the committee included that the government prohibit emissions of dark smoke from chimneys, require that industrial plants install equipment to filter grit and dust and allow local authorities to establish smokeless and smoke-control zones.

Although this particular example was confined to London other British cities had experienced similar problems, leading to calls for pollution controls. Combined with significant

media interest the 'London smog' was perhaps the first environmental issue to capture the attention of most if not all of the British public. Furthermore it was the first time that environmental issues had been discussed significantly by the media and public. The effect of this combination of environmental event and increased public concern culminated in the passing of The Clean Air Act in July 1956. This introduced most of the recommendations made in The Beaver Report and gave local authorities the power to declare smokeless zones within their areas. Furthermore, the Clean Air Act signified;

the beginning of a period of greater public and political concern which ensured a higher priority for the control of air pollution (Rhodes, 1981, in Vogel 1986, p. 39)

Whilst the London smog generated a great deal of concern and debate amongst the British public it did not lead to the emergence of what we would consider to be an environment 'movement'. Nevertheless it is probable that the public concern of the 1950s raised awareness such that the development of environmental protest of the 1960s was influenced by what went before it. There is little doubt that concern for environment issues increased dramatically in Britain in the 1960s, mirroring the simultaneous growth in concern for the environment that occurred throughout the western world at that time.

The publication in 1962 of Rachel Carson's *Silent Spring* is considered by many as providing the initial kick-start to the environment movement. (Cotgrove, 1982; Sandbach 1980) Carson's book dealt with the effects of pesticides in the food chain. She argued that these pesticides were harming the reproductive abilities of certain animals, particularly birds. As a result fewer and fewer eggs were hatching. The consequent lowering of the bird population would inevitably lead to a 'silent spring' as birdsong vanished. The impact of Carson's work was enhanced by the great deal of media coverage and serialisation in magazines thereby raising public awareness and concern.

A little later Paul Ehrlich's 1968 work *The Population Bomb* warned; 'The battle to feed all of humanity is upon us.' (1968, pp1) This stressed the dangers of over-population and predicted that the 70s and 80s would see millions of people starving to death due to famine. Ehrlich's work received media coverage and debate similar to that of Carson's. Allied to this a number of environmental disasters occurred or became known at this time. For example: the death of Lake Erie in the USA due to pollution from household detergents and oil discharges from passing ships; the Torrey Canyon oil spill off the coast of the UK; the mercury poisoning of Lake Minamata in Japan; and the awareness of increasing air pollution from car exhausts. (Cotgrove, 1982; O'Riordan, 1976; Sandbach, 1980) To paraphrase Downs, this 'alarmed

discovery' propelled the environment on to the public agenda and initiated widespread public concern. An effect neatly summed up by Sandbach:

The importance of the disturbing revelations of the late 60s was not only that they suddenly uncovered a mass of hitherto unsuspected environmental problems but also that they created a sense of insecurity; alarmism and predictions of catastrophe inevitably aroused fear (1982. pp31)

Concern continued to grow during the early 70s. *The Limits to Growth*, the findings of the Club of Rome were published. (Meadows et al, 1972), This report suggested that the root of the environmental crisis was exponential population growth. Growth, in population terms, would inevitably lead to resource exhaustion, famine and rising death rates. Again heavily publicised by the media, this fuelled debate and contributed to the growing awareness of environmental issues. Opinion polls reflected this environmental concern. A Gallup poll conducted in the USA in May 1970 indicated that 53% of respondents chose reducing air and water pollution as one of the three most important problems of the time. (Sandbach, 1982)

The late sixties and early seventies were the first period to display widespread public concern and a new environmental movement emerged as a result. What was new about the environmentalism that emerged in the late 60s was the direction it took, the tactics it adopted and the message it attempted to put across.

Here it is useful to make a distinction between 'old environmentalism' and what Cotgrove refers to as the 'new environmentalism' of the 60s and 70s. This is typified by the distinction between earlier environmental pressure groups such as The National Trust and those, such as Friends of the Earth, which formed as a consequence of the upsurge in environmental concern in the 60s. As mentioned previously, environmental groups formed in the 19th century and first half of the 20th century were primarily concerned with ensuring the conservation of the countryside and ancient buildings and preserving rights to walk on open countryside. Tactics usually involved consultation and low-key discussions although sometimes groups used more radical tactics to make their point. Contemporary groups however reflected a more global and catastrophic view of environmental problems. They pointed to studies such as *The Limits to Growth* indicating the finite nature of the Earth's resources and the profligate consumption of them. They warned of the dangers of population growth and argued for fundamental changes in the way society and production was organised from, in their view, destructive growth led policies to ones designed to halt and ultimately reverse these trends.

Tactics were similarly radical and designed to capture media attention. Greenpeace, for instance, first came to public attention by sailing a boat close to the site of a US nuclear test on the Aleutian Islands off the coast of Alaska. Although the bomb was eventually detonated Greenpeace were successful in delaying this and a few months later the US government announced the end of testing on the Aleutians. (Yearley, 1991) Similar scenes occurred in the South Pacific in 1995 when Greenpeace ships attempted to stop French nuclear testing on Mururoa Atoll. This new environmentalism was epitomised by a call for social change and a challenge to the dominant social paradigm of industrialism. (Cotgrove, 1982) A number of indicators serve to confirm growing environmental concern and changing public opinion.

The lack of clear and consistent survey data on environmental concern during the early 70s means that the growth in numbers and membership of green pressure groups is the best indicator of public awareness of environmental issues at this time. (See Table 2.1) For instance Greenpeace, founded in 1971, has by 1990 327 000 members. Most of this growth occurred between 1985 and 1990 but the years in between show steadily rising memberships. Membership of traditional groups also increased. For example, membership of The RSPB more than trebled between 1967 and 1972 whilst membership of the National Trust increased by over 180 000 in the same period. (Sandbach, 1980)

Table 2.1 *Increase in the membership of major environmental groups 1971-1989*

Group	1971	1980	1985	1989
Greenpeace		10 000	50 000	320 000
FOE	1 000	12 000	27 000	120 000
WWF	12 000	51 000	91 000	202 000
Ramblers	22 000	36 000	50 000	73 000
National Trust		950 000	1.32m	1.75m
CPRE	21 000	27 000	26 500	44 500
RSNC	64 000	140 000	165 000	205 000
RSPB	98 000	321 000	390 000	433 000

Source: Garner (1996)

Public policy of the late 60s and early 70s mirrored this rising public concern. In the U.K. a standing Royal Commission on Environmental Pollution was established whilst legislation such as the Control of Pollution act was passed in 1974. Both the 70-74 Conservative governments and the incoming Labour government passed bills controlling pollution indicating political recognition of changing public opinion. In the USA similar institutions were established and legislation passed. For example, the National Environmental Policy Act was passed in 1969. In 1970 The Environmental Protection Agency and the President's Council on Environmental

Quality were both established. The Clean Air Act was introduced in the same year and the Federal Water Pollution Control Act was passed in 1972. (O'Riordan, 1976; Sandbach 1980)

In 1973, one year after the establishment of the world's first green political party in New Zealand, Europe's first environmental political party was founded in Britain. Initially named 'People' in 1975 it became the Ecology Party and in 1985 The Green Party. Its ideology was motivated by much of the limits to growth debate and stressed the need for radical social and economic change, the benefits of an ecological society and the promotion of de-industrialisation and decentralisation.

It is apparent therefore that the late 60s witnessed a burst of concern for environmental issues. Later research highlights the fact that this concern waned during the 70s but remained higher than previous times. Sandbach (1980) examines survey data from the USA and Britain that indicates that the take-off point for public concern was the late 60s, reaching a peak in 1972. Environmental concern declined, as did legislation and pressure group membership. Nevertheless the dramatic growth in group membership in the late 60s alongside the increased public concern at the same time meant that a residue of public concern for the environment remained.

Within Downs' issue-attention cycle it can be suggested that public opinion and concern for the environment developed very slowly throughout most of the 20th century, remaining at the pre-problem stage until the late 60s when scientific evidence and environmental disasters brought it to the attention of the public. This discovery and concern prompted government action such as new policies and agencies. During the early 70s however the issue passed through to at least stage four as public concern declined. This was perhaps a response to the fact that publics believed that the policies implemented were solving the environmental problem or the fact that other issues, such as rising inflation, took centre stage. The environment had not however entered the post-problem stage. Concern for the environment remained higher than previous levels and as the 70s progressed the residue of concern became focussed on new issues, particularly the issue of nuclear power and nuclear weapons.

Yearley (1991) details the work of Greenpeace throughout the 70s. Buoyed by their success in the Aleutians Greenpeace spent the following two years in the South Pacific protesting against French nuclear testing. The press in North America and Europe were happy to show pictures of Greenpeace vessels being 'intimidated' by French warships and boarded by French troops. All of this raised awareness of the issue and brought it to worldwide attention. Rudig (1991) highlights the campaign against the construction of a nuclear reprocessing plant at

Sellafield that raised a great deal of anti-nuclear feeling. In 1978 and 1979 demonstrators protesting against the construction of a nuclear power plant at Torness occupied the construction site, gaining substantial media coverage. Similar demonstrations in Cornwall in 1981 kept the issue on the agenda. By 1981 however attention was focusing more closely upon nuclear weapons rather than power. The Campaign for Nuclear Disarmament (CND) was the major mobilising group involved. Large demonstrations were held and a peace camp established at the United States Air Force base at Greenham Common, in protest at the siting of Cruise missiles at the base.

By the late 1980s environmental concern had shifted from mainly national to global issues such as the Ozone layer and global warming and environmental awareness and concern increased greatly at this time. A number of indicators highlight this. Opinion polls conducted for Friends of the Earth prior to the 1987 General Election revealed that 81% of those polled believed that the government should give a much higher priority to protecting the environment. The 1987 British Social Attitudes report revealed a similar rise in concern. The percentage of people feeling that the issue of waste from nuclear power stations was a very serious issue rose from, an already high, 82% to 90% in one year. (Porritt & Winner, 1988) A Gallup poll conducted in November 1988 indicated that the percentage of people who felt that water pollution was a serious issue had risen to 44% compared to 35% in a similar survey in 1985.

Dalton (1988) conducted a cross-European study of social attitudes and indicated that concern for the environment rose Europe-wide throughout the 1980s. His results, taken from Eurobarometer studies, revealed that over 90% of respondents in West Germany, France and the UK believed the environment to be an important issue. Significantly, the majority of respondents indicated that the environment was more important an issue than both economic growth and prices.

Gallup regularly conducts opinion polls that ask respondents to identify the first and second most important issues facing the country at that time. The environment does not appear as a specific concern on the survey results until early 1989 but quickly takes off. The result of these polls show the percentage of respondents listing the environment as the most or the second most pressing problem facing the country. Environmental concern grew rapidly during 1989. The early months of 1989 saw the environment top the political agenda. In February Prime Minister Thatcher hosted an international conference on ozone depletion. The Exxon Valdez oil spill in Alaska occurred in March 1989. The media covered both extensively, especially the Exxon Valdez disaster. Water privatisation was also the subject of intense debate and media coverage. This concern culminated in July 1989 when figures peaked at 28%. The figures

decline in the later months of 1989 before jumping again in January 1990, the result of increased debate surrounding water privatisation and pollution and further media coverage of the ozone depletion issue. A further jump in May 1990 may be attributable to the increased awareness of the issue of climate change and the greenhouse effect brought on by media coverage of an international conference on the issue held in Norway. At this, other countries accused the UK of dragging its feet in attempting to limit harmful CFC emissions. Steady decline continues throughout 1990 and 1991 until the Rio earth summit in June 1992 prompts an 8% increase to 10%. (Young, 1992)

The July 1989 peak of 28% followed from the unprecedented success of The Green Party in the European elections of the previous month. The electoral record of the party since its birth had been poor. It did not come to nation-wide attention until the 1979 General Election when it ran 53 candidates, a number sufficient to qualify for access to television and radio for party election broadcasts. However the party did achieve some gains at the local level and by 1987 it had 55 local councillors. Nevertheless, the highest percentage of the vote they had received was 5.9%. In 1989 however the Green party attained 14.9% of the vote in the European election reflecting the growing public concern for environmental issues. Party membership also grew from 650 in 1979 to 18 500 in 1990. (Young, 1993)

Opinion polls and elections are not the only indicators of public opinion concerning the environment. The 1980s witnessed a massive growth in membership of environmental groups and the birth of green consumerism. As Table 1.1 indicated, the membership of Greenpeace doubled between 1986 and 1988 and by 1990 had risen to 327 000 members, six times as many as 1985. Membership of the RSPB rose also and by 1992 The National Trust had 1.8 million members. Overall, membership of green groups had risen from 2 million in 1980 to 5 million by 1988, with a combined income of over £170 million.

Rudig et al (1990) however contend that the most dramatic development of the rise in public opinion for the environment was the emergence of green consumerism. They cite MORI polls which indicated that those who purchased 'environmentally friendly' goods rose from 19% in September 1988 to 47% in July 1989. Similarly, the numbers of those using lead-free petrol also rose by almost 10%, although this may be the result of its tax-advantaged status.

To what extent did policy change or develop in recognition of changing public opinion? The period 1988-93 witnessed a flurry of policies designed, apparently, to protect or conserve the environment. The most significant Government response to increased environmental concern was the White Paper *This Common Inheritance* published in September 1990. This

catalogued more than 350 measures taken by the government to improve the environment. Government actions outlined in the White paper often involved 'promoting measures which encourage', or continuing 'to support the work of environmental bodies', or 'to make people more aware'. This led critics to point to its failure to address global issues and its unimaginative approach. (Young, 1993) Major legislation enacted in this time included the 1990 Environmental Protection Act (EPA). This introduced increased penalties for littering, obligations on local authorities to control litter, and new powers for local authorities to reduce noise. It sought to impose tighter controls on air and water pollution and regulation of waste disposal. Dumping of wastes at sea was restricted, and local authorities had to separate their roles as waste collectors and regulators of waste sites thus avoiding possible conflicts of interest. Penalties and prison sentences were introduced as deterrents and punishments for those companies or local authorities that did not meet the new standards. Recycling of waste was also promoted.

At the local level, local authorities were required to consider sustainable development when formulating structure plans and economic initiatives. Environmental Impact Assessments were given a statutory basis in 1991 whereby developers must give an Environmental Statement with documents seeking planning permission. This must assess the environmental impact of the development in terms of its effect on air and water quality, and noise pollution. Significantly, efforts to deal with nuclear waste were limited whilst transport policy remained committed to promotion of increased car and road use with no emphasis given to improving public transport. (Young, 1993) Consequently, it can be argued that during this period a veneer of environmental respectability was applied to many existing policies whilst new legislation did not go far enough to satisfy green pressure groups. The late 80s and early 90s therefore mirrors the previous period of rapid increases in public environmental concern. As in the late 60s and early 70s government policy emerged as a response to changing public opinion.

The reasons for this resurgence in environmental concern that manifested in the above indicators and policy outcomes are similar to those that prompted the initial burst in the late 60s. Once again it is possible to trace this rise in concern for the environment through Downs' issue-attention cycle and it is clear that a broadly similar pattern to that of the 50s, 60s and 70s emerges. However, due to the relatively high levels of concern in the late 70s and early 80s for the issue of nuclear power and weapons the next wave which emerged in the late 80s began from point of increased awareness. As a result there is no real stage 1 or 2 of the issue-attention cycle to go through, no alarmed discovery of the environment as a concern, but instead the alarmed discovery and addition of other specific environmental issues to an existing area of public interest. Consequently, public opinion is quicker to mobilise and form around particular environmental issues. Of crucial importance was the effect of specific stimuli such as

environmental disasters. There was no shortage of environmental disasters in the 1980s with Chernobyl and The Exxon Valdez perhaps the two most significant and best remembered. Scientific evidence pointing to the discovery of the greenhouse effect and holes in the ozone layer also reinforced much of the literature of the 70s. The response of pressure groups and the media to these events were also crucial. Environmental groups were quick to seize on scientific evidence or point to disasters as proof their arguments. The media likewise were quick to publicise environmental issues and offer groups platforms to discuss their claims. Further credibility came in a speech to the Royal Society in 1988 when Prime Minister Margaret Thatcher declared her commitment to the environment, in particular to tackling the problem of global warming. The consequences of these, and of existing heightened awareness of the environment as a consequence of the concern of the 70s and early 80s, was that the environment quickly rose to the top of the agenda.

Whilst Downs' model is useful in describing the flow of public concern for the environment and the process whereby issues enter and exit the public consciousness, Inglehart (1977) offers a complementary theory which seeks to explain the rise in environmental concern. He attributes the growth of environmentalism not to events, such as environmental catastrophes, but instead to changes in the value systems of society. Specifically he proposes that societies shifted from domination by materialist values towards post-materialist. The affluence, peace and prosperity that typified western post-war societies have resulted in the fulfilment of primary material needs such as food, shelter and economic security. When these needs have been met the individual seeks to meet 'higher-order values' such as self-expression, self-fulfilment, participation and freedom. Environmentalism complements post-materialism by its rejection of industrial and economic growth its criticism of materialism and its promotion of decentralisation.

For Inglehart, the rise in environmental consciousness is a consequence of the structural changes to society which occurred post WW2. These structural changes include: increasing wealth and prosperity; improved education; changes in occupational structure (rise of new middle-class); development of a welfare state and the security it brings; and a greater redistribution of wealth.

His theory rests on two key hypothesis: firstly, a scarcity hypothesis which says that an individuals' priorities reflect the socio-economic environment and that people place the greatest subjective value on those things which are in short supply. This implies that humans experience a hierarchy of needs. Physiological needs, such as the need for food and shelter, take precedence over economic needs for security and jobs which take precedence over psychological or social needs, such as the need for self-expression and self-actualisation. Inglehart bases much of this on

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the work of Abraham Maslow, who first developed the idea that people have a hierarchy of needs. The result of the structural changes which occurred post WW2 is that for the majority of people their basic physiological and economic needs are met. Prolonged periods of prosperity encourage individuals to seek to meet their psychological needs. This is reflected in the emergence of post-materialist values. The prosperity of the 50s and 60s produced a distinct generation of economically secure people who could afford to be concerned with higher order, post-materialist issues such as the environment. Furthermore, the establishment of a welfare state results in a decline in class conflict and leads to the development of a different type of political participation, one more concerned with single issues, which do not necessarily revolve around economic concerns.

Inglehart concedes that it is not enough to say that increased prosperity automatically leads to change in values, he suggests that values are also influenced by the cultural setting in which people are raised, in other words socialisation. This leads to his second 'socialisation' hypothesis, which suggests that the relationship between socio-economic environment and value priorities is not one of immediate adjustment: A substantial time lag is involved because people's values reflect the conditions that prevailed during their pre-adult years.

It is for this reason that post-materialist values do not start emerging until the 60s and 70s. Post-materialism does not emerge overnight, it develops gradually as one generation replaces another. Inglehart suggests that it might be 10 years after an era of prosperity before the age cohorts who were raised in that time begin to enter the electorate, and another 10 years before they enter positions of power and are able to change anything.

Inglehart's theory complements Downs' model in that both suggest that issues compete with each other for public attention. Inglehart seeks to demonstrate why certain issues become more important at particular times, whilst Downs describes the process through which this issue rises to prominence. In addition Inglehart's theory takes a long-term perspective in attempting to explain the rise of environmentalism whilst Downs, on the other hand, adopts a more short-term view of competing issues rising to the top of the agenda.

Linked to Inglehart's theory Lowe & Goyder (1983) suggest that level of environmental concern is influenced by the economic cycle. That; 'periods of sudden growth (of environmental groups) occurred towards the end of periods of sustained economic growth.' (pp25) The periods of greatest growth in environmental concern in post-war Britain, the late 60s and late 80s, were also the ends of periods of sustained economic growth. Firstly the post-war boom of the fifties and sixties which finally ended in the early 70s; and secondly the boom times of the mid 80s which shuddered to a halt in 1990. These periods of growth enabled individuals to fulfil their

materialist needs and move onto post-materialist ones. When recession set in concern quickly shifted back to meeting materialist needs and concern for the environment diminished.

Dalton (1988) attempted to determine whether a value change had occurred in the United States and Europe during the 1980s. He did this by assessing the priorities of individuals surveyed and assigning them to a scale of those exhibiting only materialist views, those exhibiting only post-materialist views and those exhibiting both. Dalton's work revealed that whilst the number of respondents expressing post-materialist values was still far behind those expressing exclusively materialist ones there was a noticeable trend towards post-materialism. In Great Britain in 1970 the number of respondents with post-materialist priorities was 8% by 1984 this had risen to 17%; similarly West Germany, France and the USA all indicate a rise of between 6 and 11%. Significantly, Dalton's study indicates that although post-materialist values are not dominant in any country, more than half of respondents expressed some post-materialist views leading him to support the value change theory.

Thus it can be argued that the pattern of changing public opinion during the 80s matches that of the 50, 60 & 70s with one exception. According to Downs the environment had already passed through the issue-attention cycle, it was therefore starting from a slightly higher base of concern during the 80s. Issues and events during the previous decade had maintained interest. Specific stimuli, such as the Exxon Valdez, and Chernobyl, led to growing alarm, growth in group membership and calls for action as the issue again passed through stage 2 of the cycle. Other issues then become more important such as fears about unemployment and job security and the issue goes through stages 3 and 4 until by 1993 it has entered the post-problem stage once again. However, as with the 70s, environmental concern did not completely fade away. During the 70s attention switched from issues of global concern such as population growth and others such as air and water pollution to the issue of nuclear power. In this way it is possible to see how Downs' model and Inglehart's theory are linked and complementary.

Public concern for the environment increased during the 90s as the recession ended. It did not, however, rise to the level of the 80s. This was not because of a lack of environmental disasters, but because other issues tended to dominate the news at this time. Nevertheless there were some significant developments during this time including the 1992 United Nations Conference on Environment and Development, more commonly known as the Rio Earth Summit. The summit resulted in five agreements. The first was the Rio Declaration, a set of guiding principles for national and international environmental behaviour. The second was Agenda 21, which sought to highlight the inter-connection between environmental destruction and international development and demonstrate appropriate approaches, at all levels of

government, to reconciling the two. Those remaining were a Declaration on Forest Principles, a Convention on Climate Change and a Convention on Biological Diversity. Critics of the Rio agreements pointed to the lack of firm commitments on a number of important issues, particularly third-world debt. Despite this however Rio demonstrated the first truly international attempt to deal with environmental problems and was undoubtedly a response to the globalisation of environmentalism that occurred during the 80s. A further summit in 1997, The Kyoto Global Climate Change Conference, continued this approach. (Connelly & Smith, 1999)

There were also a number of policy developments in the UK during the 90s. The most significant being the establishment of The Environment Agency in 1995 and in Scotland The Scottish Environmental Protection Agency. This brought together the functions of a number of government departments under one agency and proposed a unified holistic approach to environmental protection.

The cyclical nature of environmental politics is apparent from the above overview of public opinion and concern for green issues. It is clear, as Downs proposed, that each wave of environmental concern passes through stages of public salience, from pre-problem to post-problem. It is also apparent that each cycle of concern appears to leave behind a sediment of public awareness which the next wave draws upon to influence and mobilise opinion. Furthermore, it is also evident that the works of Inglehart and Downs complement each other in this regard giving an explanatory theory or model of developing environmental consciousness which is based upon both long-term factors such as socialisation and economic security and precipitating factors such as specific stimuli. In the 90s public concern for the environment did recede, with the exception of one significant area, namely road building. In many respects however the anti-road movement which developed in the UK was unique in that it was a coalition of a diverse range of groups. On the one hand there were so called eco-warriors who engaged in direct action in an attempt to halt road developments. On the other hand there were numerous local amenity and community groups who also endeavoured to stop construction and whilst the means may have differed the end was, arguably, the same. There can be no doubt that there was a broad spectrum of people engaged in opposition to road construction in the UK. It could be argued that this depth and range of feeling was the result of the combination of long-term and precipitating factors which also influenced earlier waves of environmental concern. Certainly the roads issue seemed to mobilise a specifically politicised generation who grew up in the 80s when the environment was at the top of the agenda, and once again the 'residue' of earlier waves was drawn upon by those that followed in order to mobilise concern.

As noted above, perhaps the most unusual nature of the anti-roads movement was the fact that it brought radical and conventional political groups together under one cause. Different strategies and tactics were often utilised but each had the same goal, namely to stop the construction of roads, or specific road developments. It has largely been assumed that this was a coalition between radical environmentalists and conservative NIMBYists, a pragmatic union of local and global interests. However, this needs exploration to determine if this is indeed the case. The remainder of this chapter sets out to examine the nature of the radical environmentalism which surfaced around the roads issue and the local opposition to which it was frequently united. Beginning with a discussion of the eco-warrior wing of the movement and followed by a discussion of NIMBYism what follows aims to raise some questions which will be tackled in later chapters.

Social Movements and the Environment: The UK Anti-Road Movement

It is often suggested that the UK anti-road movement was born at Twyford Down in 1992 when protestors gathered to protest and oppose the construction of the M3. Road protests had however been occurring, in some form, in Britain for almost 100 years. The significance of Twyford Down was the fact that it marked a new era in roads protesting, the era of large-scale direct action protests against roads as symbols of a society dominated by capitalism and consumerism.

Wall (1999) covers the history of anti-road and anti-car protest in Britain and points out that protests against roads have been a recurring part of British life for almost as long as there have been cars requiring them. He describes Victorian opponents to the motor vehicle as being primarily motivated by a desire to protect the livelihoods of livery stable workers but also notes that the growth of car use in Britain prompted a demand for better and more roads. Increased car use had the consequence of more deaths on the road and, in light of this, the government of the time established a Royal Commission on Transport in 1928 and the establishment of the Pedestrians' Association for Road Safety in 1929.

The first to propose the idea of a comprehensive motorway network were The Institution of Highway Engineers who, in 1936, advocated the construction of 2800 miles of motorway. Two years later The County Surveyors' Society proposed constructing 1000 miles of motorway, basing their ideas and proposals on the success of existing motorway networks in Germany and Italy. Faced with a booming economy and steadily growing car ownership rates successive post-war governments placed their faith in motorways as essential to Britain's economic future. The 1946 Labour government closely followed the 1938 suggestions by announcing plans for 1000

miles of new trunk roads and motorways to link major cities and industrial areas. Over the next three years legislation was passed giving Ministers the power to modify and expand the trunk road network and to designate roads only for certain classes of traffic. Work on those roads proposed in the 1946 plan did not begin until the mid-1950s and in 1958 Britain's first motorway, the Preston By-Pass, was opened. One year later the first major length of the motorway network in Britain was running with the opening of the first 72 mile section of the M1. Construction accelerated in the 1960s as governments revised road programmes to accommodate economic growth and increased car ownership. By 1967 500 miles of motorways were completed and by 1973 the 1946 target of 1000 miles was achieved. Furthermore, by this time, 3500 miles of new trunk roads and 2000 miles of new motorways were proposed. (Hughes, 1980)

Unsurprisingly not everybody welcomed the construction of so many miles of new motorway and opposition emerged. Painter (1981) identifies three distinct phases of motorway opposition in Britain up to 1979, and notes that as each phase developed opposition, in terms of the issues under discussion, became increasingly wider. The first phase mainly involved local landowners, particularly farmers, objecting to loss of land, livelihood and property values. The Ministry of Transport effectively dealt with protests of this nature through consultation and compensation procedures. The second phase identified by Painter occurred during the 1960s when national and local amenity societies became involved in opposing motorway construction. Generally however this opposition centred on issues of aesthetics and design and of ensuring that the motorway in question posed no real threat to the look of the countryside. Consequently they did not question the programme overall and therefore did not necessarily hinder the acceleration of motorway construction. With the advent of the 1970s however motorway opposition took a new and more militant form and this is the third phase identified by Painter. In many respects this more militant phase of opposition was a result of what was perceived as highly undemocratic planning procedures and public inquiries. This, allied with the growth of the environmental movement and groups such as Friends of the Earth entering the debate, ensured that previous motorway protests which focussed on the route of roads were replaced by protests which questioned the need of the roads programme itself. Protests at this time challenged not only the need for roads but also the legitimacy of the participation process. Public Inquiries became long drawn-out 'highly charged political arenas.' (Painter, 1981, p.214) Protestors complained that the rules were set out in such a way as to ensure that the government could not be defeated and that the, by now, Department of Transport (DoT) did not act in the interests of the public but rather in the interests of the road lobby. John Tyme's 1978 book *Motorway versus Democracy* provides an account of many such protests he was involved in at this time, its title captures his feelings about the democratic process surrounding motorway developments. In the introduction he notes that the 1973 public inquiry into the M42 motorway was the first where

protestors were able to challenge the road on the basis of need and therefore challenge the road programme itself.

The protests of these times did successfully delay the construction of many proposed roads. Painter notes that in 1969 schemes usually took four years to complete but by 1973 it was up to ten years. Furthermore as the economic crises of the mid-70s forced governments to cut public spending the plans of the 60s and 70s struggled to come to fruition. The 1977 Labour government published a transport white paper which set a spending ceiling of £300 million per year for new motorways, a ceiling which persisted until the early 1980s. The Conservative governments of this time were however more favourably inclined towards the construction of new roads. Road construction fitted nicely with what Margaret Thatcher referred to as the 'great car economy' and broader encouragement of out-of-town retail and leisure developments heavily dependent on car use for success. (McNeish, 1997) In 1989, and faced with forecasts which predicted massive increases in traffic, the Conservatives announced their £23 billion 'Roads to Prosperity' programme. It was this programme which led to the development of 'the fourth and most militant phase of opposition to road building in Britain' (McNeish, 1997, p.3)

This fourth phase had its roots in protests that occurred prior to the publication of 'Roads to Prosperity' when in 1988 the DoT announced plans to spend up to £20 million improving the road system around London. This was to include road widening, new bypasses and the construction of new motorways. A number of local groups sprang up in opposition to these proposals, eventually a London-wide alliance emerged, and Alarm (later Alarm UK) formed. The tactics of this group included media-friendly publicity stunts, mass letter writing and direct action; and they were successful. In 1990 the Conservative government announced that the proposed new road developments for London were being withdrawn. The success of this new-style of protest, with its emphasis on opposition outwith planning procedures and public inquiries, laid the tactical foundations for further roads protests during the 1990s. (McNeish, 1997)

The new militant phase of the late 80s intensified in the 90s as road protests exploded onto the political agenda. The catalyst for this was the extension of the M3 motorway through the ancient chalk downland of Twyford Down. Statutorily this was one of the most heavily protected areas of countryside in Britain in that it contained two Sites of Special Scientific Interest, one Area of Outstanding Natural Beauty and two ancient monuments. Local opposition to the proposal had existed for over twenty years and there had been public Inquiries in 1971, 1976 and 1985. In 1992 however a new type of anti-road protestor joined locals. The Twyford Down protest is widely regarded as being the birthplace of the UK anti-road direct action movement

and saw the first involvement of groups such as Earth First (EF) in motorway opposition. These protests differed from previous ones in both the tactics utilised by protestors and their goals.

Although the M3 was the focus the overall goals of the eco-warrior wing of the anti-road movement are more expansive. Roads are seen to be a symptom of a society dedicated to consumption and industrialisation. Indeed the notion of rejecting the culture of consumerism promoted by what is perceived as a centralised, undemocratic state is often central to the motivations of the anti-road movement. (Doherty, 1996) From Twyford Down roads protests expanded throughout Britain and included such protests as the M11 link road in London, the M65 near Blackburn, the M77 in Glasgow, the Newbury Bypass and the Fairmile protest in Dorset. Roads protest and construction shot to the top of both the news and the political agenda on numerous occasions throughout the 90s.

Although described as a 'movement' it is inaccurate to suggest that the anti-road movement can be encapsulated within one or two groups. A number of protest organisations have developed around the issue of road building. These include local amenity groups and communities. These groups have often protesting for many years against road developments with limited success. Typically they are said to have a NIMBY (Not-In-My-Back-Yard) approach to opposition which seeks to alter the route of the road such that its effects are displaced. Also involved in opposing roads are the more established core environmental groups such as Friends of the Earth and the Council for the Protection of Rural England. Their involvement usually revolves around lobbying government and offering legal guidance and advice to campaigners. Alongside these have emerged radical 'disorganisations' such as Earth First! and Reclaim The Streets and strategic groups such as ALARM UK and Road Alert. Lastly various 'tribes' have developed such as the Dongas, the Flowerpot and the Rainbow tribes. These are mostly New Age Travellers, or young people concerned about the issue of road building. They follow a specific lifestyle geared towards protest and move around from protest site to protest site. Roads may not be the only issue against which they protest but in the 90s it was probably the most prevalent. Composition fluctuates however and some established groups are not keen on getting involved with radical groups.

Of the groups involved perhaps the most significant have been Earth First, ALARM UK and Reclaim the Streets (RTS). The latter two developed from the successful protests against the proposed construction of new motorways in London announced in 1988. Earth First! however first came to significant prominence during the Twyford Down protest when it united with local

residents and the Dongas tribe¹. (Rowell, 1996) The principles of Earth First stress protecting the environment and challenging the existing assumptions and acceptance of growth dominated society. Furthermore it makes a great deal out of the fact that it is not a pressure group, not even an organisation, and instead refers to itself as a movement, sometimes a disorganisation, with no committees, boards or employees.

The radical direct-action wing of the anti-road movement that first surfaced at Twyford Down tended to come from those environmental activists dissatisfied with the rather passive stance taken by existing groups such as FoE. They criticised these groups for being too big, too bureaucratic and hierarchical, too concerned with getting their subscriptions and too busy giving talks to international heads of government. Their strategy and tactics are made up of a combination of radical deep ecology and limited reformism. Eco-warriors and EF represent the deep ecological wing, whilst groups such as ALARM UK, FoE, and often local groups, tend to attempt change through reformist incremental means such as lobbying, and Public Inquiries.

Tactics include building camps on the road route forcing contractors to evict them. These camps usually involve a mixture of tents, treehouses and underground tunnels. Eviction is often a long and messy legal process. After legal eviction they have to be forcibly evicted and protestors try to ensure that this will be as difficult, protracted and expensive for the authorities as they possible can. This involves chaining themselves to equipment, or hiding in treehouses and tunnels. These are frequently dangerous activities but crucially a lot of time and money is expended in removing them. Central to the anti-road protestors is the idea that the medium is message: In other words, the method of protest is often a symbolic appeal to public opinion. The media is a crucial tool for Eco-warriors, by getting their message on to television they broaden the debate, inform and inspire others to act. This quote from a protestor at the M77 protest sums up this attitude;

The more we get on TV the better. We're trying to use TV and the media, to get people off their arses, to get them angry, and get them involved. (in Seel, 1997)

It is clear that whilst the issue of roads provided the catalyst for the anti-road movement to mobilise it is not concerned merely with roads but with all aspects of the environment. It is particularly concerned with building a new consensus that replaces the post-war culture of growth and industrialisation. Eco-warriors are concerned with the notion of rejecting the current culture of consumerism, materialism and what is perceived as an increasingly centralised

¹ The Dongas were mostly young people who had established camps on Twford Down to oppose the road construction. The name derives from the ancient paths and track which criss-crossed

undemocratic state. Road protest, therefore, is merely a reaction to the state's undemocratic activities, however road building is not the only issue which motivates eco-warriors. Quality of life issues such as freedom and participation also motivate movements like this. For many of the front-line Eco-warriors this counter culture is grounded not only in respect for nature but in a desire to protect the earth, and is often distinguished by a belief in spirituality, magic and paganism. Activists describe drawing their power from the land they are seeking to protect.

Thus, it seems that in many respects, roads protest forms only one aspect of the life of an Eco-warrior. The issue often acts as a catalyst for action but is perhaps not the driving force behind their behaviour. Instead the ultimate aim is to attack the cultural acceptance of environmental destruction which roads, possibly more than any other development in the UK in the 90s, contributed to. Alongside this redefinition is also an attempt to redefine the relationship between mankind and the land from the existing one of exploitation to one of respect and reverence.

In terms of their effectiveness, it is argued that the anti-road movement has been effective in four ways. (Doherty, 1998) Firstly, they have challenged the hegemony of the idea of roads as the solution to transport problems. By demonstrating the effect roads have on the environment and pointing to the less environmentally harmful alternatives, anti-road protestors challenged the public assumption and government belief that roads were the answer to transport congestion. Secondly, there have been cuts in the roads programme. Cuts in 1994 saw the cancellation or postponement of a third of proposed roads and in 1995 the remainder were also cut by a third. Thirdly, there has been a challenge to established environmental groups. Groups such as FoE have been forced to respond to these new groups and made to reconsider the worth of existing strategies. Lastly there has been the promotion of shifting attitudes from NIMBY (Not In My Backyard) to NOPE (Not On Planet Earth). By joining local protests against roads, it is suggested that anti-road protestors have endeavoured to raise consciousness amongst the wider public. They have sought to politicise people to environmental concerns and to demonstrate that roads are not local problems but global problems also. It is this I now wish to explore.

NIMBY to NOPE? The Impact of Social Movements

The potential of radical movements to facilitate wider societal changes in attitudes is noted by a number of writers in this field. For example, for Melucci, social movements expose to public debate that which is hidden by the decision-making process. Moreover, movement activity;

is in itself a message broadcast to society conveying symbolic forms and relational patterns which cast light on the 'dark side of the moon' - a system of meanings which runs counter to the sense that the apparatuses (of state and media) seek to impose on individual and collective events. (1992, p.75)

Furthermore, the form of the movement is also a message, an example of alternative methods of organisation. Form is not a means to an end but rather an end in itself, constituting 'cultural laboratories' where movements test their ability to challenge dominant meanings. Thus movements seek to influence society by challenging dominant perceptions of issues presented by government and media, exposing these issues to public discussion and offering alternatives to culturally dominant messages. In a later article he notes the inroads social movements have made into political debate, daily habits, forms of relationship and the collective consciousness. He concedes however that there is a conceptual gap which extends from everyday life experience to collective action; in other words how do people make connections between their everyday individual concerns and the concerns of contemporary social movements? Although writing some time earlier, Habermas noted the potential for social movements to make connections with everyday life concerns.

I discussed earlier the work of Inglehart in relation to explaining changes in public opinion regarding the environment. Inglehart's work has also significantly influenced the writings of Habermas on the topic of the emergence of social movements. Habermas (1987) notes the advent of new areas of conflict, which have arisen since the 1960s. These:

arise in domains of cultural reproduction, social integration and socialisation; they are carried out in sub-institutional, or at least extra-parliamentary, forms of protest; ..the new conflicts are not ignited by distribution problems but by questions having to do with the grammar of forms of life. (p.392).

Thus new social movements are distinguished from previous political movements by the issues which motivate them and the tactics adopted to achieve their aims. Traditional political movements are concerned largely with the issue of resource distribution, either achieving a more equitable distribution or maintaining existing differences; tactics are located within the bureaucratic structure of post-war corporatist politics. For Habermas, new social movements develop as a consequence a crisis of legitimation in modern society.

Habermas contends that amongst advanced societies mass demands are generated by individuals, demands that may be either materialist or post-materialist. These demands are such that the state can only satisfy them by altering the cultural and economic basis of the way of life

for large sections of the population. Furthermore, individuals find it difficult to adequately articulate these demands within the existing political structure and come to question their loyalty to the state. The state, in an attempt to offset this crisis of legitimation, extends its activities into previously autonomous socio-cultural areas of citizen activity and increasingly regulates citizens' lives. The result of this process is paradoxical however, for whilst the states authority is extended the need for legitimation for increased government intervention grows. For Habermas, this leads to the politicisation of areas of life previously ruled by tradition. Political conflict occurs because;

The end effect is a consciousness of the contingency, not only of the contents of tradition, but also of the techniques of tradition. The stirring up of cultural affairs that are taken for granted thus furthers the politicisation of areas of life...But this development signifies danger for the civil privatism that is secured informally through the structures of the public realm. Efforts at participation and the plethora of alternative models..are indicators of this danger, as is the increasing number of citizen initiatives. (1976, p.72)

For Habermas, the consequence of this process is that legitimation deficits occur and conflict develops. He believes social movements are reactions to the increasing rationalisation of society and life, a process he referred to as 'the colonisation of the lifeworld'.(1987) He argues that advanced societies are split into two realms: lifeworld and system. The lifeworld refers to the realm of personal relationships and socio-cultural norms. This is distinguished from media-steered subsystems (power and money) which gradually extend their power and influence into the lifeworld. New social movements (NSMs) develop at the seam between both, where system and lifeworld come into conflict. Their goal is to resist the system's colonisation of the lifeworld. He distinguishes between two types of social movements which emerge as a result of this process: resistance and withdrawal, and emancipatory. The former includes environmental groups whilst he contends that the feminist movement is the best example of the latter. He further divides resistance movements into two; those which seek to defend tradition and rank, such as protests by middle-classes against threats to neighbourhoods, and those which are based upon a defence that already operates on the basis of a rationalised lifeworld and tries out new ways of co-operating and living together. This second type of movement is characterised by a critique of economic growth, develops in response to lifeworld colonisation and begins with reactions to specific problem areas. This most notably occurs in green issues, where the health effects of environmental destruction and pollution 'noticeably affect the organic foundations of the lifeworld'(p.394). Other areas to the fore include peace and cultural/lifestyle issues.

Habermas suggests therefore that whilst all new politics reflect issues of quality of life, freedom, and participation, only some groups develop as resistance movements to further

lifeworld colonisation and are motivated by moral concerns. Others simply reflect growing middle-class awareness of environmental threats and efforts to defend localities and neighbourhoods from environmentally damaging developments. He does however point to the emancipatory potential of groups involved in radical environmental protest to facilitate wider societal changes in attitude toward the environment. He contends that as the environmental movement forms, a foundation of ideas and principles develop which, as environmental conditions deteriorate, gain credence and support amongst those sections of society who previously did not consider them. Thus Habermas appears to bridge that conceptual gap noted by Melucci, and contends that the concerns of everyday life can be connected to the wider concerns of social movements through dissemination of their principles and activities. As an example, White suggests that middle-class opposition to environmentally detrimental developments, which in many cases is based on NIMBY attitudes of moving the hazard or development to some other location, may alter to reflect the ideas and practices of NSMs. In other words short-term local concerns would be replaced by a more open universalistic approach to solving environmental problems, a shift from NIMBY to NOPE. Consequently the actions of radical environmental groups can succeed in building bridges between parochial and global issues, between 'everyday life concerns and global ones.'

Theoretically therefore it would appear that the actions of social movements can have broader effects. It may be that interaction between community groups and radical movements could lead to a broadening of concern and change of approach from local protestors. This will be explored in later chapters however before doing so some clarification of the concept of NIMBYism is required.

Community Protest and NIMBYism

The proliferation of groups and movements in the participation process since the late 1960s is not confined to social movements such as the environmental and peace campaigns. Perhaps the most prevalent type of group participation is in the flourishing of local action groups or groups who are concerned with protecting localities from developments which threaten their quality of life. These groups often adopt confrontational stands towards developments which they feel will have adverse impacts on their day-to-day lives; typically protests revolve around developments such as waste recycling, nuclear power plants and, increasingly frequently, the building of new roads. Opposition of this nature has been termed the Not-In-My-Back-Yard (NIMBY) response.

Empirically NIMBYism is linked to proximity and perceptions of risk. Thus the nearer someone is to a development they perceive as risky the more likely they are to oppose it and as distance between them and the development increases their level and intensity of opposition also declines. As NIMBY groups have proliferated research into the phenomenon has tended to fall into two categories. One is broadly positive and sees NIMBYism as rational responses by citizens who find it difficult to influence government decisions and which may serve the public interest by highlighting failings in existing decisions and processes. The negative perspective of NIMBYism as an impediment to rationally planned facility siting is however predominant. This is due in part to a number of assumptions that have come to be attached to the meaning of the term NIMBY as its use has become more common. Indeed it is suggested that its use has become so widespread that its precise meaning has become lost, a point stressed by Wolsink who states;

Authors use the term NIMBY to indicate all local opposition..(but)..in most literature there is no attempt to explain the nature of the concept. There is an implicit assumption that everyone knows what the phenomenon involves...If we are to assess the concept of NIMBY, we must first have a clear understanding of what it entails. In theory, the NIMBY phenomenon may be a social dilemma; in practice, however, there is only a dilemma if the assumptions behind (the theory) are true. (1994, p.853)

The implicit assumption behind the term is generally negative and associated with irrationality, selfishness and parochialism. NIMBY protests are said to place private interests of health, noise disturbance, and property prices before the public good. This is so because the burden of building and operating a public good are seen to fall on only one community while the benefits go to all other areas. It is this imbalance in the distribution of costs and benefits which leads to NIMBY protests. This emphasis on the irrational, egotistical aspect of the NIMBY syndrome has come to dominate, leading Wolsink to outline six implicit premises on which the theory is based and against which local opposition can be tested. Wolsink's premises refer largely to issues of facility siting however I have adapted them for motorway protests. The assumptions are listed below.

- The decision making process concerning the proposed development is laborious. This premise is self-evident; from initial proposal to final construction may take a number of years and involve a painstaking process of protest and opposition.
- The projects involved represent 'higher' interests than those of the local population. This premise rests on the assumption that the public goods involved are of a higher order as they serve society as a whole. The interests of the local community are therefore lower. Thus the interests met by constructing a new motorway, in terms of faster travel, advantages to

business etc. are more important than the interests of the community residents whose health and peace are affected.

- Everyone (or at least a majority) agrees on the usefulness of and need for the development. In terms of motorway construction this premise suggests that people accept the need for new motorways and are not opposed to motorway building per se. This leads to the next premise
- Everyone prefers not to have the development in his or her backyard. Following the above, motorways themselves are not opposed, simply motorways 'in my backyard'. This highlights the irrational aspect of the term in that opponents have no specific or technical reason to oppose developments but instead protest on emotional and egotistical grounds.
- Everyone prefers to have the development sited in someone else's backyard. The logical follow up to premises 3 & 4. If people accept the need for motorways but do not want them situated close to them logically they must be willing to have them constructed elsewhere where the effects impact upon other communities.
- The attitudes and opinions that go to comprise these feelings are static. The assumption behind this premise is that individual opinions do not change when confronted with proposals. In other words an individual may consider motorways to be a public good and useful but the construction of one locally does not necessarily lead to them reassessing their opinion and questioning the need for motorways generally.

Wolsink's model is a useful analytical tool as it develops almost an ideal-type model against which community opposition can be empirically tested. Despite these strengths however I believe that further qualification needs to be made to Wolsink's assumptions, in particular to four areas.

Firstly, the notion that laborious decision-making protests produce NIMBY opposition is questionable. Due to the nature of facility siting and road developments a protracted decision-making process would be expected; indeed, as Wolsink points out, a long process is preferable to decisions made in haste. What Wolsink does not specify however is whether this assumption applies to all NIMBY protests, in other words is a laborious decision-making process necessary to generate a NIMBY protest or is NIMBYism also apparent in shorter less painstaking processes? If the latter is the case we can suggest that laborious decision-making processes do often facilitate NIMBY protests but are not however necessary for them to develop. An important distinction.

Secondly, the concept of higher interests is vague and undefined. In many respects the assumption rests on a specific definition of 'higher' namely that the development is a public good with societal benefits and therefore of a higher order than local concerns regarding property prices, noise, pollution and so on. Given this definition NIMBY protests can be considered as essentially distributional in nature; they revolve around issues of the distribution of environmental costs and benefits. Higher order interests therefore are those that benefit the greatest number of people and it is the imbalance in the distribution of costs and benefits which lead to NIMBY protests. Furthermore environmental developments are frequently justified because of their economic benefit to the wider region or society. New roads are typically said to provide economic benefits to the country by reducing transport time and increasing transport options. The costs of these economic benefits however are borne by a few communities, not only economic costs in the sense of reduced house prices but health and lifestyle costs also. Distributional issues therefore dominate NIMBY protests both in the sense of the number of people who either benefit or are disadvantaged and in the sense of the distribution of economic costs and benefits. It is for this reason that in many cases the first action of local groups is to petition local people on their views and thereby highlight, in distributional terms, the number of people opposed. Significantly local arguments against the proposed developments are considered as being of lower order because they are not concerned with 'higher' order distributional issues; local opposition is considered lower because it is based on emotional, irrational arguments. I will discuss the issue of the supposed irrationality of NIMBY protests when examining premise 4.

Thirdly, it is important to distinguish between 'everybody' in a global or national sense and 'everybody' in the sense of residents of affected communities. Wolsink recognises that it may not necessarily be the case that national opinion supports environmentally harmful developments. For example evidence indicates that in 1993 59% of survey respondents stated that in urban areas government spending should be used to improve public transport rather than the road network. Thus local opposition to motorway building may not be the result of NIMBYism but rather reflect the fact the people do not support the construction of new motorways. In a local sense the term also requires clarification. In this connotation the term refers to everyone directly detrimentally affected by the construction of the road. Consequently residents affected in this way accept the need for motorway construction but 'not in my backyard'

Lastly, the perception of irrationality in NIMBYism is questionable. Rationality in classical economic theory rests on the assumption that individuals will seek to maximise their utility and

minimise their costs. In this respect NIMBY protests are perfectly rational responses to developments which reduce individual utility by damaging local environments. Concerns about the health effects of living nearby a motorway are not irrational; they are legitimate, rational fears. Nevertheless, the perception of the irrational NIMBY is one that remains. The reason for this is primarily because local arguments against developments are based on emotional rather than technical arguments.

This invalidation of emotion as the basis for argument is central to those who endeavour to overcome NIMBY opposition. Put simply, according to the developer, local protest is based on emotion and therefore less legitimate than protest on technical grounds. The separation of reason and emotion is noted by Feree who contends that historically it is a value-laden act: for reason/emotion read strong/weak; male/female; middle class/working class. Emotion therefore is an impediment to good decision-making. The emotional nature of local opposition is further denigrated by referring to it as the 'NIMBY syndrome' which, as Wolsink notes, suggests it is akin to a disease (for example AIDS stands for Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome). Given the irrational nature of NIMBYism it is presumably a disease of the mind, a type of madness.

It can be argued therefore that NIMBYism and NIMBY protests represent a rational response by communities who feel their lifestyle will be threatened and who have no other method of expressing these feelings. NIMBYism may therefore be the rational result of citizens' and communities' inability to significantly participate in the decision-making process. Furthermore, research has indicated that the emotional content of NIMBY protests is often very low. We could conclude therefore that the perceived irrationality of NIMBY protests does not stand up to theoretical examination. It can be argued that the motives, justification, and strategy of NIMBY protest can all be considered rational.

The origins of citizen groups of this nature can be located within the wider development of new political mobilisations in post-war societies and thus have similar origins to new social movements. The rise in affluence and educational attainment produced by post-war welfare states, combined with growing levels of home ownership amongst the middle-classes resulted in the formation of groups with a direct interest, in terms of property values, in halting developments which threaten their amenity. In addition, these groups are aware of the risks associated with these developments, and have the resources and communication skills to articulate their demands. I noted earlier Habermas's contention that lifeworld colonisation also results in groups which seek to defend tradition and rank. In this respect NIMBYism can therefore be considered as a particular form of the radicalism which also produced new social movements, and a particular type of response to the perception of a participation deficit in post-war societies.

NIMBY movements then are also concerned with quality of life issues, although their concerns differ from NSMs in that they seek to defend the quality of life of certain groups of people at the expense of others rather than improve the quality of life for all. Unlike new social movements their aims are limited, geographically confined and temporary.

It can be argued that alongside these social factors the institutional structure of the planning process in Britain inevitably results in NIMBY opposition. According to Cullingworth current planning legislation in Britain is the result of the breakdown of political consensus in the 60s and subsequent public demands for increased participation. The report of The Skeffington Committee in 1969, established to examine planning procedures, responded to this demand by recommending increased statutory participation in planning decisions thus giving the public greater input. However the nature of the planning process, with its emphasis on public meetings and Public Inquiries in the case of contested decisions, places people in an environment which forces them to adopt opposing views. In the case of Public Inquiries the proposal under debate is strictly controlled and discussion is often limited to technical issues, limiting the opportunities for groups wishing to expand the scope of the debate. Discussions therefore revolve around the arguments for and against the building of a particular power station or road and not around the need for nuclear power or road building. Opponents therefore have no option but to argue against proposals on the NIMBY grounds of their effect on the locality.

In terms of structure NIMBY groups, although ad hoc in nature, tend to quickly form into organisations and seek support for their stance. Committees are formed to organise opposition and resources and publics are mobilised. Tactics vary but usually revolve around local planning procedures and Public Inquiries; however local groups do attempt to influence decisions by conducting petitions, staging demonstrations and gaining media attention through a variety of activities. Local groups are also quick to enter alliances with other organisations with similar goals to advance their arguments. For example Baggott (1995) describes the activities of a number of local groups protesting at their areas being chosen as potential sites for the disposal of nuclear waste. The groups involved worked closely with local authorities also opposed to the decision and with members of parliament whose constituencies would be effected. This enabled them to mobilise large numbers of people to protest the decision; local groups also formed a national umbrella group to take the debate to a higher level.

Despite the assumed differences between the eco-warrior element of the anti-roads movement and the local (NIMBY) component it is possible, from the above, discussion to identify some features common to both and perhaps to suggest that they are not as different as first imagined. Firstly, both approaches can be described as the rational response of people seeking

to protect the utility derived from the environment. The anti-road movement looks to maximise the utility which **everyone** gains from the global environment by opposing developments which detrimentally effect it. NIMBY groups on the other hand endeavour to maximise the utility gained by a relatively limited number of people within a geographically specific environment. Secondly, although adopting different strategies and tactics of opposition each can be considered as the rational response to a system which they perceive as being either unreceptive to their concerns or which relegates these concerns to issues of secondary importance. The anti-road movement criticise a capitalist economic system which promotes economic growth and materialism thereby ensuring that environment policy is subordinate to economic issues. NIMBY groups meanwhile often form in response to a planning system that offers little scope for meaningful participation and considers 'emotional' concerns to be secondary to technical ones. Furthermore both groups seek to build coalitions and establish broad alliances with other groups. However, the anti-road movement tends to be unstructured and non-hierarchical whilst NIMBY groups are not. The fundamental difference between the two groups however revolves around distributional issues. The anti-road movement challenges the need for further road construction and argues that the global environmental costs of such developments outweigh the justifications. NIMBY groups make no claims about the global costs of road construction but instead focus on the local effects arguing that the route of the road should be altered to minimise these and consequently shift them elsewhere. As a result NIMBY protests are essentially distributional protests.

Conclusion: Social movements, Eco-Warriors and NIMBYists

This chapter has sought to establish some of the historical framework within which later discussions will be based. I examined three broad themes. The first was the development of public opinion about the environment. The second focused upon a particular example of an environmental social movement, namely the UK anti-road movement that emerged in the 90s. The third examined the concept of NIMBYism and explored the possible consequences of the marriage of radical and community protest.

Clearly, the period since the 1960s has witnessed a rise in public concern for the environment and I highlighted a number of indicators of changing public opinion. These included growing membership of environmental groups, evidence from public opinion surveys and government policies. The fact that numerous government policies emerged appears to indicate that public opinion does indeed influence government policy. The development of social movements and community protest sheds doubts on this claim however. I noted that social movements develop as a consequence of a participation and legitimisation deficit in post-war societies. Furthermore, the development of community protests is arguably the result of similar

processes. In other words, it is because governments seem to ignore certain facets of public opinion that protest movements develop.

This chapter also noted the development of the UK anti-road movement and offered some consideration of community responses to developments that threaten their quality of life. It has raised a number of interesting points about the shape and dynamic of the anti-road movement which emerged in the UK in the 90s. Clearly the anti-road movement is a nebulous, shifting mass of different groups, organisations, disorganisations and people. The dynamics of the movement are such that it has the potential to create coalitions between radical and traditional protest groups who may, at first glance, seem to be too far removed from each other for meaningful co-operation to succeed. Deeper analysis suggests however that in terms of motivations for protests these groups may not be as different as first expected.

The bridge between the two discussions of eco-warriors and NIMBYists was a section which sought to theoretically explore the possibility that the actions of social movements may have wider impacts upon the consciousness of society. This raises the question of the broader impact of the anti-road movement in the UK but may also offer an insight into why the depth and strength of feeling against road building was so strong in the 90s. The answer may be an accident of history or the result of a specific mobilisation in the 90s. There is no doubt that there were a significant number of roads constructed in the 90s, at a time when other environmental issues had dropped off the agenda. This could be the reason that roads seemed to be the focus for many environmental groups. On the other hand it could be argued that the combination of the 'residue' of environmental consciousness left behind from the 80s, the actions of social movements in opposing roads and the ability of groups to build successful coalitions to oppose road construction ensured that they became a focal point for more than just environmental groups but threatened local communities as well.

This coalition of radical and local which occurred in the 90s raises another series of questions. Firstly, what is the potential for the direct-action element of the roads movement to effect deeper changes in society? Secondly, to what extent are the local and radical elements of the movement protesting about the same things or sharing the same goals? Thirdly, does the marriage of radical and traditional lead to change in protest dynamics? In other words, do local communities become more direct in their approach when united with eco-warriors or are there pragmatic divisions of responsibility regarding strategy and tactics? These questions cannot be answered at this point but they will form the basis of concrete exploration in later chapters.

The next chapter takes this discussion of the historical emergence of roads protests and focuses upon one particular account of community opposition to roads construction. The history of the M77 in Glasgow and community opposition to its construction forms the foundation of subsequent analysis where many of the issues and points raised in the previous two chapters will be explored and expanded.

Chapter 3: Community Protest and the M77

**'We are a little colony, and placed where all is still.
The watchword, have you heard sir is - keep your eye on Corkerhill.'**
(Extract from poem to commemorate the establishment of the community of Corkerhill.
Author Unknown)

Introduction

On Friday, December 6 1996 a new motorway was officially opened on the south-side of Glasgow. During its construction this motorway, like others before and after, was a scene of confrontation and debate. This debate was about both the nature of the world in which we are living, about the need to constantly build new roads and motorways and also about the harmful effects urban motorways have on the health and well being of those living nearby. The confrontation was between local residents and environmental activists seeking to halt the roads construction and the police and employere of Wimpey Construction attempting to fell trees on the motorway route. It was a motorway which took thirty years to build; which led to a government minister resigning his post; and which, a small community in Glasgow fought to have stopped for almost thirty years. This motorway was the M77 extension and the community was Corkerhill.

This chapter will focus upon the broader historical background to the M77 construction and protest. This will enable later discussions of opposition to the M77 to be located within both a wider historical context and, building on previous chapters, a broader theoretical context. It will seek to paint a portrait of the historical struggle against the M77 motorway. A struggle that exploded onto our television screens and newspapers in 1995 but which had existed for many years before that. As such it is a portrait of a community campaigning against a development which it believed would have a detrimental effect on the lives of its' residents. At the forefront of this campaign was the local Community Council. The methods undertaken by the council, not only to protest against the road, but also to act with the support of their community, to provide information to the community, and to discuss developments and further action will be outlined. Before this discussion of history and context however it is necessary to explain the process and thinking behind this paper and to outline the methodological approaches used in later chapters.

Process and Methodology: Why Corkerhill?

This research emerged from two sources. The first was a desire to understand the nature and role of public opinion in protests of this nature, borne from a perception that existing approaches to studying protests of this nature overlooked or ignored the role of opinion. The second source was a desire to understand more fully the role of local people and communities in anti-roads protests. At the time of formulation, opposition to road construction was the most significant expression of environmental concern and protest in Britain. Media coverage of road protests was extensive, and the M77 protest was no different; however in almost every case the role of local residents was overlooked. I had participated, briefly, in the protest against the M77 by attending rallies and demonstrations and I knew that many of those involved in organising and mobilising protest were local people. The media however chose to focus almost exclusively on the eco-warrior element of the protest. The original research therefore proposed to examine the role of public opinion in environmental decision-making, focusing particularly on the nature and role of public opinion regarding the M77 motorway by those local communities most affected by its construction.

Three communities along the route of the M77 were chosen for study: Corkerhill; Arden and Thornliebank. Corkerhill was chosen because it was the focus of much of the protest and the community which stood to lose most from the M77 construction. Arden was chosen because it is a community much like Corkerhill; poor and relatively run-down and which the M77 would skirt closely when constructed. Thornliebank was chosen for comparative purposes as it is an affluent area which stood to gain from the construction of the M77, as vehicles which used the main road through the community were to be diverted onto the new road. In this way it was hoped that a broad variety of opinions and information could be gathered and used for analysis.

The first step in understanding the role of public opinion in the M77 protest was to determine what opinion was. To that end an opinion questionnaire was developed. The opinion survey intended to examine a number of factors concerning the M77. These included: opinion regarding the road; concern about the road; propensity to engage in protest activities; group membership; sources of information about the M77 and possible effects the M77 protest had on those involved. It was pilot tested prior to being conducted and on the basis of this pilot minor alterations were made to the wording of some questions in order to make them easier to understand. The survey was administered by the author. In order to ensure a representative sample from each community the survey was conducted at various times of the day and week,

including mornings, afternoons, evenings and weekends. This ensured that those surveyed were as representative of the communities as possible. To further ensure this, comparison was made with the census results of the areas involved, consequently a limited number of extra surveys were conducted to proximate the social composition of the communities, in terms of the age of residents, as close to that suggested by the 1991 census. In total 413 interviews were conducted across the three communities. A copy of the survey can be found in Appendix 1.

The survey results were analysed using SPSS and whilst they provided important insights into the nature of community opinion and the differences between the communities, it was clear that a survey on its own would not be sufficient to fully understand the processes at work within the communities studied. It became apparent that the 'polling' approach I had adopted offered a limited view of residents' opinions about the M77. Of particular interest to the study were residents' perceptions and feelings about the road, and an opinion survey did not adequately capture these. At the time, however, this did not seem to be a significant problem, as interviews with local people had always been planned and I felt that these would offer the insights required. However, the process of analysing the survey data not only led me to recognise the weakness of the methodology, it also subsequently pointed to the theoretical limitations of exclusively utilising public opinion concepts as a means of exploring complex processes of collective action such as those which arose around the M77. The theoretical difficulties I encountered were exactly those discussed in Chapter 1's discussion of public opinion theory, namely I was reducing processes of communication, discussion, debate, analysis, perception and feeling to a numerical answer to a question I had set. The methodology I had chosen was bound to a theoretical model of public opinion which tended to preclude real analysis of the very processes I had set out to investigate.

This realisation prompted a period of reflection about the nature of the study. It had become clear that public opinion theory alone would not offer the insights required to truly understand the character of local protest against the M77. Given this, I felt that the only way to better understand the processes and dynamics of the M77 protest was to explore the nature of the collective processes at work, and the motivations lying behind protests. Public opinion theory, whilst referring to opinion as a collective process, says little about the development lying behind collective action. Consequently I had to broaden the theoretical scope of the research to include the study of collective action and social movements as this offered a substantial body of work which could be drawn upon.

It soon became clear that there were broad similarities between the concepts of social movements and public opinion. Notions of leadership and communication appeared central to both and this realisation led to a further refinement in the approach of the research. I decided that instead of focusing on the role of public opinion in environmental protest and decisions, a more productive approach for the overall study would be to attempt to understand more fully the processes of communication which lead to the emergence and mobilisation of community protests of this type. This subsequently led to something of a narrowing of the focus of the research and a greater concentration on Corkerhill. This was for two main reasons. Firstly it was clear that Corkerhill had been the focus of much of the protest against the M77 and that the community had not only protested in the 1990s but had been doing so since the 1960s. Secondly, for practical reasons it was easier to focus the second stage of the methodology on one community. This second stage consisted of interviews with Corkerhill residents involved in the protest.

The interviews were semi-structured and tape-recorded. They were conducted between June and September 1996, just over one year after the main opposition to the M77 ended and a few months before the road officially opened. A sample of residents for interview was constructed by approaching community council members. From this, more names were gathered and the sample 'snowballed' upwards. Interviews were usually conducted in residents' homes at times suitable to them, two interviews were conducted at the premises of Corkerhill Community Council and some respondents were interviewed more than once. On one occasion a small 'focus group' of sorts was established by interviewing four residents as a group. The fact that the interviews were semi-structured, following only topic guidelines, meant that there was the opportunity to explore in more detail any interesting points that arose. In total thirteen people were interviewed. The use of qualitative data in this way ensured that any discussion of Corkerhill's protest experience revolved around illustrative cases of the experience of residents. Furthermore, it enabled this experience to be presented and constructed more as it was seen by those involved, and less through pre-conceived categories. The fact that these cases relate to processes, feelings and experiences also means that the interaction of different factors over time can be drawn upon in any analysis.

The author recognises that data of this type (oral history) which relies on the memory of the respondents may be subject to *post hoc* rationalisation, particularly in circumstances where opposition has been unsuccessful. However in this case the oral histories were supported by the third method of data collection, namely documentation produced at the time of the protest. These

indicate that residents' feelings about, and interpretations of, the M77 construction did not arise after the fact or as a result of failed protest but were indeed prevalent at the original time of protest. The quotes used are selected as being typical of the feelings and interpretations of Corkerhill residents.

In this way, the original conceptual and methodological focus of study altered during the research process. Conceptually it altered from a study which aimed to explore the nature and role of public opinion in environmental politics to one which sought to examine the communicative processes which underpin collective action of this nature. Methodologically, the study narrowed so that although the other surveyed communities were still examined in detail the main focus of the substantive analysis was on Corkerhill and its residents.

The history of Corkerhill's struggle against the M77 is discussed in detail below. To place this history in context, however, requires a discussion of the history of Glasgow's motorway network. In this way it is possible to place Corkerhill's protest within broader historical processes and events.

Glasgow: 'Motorway City'

Chapter 2 outlined the way that national governments embraced motorways as economically essential and it is correct to state that Glasgow local authorities did likewise. Motorway construction was part of a planning revolution in Glasgow 'characterised by a ruthlessness of purpose unmatched in the UK' (McKean & McKean, 1971, p.902) designed to alleviate the problems of slum housing, dilapidation and traffic congestion. Glasgow's road plan was proposed in 1946 but was only confirmed by Scott Wilson & Kirkpatrick's 'Highway Plan for Glasgow' in 1965. This proposed a radical plan for a double-ring system (inner and outer) linked by several radial routes with the northern inner-ring passing through the centre of the city (see Figure 1). Radiating out from the IRR would be seven motorways. To the north the Maryhill motorway would run whilst the Springburn motorway would go north-east. The Monklands motorway went east and from this would branch the Stirling motorway. The Hamilton motorway ran south-east. The Renfrew motorway headed west with the Ayr motorway (later to become the M77) going south-west. Beyond this, about 2-3 miles from the city centre, would be a series of expressways carrying traffic to the motorway network. The outer-ring would be roughly 5-10 miles from the city centre and would comprise some motorway and some expressway segments.

Both the intermediate expressways and outer-ring would connect at various points with the seven motorways mentioned above.(Greater Glasgow Transportation Study, 1965)

By 1971 the northern and western section of the inner-ring road (IRR), part of the M8 motorway, was complete, the Kingston Bridge was constructed to take traffic over the Clyde and Glasgow became a 'motorway city'. (McKean & McKean, 1971) To accommodate this section of the IRR a shopping centre was destroyed, as was part of the community of Garnethill and almost all of the community of Anderston. Dow & Moss (1986) record that 8000 people from Anderston's population of just over 11 000 were moved to make way for the M8 and the Kingston Bridge. The eastern section of the IRR proposed to proceed up Glasgow High Street, destined to destroy a 1751 Chapel and a school designed by world famous architect Charles Rennie Mackintosh. A further bridge was considered necessary for this eastern section to cross the Clyde whilst at its upper, northern, end it would leave Glasgow cathedral isolated in a traffic island surrounded by motorway.

McKean & McKean note the socially divisive consequences of this passionate embrace of the motorway. They particularly note that the eastern section of the IRR divided the poor areas to the east of the city from the city centre and the more affluent areas to the west. They stated;

Were this flank constructed, those who could afford to would abandon east Glasgow: and further deterioration of an already neglected area seems inevitable. (P.903)

They further note the potential threat to areas such as Dumbreck, Corkerhill and Pollok from the construction of the outer-ring motorway. and also observe that most of the radial routes were designed such that affluent commuters could easily journey from the suburbs to the city centre. Many of the motorways, on the other hand, went through poor neighbourhoods. (Keating, 1988) The residents of Glasgow were also aware of the threat posed by the motorway. Bow and Moss (1986) record that the announcement of the plans for Anderston redevelopment were 'greeted with a storm of protests'. (p.110)

Figure 3:1 Greater Glasgow Transportation Plan: Glasgow's Motorway System

Source: Keating (1988)

Local business leaders formed the Anderston Business Association and objected to being forced from their premises, to make way for the motorway and new business developments, in return for ones with inferior tenancy agreements and no rent guarantees. Further objections from the business community centred on concern that they would be unable to hold on to their workforce once Anderston residents were decanted. A Public Inquiry was held to discuss these concerns but subsequently approved Glasgow Corporation's plans for the area. It must also be pointed out that local residents largely welcomed these plans, primarily because they promised a move to better housing in the new schemes on the periphery of the city.

Spending restrictions forced a rethink by the City Corporation after the opening of the Kingston Bridge in 1971. This led to the abandonment of plans for lengths of the intermediate ring-road but retained the intention to complete the inner and outer ones and the construction of the Ayr Motorway, the Stirling Motorway and the Maryhill Motorway. Keating (1988) notes that at this time local amenity groups began to question the need for these urban motorway schemes in a city that at that time had the lowest levels of car ownership in Britain. In one notable case local amenity groups and residents of largely middle-class areas objected to the proposals to construct the Great Western Road Expressway on the grounds that it would damage the architectural heritage and amenity of the area. They argued that the expressway should be constructed through the working-class area of Maryhill immediately to the north and because of their well organised campaign and their ability to utilise the skills of the middle-class protestors involved the campaign was successful. (Keating, 1988)

By the mid-to late-1970s objection to urban motorways focussed on their environmental effects and Glasgow groups such as The Motorway Movement called for greater emphasis on public transport as solutions to transport problems. In addition, the spending crisis of the mid-70s was beginning to bite and Glasgow once again reviewed the motorway plans. This review resulted in the retention of seventeen schemes which the, by now, Strathclyde Regional Council (formed in 1975 as a result of local government reorganisation and with responsibility for roads) deemed as having a reasonable chance of completion. This included the eastern and southern sections of the IRR and the Stirling and Ayr Motorways. Once again local amenity and conservation groups objected to the plans and alongside these working-class community groups began to protest that Glasgow's motorways adversely effected working-class communities whilst benefiting the middle-class areas on the city's outskirts. (Keating, 1988). By 1981, of the original 1965 plan, only the northern and western sections of the IRR, the Clydeside Expressway, the Springburn Expressway (which replaced the Springburn Motorway) and the first 1.4 miles of the Ayr Motorway (by now the M77 Motorway) were complete. Proposals for the construction of the

southern and eastern sections of the IRR and the extension of the M77 were included in the 1979 Structure Plan drawn up by Strathclyde Regional Council.

The 1980s were relatively quiet as the spending restrictions imposed by the 1974-79 Labour government filtered down to Local Authorities. Strathclyde Regional Council (SRC) was however involved in promoting the construction of the M77 extension through the planning process, despite objections from Glasgow District Council and local amenity and community groups (this will be discussed in more detail below). In its 1988 Structure Plan however, SRC announced a massive new road building programme. This included not only the construction of the M77 extension but also the completion of the IRR by the construction of the eastern and southern sections. By this time the eastern section was called the Townhead to Glasgow Green Expressway and the southern section was the M74 Extension. The biggest surprise however was the announcement of two new bridges over the Clyde to relieve the congestion on the Kingston Bridge. Once again a flurry of protest followed the publication of SRC's plans. As in previous years, the protests centred on the fact that SRC had given no consideration of the potential for public transport to relieve traffic congestion and pointed to the lack of public consultation before the plans were announced, particularly with regard to the plans for the two new bridges.

At the forefront of these protests were groups such as Glasgow for People (GfP). Formed in the late 80s GfP was an umbrella organisation supported by a mix of amenity, transport, environmental and community groups such as The New Glasgow Society, The Railway Development Society, Friends of the Earth, The Scottish Association for Public Transport and Corkehill Community Council. With a particular interest in transport issues its aims were fourfold. Firstly, to create an environment good to live in where the city is neither engulfed in traffic or paved over for more roads. Secondly, to oppose the expansion of the urban motorway network. Thirdly, to advocate public transport alternatives and finally to promote community participation; hence Glasgow for People not traffic. GfP quickly mobilised opposition to SRC's draft structure plan and by February 1989 400 letters of objection were lodged questioning why public transport was not considered and the lack of consultation. (Keating, 1988) In the summer of 1989 Glasgow District Council objected to the draft structure plan but in early 1990 SRC's proposals were approved by the then Secretary of State for Scotland Malcolm Rifkind. Despite this, SRC's roads proposals ground to a halt because of spending restrictions imposed by The Scottish Office; in 1993 a cut in the Region's capital allocation resulted in a shortfall of £58 million over five years. The Council's road budget was more than the entire deficit, forcing the indefinite shelving of the new bridges and the delay of the M74 Extension and

the Townhead to Glasgow Green Expressway. In early 1994 however SRC and The Scottish Office agreed a £27 million funding package specifically for the M77 extension.

At the time of writing the completed sections of the original 1965 plans are: the northern and western sections of the IRR (incorporating the M8 motorway and Kingston Bridge); the Renfrew, Stirling, Monklands and Ayr motorways of the radial routes. Completion of the Hamilton Motorway is intended with the construction of the M74 extension. Of the intermediate ring the Clydeside Expressway was constructed and the Springburn and Maryhill Motorways became expressways. Surviving proposals still outstanding include the eastern and southern sections of the IRR. The remainder, including all of the outer-ring, having been shelved.

Thus in some respects Glasgow's motorway plans have been successful and in others not. The plans have been successful in that Glasgow now has more miles of urban motorway than any other city in the UK but unsuccessful in that the original plans have only partially been completed. In many respects the history of roads building in Glasgow mirrors that of the UK in general. An initial burst in the 60s, deceleration due to financial crises in the 70s, piecemeal progress for most of the 80s followed by another burst in the late 80s and early 90s, at least of intent if not actual miles constructed in Glasgow's case. A similar mirror image can be observed in the response of Glasgow citizens to road building. Motorway opposition in Glasgow certainly appears to follow a similar path. Initial opposition to the northern and western sections of the IRR came from business societies such as the Anderston Business Association objecting to potential threats to their livelihood. Later opposition came from amenity groups who feared motorway construction would destroy the aesthetic quality, certainly in some areas, of Glasgow. By the 1970s groups such as The Motorway Movement were questioning the need for urban motorways and advocating public transport instead and certainly by the 80s groups were focussing on what they perceived as the undemocratic manner in which these decisions were arrived at. Opposition in Glasgow therefore does appear to follow the same evolutionary path as national opposition until this point. With the building of the M77 motorway opposition in Glasgow also entered the direct-action phase and it is to this I now wish to turn.

The Three Communities

Although opposition to the M77 did emerge in Glasgow it would be incorrect to say that the road was not welcomed in certain quarters and by certain residents of Glasgow. Given that the purpose of this paper is to explore the opposition to the M77 it will examine in some detail the community where that opposition was most sustained and focussed, namely Corkerhill. However, as stated above, for the purpose of comparison other communities along the route of

the M77 were also studied: Arden and Thornliebank. (see figure 2 for map of route of M77 showing the three communities)

Arden

The history of Arden is inextricably linked to the history of the surrounding area of Darnley, and although what we now consider to be the housing estate of Arden did not exist until 1946 the surrounding area has a rich and varied history.

The entire area of what we now know as the south-side of Glasgow has been populated for centuries. Prehistoric remains were found during the excavation of the Glasgow to Ayr railway line and evidence of Roman encampments can also be found. From the thirteenth century the land in this area was agricultural with one or two small villages. The history of this area is dominated by two families: the Stewarts and the Maxwells. In the thirteenth century a Stewart was Lord Darnley whilst John Maxwell was made first Knight of Pollok. By the 1500s, with the death of Henry Stewart then Lord Darnley the lands they owned passed to the Maxwells.

By the seventeenth century the villages began to have familiar names, Pollokshaws and Nitshill were established. Coal was mined in the area and by the eighteenth century industry, particularly textiles, had been established and limestone quarries had been opened in Arden. The presence of the quarries led to the establishment of a lime works in the area. To service this and the coal also mined in the area roads and railways were constructed in the mid-1800s and journey times to Glasgow were reduced from half a day to half an hour. The continued expansion of the transport network in the area gradually saw Glasgow expand. With the establishment of the tram network in 1907 it expanded to the very outskirts of Glasgow. Areas previously thought of as rural, including Arden, gradually became suburbs of Glasgow.

The 20s and 30s witnessed further decline in agriculture and the City of Glasgow absorbed parts of Darnley (up to Thornliebank) to give the city boundaries which remain today. After the war, the City Council embarked upon a major house building programme. The housing estate of Arden began in 1956 on land annexed from the Maxwell family business Nether Pollok Ltd. By the 1960s the population of the area of Darnley was over 40 000 with most new residents having moved from elsewhere in the city and therefore having little or no connection to the area.

Figure 3.2: Map of south side of Glasgow showing route of M77

All of the new housing estates in this area (Darnley, Priesthill, Nitshill, Arden, Pollok) shared the same problems. The quality of house building was frequently poor and many houses had dampness problems. The estates were isolated, poorly served by public transport, far from the city centre and lacked amenities. Arden was comprised mostly of three and four storey tenements the major landlord being the Scottish Special Housing Association. This was an Association started in the 1930s whose major remit was the relief of unemployment through a state-sponsored housebuilding programme and provision of housing for the unemployed. It was a Quango and therefore independent of local authorities, but its letting policy was generally linked to those of the local authorities in the areas in which they operated. In the post-war years its role shifted to that of providing housing in areas of economic expansion (New Towns etc.) and by the 1970s it had become a major housing provider - in fact the second biggest in Scotland after Glasgow District Council.² By the 1980s the community was fairly run down due to lack of investment, it had a male unemployment rate of 28% and the degree of overcrowding was higher than the city average. The south side of the community ran along Nitshill road, a busy artery between Paisley to the west and parts of Glasgow and Lanarkshire to the east. The 1981 Local Plan notes that residents whose property faces on to this road are exposed to traffic fumes and noise. It also notes the proposed construction of the M77 on the western edge of Arden and suggests landscaping to enhance the community's enclosure from the road.

In 1989 the Scottish Special Housing Association was incorporated into the newly established Scottish Homes. The new body embarked upon a housing renewal strategy which involved building new homes, the conversion of existing ones, the promotion of alternative landlords through stock transfer and the right-to-buy. Socially however Arden had altered little. The 1991 Census revealed that the area has a population of just over 6000. Of this almost 12% are unemployed although over 50% are either unemployed or economically inactive. Furthermore 86% of households live in public sector houses whilst only 13% are owner occupiers. In addition, 77% of Arden residents have no access to a car and there is a substantial elderly population. In 1993/94 Scottish Homes attempted to divest its landlord role in Arden and transfer ownership of properties to community based Housing Associations. Opposition from local residents however, in large part due to the fact that the local authority was discounted as a potential landlord, meant that this proposal never passed the preliminary stages.

Thornliebank

² I am indebted to my colleague Chik Collins for this brief history of the Scottish Special Housing

The 'village' of Thornliebank does not appear on any maps or records of the area until the end of the 18th century when the community of 'Thorny Bank' first appears. The village itself is the result of industrial expansion on the southside of Glasgow at this time, particularly in the cotton and linen industries. In 1774 Robert Osburn a linen printer feued from the Earl of Eglinton a large tract of land to the south of Glasgow in the area known as Eastwood and established a cotton dyeing business. By the 1780s however Osburn's business was in trouble and he went bankrupt allowing two brothers, Alexander and James Crum, to move in and develop the area industrially. The Crums were also in the cotton and linen industry and the works quickly became famous for its calico printing. The village expanded in size as the printworks did and by the mid-1800s the factory employed 850 workers whilst the village population was 1400.

The growth of the village was also the product of the philanthropy of the Crum brothers. They built (what was then) high quality houses for their workers and installed sewage, gas and water systems to the village. Because of this the health of the workers in Thornliebank was noticeably better than those in surrounding areas, as was the productivity of the factory. Throughout the 19th century Alexander Crum in particular was involved in the establishment of schools, libraries, public baths and with general landscaping earning Thornliebank the recognition of the title 'model village'.

Despite these apparently healthy surroundings and the philanthropic nature of the Crums, life for those residents of Thornliebank who worked in the linen dyeing factory life could be very hard. Employees routinely worked 80 hours per week, as did the children employed at the plant. During times of peak production the plant would continue operating around the clock, and the workers were expected to do likewise. In times of industrial strife workers threatening to strike for better wages were often sacked and replaced by the local unemployed.

Thornliebank continued to expand throughout the 19th century. By the end of the century the village population was 2500. The Glasgow to Paisley coach service stopped at Thornliebank but in 1881 Thornliebank Railway Station was opened and by 1907 there was a tramcar service from Glasgow city centre to Rouken Glen on the outskirts of Thornliebank.

However by the 1920s there was a major recession of the Cotton and Linen trade and in 1929 The Printworks closed. This was described by the local press of the time as a 'catastrophe for the village'. The loss of the printworks resulted in the loss of many jobs within the village. However this was somewhat mitigated by the fact that Glasgow was gradually expanding and becoming closer to Thornliebank every day, thus offering opportunities for local residents to seek

work there. The Printworks site lay unused for over ten years until it was requisitioned by the government during World War 2 for use as a food supply depot. However after the war it again lay empty and unused, gradually falling into disrepair until it was demolished in 1975.

Thornliebank was gradually swallowed up by the expanding Glasgow and because of this became something of a dormitory community at the edge of the city. Perhaps as a result of this Thornliebank continued to grow and by 1951 the population stood at 3450. The 1975 local government reorganisation in Scotland meant that Thornliebank was contained within Eastwood district. Eastwood was one of the most affluent areas in Scotland, indeed 90% of houses in the district were privately owned and although Thornliebank was always a relatively affluent area of Glasgow by the 1980s it was a distinctly sought after locale. This is reflected in the 1991 census results that indicated that whereas Glasgow City had a male unemployment rate of almost 15% Thornliebank's was less than 2%. Furthermore, of Thornliebank's then 1894 households, 1289 (78%) had access to a car whilst 3% had access to three or more cars. Only 25% of residents do not have access to a car with the figure for Glasgow being over 60%.³

Thus it is clear that out of its industrial origins Thornliebank has emerged as an affluent suburb of Glasgow. This picture is reflected politically with the constituency of Eastwood, of which Thornliebank is a part, consistently electing Conservative members of parliament. In fact Eastwood was considered the safest Conservative seat in Scotland during the 80s and 90s, until Labour captured the seat at the 1997 election.

Corkerhill

Situated on the south-west side of Glasgow the community of Corkerhill has existed since 1897. Prior to that year Corkerhill was merely a junction box on the railway line from Glasgow to the Ayrshire coast. In 1896 The Glasgow and South Western Railway decided that new engine sheds were required for their locomotives as the existing ones in Glasgow were overburdened. Easy access to the railway was required and because of this, and also because of the then green field location, a site four miles south-west of Glasgow was chosen. To accommodate the engineers, stokers and drivers using the new sheds the railway company constructed houses for the men and their families. In November 1897 residents moved into the first 60 dwellings and the community of Corkerhill was born. By 1900 the population was just over 600; the opening of a Railway Institute provided a focus for the community, a hall for holding dances, rooms for meetings, and a local shop. At its opening the provost of Glasgow

³ Source: 1991 Census

commented on the benefits of a fine healthy life the residents of Corkerhill would have in the country. A local, unnamed poet read a verse which, rather prophetically, said;

We are a little colony, and placed where all is still. The watchword, have you heard sir is - keep your eye on Corkerhill. (in The Partick & Maryhill Press, 2/4/1900)

The community continued to grow and by 1911 numbered over 700 people. Even at this early stage Corkerhill was demonstrating its commitment to the principles of democracy and the close knit nature of the residents. The community elected a committee to organise and manage the village, a committee which functioned similar to a council. They had initiated a rent club where all residents paid a penny a week into a single fund. This fund was used to the pay the rent of those residents who could not pay due to illness or injury. Gradually however the expanding Glasgow swallowed up the village of Corkerhill. The Railway Company moved out and the village came under the remit of Glasgow Council. In 1970 Glasgow Corporation compulsorily purchased Corkerhill village because it lay in the path of the proposed M77 motorway. Slowly the old tenement houses were replaced with new purpose built flats and terraced houses and in 1971 the last of the old railway built dwellings was destroyed. The railway institute existed for a further nine years until it too was destroyed in 1980. The community now has two shops, a newsagent and a chip-shop, one public house, a community shop where public and Community Council meetings are held, and a tenants hall built to replace the Railway Institute and provide a venue for local clubs, nurseries and, occasionally, weddings.

Geographically Corkerhill does not now enjoy the benefits of the open spaces of country life its original residents did. To the north and south the housing schemes of Mossspark and Pollok have been constructed as Glasgow expanded outwards. The Paisley to Glasgow Railway line marks the northern edge of Corkerhill, to the south it is bounded by the river Cart and to the west by the Corkerhill Road dual-carriageway. For many years the areas only amenity was Pollok Park to the east although, as will be discussed later, access to the park was threatened by the construction of the M77. Alongside this apparent geographical marginalisation Corkerhill residents also believe they have suffered from political marginalisation. Shunted from constituency to constituency, in the 1960s it was part of the constituency of Pollokshields which had a Conservative Member of Parliament. Later it was included within the seat of Pollok before a further boundary change included it within the constituency of Craigton. Further changes in the 1980s saw it become part of the Govan constituency; Corkerhill was stuck on to each. At a local level it has suffered similarly; having once been part of the Pollok ward at the district level it is now contained within the Mossspark ward. Only with the establishment of, first The Corkerhill

Residents Association and later Corkerhill Community Council has Corkerhill had effective representation. The residents believe that this has hindered their attempts to influence decisions taken, firstly because numerous boundary changes resulted in difficulties in gaining long-term political support due in part to the constantly changing representatives. Also because they have always, effectively, been stuck on to other areas they believe that Corkerhill tend to get swallowed up or overlooked by the wider constituency. The 1991 census indicated that the population of Corkerhill was 1379. Of these: 9.3% were unemployed, a figure 1% higher than the Glasgow average; 44% of community residents were economically inactive, 6% more than corresponding figures for Glasgow; four out of five households received state benefits and 92% of households lived in local authority rented accommodation. Of the 558 households 88% had no access to a car, compared to the Glasgow figure of 65%.⁴

It is for these reasons, social disadvantage combined with geographical and political isolation, that Corkerhill has developed a tradition of community activism. At the forefront of the community's many campaigns has been the local Community Council, it was this organisation which led the opposition to the M77.

Corkerhill and The M77

The M77 'Ayr Road Route' was first proposed in 1965 as part of the 'Highway Plan for Glasgow' developed by Scott Wilson Kirkpatrick for the then Glasgow Corporation. Initially referred to as the Ayr Motorway the M77 was one of the seven radial motorways intended to feed traffic into the city. Corkerhill's first knowledge of and involvement with the road occurred in 1969 when members of the local Community Association were invited to a nearby school where they were given details about the road and transport plans for the city. The Association then started investigating the route of the M77 and the effect it would have on the community. It quickly became apparent that the construction of the motorway, along the designated route, would destroy the traditional right-of-way between Corkerhill and neighbouring Pollok Country Park and pass within 20-30 metres of the community. It was around this issue that the Community Association rallied the wider community and provided a linchpin for broader arguments regarding health and safety. Community Association members referred to Pollok Country Park as 'Corkerhill's Lung' and they argued that by denying the community the right-of-way to the park they were being denied their breathing space and the community's only source of recreation and enjoyment.

⁴ Source: 1991 Census

To spread knowledge and mobilise the support of the community the Community Association went round every door in Corkehill explaining the road proposals and what it would mean to the community. Public meetings were held to outline and explain the issues, attendance at these was, according to Community Association members, usually around 300. The meetings were lively with discussion focussed on the most effective way the community could retain its access to the park. They set up detailed plans of the roads proposal in the local community shop to enable residents to see for themselves the planned route. Community Association members were on hand to explain the plans if need be. They started an objection box for residents to register their disapproval and quickly received 803 individual letters of objection from an adult population of just under 1000.

Corkehill's initial response to the development proposal was to point to the Pollok Estate Conservation Agreement with the National Trust for Scotland (NTS) which owned the land. This agreement, drawn up in 1939, stated;

The said lands should remain forever as open spaces of woodland for the enhancement of the beauty of the neighbourhood and so far as possible for the benefit of the citizens of Glasgow. (Corkehill Community Council, unpublished document, 1994).

In 1972 Glasgow Corporation purchased some estate land for the purpose of the motorway, without the legally necessary agreement of the NTS. This condition of the 1939 agreement was waived by the NTS in 1974. The community's opposition to the roads proposal at this point in time tended to concentrate on legal arguments regarding the wording of the Maxwell Family Agreement, particularly on the section which read 'so far as possible'. The inclusion of this term allowed the NTS to claim that they were acting in accordance with the agreement. Glasgow Corporation paid £85 000 to the estate owners Nether Pollok Ltd to cover the design and reconstruction of Haggs Castle Golf Club contained within the estate, which lost some land as a result of the compulsory purchase. Haggs Castle Golf club subsequently expanded in size and ploughed up the right-of-way between Pollok Park and Corkehill, although planning permission for this was never received. Corkehill residents claimed that this was compensation for the building of the motorway adjacent to the golf course and the loss of some golf course land. Furthermore, following this Nether Pollok Ltd raised the commercial rates for the land at Haggs Castle thereby increasing their income from the, now much larger, golf course. In light of this Corkehill residents pointed out that both the golf course and the landowners had benefited from the M77, at the expense of £85 000 of public money, whilst the local communities had suffered losses.

In response to the loss of their right-of-way Corkerhill residents began organising direct protests on the golf course which now covered the old right-of-way. Often up to 200 residents would march across to the golf course, over the ploughed-up right-of-way, and proclaim their legal right to do so. In 1978 they disrupted an international golf tournament at Hags Castle by again peacefully proclaiming their right of access to the park. These protests continued over a period of four or five years. Each time there was a development regarding the road, or Glasgow Council made a proposal, the Community Council would call public meetings and organise protest. At all times the Community Association could point to the overwhelming support of their community for the actions they took. In fact the turnout for elections to the Community Council regularly tops 30%, a figure which is comparable to local authority elections. They realised that disorganised action would be ineffective and therefore did not act with impunity but always sought the approval of the wider community. The Community Council was able to mobilise this support not only because of the obvious strength of feeling against the road but because they were able to argue that there was a possibility of stopping it if the community was united. The actions of the Community Association, and later the Community Council were successful in delaying the construction which was initially scheduled to begin in the early 1970s.

The M77 was not, however, the only issue the residents of Corkerhill campaigned about. Throughout the 70s the community was at the forefront of the campaign against the proposed closure of the Glasgow/Kilmacolm railway line which provided Corkerhill with its' rail link to Glasgow city centre. Although this line was eventually closed the campaign for the re-opening of the line started and Corkerhill Community Council (CCC) was once again involved. Further protests were held regarding work by Glasgow Council to replace old gas fires in Corkerhill houses. CCC sought guarantees from Glasgow Council that any damage caused by replacing fires would be properly repaired. The CC even went as far as banning contractors from Corkerhill homes until guarantees were given, an action supported by almost all of the local authority residents in the area. Residents took to the streets of Glasgow City centre in May 1976. This issue was resolved by taking the case to the Local Government Ombudsman. In 1989 the Community Council campaigned on the issue of dampness in Corkerhill houses, once again taking to the Glasgow streets to make their point to local councillors. When this tactic did not produce the desired results CCC organised a Damphouse Inquiry and brought about the presentation of 13 test cases against Glasgow City Housing. As a result of this Corkerhill tenants have received compensation and been re-housed. In the 1990s they campaigned for the introduction of smoke detectors, which the council finally agreed to, and for safe windows and balconies.

There can be no doubt therefore that the M77 was not the only issue Corkerhill campaigned about. As I noted previously, the combination of relative isolation and deprivation has led to the development of a tradition of community activism. Corkerhill residents concluded that the only people who were willing to fight for Corkerhill were residents of the community and the active role of CCC across a number of issues reflects this.

By 1975 Strathclyde Regional Council (SRC) had been established and it was now responsible for the M77 development. However, as noted earlier, due to spending restrictions brought on by the economic crises of the early 70s, from the mid to late 70s Glasgow's motorway plans, including the M77, were the subject of debate. It was not known for certain if the road would go ahead as planned. All the residents of Corkerhill could do during this period was wait and see what happened. In 1980 SRC began construction of the first 1.4 kilometres of the motorway, the section from the M8 motorway to the edge of Pollok Country Park, and this opened in August 1981 with the further extension proposed for 1983.

Although the future of the M77 was uncertain CCC did not stop campaigning at this time and a change of strategy was adopted to combat the construction of the M77. Instead of focusing on the issue of the right-of-way they concentrated instead on the effect the road would have on the health of the community. They realised that the issue of the right-of-way would not be effective in gaining outside support and so produced a number of documents highlighting the health risks posed by the road. These were presented to Glasgow City Council, Strathclyde Regional Council, and the Scottish Office. Again the method of action was determined only after consultation with the wider community, after more leafleting and public meetings. Despite this Strathclyde Regional Council approved the extension to the M77 in March 1983. There were however a further two years before they applied to Glasgow District Council for planning permission.

By this time other affected communities such as Darnley had become involved in opposing the motorway. Corkerhill Community Council was by that time able to send representatives to the South West Area management Committee of Glasgow District Council. This was a committee composed of local MPs, District and Regional councillors and Community Councillors. Its remit dealt mainly with local finance matters but also with issues surrounding transport and planning. At the committee meeting of 13 May 1986 Corkerhill Community Council stressed to this committee the dangers the M77 would bring; concentrating on dangers to the health and safety of Corkerhill and its residents. The committee unanimously decided to oppose the M77. Subsequently the committee passed on its views to the planning committee of Glasgow District Council who were considering SRC's planning application. To reaffirm their presentation

to the Area Management Committee CCC submitted their objections to the planning committee. These were: that Corkehill would not benefit at all from the construction of the M77 as the road would 'speed the area towards further deprivation'; destroy a number of mature trees and wildlife habitats; it would cut the community off from its' breathing space of Pollok Country park and result in a form of social apartheid which would leave the golfers of Hags Castle Golf Course with 'twice as much room to play golf as the residents of Corkehill had to work, rest and die'. (Corkehill Community Council, 1987) A further protest was held outside Glasgow District Council chambers on the day the planning committee met and a petition of over 3000 names opposing the M77 submitted. With the decision of the Area management Committee to oppose the M77 and a display of public support to assist it the planning committee decided to refuse SRCs planning application. The main reasons cited for this were that it would benefit affluent areas at the expense of already disadvantaged ones and that it would lead to unacceptable increases in traffic on already congested roads. A subsequent meeting of the full council of Glasgow District endorsed this decision and planning permission was denied. SRC reiterated their intention to build the M77 and a Public Inquiry was called for to settle the decision.

This was the most crucial time for Corkehill residents. Almost twenty years of slow deliberate campaigning had eventually got them to the stage where they would be able to present their views at a Public Inquiry. The opposition had begun with a few residents within Corkehill who had successfully mobilised their community and expanded the protest outwards. Years of demonstrations occurred before they were finally able to successfully gain the support of local politicians, until by 1988 the protest had expanded to the stage where two local authorities were in opposition. Throughout this period, from the late 60s to the late 80s CCC's strategy for mobilising the community varied little. Community Council members would set up a stall outside the local community shop and ask the residents to sign objections to the road. If new residents came along the council members would explain the issues and the consequences to them and ask them if they wished to add their support to the list of objectors. Door to door sessions were conducted to try and spread the message to those who had not signed objections, in this way residents were kept up-to-date with new developments and proposed demonstrations and new members of the community started to learn about the issue . At all times the community was involved in decisions taken to fight the road mostly by holding a public meeting which outlined the latest developments and discussing the community's response. The Council frequently distributed leaflets to every house, again to explain what had occurred.

A Public Inquiry was held in the early months of 1988. Lasting for nine weeks the Inquiry heard objections from Glasgow District Council; Corkehill and North Pollok Community Councils and residents of Arden, Corkehill, Pollok, and Mossbank. These were all communities who

would be directly effected by the M77 construction and all were opposed to the development. Pressure groups such as Glasgow for People and Friends of the Earth Scotland also made submissions objecting to the M77. Glasgow District Council again focused on the effect the M77 would have on existing congested roads and in their presentation stated;

..it is clear that if the Ayr Road is implemented as proposed the existing problem of traffic congestion on the M8 motorway will worsen to an unacceptable level.(in Glasgow for People, 1994)

Corkerhill Community Council took the view that they would be unable to challenge SRC on their own and were hopeful that the arguments presented by Glasgow District Council would be able to influence the decision. Nevertheless they did present a sophisticated objection to the M77. The main point of their objection was that the M77 fundamentally contradicted SRC's 'Social Strategy for the Eighties'. This was a document brought out in 1983 by SRC highlighting its commitment to tackling multiple deprivation in Strathclyde and the strategy to combat it. SRC's approach was based on identifying Areas of Priority Treatment (APTs), those areas deemed to be suffering from multiple deprivation, and areas classified as 'At Risk' which were those deemed to be at risk of slipping into multiple deprivation. Corkerhill was designated as one of the latter. The chairman of the Social Strategy Sub-committee, Councillor Ron Young, stated that the test of SRC's strategy would be whether it could halt social division and exclusion and create one community rather than two communities. In their objection to the M77 CCC pointed to this strategy. They argued that, if the M77 were to be constructed Corkerhill would be separated from Pollok Park. They further noted that the local environment would suffer and that the influx of the 53 000 vehicles a day using the M77 only a matter of 20-30 metres from Corkerhill would speed an area already 'at risk' towards further deprivation. Their objection said;

Strathclyde Regional Council should explain how they can reconcile the planned segregation of Corkerhill into two quite separate areas, with one side of the divide developed as a world tourist attraction at the cost of millions, while the other side destined to become a neglected cul-de-sac ghetto with damp houses, is deprived of its countryside environment and its people deliberately driven into an ever shrinking claustrophobic environment. **Surely this amounts to a total contradiction of Strathclyde Regional Council's Social Strategy for the Eighties..** (CCC, 1984, p.3, original emphasis)

By exposing the contradiction of the M77, CCC hoped to demonstrate not only that Corkerhill would suffer but that SRC was flying in the face of its own policies. It also demonstrates that CCC developed an advanced and multi-faceted opposition to the M77 that challenged it on the grounds of both loss of amenity and on wider policy considerations.

In addition to the formal objection CCC made a powerful presentation, on behalf of the community, highlighting the effect the motorway would have and the costs the community would suffer. They made two videos which they presented to the Public Inquiry, one demonstrated the extent of poverty and deprivation within Corkerhill, highlighting in particular, the poor housing conditions. The other focused on the green belt and the beneficial effects of Pollok Country Park as Corkerhill's breathing space.

SRC submitted a scheme justification report to the Inquiry. This defended the construction of the motorway on three counts: environmental, economic and road safety. These were:

1. Environmental

- Reduced air and noise pollution in congested areas would improve conditions for residents and shoppers.
- 4.5 Km of new footpaths and cycleways would be built linking Corkerhill and other communities to each other and to Pollok park.
- Construction of a new children's playground in Corkerhill
- Funding for resurfacing football pitches in Pollok park.
- The planting of 165 000 new trees along the route - planted on grass mounds built between the motorway and local communities to screen them from noise pollution and from a view of the motorway.
- The removal of 1080 trees 494 of which were dying.

2. Economic

- The M77 was referred to as 'one of the most economically justified road schemes in Scotland' as it would:
 - Realise the potential of strategic industrial sites in the south-west of Glasgow and in north Ayrshire
 - Enhance shopping areas in the Shawlands, Giffnock and Thornliebank of Glasgow by moving traffic in these areas onto the new road.
 - Improve links between Glasgow & Ayrshire and ferry and air routes to Ireland
 - Increase access to education, training and employment

3. Road Safety

- It would provide traffic relief in built-up areas and allow for traffic calming measures to be introduced. It would reduce on 71% of roads in the southside of Glasgow and increase it in only 18%.
- It would produce a net saving of 3 700 deaths over a 30 year period and a financial saving of £147.7 million. (SRC, 1988)

In his report, Brian K Parnell the Inquiry reporter conceded that the building of the road would adversely effect Corkerhill on four grounds: increased noise; increased air pollution; visual intrusion; and reduced access to Pollok Country Park. He stated;

Corkerhill has a high unemployment rate, poor housing with associated illnesses, and few community facilities. Its environment would be substantially worsened by the Ayr Road Route. (Parnell, 1989)

Permission for construction was subsequently granted however, the main reason being the fact that the construction did not require the destruction of any existing property. A number of minor route alterations were also made. The reporter also noted however that Corkerhill had little amenity other than its access to Pollok Park and recommended that access be maintained. This involved the construction of a new path. Whilst welcomed by Corkerhill residents CCC gave notice that it still upheld the traditional right-of-way to Pollok Park and would continue to contest this.

Despite their intention to contest the right-of-way the Community Council at this point all but conceded defeat in their battle against the road. For 20 years their goal had been to raise awareness and gather support so that a Public Inquiry could be held. They won the right to present their argument but not the argument itself. The knowledge that their efforts to stop the road had been in vain did not however stop them fighting for the best deal for Corkerhill. They turned their attention to the issue of compensation for Corkerhill residents and thanks partly to their protests Corkerhill Community was allocated £660 000 for landscaping, and a children's play area. Here, again, we see another change of emphasis for the community activists, who began focusing instead on the issue of compensation and reparation. To get the community involved again the Community Council impressed on the residents that they should be complaining and fighting for compensation for the losses they were incurring because of the M77. They convinced the community that the way forward was to play on their losses. Over 400 people signed a petition calling for compensation;

From the time of the Public Inquiry in 1988 to 1993, the future of the M77 was never clear. SRC's roads plans were hit by the spending restrictions imposed by the Scottish Office and this included the M77. This acrimonious four year dispute between the Scottish Office and SRC over transport funding cuts led to construction of the road being delayed on numerous occasions and CCC realised that, at this point the future of the road was very delicately balanced indeed. At this time in the campaign the hardest part was keeping people interested, the Community Council would announce delays of another year before construction and eventually the community became complacent. It must be remembered that some of the older members of the community had gone through this on, off, on again, off again scenario since 1969. The dispute between SRC and the Scottish Office was finally resolved in March 1994 when an 'innovative' funding package was drawn up between the two. The Scottish Office actually threatened to take over the responsibility for construction and further reduce SRC's roads budget leading to accusations of browbeating and coercion in the media (Hunston, 2/3/1994). The package meant that the two sections of road proposed, the 4.1 miles to be constructed by SRC and the 2.7 miles by The Scottish Office, would be combined and managed as one with one contractor.

At this point the protest against the road entered a new phase; it became more direct. During this time Colin MacLeod became involved in the protest against the motorway. Macleod was born and grew up in neighboring Pollok, he spent many days as a child playing in the woods on the Pollok Estate and his enthusiasm for stopping the road was intense. In 1992 when SRC began the preliminary earth-works for the M77 Colin Macleod spent twenty days hanging from a hammock slung on the branches of a tree scheduled for destruction. CCC realized that despite their years of protest here was someone who could draw attention to their plight. They were also aware of the rise of the environment as a political issue and the publicity given to later road protests elsewhere in the country. In 1994 other environmental activists and veterans of roads protests at Twyford Down and in East London were contacted and anti-roads demonstrators began to converge on the Pollok Estate. It was from this that the idea of the protest camp in the estate developed.

In April of 1994 the protest camp proclaimed itself as the 'Pollok Free State' with the aim of protecting the trees in Pollock wood threatened by the motorway construction. A mix of locals and experienced green campaigners populated the camp and they were frequently joined by local schoolchildren campaigning to save the trees. All were committed to halting the construction.

Residents of the Free State, which was described as 'a curious canvas fairyland' and likened to the summer camp of a Red Indian chief, (Clouston, 1994) adopted an alternative lifestyle. They lived in tents and tree houses, recycled extensively and goods and possessions were communal. Cooking and work were organised to benefit the camp rather than individuals. In early 1995 some Corkehill residents followed this and established their own protest camp set up along similar lines. The tactics reflected those of the anti-roads direct action movement in that protestors attempted to stop construction by chaining themselves to trees and machinery.

CCC welcomed the establishment of the Free State and altered its strategy towards the M77. The change of strategy involved adopting the arguments of the wider protest groups, going beyond the confines of the community and ceasing to be a parochial protest. It became a wider issue about the environment and the need for roads. In light of the development of the protest camp and the Free State the Community Council had to go back out into the community and mobilise them once more - to attempt to convince them that perhaps the road could still be stopped.

Council members once again sat outside the community shops for months. They displayed posters and banners opposing the M77; they ran slide shows for anybody who wished to know what the protest was about, presented them with numerous documents outlining the history of the protest and the reasons for opposition. Pamphlets were distributed to every house in Corkehill explaining the presence of the camp and asking the residents to support it. This was to ensure that nobody lost sight of the campaign.

As a result of the Free State and the reawakening of the campaign to stop the M77 an umbrella organization known as STARR (Stop the Ayr Road Route) was established. The list of members was extensive: Corkehill Community Council; Park Community Council; North Pollock Community Council; Templar Community Council; World Wide Fund for Nature-Scotland; Friends of the Earth Scotland; Earth First; Transport 2000; Glasgow Cycling Campaign; Glasgow for People; Ramblers Association Scotland. The Free State became a focus for environmental movements such as FoE and as a result the argument against the road began to revolve more and more around environmental issues. The diversity of groups involved often meant that there were differences of opinion in the strategy for taking the protest forward. Earth First members for instance were more radical in their ideas than those members of Glasgow for People and FoE. This very diversity also proved to be a strength however.

Protest continued outwith the Pollok Estate and the route of the road. In late April 1994 protesters invaded the offices of SRCs roads department and chained themselves to office

furniture. A few days later protesters packed the public gallery of SRCs council meeting and voiced their objections to the road. Glasgow for People commissioned transport economist David Spaven to look at alternatives to the route and in August 1994 produced a report entitled 'Instead of the Ayr Road Route'. This report focused on the changes since the 1988 Public Inquiry - changes in the public attitudes to new roads, changes in the Labour Party's' approach to road building and transport policy (the report emphasized the belief that SRC's ruling Labour group were at odds with the transport policies of the national party), and new scientific evidence regarding exhaust emissions which had come to light since the public inquiry. The report offered a five point alternative, at no extra cost:

1. Construction of the Eaglesham by-pass offering access to the M74 south and Edinburgh and avoiding Glasgow.
2. Greater priority to be given to high-quality maintenance of existing road network.
3. A Comprehensive package of traffic calming and bus priority for Eastwood and south-west suburbs.
4. A major program of passenger rail improvements including the doubling of the single-track Kilmarnock-Glasgow line and extension of the electrified Glasgow-Ayr line.
5. Investment in new intermodal freight terminal linking Ayr/Prestwick Airport/Kilmarnock to the Channel Tunnel.

This would cost an estimated £51 million, the same as the cost of the construction of the M77.

The report further outlined a number of reasons why the M77 should not be built and examined the claims made by SRC in their justification report to the Public Inquiry. It argued:

Economic Benefits

- New roads are inefficient in boosting employment as they work on a boom/bust basis. Labour intensive maintenance programs employ more people for longer.

- Transport costs account for only 2% of company sales. Costs arise in time spent loading and unloading and are therefore unaffected by new road building.
- Strathclyde has employment stakes in rail-based infrastructure with railway supply industries at Kilmarnock, Shotts and Wishaw.

Road Safety Benefits

- Traffic calming measures on existing routes would result in a similar reduction in casualties and fatalities.

Environmental Benefits

- The M77 would enhance the environment of affluent areas at the expense of disadvantaged ones. The health of residents of Corkehill would be worsened.
- 95 000 yards of parkland would be concreted over in an important wildlife corridor of the green belt.
- New evidence had come to light since the Public Inquiry into the health dangers of benzene in unleaded petrol, and the respiratory and cancer risks from car exhausts. (Glasgow for People, 1994)

Furthermore the report pointed to evidence from the 1994 Royal Commission inquiry into the effect of building new roads which indicated that new roads bring only temporary relief from congestion. It argued that new roads encourage increased car use and lead to journeys of increased length and new trips which would not previously have been made, such that the new road itself quickly becomes congested. SRC responded to the alternative by saying that the construction of freight terminals was not their concern, and the alteration of railways was the responsibility of Railtrack. They said they welcomed the alternative but it would not be debated.

Politically the row surrounding the M77 also continued. In September 1994 Glasgow District Councillors again called for the road to be scrapped claiming that it would exacerbate deprivation in many areas and deny access to Pollok Country Park. The motorway also highlighted some embarrassing political contradictions. For example, at the SNP conference in September 1994 Glasgow councillors opposing the motorway development found themselves opposed by Ayrshire MPs and councillors who supported it and who eventually, albeit narrowly, won the vote on the debate. (The Scotsman, 22/09/94)

In November of that year SRC met to approve the £51 million contract for the road. Around 60 protesters demonstrated outside the council chambers and eight were admitted to the public gallery. Representatives of Corkerhill Community Council, Glasgow for People, Earth First, David Spaven and Glasgow District councillors attended the meeting. Not surprisingly it was volatile. Many protesters attempted to speak on the issue but were refused permission by the chair; others shouted their opposition. Objections to the M77 were varied. Glasgow for People pointed out that SRC's ruling Labour group were flying in the face of national party policy and pointed to 'In Trust for Tomorrow' the report from the Labour Party commission on the environment and the commitment to a moratorium on new road schemes contained therein. They further accused SRC of denying democracy and failing to comply with commitments made in its own anti-poverty strategy by increasing pollution in deprived areas. The secretary of Corkerhill Community Council supported this and claimed that the road would lead to increased levels of air and noise pollution in effected areas. Many other protesters, including Earth First, objected to the destruction of the countryside which construction of the road would entail. Despite these widespread protests, SRC approved the contract for the construction of the extension to the M77 motorway and awarded the contract to Wimpey Construction. (The Scotsman, 04/11/94)

Wimpey moved in to begin the tree-clearing on 31 January 1995, three weeks later than scheduled. Activists responded by chaining themselves to trees, vehicles and equipment. Following this the Wimpey contractors stopped work. The estate quickly became the focus of the most public confrontations between those for and against the road: between SRC, Wimpey and the police; and the road protesters and local residents. The following days witnessed numerous clandestine attempts by the contractor to begin work which the protesters managed to disrupt successfully. Extensive media coverage ensured a nation-wide audience and, in line with the words of the local poet 100 years previously everybody had their eye on Corkerhill.

Despite their early success a dawn raid on February 14 by Wimpey resulted in the felling of 100 trees before protesters could get to the site and prevent further clearing. When they did police held them back and prevented interference. Later that day schoolchildren from the local Bellarmine Secondary School rushed the site. Evading the police, they climbed on to equipment and placed themselves in the path of bulldozers. This act was not only effective in halting the felling but also gained nation-wide media attention.

As noted above, Corkerhill Community Council and the residents of Corkerhill welcomed these developments. They had conceded the fight and set about trying to win compensation. The Free State however renewed hope that their plight would become apparent to a wider audience

and that as the protest continued the cost of the M77 would become prohibitive. In many respects however the predicament of Corkerhill was lost amongst the wider arguments concerning the environment and the protest. The media focused upon the Free State with little or no coverage of the Corkerhill camp established by locals. The activities of local residents, with the exception of the part played by the schoolchildren, were usually overlooked. Furthermore, the activities of the protesters allowed SRC and those in favour of the road to blame outside troublemakers for the protest. Alan Stewart Conservative MP for Eastwood claimed that the protesters were foreigners with funny accents and asked; 'why are people coming from all over the world to stop a road that local people want?' (Glasgow Herald, 24/02/94)

Later, Councillor Charles Gordon, leader of the roads committee of SRC stated;

These people are fanatics, they are extremists, fundamentalists who have concluded that roads are bad for the environment..it's dangerous. A form of fascism. They have made their point.They should go home now. (The Herald, 25/02/94)

Locals and Free State residents refuted these claims.

At 4.30 a.m. on the morning of March 3rd 1995 a new tactic was utilised by Wimpey and the Police. Over 500 police and security guards entered the Corkerhill estate and erected barriers between the estate and the construction site thereby effectively denying Corkerhill residents access to the site and to support the protest camp. Thus the contractors effectively denied the camp residents access to one of their primary sources of support and manpower, Corkerhill residents and children. Early morning raids by the police and Wimpey security on 14 and 15 of March saw more trees felled and more protesters arrested. On 22 March the last 40 trees on the route were cut down. *The Scotsman* the next day reported; 'The battle to save the trees on the route of the M77 finally ended in defeat for the protesters last night.'

With the trees gone the protest against the M77 lost its focus and the confrontation faded. With no conflict to report the media moved on. The Free State remained for a number of months, however, before residents left to pursue other issues. Corkerhill Community Council continued the fight; they organised a petition again calling for compensation, a petition signed by over 800 residents. A public meeting in June 1995 was attended by over 100 people who agreed that the next step forward was to continue with the legal claim for compensation. Work continued on the M77 and in December 1996 it was formally opened.

So the battle was lost, but at least Corkerhill could say that it delayed the road for 23 years. In many ways it was a victim of its' success. The fact that local authorities have the time

and resources to play the patient game often means that people become disillusioned or disenchanted. This quote from Walter, secretary of CCC sums this up:

The sad thing about it is, having marched the people up to the top of the hill and marched them back down again, every time they (SRC) withdrew. The people of Corkerhill didn't know if they were coming or going. A lot..of complacency set into Corkerhill. When it came to what I consider to be the real action that we might have been able to take in Corkerhill if we had the same level of commitment we had back in they (early) days then I suggest that they would have had some difficulty trying to cut those trees down. If we had a weakness it was because we stopped it so many times.

Conclusion: Community Strategy

It is apparent from this study of the protest against the M77 that the events in late 1994 and early 1995 perhaps overshadowed the 25 years of protest by Corkerhill community that had gone before. Indeed if we talk in terms of degrees of success and failure then it could be argued that whilst the Free State protesters delayed the motorway construction for about six months, Corkerhill community delayed it for over 20 years. Protests such as this should not be judged in these terms however but instead in terms of their effect on the people involved.

It is also evident that the actions of the Community cannot neatly be pigeonholed. Community action of this type is often labelled as being consensual or conflictual in nature. In this respect the protest was both, however the level of government involved often determined the type of approach adopted. Corkerhill Community Council concentrated on building relationships with local District councillors and spreading the message amongst them. They were aware that if the proposal were to be taken to a Public Inquiry Glasgow District Council would have to be convinced. At the Regional level protest tended to be more contentious. In many respects the message was relayed to SRC through demonstrations, petitions and videos. Those opposed to the M77 openly challenged SRCs' claims, particularly with regard to the claims made in the scheme justification report and the contradictions with SRCs' social strategy.

What is also clear from this is the evolution of Corkerhill's strategy to combat the M77. The initial period of protest concerned the right-of-way to the Pollok Country Park and this was the issue around which the community moved for about ten years. Realisation that this strategy would prove ineffective resulted in a shift of emphasis to matters of health and safety. This proved to be partially successful but the resultant Public Inquiry ruled in favour of construction causing a shift of strategy once more, this time towards the issue of compensation. By the early 1990s other groups with a different message, focussing on the need for construction and

emphasising public transport alternatives had taken up the opposition to the motorway. Corkerhill community saw the benefit in adopting their strategy and attempting different methods of halting construction. Thus opposition to the M77 follows the same track as opposition nationally and in Glasgow, but with one exception: opposition to the M77 does not appear to start within the business community protesting about threats to their livelihood. Thereafter opposition is on the grounds of loss of amenity (access to Pollok Park), on the need for the road and public transport as an alternative (Glasgow for People and the 'Instead of the Ayr Road Route report') and on the wider grounds of the need for the roads programme itself (The Pollok Free State). This evolutionary process is perhaps not as systematic as that suggested by Painter for the UK as the latter two phases appear to occur almost simultaneously during the 90s. It must be remembered however that, in Glasgow, opposition to urban motorways in the 70s included opposition to the M77 and thus perhaps on closer examination opposition to the M77 does follow those wider historical processes.

Opposition by Corkerhill residents also appears to broaden in nature as it develops. As noted, opposition initially centred on the loss of the right-of-way before moving on to focus on the effect the M77 would have on the health of local people. Thus Corkerhill's early disagreement to the M77 revolved around the impact of the road on Corkerhill. Later opposition however appears to take a more expansive view of the M77. Corkerhill Community Council was a member of STARR, which opposed the road on the grounds that it is not the solution to Glasgow's traffic problems. They took the view that public transport was the answer. In line with this Corkerhill residents appear to adopt the strategy and tactics of the anti-roads movement in that they establish protest camps and engage in direct action against road constructors.

Furthermore, the support of the Community was always sought before action was taken. Clearly the actions of the Community Council were important in Corkerhill's opposition to the M77. Corkerhill Community Council has consistently fought for its community on a number of issues. Generally the campaigns were organised in such a way that the rest of the community had a great deal of input into the strategy. If not, they were always kept aware of developments. In this respect information about the M77 flowed from community leaders to other members of the community through public meetings and leaflets. These community leaders made themselves available to provide information and because Corkerhill is a small community of just over 1000 people it was rare for someone not to know the latest news. Information would come directly from the Community Council, or from neighbours who had heard the latest developments. When going to the shop or the local pub they would pass Community Council members sitting outside the Community shop, its windows full of updates and posters. The networks of communication within Corkerhill ensured this flow of information.

Corkerhill's campaign represents almost 30 years of collective action in opposition to the M77 involving collective action and campaigns such as demonstrations, petitions, public meetings, letters, Public Inquiries and protest camps. A number of questions arise from this historical analysis.

How did collective action emerge in Corkerhill and how was it sustained? Reading the above account would appear to suggest that CCC played a crucial role in mobilising Corkerhill residents to protest. The Community Council was at the forefront of opposition, representing Corkerhill at the Public Inquiry and organising demonstrations and petitions. Does this mean that the Community Council mobilised collective action in Corkerhill and if so how? Furthermore it is reasonable to suggest that before collective action can emerge individuals must know the purpose of this action, must be aware of what it is they are protesting about and why. If this is so, then is it not the case that knowledge must be disseminated and opinion shaped before action can take place? Given the apparent role of the Community Council in mobilising protest can it be assumed that they also mobilised opinion? Did the Community Council act as opinion leaders or influentials in Corkerhill, shaping community opinion? How important were the networks of communication within Corkerhill in this process? These questions therefore are concerned with the processes of macro-mobilisation within Corkerhill. They draw attention to how collective action emerged in Corkerhill, and therefore how Corkerhill was mobilised.

Part 3: Opinion Mobilisation and Movement Dynamics

Chapter Four: Shaping & Forming Opinion in Corkerhill

Introduction

The previous chapter covered the history of opposition against the M77 and introduced the three communities covered in the survey. In particular it focussed on the long struggle by Corkerhill community. I noted the central position of Corkerhill Community Council in this process and raised the possibility of CC members having the role of opinion leaders or influentials within the community. In addition, I also noted the apparent existence of social networks of communication that facilitated this opposition. Theories that seek to explain mobilisation typically focus on answering questions such as why are certain individuals mobilised rather than others? What conditions are necessary for individuals to mobilise into collective groups? This chapter aims to explore empirically the processes of mobilisation by asking, and seeking to answer, the question: how were people in Corkerhill mobilised to participate in collective action and therefore how did grass-roots collective action emerge? By examining the networks of communication within Corkerhill I will endeavour to demonstrate that communication processes were essential to grass-roots mobilisation. Furthermore I hope to also demonstrate the importance of community influentials in shaping and mobilising community opinion. Before doing so however it is important to understand and clarify the focus on Corkerhill as the object of study. In other words, why Corkerhill and not the other communities?

I stated in the previous chapter that Corkerhill opposed the M77 for a period of 25 years and this alone may be reason enough to warrant further study. I hope to empirically demonstrate however that Corkerhill is distinct in many other ways from both Arden and Thornliebank and that these differences contributed to the longevity and nature of Corkerhill's protest.

Differences with Thornliebank are immediately apparent from the census data of the previous chapter. Thornliebank is a relatively affluent area whilst Corkerhill is not. Differences with Arden are less apparent. Socio-economically the communities are alike, with broadly equivalent levels of unemployment and similar neighbourhood characteristics. In addition, the construction of the M77 stood to effect both communities in a similar way. The M77 came as close to Arden in places as it did to Corkerhill.

Given these similarities a similar reaction from both communities to the threat of the M77 may be expected. Yet, as I hope to demonstrate, this did not occur. Analysis of the survey data

demonstrates differences amongst all the communities and it is to this I now wish to turn, focussing initially on a broad overview of opinion. The first area covered will be respondents' opinion of the M77.

Opinion Within the Three Communities

It is first necessary to determine what opinion of the road was. To this end residents in the three communities were asked to state their opinion about the M77. The results are displayed in Table 4.1

Table 4.1: Opinion of the M77 (all communities)

	Opinion (%)
Str Agree	6
Agree	37
Neither Agree/Disagr	22
Disagree	24
Str Disagree	10
	N: 413

Table 4.2: Opinion of the M77 amongst three communities

Opinion	Area (%)			
	Corkerhill	Arden	Thornliebank	
Str Agree		2	12	
Agree	9	39	64	
Neither Agree/ Disagree	30	26	13	
Disagree	40	23	10	
Str Disagree	21	11	1	
N:	139	135	139	N:413

As is clear from Table 4.1 more respondents indicated that they agreed with the construction of the M77 than those who did not, 43% indicating they either agreed or strongly agreed compared to 34% who indicated that they either disagreed or strongly disagreed. As might be expected however opinion within the different communities differs as is demonstrated in Table 4.2.

Clearly there are disparities between communities in terms of the opinion of

respondents. For example 12% of Thornliebank residents strongly agreed whilst 64% agreed. In comparison no residents of Corkerhill strongly agreed with construction whilst over 60% either disagreed or strongly disagreed. In Arden 41% agreed whilst 32% of residents either disagreed or strongly disagreed with the construction of the M77. Of interest is the relatively high numbers of people who indicated that they neither agreed nor disagreed, almost 30% in Corkerhill, 25% in Arden and 12% in Thornliebank. The higher figures for the former two may be a result of the deprived nature of these communities and a reflection of the fact that residents had other more pressing concerns at the time of the survey.

The survey does appear therefore to vindicate the decision to construct the M77. Overall opinion along the route of the road does support its construction. This is perhaps to be expected in Thornliebank, which stood to benefit from construction in the form of reduced traffic. Less expected is the level of agreement in Arden.

Respondents were also asked to state why they either agreed or disagreed with construction. The vast majority (70%) of respondents who agreed indicated that they did so because they believed the M77 would reduce traffic in their community. Reasons for disagreeing with the M77 were more varied and are outlined in Table 4.3 below.

Table 4:3: Reasons for disagreeing with M77

Reason	%
Health Fears	40
Increased Pollution	26
Public Transport Better	5
Parkland Destroyed	8
Damage to Environment	15
N: 144	

As Table 4:3 illustrates the major concerns for those respondents who disagreed with construction were issues of health and pollution. It is true however that concern does not automatically translate into opposition or protest and thus the survey also asked respondents if they had protested against the M77. The results of this question are outlined in Table 4.4 below:

There is a clear and sharp difference between the three communities in this regard. The majority (64%) of Corkerhill residents engaged in some kind of protest activity against the M77. Protest activity includes attending public meetings, signing petitions, attending demonstrations or marches and 'direct' protest against construction. In the other communities the numbers protesting are significantly lower. Table 4.2 demonstrated that within Arden there was a fairly

significant number of residents surveyed who either disagreed or strongly disagreed with the construction of the M77, 33% in fact. As Table 4.4 illustrates however only 16% of Arden residents engaged in any protest activity. Clearly Corkerhill residents converted their disagreement into protest whilst many Arden residents did not.

Table 4.4: Percentage of community residents who protested against M77

Protest	Area (%)		
	Corkerhill	Arden	Thornliebank
Yes	64	16	10
No	36	84	90
			N: 413

Thus it is clear, from the survey results, that with regard to the M77, Corkerhill is distinct from the other communities. Residents of both Arden and Thornliebank supported construction whilst residents of Corkerhill did not. Corkerhill residents are more concerned about the construction of the M77. Their opinion generally differs from that of residents in other communities in that whilst the majority of people surveyed in Arden and Thornliebank support construction the opposite is the case for Corkerhill.

Demonstrating the differences between the communities is in many respects relatively easy; explaining why the differences exist is a more challenging proposition. Exploring possible explanations for these differences will, I hope, shed some light on the questions raised at the beginning of this chapter: how are people mobilised to participate in collective action and how does grass-roots collective action emerge? I suggested earlier that social networks of communication appear to be important for mobilising collective action and that within these networks certain individuals, or influentials, were crucial sources of information. I also suggested that both might have been important in Corkerhill. I now wish to look in more detail at the mobilisation processes at work within Corkerhill, beginning with establishing if any Corkerhill residents could be considered as influentials.

Shaping Opinion in Corkerhill: Community Influentials

I have suggested that the actions of Corkerhill Community Council (CCC) were important in sustaining protest against the M77. In this section I aim to demonstrate that CCC members were influential in shaping and forming opinions within the community. To do so I will initially examine where Corkerhill residents received information about the M77. In this way it will

be possible to determine whether 'influentials' within Corkerhill did indeed inform other residents of developments.

Table 4.5: Sources of Information about M77 in surveyed areas

Ques: Can you remember where you first heard about the construction of the M77 extension?

Information Source	Area (%)			Row Total (%)
	Corkerhill	Arden	Th'bank	
Newspaper	5	27	42	25
Television	3	2	2	2
Comm Council	46	4	0	17
Friends/N'bours	40	54	45	46
Other	6	13	11	10
				N: 413

The figures in table 4.5 indicate that within all communities there exist networks of communication between friends, neighbours, etc. and as is apparent over 40% of respondents first heard of the M77 from this source. More Corkerhill residents however first learned of the M77 through their Community Council. The number relying on friends and neighbours is more or less comparable with other areas, however in Arden and Thornliebank many more rely on the media as a source of information. In terms of sources of information, it is this which most clearly signifies Corkerhill's difference from the other surveyed communities. As Table 4.5 demonstrates 46% of Corkerhill residents first learned about the M77 from the CC whilst 8% learned through the media. In comparison only 4% of Arden residents and no Thornliebank residents surveyed stated that their initial source of information regarding the M77 was their local community council.

Thus this would appear to suggest that in Corkerhill the members of the Community Council does indeed fill the role of influentials and act as conduits of information; first hearing the information, then passing it on to other residents who then inform friends, neighbours etc. From this it is possible to argue that CCC was an important *initial* source of information for Corkerhill residents. This however does not mean to say that it remained an important source. It may be that after initially hearing from the CC Corkerhill residents then turned to the media or neighbours to keep them up-to-date. To establish if this was the case surveyed residents were asked a further question regarding information sources. This question asked them to state where they received their information about the protest during the period 1994-1995 when the Free State had been established and protest against the M77 was at its most intense. This was a period when the M77 and issues surrounding it were extensively covered by both local and national

media and we may expect residents to utilise these information sources more than previously. The results are outlined below.

Table 4.6: Protest Information by Area

Ques: During the recent protest to stop construction can you remember where you got your information about it?

Information source	Area (%)			Row Total
	Corkerhill	Arden	Thornliebank	
Newspapers	7	64	76	48
Television	9	13	17	13
Comm Council	79	10	1	30
Friends, neighbours	5	13	6	8
Other	0	1	1	0
				N:413

As Table 4.6 indicates the Community Council in Corkerhill actually becomes a much greater source of information during the period of greatest activity in attempting to halt the road. In the early months of 1994 when the protest camp was active and the issue dominated the news 79% of Corkerhill residents stated that their main source of information about the protest at this time was the CC. This is compared to 46% who cited the CC as their initial source of information. In the other areas the predominant source of knowledge was the media. Even at this time when Corkerhill was on the front pages of local and national newspapers and the protest featured on the television news residents still appear to turn to the CC for up-to-date information. Furthermore, the majority of those who previously kept up to date through their neighbours also cite the CC as their source of information at this time. This expansion is in part the result of the increased activity of the CC at this time to ensure the community was aware of events and partly the result of more people approaching the CC at this time because of the high profile of the campaign. Furthermore it does relate favourably to the suggestion promoted by Melucci: that local movements act as alternatives to dominant sources of information. Within Arden and Thornliebank the numbers citing the media as their initial source of knowledge about the M77 are 29 and 44% respectively, in Corkerhill this falls to 8%. It is possible that the formal or semi-formal network that exists between the community and the CC is responsible for this difference. The CCs pro-active strategy of knocking on doors, distributing leaflets, holding meetings and staging demonstrations certainly appears to have removed the need for residents to rely on alternative sources of information to keep abreast of developments.

Following this it could be suggested that it is possible to tentatively categorise the communities according to the information sources residents utilise to remain up-to-date with recent developments. Arden and Thornliebank seem to rely on existing media such as television and newspapers for information on the M77 and could thus be categorised as 'media-dependent communities'. Corkerhill, alternatively, could be classified as a 'discursive community' in that the dominant source of information appears to be discursive in nature. This communication may occur between influentials in the CC and residents or between residents themselves. It is possible that only communities which are able to overcome their dependence upon dominant media as the principal source of information about local events are able to organise successfully in opposition to a perceived threatening development.

I have suggested that CCC can be considered as opinion leaders or influentials within the community and demonstrated that for the majority of Corkerhill residents surveyed the CC was their most important source of information about the M77. Residents of other surveyed areas by comparison show a far greater reliance on the media for information. Previously however I noted a number of features said to characterise opinion influentials. These are: opinion leaders are typically more socially active; more involved in social organisations and centrally located in personal networks.

It is reasonable to hypothesise that those who would fulfil the role of opinion leader or community influential would be active in local organisations and activities. If it is the case that community councillors fill this role we should expect them to be more interested and involved in local politics and local issues. Thus we would expect to find those most interested in local issues joining local organisations. To examine this possibility surveyed residents were asked their interest in politics and local issues. They were further asked to indicate if they were members of any groups, in particular if they were a member of a Trade Union or a member of the Community Council. In this way it was possible to determine whether interest in politics expressed itself at the workplace, on a national level, or at a community level.

Table 4.7: Interest in Politics and local Issues by Group Membership (Corkerhill)
Ques: generally speaking how interested would you say you are in local politics and issues?
 Group Membership (%)

Interest in Politics and local Issues	Trade Union	Comm Council	None
Very	0	17	0
Quite	21	42	15
Not Very	57	42	46

Not At All

23

0

39
N:139

Table 4.7 indicates that members of CCC did indeed express greater interest in political and local issues, and thus their interest in local issues is expressed through membership of local organisations. People who are uninterested in local concerns rarely go to the trouble to stand for election to the community council. As the survey data indicates 59% of CC members stated that they were quite or very interested in politics and local issues. This is compared to 21% of Trade Union members and 15% of respondents who did not belong to a group. The number of Corkerhill residents who said they were either not very or not at all interested in politics is also significantly lower amongst community council members. Indeed no member of the community council indicated a complete lack of interest. Thus it is possible to suggest that following the typology of opinion leaders mentioned above CCC members were more active in local organisations and more interested and involved in local issues. Furthermore this involvement is not confined to membership of local groups. CC members indicate a greater willingness to actively protest about issues that concern them. Residents were asked whether or not they had protested in the past about issues other than the M77. (Table 4.8 below) The results indicated that 54% of Corkerhill residents who had previously protested were members of the CC. This compares to 8% who were members of trade unions and 38% who stated that they were not a member of any group.

Table 4.8: Propensity to Protest by Group Membership (Corkerhill residents)

Ques: Have you ever protested about an issue you felt strongly about before the M77 protest?

Previously Protested	Group Membership (%)			Row Total
	Trade Union	Comm Council	None	
Yes	8	54	38	13
No	51	7	42	76
Col Total	45	13	42	N: 89

Furthermore alongside a greater propensity to be involved in local organisations and issues it is reasonable to expect those with greater interest in a particular issue to demonstrate greater knowledge and awareness. To examine if this is the case regarding the M77 Corkerhill residents were asked to indicate how long they had known about the M77 and whether or not they knew who was responsible for the decision to construct the road. If CC members are indeed

to be considered as influentials and movement leaders we should expect them to have known longer and be more knowledgeable about the M77 because of their involvement in local issues.

Table 4.9: First heard about M77 by Group Membership

Ques: Can you remember when you first heard about the M77?

First knew about M77	Group Membership (%)			Row Total (%)
	Trade Union	Community Council	None	
1-2 years	11		14	16
2-5 years	42	17	43	56
5-10 years	34	33	32	46
Over 10 years	13	50	11	21
				N: 139

As is apparent from Table 4.10 CC members have known about the M77 for a greater length of time and display better knowledge about the issue when compared to other Corkerhill residents. For example 50% of CC members have known about the M77 for over 10 years and 88% for over 5 years. In comparison Trade Union members and residents who are not group members have typically known for less time, 47% of Trade Unionists and 43% of non-group members knowing for over five years. In addition 100% of CC members correctly stated that SRC was responsible for the decision to construct the M77. By comparison, 61% of TU members and 48% non-group members also correctly identified SRC. More significantly however, a great deal of respondents in these categories either incorrectly attributed the decision to other government institutions or stated that they did not know who was responsible.

Table 4.10: Knowledge of responsibility for M77 by Group Membership

Ques: Do you know who is responsible for the M77 being constructed?

Responsibility for M77	Group Membership (%)			Row Total
	Trade Union	Community Council	None	
Cent Gov.	6		9	4
Scot Office	2		48	7
SRC	61	100	43	113
Don't Know	31			15
				N:139

It is apparent therefore that Corkerhill Community Council acted as a source of information and knowledge within the community. Raising awareness and helping to shape and form opinion does not however automatically result in protest activities. In light of this I now wish move on and explore the success or otherwise the CC had in mobilising residents to protest against the M77. Once again we can postulate a number of hypotheses regarding the mobilising influence of the CC. Firstly, It may be the case that protest against the M77 arises simply from its proximity to Corkerhill. In other words residents demonstrated against the M77 because it was an issue which specifically affected them and their quality of life. This may indeed be the case, however it could also be argued that without the CC to rally around and give a focus for opposition protest still may not have occurred. Thus it can be suggested that, if the CC are movement mobilisers in addition to opinion mobilisers, when asked how they became involved in protesting against the M77 a significant amount of Corkerhill residents will have done so following a public meeting or talking to a CC member.

Mobilising Opinion in Corkerhill

Sixty four percent of Corkerhill residents surveyed protested against the M77, of that number only 15% had previously engaged in any (i.e. not necessarily M77 related) form of protest activity. Table 4.11 outlines the reasons why residents said they protested.

Table 4.11: Reasons for Protest
Ques: Why did you protest against the M77?

Why Protest	%
Feared for Health of Family	49
Pollution Effects of M77	25
Protect Parkland Destroyed	14
Damage to Environment	6
Other	7
N: 89	

Clearly the immediate effects of the M77 in terms of increased noise and air pollution and the consequent health effects were important factors in individual motivations to protest; this will be explored in more detail in subsequent chapters. As Melucci (1989) notes however explaining the reasons **why** protest develops is not the same as explaining **how** it emerges and is sustained. Corkerhill Community Council, by ensuring the community remained aware and up-to-date with developments, were able to increase the mobilisation potential of the community

such that collective protest was possible. For this possibility to become a reality CC members added the role of movement leaders to their existing one of opinion leaders. I noted above that only 15% of residents surveyed indicated that they had protested about other issues prior to protesting about the M77. The majority of Corkerhill residents therefore were not active protesters. It could be argued therefore that the CC both facilitated protest and encouraged protest. The CC facilitated it by organising petitions and demonstrations and encouraged it by holding public meetings and stressing to other residents the importance of protesting against the M77.

Table 4.12: Protest Involvement of Corkerhill Residents

Ques: How did you first get involved in protesting against the M77?

	%
Talking to neighbour/friend	1
Attending meeting	16
Talking to local group	83
N: 89	

Table 4.12 demonstrates that 83% of Corkerhill residents became involved in protesting against the M77 after talking to a member of the local Community Council. A further 16% became involved because they attended a public meeting (invariably organised by the CC). Arguably therefore 99% of Corkerhill residents who protested participated in protest activities because of the actions of the CC. The reason for the success of the CC in mobilising protest may be their recognition that people need to be informed and encouraged and the realisation that protest was more likely if the source of this encouragement was a friend or neighbour. This quote from a Corkerhill resident highlights this.

See if you go to a meeting and its a councillor thats talking, you listen to him but you dont take it all in⁵. If its one of your neighbours thats telling you, about the environment, you listen to them. I talked to a lot of my neighbours and, no using fancy words and that, I said get oot your hoose and get up there and help protect your community and your weans health. I stopped people in the street, if they were going to the shops, and I said, soon you'll no be able to go to the shops, youll no be able to breath for pollution. And you got them thinking, and see the next day they would be sitting wi ye. People would ask you what was happening, what was going on, and you tell them, you're like a newspaper. (Karen)

Thus community councillors and other active residents perceive their role as akin to that of a newspaper: providing up-to-date information to Corkerhill residents and encouraging them to act to oppose the M77. The newspaper perception is perhaps not strictly accurate however as

⁵ In this case she is referring to a local government councillor not a community councillor

clearly the most effective source of interaction between councillors and residents is face-to-face rather than through the printed word; a point stressed by a CC member, Ralph:

Its amazing how people talk about this and talk about that, but trying to get them to come to a meeting is hard; so you talk to them in the street or go to their house. Its all done mouth-to-mouth outside.

Once again, as with spreading information, the relatively small size of Corkerhill in both spatial and population terms and the close-knit nature of the community ensures that CC members can fairly easily meet people in the streets, shops etc. and that word spreads rapidly throughout the community.

Its a small community, I could shout at that end in the morning and everybody in Corkerhill would know at night, and as the leader of a local community I need to decide the best way to help them (Walter)

It is apparent from this that there is an awareness amongst CC members of the leadership role they play in the community. Karen stated that the role of the CC was similar to that of a newspaper whilst Walter, more explicitly, describes himself as a community leader.

The CC therefore was able to successfully mobilise a group of residents to collectively demonstrate their opposition to the M77. This collective demonstration takes different forms and intensity. Some register their opposition by signing a petition others participate in direct forms of activity such as marches and demonstrations. Sixty percent of Corkerhill residents surveyed expressed their opposition to the M77 by signing a petition, 16% attended a public meeting and 24% participated in direct demonstrations against the road. What is perhaps more significant however is that 96% of those who signed a petition did so after talking to a member of the CC. It is true that petitions are perceived as being relatively weak and easy forms of protest this does not mean to say that they are not valid however. The petitions were organised by the CC who went round the doors in Corkerhill, or sat outside the shops gathering signatures. This provided an opportunity for residents to protest, residents who may not otherwise have done so either because they do not have the time or because they were of an age were they considered other forms of participation such as marches and demonstrations beyond them. The survey data does tend to support this, 75% of residents over 50 years old who protested did so by signing a petition, likewise 62% of residents who were employed and therefore perhaps did not have the time to participate more fully did so by signing a petition.

Thus it is possible to argue that Corkerhill's protest against the M77 is generated and sustained by people actively mobilising themselves and others to participate. The presence of

the Community Council as a mobilising factor was crucial to the development of protest. However what is perhaps of greater importance is the presence of an **active** Community Council, or active and motivated individuals attached to the CC. Other affected areas had Community Councils who were opposed to the M77. However it may be that because they were not as active as Corkerhill, in terms of spreading information and organising opposition, that protest in those areas did not occur. We can explore this contention by contrasting the response of the community of Arden to the M77.

I noted earlier that significant number of Arden residents surveyed who disagreed with the construction of the M77 did not protest their disagreement. Indeed only 16% of Arden residents engaged in any protest activity. Exploring this element of the survey data a little deeper reveals that 64% of Arden residents who strongly disagreed and 49% of those who disagreed with the construction did **not** protest against it. Furthermore, of those who did protest the type of protest engaged in differs from that of Corkerhill residents. In Arden protest activity never went beyond the level of attending a public meeting whereas many Corkerhill residents went further and participated in direct protest activities. This raises the following question. Why, given this relatively high degree of opposition, does protest not emerge in Arden in a similar manner to Corkerhill?

One possible answer is that Arden residents who opposed the M77 were the minority in their community, 41% of Arden residents surveyed indicated that they agreed with the building of the M77, and this represents the single biggest group within the community. Arden Community Council did however indicate its opposition to the M77 by signing and supporting the alternative '*Instead of the Ayr Road Route*' document produced by STARR. Thus it can be inferred that the lack of majority support did not hinder opposition from the local CC, in other words the CC did not feel the need to only represent the wishes of the 41% of residents who supported construction. An alternative explanation for the lack of protest in Arden is that it may be the result of the lack of an active CC such as existed in Corkerhill. It is perhaps the case that Arden CC did not fulfil the roles of opinion shaper and mobiliser that Corkerhill CC did. Perhaps Arden CC was not as pro-active as Corkerhill's in terms of spreading information and organising protest. The lack of strategic individuals and groups within Arden opposed to the M77, mobilising support and spreading information, around which other residents could rally may be a significant explanatory factor.

Table 4.6 established that sources of information about the M77 differed between Corkerhill and Arden. In Corkerhill 46% of residents surveyed indicated that their main

information source was the local CC in Arden this figure is 4%. By comparison, 8% of Corkerhill residents surveyed stated the media as their information source whilst 40% indicated that they had heard through friends & neighbours, in Arden these figures are 29% and 54% respectively. Thus in terms of sources of information there are clear differences. The opinion shaping role of Corkerhill CC is not repeated by Arden CC. With regard to keeping residents informed during the protest itself again there are clear distinctions between both communities (see Table 4.7). In Corkerhill the percentage of residents citing the CC as their information source at this time increased to 79% (from the 46% who indicated that the CC was their source of information about the M77 during less high profile times). In Arden the percentage also increased but only to 10% whilst the percentage who indicated that their major source of information at this time was the media increased to 64%. Clearly therefore Arden residents were much more reliant on the media for information and knowledge about the M77. Consequently the opinion shaping and forming role performed by Corkerhill Community Council does not appear to be undertaken by the community council in Arden.

Another possible explanation is that Arden Community Councillors were less concerned about the M77 or held different attitudes to those of members of Corkerhill Community Council. Unfortunately only 4% of Arden residents surveyed stated that they were members of the local community council (Perhaps significant in itself). If we examine the attitudes of members of both CCs across a variety of variables we can determine if the different response to the M77 between the two communities is the consequence of differing attitudes or other factors.

Table 4.13: Community Council Members Opinion of M77 (Corkerhill & Arden)

	Area Community Council Members (%)	
	Arden	Corkerhill
Str Agree		
Agree	17	8
Neither Agr/Disagr		25
Disagree	67	68
Str Disagree	16	
		N:20

As table 4.15 shows, there are broad similarities in opinion about the M77 in both Community Councils; 93% of Corkerhill CC members stated that they either disagree or disagree strongly with the M77 whilst 83% of Arden CC members did likewise. Thus it is not the case that Arden's lack of protest against the M77 was a consequence of the local CC being in favour of it. Instead, the only possible explanation is that the members of Corkerhill CC responded differently

to the threat of the M77. They responded by mobilising the community, spreading information and knowledge, mobilising protest and thus the actions of CCC categorises them as distinct from Arden and could explain the differing responses.

We can examine the influence of the two Community Councils by testing local knowledge of the M77. If, as I have suggested, Corkerhill CC was more active than other community councils in spreading information and knowledge, then there should be clear differences between the residents of surveyed communities in their understanding of the issues and actors involved in the protest. To explore this, residents were asked if they knew who, or which organisation, was responsible for taking the decision to construct the M77. The results by area are outlined in Table 4.16.

Table 4.14: Knowledge of M77 by Area

Ques: Do you know who is responsible for the decision to build the M77?

Responsible	Area (%)		
	Corkerhill	Arden	Thornliebank
Central Gov'mt	3	9	5
Scottish Office	5	9	14
SRC	81	46	44
Other	0	2	1
Don't Know	11	33	36
			N: 413

As is apparent from Table 4.16 the claim made above that levels of knowledge within the communities would differ is supported. In Corkerhill, 81% of residents surveyed correctly stated that SRC was responsible for the decision to build the M77. In Arden and Thornliebank this falls to 46% and 44% respectively. The percentage of Arden residents indicating that they do not know who was responsible is 33% whilst in Corkerhill it is 11%. It is possible to suggest therefore that the highly active approach of Corkerhill CC was successful in keeping residents aware of developments and that the approach they adopted to achieve this was more effective than the measures taken by Arden community council.

What emerges from this discussion is a contradictory picture of two communities, Corkerhill and Arden, who in some respects are very similar yet in others appear completely different. They are similar in their socio-economic characteristics yet differ markedly in their response to a development which will adversely affect their local environment, namely the construction of the M77. In one community, Corkerhill, the residents appear to be well informed about the development, the vast majority of residents gathering their information from the local

community council and protesting vociferously against it, many engaging in direct action to register their opposition. Residents of Arden on the other hand do not seem to be as well informed. The majority of residents rely on the media and friends as sources of information. Fewer of them participate in protest activities and the activities they do engage in are less intense and direct than those of the residents of Corkerhill. It is possible to argue therefore that these differences are the consequence of the major overarching difference between the two communities and that is the response of the respective community councils to the construction of the M77. Thus it appears to be the case that the difference in protest participation, in both the proportion of residents opposed to the M77 participating in protest and in the level of protest activity, can be explained by the activities of the local community councils. In Corkerhill's case the CC was extremely active in mobilising opinion and protest, Arden CC was less active and thus protest did not emerge to the same extent.

Networks of Communication in Corkerhill

What is apparent from the survey data and the above discussion is that within Corkerhill there exists a body of residents who could be considered as community leaders. They are more informed about the M77 issues, have a better knowledge than other residents, are more interested in local issues and take a more active role in local issues by joining local organisations and participating in local protest. Greater knowledge and interest is not enough however to claim that strategic individuals within a community fulfil the role of influentials in addition to their role as community leaders. For this to be the case community leaders must also be sources of information for residents. This is clearly the case in Corkerhill. Those residents who are most interested and active in local issues are members of the CC and the survey evidence demonstrates that for the vast majority of Corkerhill residents the CC was not only their original information source about the M77 but also the most significant source during the protest. Corkerhill Community Council shaped and mobilised community opinion about the M77 by ensuring residents were kept informed.

Networks of information exist within all communities. I noted that Arden and Thornliebank residents received information through informal networks of friends and neighbours. Only in Corkerhill however does there appear to be a semi-formal network between opinion leaders and community residents. It is semi-formal because Corkerhill is small enough to ensure that everyone is probably familiar with almost all community residents and thus community councillors would rarely converse with their neighbours as councillor/resident but instead as councillor/neighbour, neighbour/neighbour, friend/friend etc. It is within these semi-formal networks that knowledge is disseminated. Corkerhill residents display greater knowledge

of the M77 issue and it is possible to suggest that this greater level of knowledge is the result of different sources of information. In Corkerhill residents are kept continually up-to-date by the CC, those that do not hear directly from the CC receive information from those who have. In other areas there is no group disseminating news, residents are still relatively well informed but information comes from media and friends and is likely to be less detailed and informative leading to knowledge which is partial and based on speculation. The close knit nature of Corkerhill (there is one shop, one take-away and one public house) ensured that information would spread rapidly, from the CC to residents. It was also spread between residents, as they met each other on the way to the shops, in the community and on the communal stairs of the tenement housing. The secretary of Corkerhill CC highlights this mobilising role. He states:

Disorganised communities can find it awfully, awfully difficult, and sometimes it takes a ..smaller body of people to try to get to their neighbours.. What we were able to do was argue that there was a possibility we could win. .. At every turn we tried to involve as many of the community as possible in any decision. There is absolutely no way you could go to the outside world without that..You had to have your community behind you....Thats how we got the community involved, almost on a daily basis, mountains of leaflets, things in the (community) shop, public meetings.

Thus there is an acceptance by residents of the organising role of the CC and the part it played in providing information to the rest of the community. Alongside the usual methods of doing this (leaflets, meetings) the CC exploited the fact that the community shop where CC meetings were held was next door to the only grocers shop in Corkerhill, this enabled them to set up stalls, display posters and engage people in conversation as they passed. In this way they were able to inform residents of the latest events, ask them to fill in petitions or send letters and tell them the dates and times of public meetings or demonstrations. The CC were pro-active in spreading information also, they did not simply wait for people to pass the shops; the CC chairperson describes how they attempted to ensure that all residents were kept up to date:

We sat at the (community) shop and spoke to the residents there, got them to send letters, and we got their addresses. The addresses we didn't have we were able to go to and tell them what was going on. That's what we would do with most things that we were doing...I don't think there was very many that didn't know about it. It is a small community, people hear from their neighbours

In this case the chairperson confirms that the close-knit nature of Corkerhill ensured that information was dispersed to all residents Later developments included the use of slide-shows in the community shop and large banners hung outside at all times as constant visible reminders of the community's campaign.

This process of opinion mobilisation is reminiscent of the theoretical models of opinion-leaders discussed previously: information flowing from influentials to the wider public within communities. It perhaps more accurately reflects the multi-step models where information does not just flow vertically from influentials to recipients but also horizontally between influentials and between less active residents.

The 'Public Sphere' In Corkerhill

Following this discussion of networks of communication within Corkerhill it is possible to make some comments on the nature and type of public discourse that characterised Corkerhill. In chapter 1 I made the connection between Habermas's concept of the public sphere and the emergence of a critically reasoning public opinion.

It could be argued that a critically reasoning public sphere of a Habermasian kind existed within Corkerhill. The networks of communication utilised by Corkerhill residents in order to disseminate information throughout the community do appear to correspond to a critically reasoning public sphere. In line with Habermas's reasoning, opinion in Corkerhill does appear to form inside processes of debate. Unlike enlightenment Europe, however, this does not occur in coffee houses and salons but in Community Council meetings, on the streets of Corkerhill and over cups of tea and coffee in residents' homes. These semi-formal networks of communication ensure that Corkerhill residents are kept informed of developments and thus the discussion of the M77 that takes place within Corkerhill is perhaps more informed than it would otherwise have been. The survey evidence does appear to back this up with Corkerhill residents appearing to be better informed.

What the survey evidence cannot tell us, and what we can therefore only surmise, is whether opposition to the M77 developed in the way it did in Corkerhill because a critically reasoning public sphere came about as a result of residents debating the issues. Or did opposition to the M77 emerge because a critically reasoning public sphere existed in Corkerhill anyway? According to Habermas the emergent public sphere of seventeenth century Europe was dependent upon the spread of trade and newsletters, clearly this is not the case in Corkerhill. In the earlier chapter detailing Corkerhill's history I made the point that the community has a history of social cohesion. In the past residents have initiated rent clubs, organised social events and have protested about many other issues other than the M77. In light of this it is possible to argue that a public sphere existed within Corkerhill. It was a public sphere of conversation and communication about 'public' issues, in other words issues that would affect

the community rather than day-to-day conversations. Because of this information about the M77 would have spread quickly around the community as would the residents interpretations and feelings of opposition.

In contrast, the survey evidence appears to indicate that this public sphere did not exist to the same extent within the other communities of Arden and Thornliebank. As noted, the networks of communication that appear to occur in Corkerhill do not do so in either Arden and Thornliebank, and earlier I labelled these communities as 'media dependent' in terms of sources of information about the M77. For Habermas (1989) a public sphere where the media dominates does not generate public opinion instead it produces popular opinion. This could account for the reasons why opposition did not arise in Arden in the same way that it did in Corkerhill, because there was no critically reasoning public sphere in Arden within which opposition to the M77 could be discussed and debated.

However in the light of other known evidence about Arden, the notion that this community is entirely 'media dependent' rather than 'discursive' seems hasty. What must then be considered is the presence of public 'spheres' within communities. For example it may be the case that within Arden other issues dominated residents' discussions. Whilst Arden residents did not participate in the M77 protest in significant numbers, the community does have a history of protest on other issues. For example, Arden Community Council and Arden residents were involved during the opposition to the poll tax. Furthermore, during the time of the most concerted opposition to the M77, early 1994, the major landlord in Arden at that time, Scottish Homes, was attempting to conduct a 'stock transfer' to another social landlord. This was the topic of much debate in Arden, and indeed organised opposition, and thus whilst there may have been a 'housing sphere' there may not, as a consequence, have been an 'M77 Sphere'. In both cases, Arden Community Council was actively involved in mobilising the community, and arguably the same kinds of 'opinion leaders' or community influentials that mobilised Corkerhill did likewise in Arden around different issues.

A further consideration is that public spheres may consist of a number of constituent spheres of discussion around which conversations are constructed and debate takes place. For example everyday conversations often cover a wide variety of topics, from the personal to the political, and it is probably the case that topics such as stock transfers or motorway developments are only going to be one part of those conversations. However the salience of a

topic is likely to depend on the extent to which it remains talked about. If topics drift off the agenda people will eventually stop discussing them. If, however a topic remains alive within community discussions a public sphere of discussion about that topic will persist. Consequently Arden residents may not be passive recipients of media messages. It is likely to be the case that many Arden residents are active in their community and do oppose developments that threaten that community. To suggest that public opinion does not exist within Arden but that popular opinion has replaced it is perhaps misleading.

Habermas suggested that in the absence of a public sphere people become consumers of ideas and opinions in the mass media. What does appear to be the case, with the exception of only a fairly small percentage of Arden residents, is that they *were* consumers of ideas and opinion about the M77, but that does not mean the same is true for every issue. It is this that marks the distinction between Corkerhill and Arden. In Corkerhill the M77 remained a salient topic within the community's public sphere. Or to look at it another way, the M77 sphere that existed in Corkerhill did not dissipate or become subsumed into others and thus Corkerhill residents continued to discuss and debate the M77 in far greater numbers than Arden residents did.

With regard to the M77, networks of communication do not appear to be as strong within Arden. What must be factored in to this discussion however is the fact that at the time of the most intense protest the impact of the M77 on the two communities differed. I noted that at this time Arden community successfully opposed the stock-transfer plans of its major social landlord. This may have been an issue of over-riding importance to residents. It is also logical to assume that this action required both the shaping and mobilisation of community opinion. Moreover it is also likely that this took place within networks of communication within the community.

This must therefore lead to a re-positioning of Arden within the earlier analysis of communication within each community. Previously I tentatively categorised each community in terms of their information sources and classified Corkerhill as discursive and Arden as media dependent. On further consideration however this is an over-generalisation. Given the fact that Arden has historically demonstrated an ability to organise protest it must therefore be concluded that the earlier classification of media dependent can only apply to the M77 issue and that Arden is less media-dependent than originally stated and even then only with the issue of the M77. For other issues Arden may well be classified as discursive.

Moreover, it is possible to suggest that the differing responses to the M77 issue may not be the result of different internal structures of communication but instead be a consequence of more fundamental differences between the two communities of Arden and Cokerhill. These differences must be factored into this discussion; in particular, the fact that the main landlord in Cokerhill was Glasgow District Council whilst in Arden it was Scottish Homes. The latter were, as we have seen, actively pursuing a stock transfer agenda. If this had not been the case Arden's response to the M77 would have been likely to have been very different, and the community may well have turned its attention to the M77 issue. Furthermore, it can also be suggested that the people within each community respond differently. Cokerhill had a well-established Community Council and a strong local voice. The Community Council appears to have had the ability to mobilise the community on a number of fronts.⁶ This does not seem to have been the case in Arden. Perhaps this is the key to Arden's different response: it is this interaction between issues and people which explains it, not a lack of suitable communication networks. Networks of communication, as strong as those within Cokerhill, may well exist in Arden also but simply revolve around different issues.

The empirical evidence available to substantiate this is limited. Consequently it cannot be said with absolute certainty that networks of communication such as existed in Cokerhill did not emerge in response to the M77 in Arden. What is clear however is that the networks within Cokerhill were crucial in shaping opinion about the M77 and in mobilising opinion against it.

Conclusion

This chapter aimed to answer the questions: how were Cokerhill residents mobilised to participate in collective action and how did grass-roots collective action emerge? By examining Cokerhill's protest against the M77 we can suggest the following answers to the above questions.

Firstly: how were people mobilised to participate in collective action? I have suggested that within Cokerhill certain influentials fulfilled the role of both opinion and movement leaders and through their activities successfully mobilised the protest against the M77. The survey evidence supports the contention that different communities have different sources of information, that Cokerhill residents received information from the CC. Residents in other surveyed areas typically relied upon friends or the media. In this way the social networks of

⁶ I noted previously that CCC ran a series of campaigns, covering issues such as rail transport, damp homes, central heating and smoke detectors, all whilst fighting the M77

communication through which information is passed, opinion shaped and collective discussion takes place differ between communities. In Corkerhill I suggested that a dynamic and fluid network existed between the CC and residents and between residents themselves, this ensured that information flowed throughout the community and that all residents (or almost all) were kept informed and up to date. Analysis of the survey evidence led to the conclusion that these networks existed in Corkerhill but not in Arden. Corkerhill CC was able to spread information and tactics because it was successful in utilising or establishing networks between itself and the community.

I also noted that perhaps the most significant difference between Corkerhill and Arden was the response of the respective CCs to the M77. Members of both CCs displayed broadly similar opinions and levels of concern about the M77 and in terms of structural socio-economic characteristics the two communities are similar. However Corkerhill CC actively opposed the M77 and took this message to the community in a pro-active manner. The survey evidence suggests that Arden CC did not respond in a similar manner. It is possible to argue therefore that Corkerhill's protest against the M77 was generated and sustained by influential Corkerhill residents who initially shaped opinion and then mobilised it. In answer to the question it can be suggested, with regards to Corkerhill, that people are mobilised by active community mobilisers operating on a number of levels, raising awareness, offering information and advice and organising protest.

How did grass-roots collective action emerge? Following empirical analysis of information sources about the M77 within the three surveyed communities I categorised Arden and Thornliebank as 'media-dependant communities' and Corkerhill as a 'discursive community', the result of the latter's' apparent reliance on face-to-face interaction as it's predominant source of information in comparison to the former's reliance on the media. Perhaps the answer to the question lies here. It could be suggested that collective action emerges when movement leaders or influentials are successfully able to construct an alternative to messages promoted in the dominant media or alternatively overcome dominant media apathy or avoidance. In this way movements are able to bring people together to engage in collective action. This has the effect of constructing an organised public by creating an alternative internal message which serves to mobilise protest. It does this by initially demonstrating that the issue is indeed public and not private, that others are suffering or will suffer and that collective action is the only response that offers any hope of success.

The next step in examining Corkerhill's mobilisation therefore is to determine the message constructed by the community in response to the M77. It is therefore necessary to

determine specific motivational and interpretative factors which mobilise collective-action and it is these 'collective-action frames' that I wish to examine in the next chapter.

Chapter 5:
Framing Corkerhill: Identity, Agency and Injustice

'goals such as a cleaner environment are goals we determine for ourselves as a community, goals we could not conceive, much less achieve as individuals....People in communities are not an aggregate of individuals or set of preferences to be satisfied. People in communities know purposes and aspirations together they could not know alone'

Mark Sagoff 'The Economy of the Earth' 1988

Introduction

The previous chapter examined the networks of communication, which existed within Corkerhill, and I suggested that, certainly in the case of the M77, the presence of these networks was a significant distinguishing feature between Corkerhill and the other surveyed areas. I also suggested that because of this Corkerhill could be considered as a 'discursive community', the others as 'media dependent'. Furthermore, I suggested that perhaps the origins of grass-roots collective action lay in the ability of a community to construct an alternative message to those dominant messages promulgated by the media and official sources. This chapter seeks to explore this alternative message. Previously I have examined the processes of micromobilisation working within Corkerhill and noted that community leaders appear to have a crucial role in the emergence and mobilisation of Corkerhill's protest against the M77. It is not enough however to claim that these factors alone can explain why certain people become involved in collective-action. To understand this requires an exploration of the deeper motivations that lie beneath the surface of grass-roots mobilisation; the 'oppositional consciousness' that develops amongst affected groups. This chapter therefore aims to explore the nature of the oppositional consciousness which Corkerhill residents developed as a response to the M77.

In order to do this, the concept of framing and collective action frames, discussed in chapter 1, will be explored in greater detail. I aim to demonstrate that because Corkerhill residents interpreted the construction of the M77 in particular ways this facilitated opposition. The process of cognitive praxis or cognitive mapping that occurs in Corkerhill is also important for shaping the collective identity of the community. This chapter will, therefore, by utilising the concept of framing, explore the motivations of those most active in opposition to the M77 and seek to demonstrate how they interpret events, construct meanings for what is going on in the world around them and define themselves as part of a collective identity. In this way, the specific oppositional consciousness of Corkerhill will be established. To achieve this reference will be made to Gamson's (1992) discussion of collective action frames and I will endeavour to demonstrate that this can help to illuminate Corkerhill's protest.

Corkerhill's Injustice Frame

Injustice is a central component of Corkerhill residents' motivations for protest and opposition to the M77; in community literature and residents' language opposition to the construction is frequently justified because of the perceived manifest unfairness of the M77. The nature of the injustice varies but is predominantly found in three components of opposition: spatial, class and political. I will discuss each in turn beginning with the spatial element.

Spatial Injustice

Corkerhill residents have developed two distinct but connected strands of spatial injustice, neither is mutually exclusive and both are used interconnectedly by residents when justifying collective action. This first strand refers to the sense of injustice of the spatial exclusion the M77 would inevitably produce whilst the second has developed around the sense of injustice at the perception of spatial segregation which would also result. For many residents the construction of the M77 will inevitably lead to these and the meanings they attach to the road reflect this perception.

Ideas of spatial exclusion are often included within existing discussions of social and political exclusion. Social exclusion refers to the inability of certain groups in society (usually the poor) to participate effectively in society, with particular reference to social, employment and political activities. Recent research on social exclusion has tended to view it as a process rather than the result of a process (Lee & Murie, 1997) and thus is concerned with relational rather than distributional issues, in particular relations between citizen and state. It is argued that social exclusion results from a failure of four systems: civic systems that ensure that all citizens are democratically equal and promote civic integration; the economic system, integration within which ensures citizens feel they are positively contributing towards society; social systems that entail the ability of the citizen to avail themselves of state provided social services and, finally, family systems which promote interpersonal integration. These references to social institutions are consistent with Marshall's concept of citizenship rights; consequently, social exclusion can be considered as the denial of citizenship rights. (Berghman, 1995) The concept of spatial exclusion has not been as extensively researched and perhaps for this reason it is, as stated, often linked in to discussions of social exclusion. For example, Berghmann refers to spatial exclusion in terms of 'poor spaces', regions or communities of poverty and deprivation. This definition however seems to mark a return to those which emphasise distributional issues and moves attention away from the fact that the term exclusion implies exclusion *from* something in the way

that people are socially excluded *from* participation in society. Thus, logically spatial exclusion refers to exclusion from participating in local space and interacting with the local environment. These concepts are similar to those to the notion of 'territorial injustice' coined by Davies (1968) and developed by Harvey (1973) who expands the term to 'territorial distributive justice' and locates it within the broader context of discussions of social justice. The role of the state in contributing to the process of spatial exclusion should not be underestimated for it is the state, through planning agencies, which determines in many cases how space is to be utilised and whether or not that use is to be exclusionary in nature.

For Corkehill residents the construction of the M77 was viewed as an exclusionary development in that they were excluded from participating in their surrounding environment; more specifically excluded from the Pollok Estate. In terms of injustice frames the M77 *meant* exclusion. This is apparent in much of the literature and pamphlets produced by the Community Council throughout their struggle to oppose the road. For example the Council's 1987 Formal Objection to the Public Inquiry made this point:

We consider that the proposed Ayr Road Route will do nothing more for the people of Corkehill other than speed the area towards further deprivation. In as much as the 'Ayr Route' is planned to plough its way through the woodlands only 30 metres away from the houses and children's play area...Not only destroying mature trees, and the plant and wildlife habitat, of rabbits, deer and foxes..but also *cutting the community off from all the much needed breathing spaces of the designated Countryside, Pollok Park and the world acclaimed amenities of Pollok House and the Burrell Museum.* (p.2. Emphasis added)

Clearly perceptions of being excluded or cut off from the local environment are important to local residents and a significant reason for opposition. A more explicit justification for objection to the M77 on the grounds of its exclusionary nature is made later in the document:

Needless to say we are..proud to live near Pollok park, Pollok House and of course the wonder of the Burrell museum. Nevertheless when one considers that with the dual-carriageway we will be totally excluded from all these amenities and much needed open place..who is to blame for at least trying to fight back..and why should we be content to suffer damp and ill-maintained houses..while the area less than a mile away is receiving world acclaim. (p.15)

As is apparent, the focus of much of this sense of injustice is the perception amongst residents that Corkehill community already suffers in many ways from the effects of an unhealthy local and especially home environment and the 'breathing space' of Pollok Park is the only recreational and health amenity enjoyed by residents. Furthermore there is a perception that other residents of Glasgow will be able to enjoy Glasgow's cultural heritage in the form of Pollok

House and The Burrell Museum whilst residents of the community in closest proximity to them will not. The former perception is highlighted by Lilly, a resident of over 20 years and member of the Community Council, in Corkerhill's presentation to the Public Inquiry Lilly emphasised these fears:

One of the men (lawyers) asked me what did I think of the M77. I replied that that the M77 was not going to do us any good whatsoever. It was going to put a lot of children and people in Corkerhill who suffer from asthma in a terrible state. (I told them) we have the trees which provide oxygen. There was another lady whose son suffered from asthma she gave a statement as well

Thus perceptions of spatial exclusion are prevalent in Corkerhill's opposition. It is clear that for residents the M77 would result in exclusion from the local environment and deny Corkerhill residents the opportunities to enjoy the local amenities which would still be easily available to residents of other areas. There is an obvious sense of injustice apparent in Corkerhill's opposition. This was fuelled by the perception amongst residents that Corkerhill already suffered in so many other ways, that to remove what may have been viewed as one of the few positive features of the community, namely it's proximity to and easy access to Pollok Park, is perhaps considered as the last straw for residents. It is significant that Corkerhill's initial opposition to the M77 surrounded the loss of the right-of-way to Pollok Park and implicitly the loss of their only source of recreation and good health. This statement by the Secretary of the Community Council demonstrates how residents linked the two together and the meaning they attached to Pollok Park:

What I would have to say is that up front the right-of-way was the (main) argument, but the health fears, definitely, because we felt..we called that (Pollok Park) Corkerhill's lung. It was our breathing space and by taking away the right-of-way and denying us this they were taking away Corkerhill's lung (Walter)

Perceived in this way and on these terms it could be suggested that Corkerhill residents believed Pollok Park to be vital to their existence and survival. The injustice and unfairness of removing their access would easily constitute a basis for collective opposition and action.

It is clear that residents are making connections between perceptions of deprivation and exclusion. This connection to the social conditions of Corkerhill is more apparent with regards to resident's perception of the spatial segregation the construction of the M77 will cause. By spatial segregation they are referring to feelings of isolation and separation from the surrounding world, part of a process of 'ghettoisation' which Corkerhill has been experiencing for many years. The injustice element of this process is evident in the use of the term 'social apartheid' which the Community Council and residents use to describe the process. The use of the term apartheid

may seem to be overemotional however it is justified by residents, in the 1985 Secretary's Report of Corkerhill Community Council under the heading 'Planned Deprivation, or a Kind of Apartheid' the justification is outlined:

one has no desire to belittle the stand against the inhuman racist system of Apartheid in South Africa...Nevertheless it is my strong conviction that any system that plans the separate development of communities ..cannot expect to escape comparison by those people subjected to their plans, and as unfortunate victims of such plans, they have no other alternative but to fight back the best way they can.. (p.2)

The nature of this separate development is detailed and includes the Secretary's contention that public money has increasingly been spent on other areas around Corkerhill, in particular on Pollok Park, The Burrell Museum and Haggs Castle Golf Course all of which benefited from Local Authority funding. This is contrasted with the District Council's unwillingness to spend money within Corkerhill. Highlighted are the demolition of the local games hall, the cancellation of the local train service, the destruction of the railway station, and the citing of Area Housing Strategy figures which indicate that no money is scheduled for repairs in Corkerhill for the period 1985-90. Whilst these concerns are flagged up by the CC the two most important issues identified are Strathclyde Regional Council's apparent contradiction of their own 'Social Strategy for the Eighties' and the expansion of Haggs Castle Golf Course at the expense of Corkerhill.

The CC point out that SRC's Social Strategy aimed to discriminate in favour of areas deemed 'at risk' such as Corkerhill and that its success could be measured by its ability to create one community rather than two separate communities. In the eyes of the Community Council this strategy has failed Corkerhill. Two communities have been created, one that is environmentally beneficial, healthy, benefiting from the injection of public funds and enjoyed primarily by the golfers in Pollok Park and other Glasgow citizens with easy access to it. The other which is in poor condition, populated mostly by the poor and the elderly and which receives proportionately much less public funding. Between the two is, or at that time was to be, the M77 which is described by the CC as akin to the Berlin Wall in that it separates two very distinct areas and communities. Furthermore it is pointed out that the route of the M77 swings away from Haggs Castle Golf Course and towards Corkerhill and that the Golf Course has expanded in size whilst Corkerhill appears, thanks to the imminent construction of the road, to be shrinking. This leads the CC to comment:

(thus) leaving a relatively few golfers with a much larger area of Corkerhill to play golf in than the entire population of the (Corkerhill) village have to live, play and die in..with this imposed segregation...the people of Corkerhill will be sacrificed by the plans for the proposed Ayr Road Route..the powers that be appear to have struck an attitude which

clearly suggests the separate development of one area at the expense and environment of another (CCC Secretary's Report 85, p.4)

The injustice element in this account is clear, the use of terms such as 'victims', 'apartheid', 'imposed segregation', 'sacrificed' and 'planned deprivation' evoke perceptions of unfairness and coercion. The spatial element is also apparent in the reference to the difference between the space the golf course has in comparison to the community. Evidently therefore the sense of injustice felt by Corkerhill residents revolves around the perception of forced separation and that they are being spatially segregated into an increasingly run-down area. This feeling is very strong in resident's discussions of the M77; for example:

I cannae understand how the golf course has all that and yet we're sitting here with nothing..I look out my windae and see a man wi all that space hitting a ball, and I think of the 400 weans in here, all screaming in the play area, looking for space (Betty)

The sense of unfairness is apparent in this statement by Betty. It is clear that she considers the fact that the residents of Corkerhill have much less space than the golfers to be an unjust situation. Furthermore there is a claustrophobic feel to the reference to 'screaming for space' a feeling which other residents also refer to:

We've got no access to the park. The children here and the community used to go there and have picnics, they've taken that away cause we don't have access. You cannae get out (of Corkerhill), your suffocating, claustrophobic (Lilly)

These feelings of claustrophobia arise because the M77 forms a concrete barrier that completes the enclosure of Corkerhill within a box of road and railway lines. The Glasgow to Paisley railway line runs along the northern boundary of the community whilst the Corkerhill Road dual carriageway borders the community on the west; the M77 completes the box to the east and south. Given this, feelings of claustrophobia are not surprising.

It is clear from the above statements that the *meaning* of the M77 for interviewed residents is exclusion and segregation. Protest therefore is in opposition to these processes:

We should fight to preserve the things that are good about Corkerhill Village..its open spaces and nearness to the amenities of Pollok Estate, its trees, plants and wildlife. ..I am against Planned Deprivation in all its forms and in that sense have absolutely no intention of meekly accepting being fenced into a hinterland reservation by those whose interests are totally alien to the people of Corkerhill. (CCC Secretary's Report 1985, p.5)

Thus the spatial exclusion of Corkerhill accords with the discussion of social exclusion above in that it is part of a process rather than the result of a process. I noted that writers on social

exclusion tend to view it in relational rather than distributional terms. However in Corkerhill's case I believe both are part of the community's oppositional consciousness. Residents feel that the distribution of environmental benefits, in this case Pollok Park, is unfair in that Corkerhill's benefits are reduced greatly. Furthermore the uneven distribution of public finances to Corkerhill's detriment is also highlighted. The notion of spatial exclusion is also relational in that it revolves around Corkerhill's relationship with its surrounding environment - a relationship which moves from one which residents describe as harmonious and beneficial to one which is portrayed as unhealthy and claustrophobic. The relationship between Pollok Park and Corkerhill is, I believe, a central component in the development of an identity frame and thus I will discuss it in more detail at that time.

Class Injustice

Socio-economically Corkerhill can easily be described as a deprived area and by almost any definition residents would be classified as working class. This has led to the development of an injustice frame that recognises the class bias in SRCs decision to construct the M77. I noted above the perception by Corkerhill residents that Hags Castle Golf Course was increasing its land and space at the expense of Corkerhill. Alongside the spatial element of this is the fact that Hags Castle is a relatively exclusive club the members of which live in areas and enjoy lifestyles well beyond that enjoyed by Corkerhill residents. I discussed above the spatially unjust elements of Corkerhill's action frames, the class element is connected to this in particular to the notion of social apartheid residents use to describe the process of segregation. Residents make the point that public money seems increasingly to be spent in other areas at the expense of Corkerhill. It is not just in monetary terms that the injustice occurs however, for example CCC notes that not only is Corkerhill set to suffer disproportionately from the construction of the M77 but that it is affluent areas which will benefit:

(SRC)..is directly responsible for the positive discrimination against the people of Corkerhill, and in particular the 400 young persons whose play areas and breathing space has been sacrificed in favour of diverting 53 000 vehicles a day away from the better off areas of Newton Mearns and Eastwood and into..Corkerhill (CCC letter to Town Clerks Office, September 1995)

The people of Corkerhill are being denied proper compensation, despite the obvious sacrifice in favour of ..the better off areas of Eastwood and Newton Mearns (CCC, unpublished leaflet)

Whilst no obvious reference to class is made in the above quotes the underlying impression is clear: the working class community of Corkerhill is being sacrificed in favour of the better off

(middle class) areas of Newton Mearns and Eastwood. Despite this, the explicit class element where the M77 is seen to benefit middle class area at the expense of the working class area of Corkerhill does not appear to be the most significant perception of class injustice perceived by Corkerhill residents. This surfaces in the third component of the injustice frame: political injustice.

Political Injustice

There is no question that feelings of injustice at the apparent unfairness of the political system resonate throughout the words and writings of Corkerhill's residents. This injustice surfaces in two ways. Firstly it surfaces in the imposition of the M77 on a small community and the perception that Corkerhill has been sacrificed by local politicians in order that other areas may benefit. Secondly it surfaces through the sense of this imposition being perpetrated by a Labour administration apparently willing to ignore the plight of a community and a people of the type it was established to protect and defend, namely working class - an administration voted for by many Corkerhill residents because they believed this to be the case.

The perception of Corkerhill as the sacrificial lamb was briefly mentioned in the above discussion of spatial injustice in that Corkerhill residents perceive that they will suffer whilst other areas benefit from the M77. This injustice is compounded by the fact that it is being perpetrated by a Labour administration which residents believe should protect disadvantaged communities like Corkerhill. I noted above the references made to SRC's *Social Strategy for the Eighties* and that residents pointed to this and SRC's failure to adhere to their commitment to discriminate in favour of 'at risk' areas. In many respects however, this is not the major injustice which Corkerhill residents attach to SRC's involvement in the M77 construction. This arises instead in the sense of betrayal that it is being perpetrated by a Labour administration which, in many cases, they voted for in order that it would protect them. Residents refer to this on numerous occasions:

The reason I would say I feel let down is that my father and his father were Labour men, and you follow that cause you think that's the right thing to do, vote Labour. ...I mean SRC could have said no but its like your voting for someone who you think is going to be on your side and yet they take that decision. I couldnae understand it (Betty)

Feelings of betrayal are mixed with feelings of injustice that the M77 was imposed upon Corkerhill which because of its size and relative isolation was not equipped to defend itself as this statement by Walter illustrates:

The people of Corkerhill were subdued wi an imposition and a strategy that been organised right from the top wi military precision..I say this now that they (SRC) should be ashamed of themselves, cause they surrendered their own people, the people they were supposed to protect..Thats what annoys me, there was a lot of them (councillors) there, and if I put blame on them that's why I do it, because they surrendered their principles. There is times and places for the greater good, the choices are who to sacrifice.....and it often comes down to that. Who's prepared to sacrifice who and who is to be sacrificed, the golfers or the people of Corkerhill? The people of Corkerhill are the easiest opponents cause they're only a wee small community but that's why you vote Labour, in order that they protect you.

These feelings that the M77 was imposed upon the people of Corkerhill against their wishes is a recurring theme in residents discourse. It is not simply that residents did not want the M77 constructed nearby but also the perception of a lack of consultation and information from SRC. Results from the survey indicate that 95% of Corkerhill residents feel that they did not receive enough information from SRC about their plans for the M77. These feelings are not confined to Corkerhill residents, over 93% of Arden and Thornliebank residents answered likewise. Peggy and James sum up the feelings of Corkerhill residents

People felt angry because, at the end of the day, they didnae ask us what we wanted. They made their decision and that was it. They didnae care what we thought. They didnae think about us. The planners, the government, the region, them that built the motorway. At the end of the day we'd nae choice.

I think Peggys right . It wouldnae have mattered (what we wanted) they were building it and that was it. I don't think they had many meetings.

When asked to what extent the views of local people were taken into consideration when the decision was taken to build the M77 only 2% of Corkerhill residents surveyed answered 'A Lot', 66% responded 'Not at All'.

From the above it can be suggested that feelings of injustice permeate Corkerhill's opposition to the M77. Spatial elements of exclusion and segregation sit alongside class and political elements of imposition and betrayal. These elements are not mutually exclusive however; they are intertwined within one injustice frame that combines all of these separate elements. In December 1996 at the official opening of the M77 Corkerhill residents performed a play symbolising what the M77 meant to the community. The introduction to the play was a statement written by Walter Morrison in which all of the above elements of the injustice frame are contained. Under the title 'Environmental Rape' the statement reads:

Let history record that to their everlasting shame Councillors of the former Strathclyde Region led by Highwayman Councillor Charles Gordon in collaboration with the Scottish Office and Wimpey Construction, were directly responsible for the wanton pillage and

environmental rape of the green belt, woodlands and breathing spaces of the small village of Corkerhill... (which) dispossess the community and imposes on it all the adverse health and safety impacts of the M77 motorway with its 53 000 vehicles a day.

Sadly, in its centenary year 1996, the people of the once Model railway Village of Corkerhill will be fenced into a claustrophobic ghetto, which segregates them in a compound behind a 30ft high wall of earth, with the M77 forming the new boundary line - a form of social apartheid.

Meantime, two thirds of the childrens play area, open spaces, and woodland strip has been confiscated in favour of Higgs Castle Golf Club leaving them with a much larger area of Corkerhill to play golf than the entire community has to live, play and die in.

I argued above that frames are about meanings and interpretations and that they are mechanisms through which people come to understand the problems facing them. It is possible to argue that the above statement clearly demonstrates the injustice frame that developed in Corkerhill as a result of residents' interpretation of the effect the M77 construction would have on the community. The first paragraph emphasises the political elements of imposition and the spatial factors of dispossession, exclusion and the subsequent health effects. The following two paragraphs stress the injustice of spatial segregation emphasising the unfair distribution of space between the golf course and Corkerhill.

The perception of the unfairness of the M77 is helpful in explaining the development of Corkerhill's injustice frame. This is so because Corkerhill residents appear to place great significance on it as a reason for opposition. The whole notion of planned segregation and social apartheid suggests the unfair treatment of one community in favour of others. For example in one document CCC exhort to the community to 'Fight back now if we are to redress this unfair carve up of our heritage'. The injustice frame created in Corkerhill was central to the development of the second component of collective action frames identified by Gamson: identity. The development of a common identity is dependent upon the identification of 'a concrete target for moral outrage' a 'them' in opposition to a 'we'. The 'them' identified by Corkerhill residents is clearly expressed above; 'councillors of the former Strathclyde Regional Council led by highwayman Charles Gordon'; Corkerhill residents unequivocally blame SRC for the imposition of the M77.

'We, the community': Collective Identity in Corkerhill

The identity frame created by Corkerhill residents is, like the injustice frame, the product of more than one factor. Before continuing however it would be useful to distinguish what I mean when I talk about identity.

In this sense I am referring to collective identity rather than personal or public identity and highlighting notions such as membership and boundaries. (Johnston et, al 1996) The construction of a collective identity can be remarkably easily. Klandermans (1997) points to psychological studies where merely randomly placing people into particular groups results in the formation of a group identity. What is not easy however is the construction of what he refers to as a politically relevant collective identity. As discussed above a politically relevant identity occurs when a 'they' is identified in opposition to a 'we'. The nature of this identity must therefore be dependent upon the identified they. For example the 'they' identified by feminist writers and activists is the male dominated social system and thus the emergent we resonates with themes of female solidarity such as sisterhood. In the case of Corkerhill the identified opposition is SRC and its councillors. The identity created reflects this in that it is primarily based on themes of community and community solidarity.

The main oppositional group throughout Corkerhill's campaign has always been the community council, although many active residents were not official members, so in this case the community organisation dedicated to protecting 'the community' is leading the opposition to a development seen as detrimental to the community. Importantly residents who talk about their reasons for opposition do not do so in selfish terms of the effect the M77 would have on them directly but instead refer to its effect on the community of Corkerhill.

I got involved because its my community..It's our community and we didnae want that road destroying our community. (Janet)

I didnae see why we should have a road going through my scheme, and why they would cut down a forest when there was a golf course there, which certainly no-one in my pay bracket could afford. That was part of (it) but primarily to maintain access to the park for the community (Joe)

Throughout interviews residents constantly refer to Corkerhill in a collective sense. The term 'Corkerhill' is used in an inclusionary manner to indicate all residents within the community, for instance Lilly when discussing her motivations to protest refers to the Maxwell Family Agreement and its effect on Corkerhill:

Sir John Maxwell said Corkerhill would always have access to the estate and that hasn't happened, we've got no access to the park now

There is a definite inclusionary and collective sense in the use of 'Corkerhill' and 'we'. Walter demonstrates this clearly when he talks about the period just after the Public Inquiry:

We, the community had accepted (the PI result) but...there was no love lost between the Scottish Office and SRC and there was still hope that it wouldnae go ahead.

The phrase 'We the community' seems to sum up the nature of the identity element of Corkerhill's collective action frame. It was not individual in nature, concerned with individual issues such as property prices; a major motivation for protest was the health effects of the M77 but it was the health effects on the community not on individual people. It is also clear from the injustice frame discussed above that injustice revolved around the exclusion and segregation of a community and not an aggregate of individuals.

Expressions of 'community' as a basis for opposition are, according to Jenkins (1996)

a powerful everyday notion in terms of which people organise their lives and understand the settlements and localities in which they live and the quality of their social relationships. (p.105).

The term itself is often utilised in spatial and geographical terms, representing specific localities with boundaries. Recent uses however have stressed the fact that a community need not be geographical in nature and that its basis can also be gender, class, ethnicity etc. Given this reformulation it is suggested that the concept of community should not simply be considered in pre-given terms but should instead be regarded as something which forms as a result of opposition to particular developments or change. This notion is captured by Dalby & MacKenzie (1997) when they state;

Environments may be socially constructed in specific controversies, but so too are the communities that are formed around the specific issue, communities...often construct specific local identities as part of the campaign against an 'external' development understood as an environmental 'threat'(p101).

In Corkerhill's case it is possible to argue that community identity was a product of the geographic and social isolation of the community. The history of protest and opposition within the community and the homogeneity of the residents, in terms of social characteristics, can form bonds of solidarity that leads to the creation or strengthening of a community identity. The identification of the M77 as an external threat may not therefore necessarily *lead* to the emergence of a community identity. Nevertheless it is not just the identification of a threat that may influence identity. As Dalby & MacKenzie point out, in specifying the threat residents also specify what is at threat;

This theoretical lens of danger.... provides a framework for rethinking the processes of local community opposition....In many cases the rhetoric of resistance is focused on threats to the local community and its values...Mobilisations of local opposition to something represented as dangerous offer texts of resistance that also allow analysis of the constitution of local community as that which is threatened. (p. 101).

In this way it could be argued that Corkerhill's community identity *reforms* as the result of opposition to the threat of the M77. This reformation involves the mobilisation, articulation and manifestation of certain symbolic representations of Corkerhill's past in particular the symbolic importance of Pollok Park to the community.

Reformations of identity typically occur during periods of crisis or change. In these periods the past is often used as a resource whilst symbolic expressions of community, referring to the past or tradition, can stabilise local identity. (Cohen, 1985) For Corkerhill, Pollok Park appears to become an important symbol of community life, certainly of a past community life which residents state revolved around Pollok Park. In their discussion of their motivations to protest Karen and Peggy both refer to Pollok Park in this symbolic way and both describe it as a place which brought the community together:

It used to be, in the summer you'd go up there (the park). Mas, Das brothers, grandparents, aw the kids going through to Pollok estate..you used to have the closes, they would all put in money in the closes. You'd no see your neighbours all winter but in the spring we used to put in money. Somebody would buy a loaf, somebody some cheese, and you'd have picnics, people fae the scheme. It was like a Sunday school trip....Now there's nothing at all like that now. You don't even see anyone (Karen)

It was like a holiday, that was your day oot. Cause we couldnae afford to go holidays. so that's what you would do, go to Pollok Park. Take your wee fishing nets, picnic, bat and ball. Families and neighbours. From first thing in the morning to last thing at night. (Peggy)

In this way, the use of the past and the symbolic representation of Pollok park as very much the centre of community life, evokes an image of Corkerhill as an integrated, friendly place, in other words a community. By denying residents access to the park and therefore their community focus residents fear that people will retreat indoors or leave the community. Thus the loss of Pollok Park is more than just a loss of amenity but also a loss of community and a loss of a way of life. Attempts to maintain access can therefore be considered as attempts to maintain a sense of community considered as under threat. Speaking just after the construction ended one resident made this point about the M77:

It separated the community. It used to be that everybody used to know each other. Everybody felt like a big family, we always done things the gither, like take the weans up the estate, get them tae draw things. The mother and toddlers group used to take the

weans on nature trails, now they wont be able to cause they'll no be able to get across the road. (Gina)

Thus not only does the road separate the community from the place which was for many residents the focus of community life but there is also the perception that it also socially separates the community in that it disconnects residents from the wider community, leaving them isolated from other residents and community life. We must also factor into this equation the perception held by residents that the noise and fumes from the M77 would inevitably drive residents indoors in an effort to escape.

The symbolic representation of Pollok Park as central to community life is not the only factor to play a part in building Corkerhill's community identity. Once again the past is evoked as an ideal which current developments threaten to destroy; in this case its is the perception of Corkerhill as a village, a village which in the past was applauded for its design. Residents utilise this image to instil a sense of community solidarity.

I have noted elsewhere that both geographically and politically Corkerhill has historically been separate from the areas surrounding it. It was initially built at the end of the 19th century when it was located six miles outside Glasgow. As Glasgow expanded the housing estates of Mossspark and Pollok developed to the north and south of Corkerhill and the community was gradually surrounded by this expansion. Nevertheless although surrounded it was never swallowed up, it always remained a distinct little community in its own right, and residents state that they felt themselves to be neither part of Mossspark nor Pollok. A similar picture developed politically. Since the 1970s Corkerhill has been part of four Westminster constituencies: Pollokshields; Pollok; Craigton; and finally Govan. Local representation is similar, with residents indicating that Corkerhill has always been stuck on to other larger areas and their concerns subsequently overlooked. Given this perception of a lack of political representation there emerges a belief that the only people willing to stand up and fight for Corkerhill are the people who live there. This leads to the development of the agency element of the collective action frame which I will go on to discuss in more depth later, however it is also important for the development of a community identity. By evoking Corkerhill's past existence as a model railway village residents create an ideal which, whilst not in itself under threat from the M77 because it no longer existed, stands as a symbol of a past life free from the threat of pollution and environmental destruction. Community identity forms not only from this depiction of community life in the past but also from the emphasis on Corkerhill as a village, a small community, vulnerable, and in need of protection:

We (have) absolutely no intention of allowing this historic, and once Model Railway Village of Corkerhill to be fenced in and the entire community completely cut off from all the open spaces of the countryside. (CCC Secretary's Report, 1985)

Corkerhill is a classic case of a small community being imposed upon...In terms of public transport you couldn't get a better argument than running down a railway line in order to promote a motorway. Now in its (Corkerhill's) centenary year they are running down the railway to build motorways. I did my best to expose it but one of the problems is that we are a small marginalised community, about 800 or 900 votes, Corkerhill is a side issue..We done our best, we had to get the community involved..its actually got a worse transport system than it did 50 years ago (Walter)

Sadly (this) serves to deny the citizens of Glasgow, and of Corkerhill in particular, their rightful claim to a legacy of open spaces, woodland and countryside, with the result that In its centenary year 1996, the people of the once **Model Railway Village** of Corkerhill will be fenced into a claustrophobic ghetto which segregates them in a compound behind a 30ft high wall of earth (CCC, Press Release, 1996; original emphasis)

The three quotes above demonstrate the importance of the perception of Corkerhill as a village to local residents. The first quote demonstrates the links residents are making between the past and the need to fight to protect this 'once model railway village'. The second highlights residents perception of the relative size of Corkerhill, the political marginalisation felt within a community of only 800 - 900 votes, and the need for the community to come together to defend Corkerhill. The final quote demonstrates the integration of these notions within the developed injustice frames. Not only is the evocation of the past a resource residents use to create a community identity, in this case the past is also used to highlight the injustice of Corkerhill's present plight in comparison to its model past.

Given the spatial element of this discussion what must also be considered is what Keith and Pile describe as 'the identity politics of place' (1993, p.2). They propose that space cannot merely be considered as a passive arena where things occur and instead highlight the relationship between space, identity and political opposition. It has been suggested that spatial ideas and elements are often the basis for the development of a sense of identity. For example Gillian Rose argues that;

identity is about how we make sense of ourselves and (many) have argued that the meanings given to a place may be so strong that they become a central part of the identity of the people experiencing them. (1995, p.88).

At the local level it is also suggested that ideas of space and identity link to promote opposition to particular developments. For example, Castells (1997) notes that urban social movements mobilise mainly around three sets of goals: living conditions and collective consumption; the conquest of local autonomy and participation and the affirmation of local identity. He further

notes that grass-roots opposition to particular developments also fosters a sense of identity and encourages citizens to develop meanings for what is happening around them, in much the same way that Gamson suggests that meanings develop. However, for Castells, the identity which develops is a defensive one focusing on the defence of their space or environment. He concludes by stating that local communities are specific sources of identities and that the oppositional politics that emerge from them reflects the defensive identity which develops.

The identity frame created by Corkerhill residents reflects therefore the meanings the M77 would have for the community and community life and residents interpretations of who their adversaries are, the nature of the threat and what is under threat. Residents perceive SRC and its councillors as being responsible for imposing the threat of the M77 upon the community. There is the perception that the construction of the M77 would lead to the loss of the sense of community that existed within Corkerhill. By this I mean the emotional and social attachment residents felt to the locality and other residents. This sense of community would disappear as Corkerhill would be cut off from the communal space that brought it together: Pollok Park; and thus what is under threat is residents' sense of identity. In discussing the injustice frame above I noted that residents believed the M77 would leave the community isolated from its surrounding environment, it is also possible to suggest that residents believed it would leave them isolated from each other. I have argued that community identity forms in response to some external threat, however in Corkerhill's case it appears that residents perceived the M77 as a threat to community identity. Thus we are presented with a chicken and egg question: did opposition to the M77 result in the development of Corkerhill's community identity, or did Corkerhill's community identity result in the development of opposition to the M77?

Answering this is no easy matter. What could be argued is that Corkerhill's identity is partly the result of its historically isolated nature producing a relatively close-knit community with a sense of togetherness and therefore not uniquely the product of opposition to the M77. Alongside this is an identity which is honed and sharpened by residents interpretations of the M77, a function of the 'we' which develops in opposition to SRC's 'they' and residents' belief that the loss of Pollok Park will lead to a loss of community. Whether or not Pollok Park actually was the symbolic focus of Corkerhill life or Corkerhill residents have merely created this rose-tinted view of the park because of their impending loss of access is not important. What is important is that Corkerhill residents believe this to be the case. They believe that Pollok Park was where the community came together, they believe that it gave the community a sense of identity and they believe that they were fighting to maintain this sense of identity. I noted above the perception held by residents that Pollok Park was 'Corkerhill's Lung', looked at from another perspective it can be argued that they also perceived it to be 'Corkerhill's Heart'.

In many respects the identity frame which emerges in Corkerhill goes beyond Gamson's depiction of the purposes of developing such a frame. According to Gamson (1992) an identity frame serves to help define a 'we' whilst causal attributions disseminated by movement leaders determine an adversarial 'they'. However as I have suggested, Corkerhill's identity frame not only identified the adversarial 'they' but also what was under threat. In recognising SRC as being responsible for the M77 Corkerhill residents define their 'they'. But by additionally identifying community identity and community way of life as that which is under threat the identity frame developed in Corkerhill seems to go a step further than the role Gamson assigns to them.

Moreover, there is an implicit acceptance that an identity frame is required to produce this sense of 'we' because people are generally not aware that grievances are commonly held and therefore do not perceive themselves as part of a broader collective. Identity frames therefore are designed to overcome the sense of isolation that can often exist in modern societies by demonstrating to people that they are not alone. This view however seems more readily applicable to large-scale movements and organisations attempting to attract potential members from a large diverse population. In Corkerhill's case it may be the case that this connecting role of the identity frame was not so prevalent or necessary. In small close-knit communities such as Corkerhill people are typically less isolated from others and therefore perhaps less likely to perceive problems from an entirely individual perspective. The very act of talking to neighbours and friends would confirm that other residents have similar fears and that it is a community under threat rather than an aggregate of individuals. In this case there is less need for movement leaders to demonstrate that injustices are collective in nature. This does not mean to say that every member of the community will be equally concerned or that the M77 will be the only issue which concerns them but their will be an awareness of a shared community concern.

D.I.Y and 'no sitting back': Perceptions of Agency

When discussing the concept of 'agency' I am referring to the awareness of the possibility of collective action. This relates to the consciousness of peoples' ability, by standing together and presenting a united front, to alter and shape their destiny. According to Gamson;

Collective action frames imply some sense of collective efficacy and deny the immutability of some undesirable situation. They empower people by defining them as potential agents of their own history. They suggest not merely that something can be done by that 'we' can do something. (1992, p.7)

Gamson cites numerous works that highlight the forces that hinder the development of collective action. Structural factors, political factors, the media all combine to produce feelings of cynicism and inefficacy amongst the majority of people in modern society. Nevertheless, it is important to distinguish between individual and collective feelings of inefficacy and the perception of the *potential* of individual and collective action. Feelings of efficacy tend to be low across both individual and collective scales, although there are variations in terms of social class and educational attainment, however feelings regarding the potential of collective action to make a difference are significantly higher than feelings of both individual and collective efficacy. In other words, whilst peoples' experiences of striving to make a difference may have resulted in feelings of inefficacy and cynicism, the belief that collective action can produce results remains. (Parry, Moyser & Day, 1992)

The agency component of Corkerhill's collective action frame surfaces throughout interviews with residents and analysis of pamphlets and documents produced by the community. Examples of the community's belief that 'we' can make a difference have already been mentioned in discussions above. I noted the comment in the 1985 CCC Secretary's Report; 'We should fight to preserve the things that are good about Corkerhill...'. Within this call for action there was a feeling amongst Corkerhill residents that collective action *could* be effective:

In the main it's sad to say, and I don't think it's apathy, it's lack of (pause)..you've been disillusioned and battered doon so much that everything seems like a mountain to climb...What we were able to do was argue that there was a possibility that we could win...we started off from the grass roots, getting our community committed..we got the community in a show of solidarity..and then...working all the time towards the decision of the city council. In terms of being able to present a united and collective protest that is how we were successful (Walter)

I think it makes you more determined, because some of the things that have happened wouldnae have happened if we hadnae fought for them. If you don't fight back. They'll just walk over the top of you. I think people have got a lot of power but don't use it. If they stand up..they might win. (Betty)

In this case Walter emphasises his belief that collective action could be effective and the fact that in arguing for the potential of collective action the community was mobilised such that their actions were effective. In this example, success lay in persuading the District Council of the harmful effects of the M77 and the need to oppose it, which they subsequently did. The statement from Betty again highlights the belief that the potential for collective action is there and that once harnessed it can be a potent force.

Corkerhill's tactics have always revolved around presenting a united front in opposition to the M77. The CC placed great emphasis on petitions and demonstrations as expressions of the community's objection to the M77. Whilst it could, quite legitimately, be argued that petitions are not collective acts of opposition but instead represent aggregates of individual opposition they are not used or perceived in this manner by Corkerhill residents. For them they are indicators of community opposition and solidarity and it is always important that as many of the community demonstrate their opposition. Frequent references are made in interviews to the success of mobilising petitions: '800 signatures from a population of just over 900' is one phrase used to emphasise community solidarity.

The contribution of the CC to the development of a sense of agency within Corkerhill cannot be overstated. I have discussed at length in the previous chapter the mobilising role of the CC and the success it had in encouraging and facilitating protest against the M77. I have also spoken of its role in raising knowledge and awareness about the M77 and in encouraging protest but have said less on its role in raising consciousness about the potential for collective action. It is difficult to determine from the empirical evidence presented in the previous chapter whether or not encouraging residents to engage in collective action also raised their awareness of the potential for collective action but it is not unrealistic to propose that people would not protest if they did not see it as potentially beneficial and worthwhile. Perhaps the prime consciousness raising activity and role the CC had was the part it played in bringing the community together in face-to-face contact thus enabling residents to discuss issues and responses. By organising demonstrations and meetings the CC facilitates a sense of agency for it is in these situations that residents become aware of the collective nature of opposition and the potential of collective action.

The work of the CC almost certainly contributed to the development of a sense of agency within Corkerhill, however it is not the only contributing factor. I have already suggested that Corkerhill's sense of agency may partly be the result of its relative isolation, however I would also suggest that, in many respects, it emerges from almost a D.I Y. (Do It Yourself) self-help perception of action held by residents. This perception results in the belief that it is important that you should fight your own battles and not leave others to do so for you:

I think everybody's got to stick together in things like this, to try and change things, that's the only way. You'll no get it by sitting back, you've got to involve the whole place. I think that's one of the main reasons why Corkerhill sticks oot fae a lot of other places, because we've always been prepared to stick oor neck out and not accept the things that other communities take. (Betty)

According to Betty a sense of collective agency emerges from both an awareness of it's potential, 'everybody's got to stick together in things like this..that 's the only way' and from the belief that you will get nowhere by 'sitting back'. The belief that you should fight your own battles also emerges when residents discuss motivations to protest:

if you want anything done for your community you need to fight for it, you cannae just leave it to somebody (else),...you've got to go for it yourself. (Karen)

That's why I got involved...I feel that if you put something in you might get something back. You cannae just let others get on with it. (Lilly)

This self-help element of Corkerhill's response to the M77 has its roots in the long tradition of working class self-help that led to the flourishing of organisations such as credit unions and Friendly and building societies. For example, building societies were established in working class areas where low cost council housing was not available. Members paid contributions until enough was available for one to purchase or build a house and they continued contributing until all members had achieved this. In similar vein, although established earlier, membership of local Friendly Societies ensured that in times of illness, injury or unemployment working class people would receive compensation to pay for a doctor or purchase essentials. (Gosden, 1973)

Corkerhill has a tradition of these self-help organisations. In the early days of it's existence residents established a rent club where members could pay a penny a week and in times of sickness and absence from work the club would pay their rent. Similarly, as was noted in chapter 3, throughout it's relatively recent history the community has fought on many fronts and around issues other than the M77. These include public transport, lead in drinking water, dampness, gas fires, smoke detectors and social security grants.

Thus the agency component of Corkerhill's collective action frame is, like the other components, multi-faceted. It can be argued that is the product of the community's relative isolation, the mobilising work of the CC and the principles of self-help that the community has historically demonstrated.

The collective action frame that developed in Corkerhill reflects therefore resident's interpretations of the construction of the M77. It reflects fears of segregation and exclusion, a sense of unfairness at the imposition of a motorway on a deprived community by politicians whom Corkerhill residents believed would protect them. It reflects the nature of Corkerhill's collective identity, symbolised by the communal living space of Pollok park and representing residents' desire to remain connected to their surrounding environment. This is grounded in the belief that only through external connection could they remain internally connected to each other.

The sense of agency that developed in Corkerhill mirrors these in that it echoes the community's history of self-help and collective action, of the community coming together to discuss potential action. All of this is the consequence of Corkerhill residents developing their understanding of the world around them - of them, as Goffman proposed, locating, perceiving, identifying and labelling events in their life space. What is clear from this analysis is that meanings do not simply exist independently, waiting to be plucked from the air and appropriated for people's use; meanings are created by people interpreting the events occurring in the world around them.

Conclusion

For Corkerhill residents the meaning of the M77 was created and developed over a number of years. Some parts of the collective action frame were no doubt created faster than others, such as the perceptions of exclusion from the park which would have been instantly apparent from examining the plans of the route. Others take longer to develop: perceptions of segregation and apartheid, of the loss of community which become apparent as residents consider the full consequences of the M77; and perceptions of class and political injustice which are exacerbated by political decisions made over a number of years. Likewise, the sense of agency that develops is the result of a slow process of raising awareness by the CC and historical factors already present. The central element throughout opposition is arguably the idea of 'community' and the notion that Corkerhill was a small community, under threat. Indeed, it is the notion that it was the *sense* of community that was under threat by the M77, a sense of community bolstered by access to the park.

In arguing that Corkerhill's identity revolves around residents' perception of a sense of community, and indeed is based on 'community' as an inclusive and collective term, it is important to bear in mind that conceptions of community may not always possess the positive meaning in which I am using it here. Sidney Plotkin (1991) reminds us that whilst a sense of community can result in feelings of connection to a locality and its people it can also produce feelings of isolation and disconnection from wider society. As a consequence this produces a partisan solidarity which reacts to perceptions of encirclement and threatens to exclude developments and members of society deemed to be undesirable. Plotkin refers to this partisan solidarity as 'enclave consciousness'.

Plotkin argues that people come to see their neighbourhoods as home, a home surrounded by threats and thus local politics is frequently a politics of place rather than power. Community action therefore is generally protective and defensive in nature, such as defending the community from an influx of (what are perceived as) undesirable groups: the poor, ethnic

minorities, and increasingly frequently in Britain, those with mental health disabilities and those seeking asylum from persecution in other countries. This also extends to larger developments such as new low income housing, industrial developments and, often, roads; all reflecting the community's desire to be left alone. Characteristic of enclave consciousness is the perception of the community as an island struggling to defend itself against invasion from external threat and remain an island, separate and detached from the world around it. As Plotkin states; 'Enclave consciousness tends towards a rigid and undifferentiated exclusionism.' (1991, p.23)

Plotkin's notion of enclave consciousness is a potentially useful explanatory tool when examining Corkerhill's opposition to the M77. The idea that communities feel under threat from external developments and respond appears to be in accord with Corkerhill's perception of the M77 as a development that threatens to complete the encirclement of the community. Opposition could subsequently be thought of as defensive and exclusionary in that it is motivated by a desire to protect Corkerhill from the effects of the M77 and exclude the development from Corkerhill's locality. Despite this however I believe that the concept of enclave consciousness cannot adequately be used to describe Corkerhill's opposition for one fundamental reason: Corkerhill's opposition was not a protest concerned with separateness and exclusion but was instead a protest concerned with connection and inclusion. Let me explain.

Perceptions of enclave consciousness produces protest which is designed to maintain the separateness of one community from others; to protect the community's enclave/island status by ensuring that all which is bad about wider society is not allowed to penetrate. Corkerhill's protest on the other hand was geared towards maintaining Corkerhill's inclusion within wider society. I have stated that ideas of spatial exclusion and segregation were central to feelings of injustice. In this way Corkerhill's opposition was not the result of enclave consciousness or of endeavouring to keep Corkerhill separate from the rest of society. Instead, it was geared towards ensuring that it remained connected to the surrounding environment and society. Residents indicate that they believed the M77 would cut Corkerhill off from the world around it and isolate the community and its residents; in striving to stop the M77 they were striving to prevent Corkerhill becoming an enclave. It is true that much of the opposition revolved around issues of access to Pollok Park, but this access brought inclusion. In contrast to the exclusionary nature of enclave consciousness what develops in Corkerhill could instead be described as 'inclusion consciousness'.

Despite this focus on inclusion there do appear to be tensions and differences amongst Corkerhill residents. This tension is concerned with the reasons for protest and the future of opposition to the M77. Until the time of the Public Inquiry the focus of opposition had been the

effect of the M77 on Corkerhill. Logically residents were concerned with the impact it would have on their community. At the Public Inquiry itself, although many other local communities protested there is still the impression that Corkerhill's focus was firmly local. The videos made by the CC concentrated on Corkerhill, with no mention of the broader impact of the M77. There is an almost NIMBY-like approach to opposition and the collective action frame that nurtured it. I noted that 'we the community' seemed to sum up the identity element of the collective action frame. There appears to be a perception amongst residents of Corkerhill standing alone and of distrust of outside agencies and assistance. The tension arises, I believe, after the Public Inquiry when the residents must decide what to do after all the legal and institutional avenues of protest have been exhausted. The options were to do nothing, to fight on for compensation or to broaden the nature of opposition. Walter highlights this tension....

At the time..I've accepted that the road is going ahead..and the only way we're going to get anything is some form of limited damages...but..I always argued that if the road was going to be stopped it would be because it would be prohibitive in costs..And I've always felt that what was really needed was a form of civil disobedience in order to focus the attention of the nation on our problems

If, as suggested, the different constituent parts of a collective action frame develop at different times and varying speeds it is therefore also possible to suggest that elements of the frame may alter or change over time or as a result of specific developments or actions. Snow et al (1997) refer to the process of constructing a collective action frame as 'frame alignment' whilst the action of altering or changing a frame is referred to as 'frame transformation'. I wish to argue that a process similar to frame transformation occurred in Corkerhill but that the nature of the alteration did not result in a fundamental transformation of the collective action frame. Instead, it is possible to witness an alteration in the identity component of the frame which, whilst tremendously significant in terms of Corkerhill's protest, should not be considered as a process of frame transformation but instead one of frame re-alignment. This re-alignment was sparked by the resolving of the tension noted above and the emergence of radical direct-action and 'civil disobedience' against the M77.

Chapter 6:

From NIMBY to NOPE: Frame Re-alignment and the Imagined Communities of the M77

Introduction

The previous chapter discussed the processes of micro-mobilisation with Corkerhill, the internal messages and frames around which opposition was mobilised and constructed. It noted that, in line with Gamson's work, three collective action frames emerged: an injustice frame which revolved primarily around spatial issues of segregation and exclusion but around ideas of class and political injustice also; an identity frame rooted in notions of community and linked to residents perceptions of Pollok Park; and an agency frame which emerges out of Corkerhill's historical background and which I argued was nourished by the work of the community council. Thus the previous two chapters have sought to establish the processes of internal mobilisation within Corkerhill. I argued that within Corkerhill there existed 'opinion leaders' who disseminated information and knowledge through networks of communication. I demonstrated that these networks appear to exist in Corkerhill but do not do so in the other surveyed areas. Thereafter the collective action frame that flowed within these networks were examined and discussed. This chapter now moves the discussion away from the emergence and mobilisation of Corkerhill's collective protest and looks instead at the dynamics of that protest and the way it altered over time. Although covering Corkerhill's entire opposition the chapter will pay particular attention to the alteration that occurred during and after the establishment of the Free State in 1994 and also the period from January to March 1995. This period could perhaps be considered, alongside the Public Inquiry, as the most significant during Corkerhill's opposition to the M77. This is not because it was a time when the community made great gains or won significant victories, in fact the opposite is the case, but because of its effect on Corkerhill residents. During this period some residents established the Corkerhill camp to oppose the construction of the road whilst all residents came face-to-face with high profile non-violent-direct-action protesting and, significantly, the state's response to this.

I suggested at the end of the previous chapter that by the end of the Public Inquiry and the period immediately following a tension had emerged within the collective action frame. I noted that until that time Corkerhill residents appeared to have an almost NIMBY-like approach to opposition - that there appeared to be tensions regarding both the reasons for opposition and the future direction of protest. I also suggested that the identity frame re-aligned in response to events during the community's opposition and I believe it is possible to argue that this was a result of actions and incidents during the period of 1994/1995. In particular I hope to demonstrate that the establishment of the Pollok Free State protest camp and the emergence of radical direct action led to this re-alignment. Furthermore I would also suggest that because of this many

Corkerhill residents became part of a broader 'Imagined Community' and their oppositional focus broadened. The broadening of this oppositional focus takes the form a shift from protest based on Not In My Back Yard (NIMBY) principles to Not on Planet Earth (NOPE) ones.

The Pollok Free State

In the discussion on the history of protest against the M77 in chapter 3 I briefly mentioned the role the Pollok Free State had in this. The Pollok Free State represented a radical alteration in the protest against the M77. For the first time since it was proposed opposition was high profile and direct. Local people had been joined by Eco-warriors.

Profiles of Eco-warriors indicate that they are predominantly drawn from the young educated middle-classes. Feelings of cynicism towards government and traditional political parties are evident and whilst this is a contributing factor in the development of radical protest groups the particular type of environmental activism in nineties protest is arguably generationally specific. The current generation of 18-30 year olds was undoubtedly influenced by the surge in environmental concern in the late 80s. Furthermore they had known years of Conservative domination and suffered from legislation which has often had the consequence of curbing the activities of young people. This legislation includes the removal of benefits for 16-18 year olds, the introduction of student loans, and the passing of The Criminal Justice Act. Thus government authority has been extended government regulation expanded into previously autonomous social and cultural spheres. This apparent colonisation process has brought many young people into conflict with what they perceive as the states undemocratic actions; this is manifested in anti-state protests, such as those against roads, and the rejection of existing state and democratic processes.

This rejection is epitomised by the founding of 'free states' established along Eco-friendly lines and lacking the formal leadership structures of so called 'normal' states. In London the independent free state of Wanstonia was set up in an attempt to halt the construction of the M11 and in June 1994 the Pollok Free State was established in protest at the construction of the M77; its declaration of independence stated;

we believe the ecological holocaust facing our lands and wider environment to be so great, that it is our right, our duty, to throw off such forms of government that allow such evils to continue, and provide for our future security. We take this step with great reluctance and it is our intention to maintain peaceful relations with Her Majesty's government of the United Kingdom and Strathclyde Regional Council. Nevertheless it is our view that the undemocratic activities of these two institutions, through the proposed Criminal Justice and Public Order Act and the M77 motorway extension, are so

unpopular, destructive and oppressive, and their behaviour so unreasonable in the face of our appeals for mercy that we face no choice but to separate and determine our own future.

Located in the Barrhead Woods of the Pollok Estate the Free State was constructed on the proposed route of the M77. Its membership fluctuated but usually consisted of between 5 and 20 members. Described, amongst other things, as 'a curious canvas fairyland' residents adopted an alternative lifestyle. They lived in tents and tree houses and recycled extensively, goods and possessions were communal and cooking and work organised to benefit the camp rather than individuals. Art and free expression such as totem carving and music workshops were encouraged and this alternative lifestyle attracted people from the local area such as carpenters, cooks and musicians who often visited and contributed in whatever way they could.

The role of the Free State was twofold. Firstly it became a focus for much of the resistance against the M77 and several events and protests were organised. These included a mass trespass of the road, mass trespasses of Wimpey show-homes and Housing Estates, demonstrations and rallies. On one occasion Free State residents and hundreds of local and other Glasgow residents marched from George Square in the centre of Glasgow to the Free State. On another occasion, a 'Carhenge' was created on the route of the road. Built in the manner of Stonehenge this involved nine cars buried engine-down on the M77 route. This served as a symbolic reminder of the environmentally destructive nature of cars.

The second role of The Free State was counter-cultural. The creation of an alternative lifestyle, promoted a counter-culture that advanced the anti-roads movement beyond calling for changes in transportation policy until it became a movement which rejected the fundamental assumptions of post-war culture. The Free State's declaration of independence and adoption of an alternative lifestyle based on living in harmony with the earth offered an alternative, a vision of a better society where growth, destruction and the car do not dominate.

In terms of the message promoted by The Free State it was, in many respects, similar to that of Corkerhill residents. The Pollok Free State also focussed on the idea of enclosure and of denying access to the local environment. Its declaration of independence states:

Our ancestors were cleared from the homelands by feudal greed...This process of enclosure, the privatisation of a peoples ultimate resource - land - has ripped people away from the earth.....Today the process of enclosure continues as this land, our land, is threatened with destruction in the name of infrastructure improvement. Pollok Estate was returned to us in 1939 and now it is threatened by privatisation for a car owning elite. (PFS Declaration of Independence, Unpublished Leaflet, 1994)

Thus, like Corkerhill residents, ideas of enclosure and separation from the land also resonate throughout the Pollok Free State's motivations for protest. Corkerhill residents viewed the Pollok Estate as being vital to the survival of their community and denial of access led to the enclosure of the community. For The Pollok Free State the enclosure of the land was simply the latest in a historical process but there is still the perception of land as being a vital resource and essential to the people. In this way there is a connection between the two protests. Each was protecting access to the environment and to the land. This access was perceived by both local people and Eco-warriors as being a fundamental right necessary for well-being.

In a recent paper Routledge (1997) utilises Anderson's concept of an imagined community with regard to the M77 protest. He focuses mainly on the community which existed between the Eco-warrior wing of the M77 protest and particularly on the interaction between different factions of that wing, Earth First! and the Pollok Free State. He makes the point that whilst Eco-warriors may appear, to those uninvolved in that lifestyle, to be a homogenous group they are in fact a combination of many different groups or individuals each with different aims, beliefs and tactics. For Routledge an imagined community of resistance exists which

engages with alliances and collaborations and involves a heterogeneous affinity across gender, generation, class and ethnicity. Hence issue-specific campaigns are frequently entangled with broader communities of interests..(and).Facets of this community combine at particular times and places into a strategic force. (p.360)

For Routledge the M77 protest brought together a number of disparate groups such as, local communities, local schoolchildren, political activists and environmental campaigners. He argues that the M77 provided the 'catalyst' for these groups to come together and that the direct action component of the campaign was articulated by Earth First! and the Pollok Free State coalescing around the formation of STARR. (Stop the Ayr Road Route).

For Routledge, the M77 campaign is an example of a postmodern politics of resistance. In particular it comprises symbolic challenges that are highly media-ated in order to expose the power relationships that underpin these developments and attract public attention. He contends that the Pollok Free State and Earth First! affected a tribal politics through the creation of an imagined community symbolically articulated by the construction of tree houses, totems, protest camps and benders. Activities such as direct action serve to forge alliances, create bonds and build a community and is further constructed through the emergence of 'temporary communal spaces of resistance' .(p.372) Through these mediated activities and the interaction of these disparate groups an imagined community emerges. It is a community that exists throughout the

M77 protest before dissipating once the protest ends. According to Routledge this imagined community of postmodern resistance held little or no appeal to local residents in Corkerhill and surrounding communities. He argues that the Free State had little 'cultural resonance' with their everyday lives and, whilst local residents sympathised, the Free State did not mobilise local people who, too concerned with unemployment and other issues, did not consider the environment to be an important issue.

Routledge's paper is a useful case study of the emergence of an imagined community around a particular issue in a particular time and place. His discussion of the internal relationship between Earth First! and the Pollok Free State is illuminating. Nevertheless in stating that local residents were not mobilised or concerned about the M77, or that direct action against the road occurred because of Earth First! or Free State activities does the local communities, and in particular Corkerhill, a disservice. I would argue that Routledge overlooks or obscures the important role played by local communities in protesting against the M77. It is correct that some residents did not participate directly in opposition to the road but many local residents *did* directly oppose the M77. Local schoolchildren placed themselves in front of bulldozers and local residents often joined Pollok Free State residents on demonstrations. In addition, the Pollok Free State was not the only protest camp established on the route of the M77, another was started and inhabited by Corkerhill residents. Furthermore local people had lived and protested the M77 for 20 years and had successfully delayed it on a number of occasions. By skimming over this Routledge creates the impression, intended or not, that Eco-warriors were fighting the battles for local people. This was not the case; local people fought their own battles on different terms. They fought back the only way they knew how: petitions, letters and meetings. In the latter stages of the protest they *also* engaged in direct action to oppose the road. Media coverage of environmental protest tends to obscure the message in favour of the messenger; thus the media focus on the Eco-warrior element. This gives the media their 'angle'. Routledge does concede this very point; neither the work by local people involved in the campaign nor its history fitted with media images of who was responsible for opposition. Because of this the media tend to ignore or overlook local people. It would appear that in endeavouring to stress that the M77 was an example of a postmodern politics of resistance Routledge has overlooked those elements of the campaign which do not fit this category.

Furthermore, it is clear that local people *did* engage in direct action against the M77 similar to that of The Free State. I would argue that the interaction of Eco-warrior and local protestor had a profound effect upon the local residents of Corkerhill. This interaction leads to the re-alignment of Corkerhill's oppositional focus from NIMBY to NOPE in the way discussed in

Chapter 2 and led to the emergence of a new 'imagined community' but one different to that proposed by Routledge.

To adequately test this proposition however we must determine if local protest was indeed NIMBY in nature and whether the presence of The Free State promoted the development of a protest based on wider environmental issues. Previously I made a number of points regarding NIMBY protests. These were: they tend to result from prolonged decision-making processes; there is usually a strong locational element with opposition receding as distance increases; they are essentially distributional in nature; they can be viewed as a rational response to lack of input into the decision-making process and, in terms of roads, are fundamentally concerned with the route of roads rather than the need for roads. Before examining this however an important point needs to be made at this juncture. That is: the distinction between NIMBY and NOPE made earlier is not a black and white one. It is possible that individuals may be motivated by NIMBY reasons such as health risks and property prices *and* be aware of the broader implications of that which they are opposing. Indeed as has been noted The Pollok Free State was started by a local, although not a Corkerhill resident, who appears to fall into this category. We can only determine this however by examining the impact radical groups have on local protest. To do this we must ascertain a number of things. Firstly, to what extent, if any, could local protest be characterised as NIMBY in nature? Secondly, to what extent did the nature of local protest change? Thirdly, to what extent was this change facilitated by a merger of local and radical (NOPE) groups? Finally, do local NIMBY protests alter to become more characteristic of NOPE protests? To achieve this we must unpack the local protest against the M77. More specifically we need to make a distinction between two of its components: reasons and strategy. In this way it will be possible to determine if Corkerhill's protest moved from NIMBY to NOPE and I will endeavour to demonstrate that within Corkerhill we can witness at least a partial move.

Building Bridges: Corkerhill, NIMBY to NOPE⁷

A cursory read of the account of Corkerhill's protest would appear to confirm the view that the protest was conducted for NIMBY reasons. Residents first of all protested about the loss of a right-of-way, then about the effects of noise and pollution on their health. Only when these avenues were exhausted did an apparent tactical alliance of NIMBYists and Eco-warriors emerge to oppose the road. I suggested above however that to determine if Corkerhill's opposition can be classified as

⁷ I first came across this acronym in Ben Seel's 1996 paper presented to the Alternative Futures and Popular Protest Conference although I have heard it many times since. In his paper Ben attributes it to John Barry

NIMBY a distinction must be made between two protest factors: motives and strategy. By so doing it will be possible to determine whether the establishment of The Pollok Free State facilitated the development of a local protest based upon NOPE values. By examining the dynamics of local protest it should be possible to evaluate whether or not local people embrace the arguments and strategies of the radical protestors. I will begin by, briefly, returning to the survey data.

Reasons for Protest

Table 6.1: Corkerhill Residents Opinion of M77 Development

Ques: What is your opinion of the construction of the M77?	%
Agree	9
Neither Agree/Disagree	30
Disagree	40
Strongly Disagree	21
	N: 139

Table 6.2: Corkerhill Residents Reasons for Disagreeing with M77

Ques: Why do you disagree with the M77	%
Because you fear it will damage your health or the health of other members of your family	46
Because it will increase noise & air pollution in your area	25
You believe the money would be better spent on improving public transport	2
Because of the trees and parkland destroyed to construct it	7
Its overall effect on the environment	13
Other	7

It is clear from Tables 6.1& 6.2 (above) that the majority of Corkerhill residents disagreed with the building of the M77 and that residents reasons for opposing the M77 could possibly be classified as NIMBY.⁸ The vast majority of residents disagreed because of the health effects and the increase in pollution they believed would result. The community council initially mobilised around the issues of the right-of-way then moved on to the effect the road would have on the health of Corkerhill residents. Thus it would appear, superficially anyway, that self-interest is a significant factor in resident opposition. Deeper analysis however suggests that this is not the case; the

⁸ Interestingly, residents claim that the original route of the M77 took it across the golf course but some high powered Nimbyism by club members ensured that it veered towards Corkerhill. I can find no evidence to support this however residents maintain that members of the golf club at that time included 'important people' in Glasgow's planning department so there may be some truth in it.

primary motivating factor was not self-interest but community interest. It is the effect the road would have on the community of Corkerhill that is significant:

That community out there is a good community, they've got all the problems: damp houses; unemployment and all that; and some of them will no have the commitment I've got but they fought to protect their community. I fought to protect my community. (Walter)

This is a point further emphasised by Janet:

I got involved because its' my community. Its our community, and we didnae want that road destroying our community

and Betty:

At the end of the day the people realise what were doing. It's no for our own gain it was for the community.

This is despite the fact that Betty's house would be closest to the completed motorway and she had more reason than anyone to be motivated by self-interest. I noted in the previous chapter that ideas of 'community' were prevalent within the identity frame constructed by Corkerhill residents. Clearly, notions of community were central to reasons for opposition.

Reasons for opposing the M77 therefore are parochial in the sense that the majority of residents were concerned about the effects on their community and not about the wider effects of motorway building. The locational element of NIMBYism does appear to be a factor therefore. Indeed, residents indicated that initially the main reason for opposition was the route of the road rather than the road itself, and that an alternative course, away from Corkerhill, would have been acceptable.

I didn't think that the road necessarily needed to take the route taken,... at that time we wernae saying we didnae want roads, what we said was it could have went straight across the golf course, it would have been cheaper. (Betty)

From this we can see that Corkerhill's initial opposition could be considered parochial and selfish in that they were content to see the environmental costs of such development displaced on to other areas. In this way it is possible to suggest the residents motivations for protest can be contained within the NIMBY framework established earlier in that motivations to protest were concerned with the route of the road and its proximity to Corkerhill rather than the need for the road. In later years however reasons for opposition broaden. The establishment of The Free

State was welcomed by residents who hoped that it would lead to a reopening of the M77 issue, an issue which they believed was finished after the 1988 Public Enquiry;

..it was a mastermove in terms of the overall arguments about the environment. Our issue was dead..what happened there was magic. Colin came along and showed the will was still there⁹ (Betty)

We were more parochial in terms of our attitude. Our opposition at that stage..wasn't against roads. Our argument was that a community was getting sacrificed A) for the road and B) to please other people.(Walter)

There seems to be an acceptance that initially the protest was concerned only with the impact the M77 would have on Corkerhill. Betty indicates that the community had given up the fight but by claiming that 'our issue was dead' appears to be accepting that the fight was now to take place around other issues. Walter states that the protest before the Free State was not against roads per se but about the effect the road would have on Corkerhill. As the Free State became established and camp residents and Corkerhill residents became more involved with the campaign there appeared to be a shift in attitudes. As contact with Free State residents increased, Corkerhill residents move away from a parochial standpoint and begin to incorporate wider environmental issues. Indeed there is a clear awareness amongst Corkerhill activists of the educational effect the Free State had on them. This education involved widening their horizons and opening their eyes.

We didn't really know about the pollution side or whatever at first, we just didn't want them to take away a chunk of Corkerhill. We learned about that stuff, about the environment and the effect roads have...its (the camp) made us more environmentally aware. (Ralph)

The community at that stage weren't thinking about the environment, sometimes people in our situation the last thing they think about is the trees in Brazil or the rainforests and stuff. So each time we were going along to the camp we were becoming educated. We begin to learn about the environment in general, we learn that whether a thing happened in timbuktoo or timbukthree the chances are it would effect us as well and we would suffer....All these people are changed people, they are all people who just don't think necessarily about themselves. It has been a learning process and I think it has been for the good. (Walter)

It is therefore possible to propose that residents' attitudes towards road building were affected by the presence of the Free State. Interviewed residents make reference to the educational effect the camp had, its success in raising awareness about environmental issues and the

⁹ Colin McLeod

environmental destruction and pollution caused by road building and cars. The clearest example of this shifting attitude can be found when respondents are asked to indicate what SRC should have done with the money consumed by the M77 construction. Residents' responses are detailed below:

Table 6.3: Alternatives to the M77

Ques: What do you think SRC should have done instead of building the M77?	%
Build another road somewhere else	16
Spend more money on trains & buses	39
Spend more money on improving social services	32
Upgrade existing roads	10
Other	1
Nothing	2

As is apparent from Table 6.3 the majority of Corkehill residents expressed no desire that the M77 be constructed in someone else's backyard. Only 16% agreed that the road should still be constructed and that it should be built elsewhere. Not only does this suggest that residents did not wish the cost of the M77 dumped elsewhere it also demonstrates that residents do not accept the need for motorway building. If attitudes towards the M77 were truly NIMBY then logically Corkehill residents would state that the solution to the problem is to build elsewhere in fact anywhere but 'their backyard'. What they appear to be saying however is why build this road at all, there is no need for it. Instead 39% of residents believed that there should be an increase in spending on public transport as an alternative to building a new motorway thus indicating that residents are moving away from seeing motorways as the only solution to traffic problems. NIMBY reasons for opposition to roads appear to be combining with arguments that point to the dangers of road construction, call for the halting of the road programme and suggest public transport as the solution. Joe and Betty make this point quite explicitly:

I think it has changed me, fae being primarily concerned wi maintaining a right-of-way I'm now very traffic conscious. I think whit is Glasgow doing to encourage public transport? And I have to say absolutely nothing (Joe)

I mean at first it was the road I didnae like, the idea of the road going through the wood when it could have taken another route...but I think now when they're saying about the amount of pollution that they kids were richt, cause you cannae keep building roads or you'll end up walking on the top of cars... I dont think we need so many roads. I think the way it is just now that they will soon no be places for people to walk. (Betty)

Thus the locational element of NIMBYism, where risk is associated with proximity, appears to be less prominent in these statements. Residents note that their original local concerns regarding the right-of-way and the route of route have broadened. The risk from roads does not appear to be connected to proximity and they are now concerned about roads building in general, not just the M77. Furthermore, residents are making calls for wider changes in transport policy, advocating greater use of public transport and less reliance on roads.

I have suggested that Corkerhill residents appear to be adopting some of the broader motivations for opposition to the M77 consistent with those of the radical environmental groups also involved in the protest. This contends that whilst motivations to protest cannot be contained within the typical NIMBY model in the sense that protesters were not motivated by self-interest but by community interest, primary objection to the M77 concerned the route it would take and the effect this would have on Corkerhill. Opposition can therefore be considered parochial and self-centred because residents were initially happy to have the route altered and the environmental costs of the M77 displaced elsewhere. In terms of the model of NIMBYism developed earlier Corkerhill residents appear to match the claim that NIMBY protesters are not concerned with motorways *per se* merely motorways in 'their backyard'. As the protest develops however there appears to be a shift in this view; the reasoning behind the opposition to the M77 becomes less local and more global, as do the solutions. There is a realisation of the wider environmental effects of the M77 and the effect pollution has on the environment. Furthermore the proposed solution to the M77 problem shifts from altering the route to investing in public transport; protesters openly question the need to build roads, not just the M77, all roads. This does not mean that previous motivating factors are abandoned in favour of newer ones that are more expansive. Instead there is an awareness of the wider global issues alongside local concerns and these are merged, as one resident says of the reasons for the establishment of the Corkerhill protest camp.

We were fighting for the community and for the environment as well (James)

Here we begin to see that local reasons for opposition are widening to include the global motivations of the Pollok Free State. Unfortunately, there is no chronological element to the survey data and thus the development of opposition cannot be traced quantitatively, however the qualitative evidence provided by Corkerhill residents does support the contention that reasons for opposition broadened over time. In line with this shift in reasoning behind opposition to the M77 there are changes in the community's strategy and tactics of resistance. This development can be traced chronologically and here too we can see more clearly the shift from strategies focussed on Corkerhill to ones that oppose the M77 on the grounds of its wider environmental

effects. Also at this time we see the beginnings of two developments. Firstly the tension that emerged after the Public Inquiry is starting to be resolved and questions about the future direction of opposition are answered by extending the motivations and repertoire of protest. Secondly, we start to see Corkerhill residents becoming part of a wider 'imagined community' of protest against the M77.

Strategy & Tactics

Corkerhill's strategy has always been pragmatic in nature, utilising various avenues of action to raise awareness and influence decisions. We can clearly see that Corkerhill's strategies of resistance to the M77 moved through an evolutionary process beginning in relative isolation and ending as one part of a diverse movement whose goal was to stop the M77.

Initially Corkerhill's strategy was to oppose the loss of the right-of-way between the community and Pollok Park, tactics were to highlight the loss and raise awareness by high profile direct action such as disrupting the international golf tournament. In the early eighties strategy and tactics altered slightly; the strategy at this time focused upon the health effects of the M77. Tactics aimed towards influencing the local authorities involved and often took the form of documents and reports, compiled by CCC, highlighting these health risks. There is a clear evolutionary process here from Corkerhill alone protesting about a right-of-way to many affected communities protesting about the road. Throughout this period however the community was fundamentally concerned with the effect of the **route** of the road on the community. Their solution was to alter that route and remained so until the early nineties and the establishment of The Free State.

With the advent of the Free State the community strategy altered again. Both groups, whilst opposing the M77, had a clear anti-roads strategy, one that, as is demonstrated in table 3 above, Corkerhill residents adopted. The community strategy also reflected the increase in environmental awareness and concern of the early 1990s and drew strength and motivation from other roads protests such as Twyford Down and those against the M11 occurring at that time

At that time we were beginning to look at the environment, to talk about the trees in terms of their worth, about roads, about pollution, car reduction..All these things fell into a place in a scientific way. Arguments for the environment were heightened even at a national level, what wi Twyford Down and all that....and it went beyond a community concern and became an environmental concern. .in general terms we (the CC) were getting involved in environmental issues..we became involved because of Local Agenda 21 and that covers everything that everyone is talking about wi the M77. So we learned that there is a higher level, and you learn as you go along..the parochial thing is a minuscule part of it, if you cannae change things higher up you've little chance. (Walter)

Thus, according to Walter, Corkerhill's strategy altered. It became less concerned only about the effects of the M77 on Corkerhill and became more aware of the effect the road would have on the environment. So the community strategy changes from being one which is anti-M77 and moves towards one which is in line with that of the Free State's anti-road strategy. Residents clearly state the view that the money for the M77 would be better spent on public transport.

I think they ought to stop building roads and get better public transport, naebody would huv tae go in their car, soon your no gonnae be able to go into toon in a motor. Fifty two million pounds would have brought public transport up to scratch and you wouldnae need to use your motor. If they had investet that on public transport naebody would drive to work, if they had new trains and buses, I think a lot of people would support that. (Joe)

To reflect this change in strategy the community residents also made a tactical alteration and it is here perhaps that we witness the most potent symbol of the Free State's effect on Corkerhill's protest. In the early months of 1995 Corkerhill residents established their own protest camp to oppose the M77. Set up adjacent to Corkerhill community the camp had all the features that characterise protest camps: benders; tents and communal living and collectively organised cooking and camp tasks. There can be no doubt as to the commitment of the local people to oppose the M77, they established a camp in January 1995, in the middle of winter, giving up their homes for life in a tent. Corkerhill's camp was not set up in opposition to The Free State but reflected the desire of local residents to fight their own battles. This does not mean to say that they resented the presence of Free State citizens but rather, reflecting the strong D.I.Y. element of their opposition, that they strongly believed that you should not expect to stand around and let others fight for you:

I don't think its right to leave it to somebody else to dae your dirty work..We wanted a camp for local people, we could have went up to the Free State, but we wanted our own camp for local people, we thought it was right (James)

Where the two camps differed however was in their stated purpose. Whilst the Free State's main goal was to stop the road its other aim was to stand as an alternative, an example of a culture where consumerism does not dominate and principles of solidarity and decentralisation do. The Corkerhill camp did not have this counter-cultural intention, it was principally established to protect Corkerhill, yet in the time spent doing so camp residents do take on similar arguments to many Eco-warriors about the purpose of protest camps. They are seen as a means of increasing the cost of road building by forcing the contractors to manually remove the protesters. Corkerhill residents embraced Eco-warrior tactics of non-violent direct action, climbing trees threatened with felling and

chaining themselves to equipment. Corkerhill residents describe how residents of the Free State gave them tips on the best methods of disrupting contractors and helped them in establishing their camp. Later both camps worked together, developing codes with whistles so that each would help the other if endangered or contractors were spotted on the route. The explicit aim of this strategy was to make the cost of road building prohibitive such that governments and local authorities would think twice about viewing roads as the solution to traffic growth. Their experiences of living in the camp caused them to reassess their relationship with the local environment and what they were fighting for. Camp residents described becoming more at one with nature, feeling closer to the trees. Perhaps it was living in such close proximity to nature that prompted this change. This statement by Joe sums up both the strategy and the effect it had on camp residents:

I certainly felt that it made you one with the trees almost, whereas in the past you just seen trees as a wood and stuff like that, things to play on. Or at night sometimes you were frightened of them, now I see them as shelter...it certainly was a focal point. Ultimately we were outflanked but they had to go to a lot more expense than they perhaps envisaged. Really after a week or two you realised that it was all about costing them as much money as you could and to put the cost of the road up

In the same interview Joe also states:

I knew what was arrayed against us. But I says if we make a big enough fuss here they'll maybe think twice about somebody elses scheme or woods.

Clearly, in these statements Joe acknowledges that the protest camp strategy was designed to delay construction thereby increasing the cost. It is possible to argue therefore that Corkerhill's oppositional strategy broadened from an anti-M77 strategy to an anti-road strategy or, in other words, from a NIMBY to NOPE strategy. Strategy was initially geared to protecting Corkerhill's right-of-way, it then altered to emphasise the health effects the road would have on Corkerhill residents before environmental issues came to the fore. Tactics of opposition also altered in line with this. Residents embraced Eco-warrior tactics of establishing protest camps, of direct action to prevent construction and of escalating the costs of road construction such that governments reconsider their worth as solutions to traffic problems. Thus there is the incorporation of new strategies into existing ones.

Thus the Free State facilitates the beginning of a process of frame re-alignment. Some Corkerhill residents see that they are not standing alone against the M77. In addition they begin to broaden their perspective from one which is focused almost exclusively on Corkerhill to one which acknowledges that Corkerhill is only part of the picture - an important part yes but contained within a broader anti-road opposition. For some residents it is no longer enough that

what is happening to Corkerhill is unfair or unjust, they appreciate the global consequences of road construction. Furthermore Corkerhill residents interviewed recognise the fact that as a result of protesting they are somehow different. Not only are global reasons for protest incorporated but residents themselves alter their perceptions of the world around them. Once again it is possible to argue that residents begin to see themselves as part of a larger protest, a protest which is not simply concerned with the M77.

In addition the establishment of The Free State and the activities leading up to it appeared to resolve the tension within Corkerhill regarding future protest that I identified in the previous chapter. Instead of accepting construction, residents now had an alternative form of opposition around which to rally. The Free State undoubtedly gave Corkerhill residents renewed heart and hope. Indeed they state that their issues were dead and that new issues were now to the fore. The presence of the Free State undoubtedly had an educating effect on Corkerhill residents, one that altered their perceptions of the protest and reasons for opposing the M77. Alongside this, other events influenced resident's perceptions of the protest and opposition. In particular the response to direct action, by both The Free State and Corkerhill residents, led to a further shift in the identity frame of Corkerhill residents. This time it was the realisation of the 'they' in opposition which led to a re-alignment of the 'we' perceived by Corkerhill residents.

Direct action of the form adopted by the anti-roads protesters and Corkerhill residents inevitably forces the state to show where its allegiances lie. The use of state apparatus such as the police and the judicial system to disperse road protests is noted elsewhere. (see, Grant, 1996) In these cases the protesters quickly come to the conclusion that the state is acting in the interests of capital rather than the people or the environment. Corkerhill residents engaging in direct-action come to the same conclusion:

Tae us it was a moral victory; in the camp we hud a book 'The War of the Flea' and that's what it was like, what it was about. It made them (the state) show their true face, tae flex their muscles and ultimately it made the camp valid cause if the camp wisnae there they wouldnae have used that force..so it made the camp successful, although ultimately futile...An operation that size has got to come from government sources..Who wants the road the maist? Big business, to move stuff aboot. If you've got a Tory government its them (business) that in it wi the Tories and they're gonnae apply pressure to get rid of us (Joe)

Joe stayed at the Corkerhill camp for some time and there is no doubt his experience of protesting caused him to re-assess who it was he was fighting. It is clear that connections are made between capital, in this case big business, and the state. Another protester, James,

highlights residents awareness that they are in opposition to more than just SRC or Wimpey, the main contractors;

You've got to blame the government, if they hadnae gied the go ahead it wouldnae huv happened. You're in opposition to the system, no just Wimpey

It has been suggested that the identification of abstract opponents such as 'the system' effectively dilutes an injustice frame by reifying the cause of the problem and transforming it into an unidentifiable mass. (Gamson, 1995) In this case it would appear that some Corkerhill residents are moving away from identifying 'councillors of the former Strathclyde Regional Council led by highway man Charles Gordon' as the concrete (as compared to abstract) focus for opposition. However the potential for collective action to induce the opposite effect has also been noted. Michael Mann (1974), for example, suggested that consciousness could explode, 'swiftly and without warning...during specified revolutionary situations' (p.46) and cites strikes and the events of May 1968 in France as consciousness raising events. Whilst it may be slightly wide of the mark to describe Corkerhill's protest against the M77 as a revolutionary situation it was nevertheless a time when residents came in to direct opposition with the forces of the state and capital. This is important not only for shaping awareness of who the 'they' are but also for who the 'we' are.

Clearly one would expect that those Corkerhill residents who chose to stay in the camp and engage in direct action would be influenced by the response to this. Not only camp residents became aware that they were also in opposition to the state however. The events of March 4 1995 highlighted this to all residents.

On this date an 'invasion force of approximately 500 police and 300 security guards entered the Corkerhill estate at 4am'. (CCC, 1995) They proceeded to erect a steel fence, stretching the entire length of the community and beyond, between Corkerhill and the woodlands on the M77 route. The residents of Corkerhill camp were awoken and restrained whilst the fence went up. This action by the police shocked and dismayed many Corkerhill residents. The overwhelming use of state power to suppress a small community led to awareness that the state was the 'enemy'. Residents describe it as similar to being at war in that they were 'invaded' and 'outflanked' by a 'commando style raid'.

What that was a show of force by the state. I know what a plan is, I know the strategy. ..They immediately fanned out around the houses and they were stopping people in the street, that must have taken a lot of expense. It was done almost identical to any military manoeuvre....at a stroke they fenced the whole of the area they were going to work in

and they kept the people of Corkerhill out. The police surrounded the outside of the barriers, the security guards were inside and the guys wi the saws were daing their work. They had it surrounded, like a fort.....I believe that this was one time when instruction came from on high. Wimpey couldn't decide to do this, the whole machinery (of the state) was turned on Corkerhill. (Walter)

It reminded me of the war, wi all these guys in their yellow jackets. I could picture them wi rifles. It was disgraceful....more or less an invasion, they were all lined up as far as the eye could see. (Ralph)

The steel fences reinforced the perception of being at war. Not only were they visible reminders of Corkerhill's exclusion from Pollok Park they were also a stark symbol of the community's enclosure. A type of POW camp designed to keep people out rather than in, people who were in many ways just as much prisoners as POWs in that they believed they were caged and trapped:

Most of the people there were women and weans..it was like a bloody concentration camp wi the fencing and the barbed wire. I'd never seen anything like that in my life. We're all trying to get in and they're stopping us

We felt as though we were caged, trapped, there was hunners of them. (security guards) (Janet & Gina)

We had seen protest in other places but they (fences) were never used. I couldnae believe it. I thought to myself, its like caging in animals, you know for such a wee place, and needing 500 or 600 people out there for two streets. (Betty)

The emotional intensity and moral indignation of Corkerhill residents to these actions is clear in the quotes. Clearly, this event significantly effected their perception of the protest and SRC and there was a sense of disbelief at the actions.

It was like caging somebody in. Surely civilised people shouldnae dae that to one another..I've never seen anything like it in my life and I thought about it and I think, how can they treat people like that? (Betty)

It was terrible..unbelievable..it was like something from another planet, lights and noise..my boys were screaming. It was a terrible feeling (Janet)

The emotion of this event is apparent in these quotes. Phrases such as 'treating people like animals' and 'caging people in' underlines the strength of feeling amongst Corkerhill residents. The image from Janet of it being like 'something from another planet' emphasises the disbelief felt by residents. It is important not to underestimate the significance of this event for Corkerhill

residents. Every resident interviewed describes this day in vivid and emotional detail and it is clear that, even now, it was a turning point in the protest against the M77.

The significance of this day lies in its effect on the identity element of Corkerhill's identity frame. As I noted, these actions by the state, or by organs of the state, resulted in the alteration of who Corkerhill residents perceived as the opponent. Residents come to believe that SRC is simply part of the problem. They realise that they are battling 'the system', 'the state', the government'. A re-alignment of the identity component of Corkerhill's collective action frame occurs such that residents now feel part of a broader collective 'we'. Furthermore, this is not the only effect protesting against the M77 appears to have. They now examine the world differently and question events they previously would not have, not only environmental issues but social and political issues also. It is to these effects I now wish to turn.

Residues of Protest: The Imagined Community of the M77

Whilst Corkerhill's protest ultimately failed, the process of protesting has affected residents in a contradictory manner. Tarrow noted that that the effect of protest may not only be direct and immediate but also that in their wake they can leave behind residues of reform. This residue is apparent in three areas: in political institutions that alter their practices; in changes in political cultures; and in the political socialisation of those involved. The latter results in three feelings, disillusionment with the political process, isolation and regret, or empowerment. In what follows I will endeavour to show that the act of protesting against the M77 confirms Tarrow's claims whilst also seeking to argue that Corkerhill residents now feel that they are members of a larger community of protest.

It is clear from the survey data that some Corkerhill residents feel democratically disempowered by the experience. Sixty six percent of respondents believed that the views of Corkerhill residents had not been listened to when the decision to build the M77 was taken, only 3% believed they had been listened to a lot or a great deal. Tarrow's claim therefore that disillusionment with the political process is often the consequence of protest is supported. In further corroboration of Tarrow's theory however, the protest against the M77 has empowered other Corkerhill residents and led to an awareness of the power of direct action. Certainly, those residents most involved in the protest now declare a willingness to engage in future protests. Of residents who regularly visited the Free State and protested alongside Free State residents, 77% indicated that their experience of doing so has made them more likely to protest about similar issues. It would appear that the positive influence of the M77 protest on Corkerhill residents is

not confined to environmental education but also to empowering residents who otherwise feel powerless.

For the most active protesters there is not only a willingness to engage in future action but also a clear acknowledgement that protesting has led them to actively participate in local and community politics and, perhaps more significantly has led to an awareness of the links between state, capital, and the local environment. For example Peggy and Karen successfully stood for election to the local community council in 1996 and both attribute this desire to become involved to the time they spent at the camp. Their experience of political protest and fighting for their community led to greater awareness of the need to fight to protect their local area:

I'm more aware of what's happening now, because of that I started going to community council meetings and eventually got elected (Peggy)

I'm into it a wee bit deeper now, I like to find out the ins and outs of things. I've learned from it, about politics. A few years back I couldnae tell you anything about things to do with your community, now I'm on the community council. I've been to quite a few demos now, no just for motorways but other things. All these things I never knew about before. I done that, so it (the protest) educated me..Its gave me the will to stand up and fight, to stand up for my rights. (Karen)

In addition to inspiring these feelings of empowerment and participation the M77 protest has led to Corkerhill residents questioning the functions of the local and national state and their effect on the local environment. It has become apparent that decisions that effect the local environment are often taken with the interests of capital in mind. Of course, contested developments of this kind are often justified in terms of job creation as indeed SRC justified the M77. In working class communities such as Corkerhill however, where unemployment is high and people might be expected to welcome developments which create jobs, there is now a feeling amongst some that the environmental costs are too high to bear and that the only real beneficiary is big business:

Aye big companies are making money out it while were suffering. ..If the council took the wishes of the people of Corkerhill they wouldnae huv built that road. They were on the side of whoever wanted it, business (Richard)

This feeling does not only apply to the M77 but has led protesters to question other developments going on around them. Joe for example questions the reasons for the siting of a new ASDA store in a busy Glasgow road, particularly the effect the traffic congestion this causes and the purposes for siting the store in that location:

They built some new traffic lights to relieve the congestion at ASDA, but noo there's tailbacks for half a mile..there never used to be and the fumes are really bad. Folk live in that street. I just think of the weans and old folk wi breathing problems living there, they're in trouble. It's criminal to put the profits of a mutimillion pound company in front of old folks' and children's health.

Clearly the effect of protesting against the M77 has led to those residents who did feeling part of a broader community of protest. Their interaction with the Pollok Free State and the establishment of the Corkerhill camp led to a connection between groups and individuals who prior to the campaign would probably have had nothing in common. During the protest it became clear that they had a common goal of stopping the road, albeit perhaps with different motivations. A form of imagined community, as identified by Anderson forms. In this case it was an imagined community of resistance that developed in Corkerhill, a community that encompassed Eco-warriors, and local people.

We met new people, thats how we met James, and it was great, and we were all there for the one thing. Thats what we talked about it was great, like a big family. (Karen)

Furthermore some local people still feel part of a broader community. They no longer feel as isolated as previously in terms of protesting against that which they perceive as unjust. As a result of the M77 protest some Corkerhill residents appear to be members of both the real community of Corkerhill and the imagined community of social protest. They straddle these two because despite locals now questioning the social and economic system in which they exist they do not go as far as, for example, The Free State in forming alternatives. Free State residents demonstrated their rejection of what they considered as existing undemocratic procedures by establishing an alternative state which sought to determine its own future. Notwithstanding these feelings of empowerment Corkerhill residents continued to accept the liberal democratic process as the basis for decision making. The 'undemocratic activities' of SRC and central government rejected in the Free State's declaration of independence were not rejected by Corkerhill residents. In fact in the case of Peggy and Karen they are now more active participants in the political system than previously. Of Corkerhill residents surveyed, only 4% indicated that the M77 would influence the way they voted in future. In all cases respondents stated that they would evaluate candidate's attitudes to the issues surrounding roads and transport before making decisions. No respondent indicated their intention not to participate in local or national elections. For Walter the political process was a problem inasmuch as the candidate elected by Corkerhill residents was in a minority party, but his solution still lay within the democratic process:

Now we've got a SNP councillor here and the big problem we've got is that he is so much in the minority that he cannae persuade they devils (Labour councillors) to do a certain thing, as long as they are democratic they are within their rights and that is the problem we face..... What we needed was a high profile member of parliament that was

doing the same things that we were doing..in terms of the politics of it we have thought the politics out and we have to go for some big name

Others however adopt a more radical left-wing stance and find allegiance within the ranks of socialist parties such as Scottish Militant Labour (SML). Their experience of the Labour party at the local level in Glasgow and its willingness to sacrifice the very communities it claims it was established to defend leads to the development of a grassroots politics which has its roots in environmentalism and socialism. At the time of the protest Militant Labour were seen as the only party which actively protested against the road. Corkerhill residents view Militant councillors as no different from themselves; they live in the same schemes, suffer the same poor housing conditions and fight for the same things.

The way I see it theyre (SML) the only wans that dae anything in oor schemes....99% a Glasgow votes Labour but I dont see why I should. They dont dae anything fur ye. Theyre aw the same. (James)

They stay in the same hooses as you dae, theyre the same as us but Labour urnae (Peggy)

In local elections I vote SML...I vote SML because they wur the only wans involved in the M77 (Joe)

For some residents of the Corkerhill camp environmental destruction is not an issue which is separate from issues such as unemployment and poverty, they are inextricably linked to the workings of the capitalist state:

I think the two root causes of it are private ownership of land, and money. Its greed really. people live in terrible conditions, suffer fae poor health, unemployment and that so that folk can make money. I just cannae see any future for the planet unless there is a radical change in attitudes. I've always felt this but my experiences of it have honed it more. I've had hands on experience so now I can relate to things. Certainly I would say that it (protesting) has left some very deep, deep views on my consciousness. (Joe)

It is mostly the younger protesters who demonstrate these feelings, older protesters, if they voted Labour in the past, tend to shift voting patterns from Labour to the SNP. The possibility is then that protest like the M77 may result in the mobilisation of new young grass roots Eco-socialists who realise that only a radical alteration of existing politics will prevent further environmentally and socially destructive developments like the M77. Nevertheless, it is important to remember that local issues still seem to be the most important for Corkerhill residents. Peggy and Karen, for instance, became involved with the Community Council in order that they could become more involved in issues which effect it. Likewise, James and Joe state that they are involved in local politics. Thus, whilst it may be the case that protesting against the M77 has left a residue of

environmental concern amongst Corkerhill residents it is probably the case that this concern influences their thoughts and views on local issues rather than forming the basis for political action. It is possible that the effect of the M77 protest has been to open the eyes of local people to the environmental issues which surround them and to demonstrate that environmental concerns are as much a feature of urban politics in a city like Glasgow as issues regarding resource distribution and services. They may indeed be young eco-socialists but their actions and concerns are firmly grounded in local issues and local politics.

Conclusion

I argued at the beginning of this chapter that the emergence of radical non-violent direct action against the M77 helped to resolve the tensions which existed after the Public Inquiry. I also suggested that the identity component of Corkerhill's collective action frame altered as a result and that instead of viewing Strathclyde Regional Council as the main opponent residents came to believe that the forces of the state were arrayed against them. Because the 'they' element to Corkerhill's protest altered, the 'we' element also altered for some Corkerhill residents. The 'we' became more expansive and included groups that perhaps previously Corkerhill residents did not feel a great deal of connection to. Over time however residents began to see the common bonds between themselves and the members of these groups and began to realise that they were fighting a common enemy. Reasons for opposition appear to broaden over time, incorporating the global concerns of the environmental movement. A similar development is apparent in the strategies and tactics of opposition, expanding to question the need for the M77 and utilising the direct action tactics of the anti-roads movement. Some residents of Corkerhill become part of the imagined community of environmental and social protest that exists in Britain today. They become involved in other forms of protest, in local politics and in grass-roots activism. They move from NIMBY to NOPE. Because Corkerhill residents continue to perceive the solutions to these issues as existing within the democratic system however it is only a partial crossing from NIMBY to NOPE. Their experiences of protesting against the M77 has led them to question the efficacy of traditional politics however unlike Free State residents, who choose to reject entirely traditional liberal democratic procedures, some local residents instead feel empowered to participate in local politics and effect change from within. What emerges is a potentially positive and dynamic form of grass roots Eco-socialism where environmental destruction is recognised alongside poverty and unemployment as a major problem affecting working class communities.

Chapter 7: Conclusion

The Emergence, Mobilisation and Dynamics of Community Opposition to the M77.

This dissertation has sought to explore the processes of mobilisation and the dynamics of community opposition to developments which threaten their way of life. In Chapter 1 an attempt was made to develop the theoretical tools required for further analysis. By examining concepts of public opinion and social movements concepts such as communication, networks and leadership were identified as being potentially crucial in analysing protest mobilisation. Chapters 2 and 3 sought to establish the historical background within which later studies would be located and serves to remind the reader of the broader historical processes at work throughout the discussion. Chapters 4, 5 and 6 endeavoured to test and develop those theoretical tools identified earlier through exploration of one particular prolonged instance of collective action.

Corkerhill's protest against the M77 is significant in that it demonstrates the importance of communication to protest mobilisation. Furthermore it also illustrates the value of a critical analysis of processes of communication to the understanding of how collective action of this type emerges in response to a threatening development. These processes of communication revolve around the role of leaders and the presence of established social networks in order to be fully effective.

I have shown that there was a core of residents within Corkerhill who filled the position of community leaders. These residents were most typically members of Corkerhill Community Council and involved in many community activities and issues. Consequently, information flowed throughout the community, and this applies to all the issues that effected Corkerhill not just the M77. The work of Corkerhill Community Council and its members ensured that no development went unnoticed. Community Council members went round Corkerhill informing residents of

developments. Community Council members collected signatures for petitions. Community Council members sat outside the local shops giving out leaflets and information. Community Council members organised petitions and demonstrations. The Community Council represented Corkerhill at the Public Inquiry. The Community Council organised public meetings and displayed the plans of the motorway. It was the Community Council who ran slide shows for residents and it was Community Council members at the forefront of protest against the M77.

The Community Council was crucial in communicating developments to other residents, indeed communication was essential for the emergence and development of opposition to the M77. The community leaders were, in effect, pro-active transmitters of knowledge and a significant source of information for other residents. What is also important however are the informal networks that exist between people; the information capillaries between individuals working alongside the arteries which carry information between the CC and residents.

For Eyerman and Jamison (1991), knowledge is the product of a series of social encounters. For residents of Corkerhill knowledge was built up through networks of social interaction; communication through conversation and learning through conversation. As Melucci suggested, the construction of knowledge is a collective process that emerges from conversation and discourse within the 'everyday networks' of Corkerhill life. It is within these submerged networks that people interact to collectively redefine the world around them. Corkerhill's network may only have been partially submerged in that the Community Council is a formal community organisation. Regardless, the communication networks enabled Corkerhill residents to collectively discuss the issues concerning the M77 with up-to-date information from the CC and ensured the mobilisation of community opinion and the development of opposition to the construction of the M77.

The role of leadership in Corkerhill must not be overlooked. The task of leaders is to communicate change, respond to developments, exploit opportunities and endeavour to ensure that the 'chilling silence' of modern society is overcome. The presence of a clear and committed leadership in Corkerhill helped facilitate the development of opposition to the M77. First the Community Association and then the Community Council provided democratically legitimate foci of opposition and organisers of protest and acted as mediating variables between the media, SRC and the people. In many respects the idea of Community Council members acting as 'opinion leaders' or 'influentials' is one that bears fruit. Moreover, organised local leadership forms the nucleus of sustained protest and action and helps to nourish community identity even in areas with high turnover rates, leadership of the kind present in Corkerhill empowers. Certainly it must be remembered that within this discussion of 'Corkerhill' the contribution of key individuals within the community must also be stressed. Corkerhill's opposition to the M77 demonstrates the importance of strong leadership to the mobilisation of sustained protest.

It is clear that networks of communication existed in Corkerhill and that community leaders were central to these. It is also clear that, concerning the M77, these networks did not occur in other areas. In Arden, despite the fact that the Community Council opposed the M77, there was no flow of information from it to the wider community. Nevertheless, other issues such as stock transfer may have eclipsed the M77 at crucial times in Arden. As a result, whilst it is possible to conclude that Corkerhill's communication networks were crucial to mobilising opposition, it cannot be said with absolute certainty that a lack of such networks precluded similar developments in Arden. It may also be too simplistic to point to the apparent lack of response from the community leaders within Arden. Working class communities rarely have the resources to fight two major battles at once; indeed they rarely have the resources to fight one. Given this it may be possible to conclude that there are 'volume' limits to community activism. Limited resources and a small number of activists may often mean that attention is focused on one issue at the expense of others. Communities have to prioritise their issues and residents of

those communities must prioritise their information sources about issues. It may also be possible to conclude that there are volume limits to the amount of information that communities can easily absorb and deal with. Consequently, in Arden, the M77 seems to have been squeezed out by the issue of housing stock transfer.¹⁰

Following the discussion of macro-mobilisation I suggested that opposition may only emerge when communities are able to mobilise an alternative internal message which overcomes or challenges existing dominant messages. Evans & Boyte (1986), in their discussion of the history of social movements in America, note that successful movements are rooted in the structures of community life. In particular community groups assist people in overcoming the 'chilling silence' of public discussion within the contemporary marketplace of politics. They suggest;

For a well-developed consciousness of broader community and generalised active citizenship to emerge requires ways for people to build direct face-to-face and egalitarian relationships, beyond their immediate circles of friends and smaller communities. Thus, a prelude to democratic movement, ..has been the emergence of avenues for wider sociability....such associations create a consciousness that many people can work together. (p.192)

Clearly it is possible to argue that Corkerhill Community Council contributed to the development of the community's consciousness in this manner: providing forums for face-to-face interaction and nourishing residents collective awareness of both the causes of and possible actions in response to the M77. In so doing an alternative message was constructed, this was determined by exploring Corkerhill's collective action frame.

The development of a collective action frame within Corkerhill assisted the emergence of opposition to the M77. The framing process enabled Corkerhill residents to interpret the events around them into a meaningful cause for opposition. Consequently, the construction of the M77 is interpreted as a threat to the community's traditional way of life and the completion of a historical process of enclosure and segregation. Again, Corkerhill's communicative nature

¹⁰ I am indebted to John Foster for this point 187

ensured that this frame would permeate throughout the community relatively easily. It is also important, however, to understand *how* the frame develops within Corkerhill and to determine if it emerged naturally or was developed by community leaders. By qualifying two points regarding Corkerhill's collective action frame I hope to shed light on this.

Firstly framing, as it is currently utilised, appears to be essentially a top-down procedure whereby movement entrepreneurs construct an explanatory package of the world and attempt to sell it to potential members. This however does not adequately explain how and why entrepreneurs construct that specific frame and neither does it offer much insight into protests where distinguishing entrepreneurs and followers is problematic. Distinguishing leaders and followers is in some respects relatively simple and I argued that CCC fulfilled the role of opinion leaders within the community and consequently can be considered as community leaders. It is true that that the CC was at the forefront of Corkerhill's opposition and it can be argued that to mobilise the community the CC had to construct a collective action frame around the themes discussed above. Indeed, much of the literature examined in this research was pamphlets and documents produced by the CC. Although the source of Corkerhill's collective action frame has been narrowed down to the CC it is still not clear why and how that frame was constructed. I would suggest that it must be remembered that the Community Council are representative of the community and when attending council meetings would not only bring along their own interpretations of the M77 but those of their family, friends and neighbours. CC discussions of the strategies to raise awareness and oppose the M77 would reflect these hopes and fears of the community. Thus, it could be contended that the collective action frame which developed in Corkerhill is not the result of a top-down process but instead a bottom-up process where community opinions and interpretations feed in to the CC. The frame reflects the entire community but is developed and articulated by the Community Council. It develops during countless conversations on the streets of Corkerhill between neighbours and in official CC meetings. The top-down view of framing does seem more appropriate to large scale social

movement organisations whose goal is the alteration of policies at a national level and whose public may be more dispersed although there must a basis for rapport between the leaders conflicts and the views and experiences of followers and members. This approach however may not sufficiently explain the mobilisation of smaller movements in opposition to specific developments such as Corkerhill's.

Secondly, it is necessary to examine the contention made by Gamson that;

the history of social movements is a reminder of those occasions when people do become mobilised and engage in various forms of collective action. These movements always offer one or more collective action frames. (1995, p. 98)

Whilst I have suggested that a collective action frame developed in Corkerhill and that it was important in explaining the community's opposition I believe that it is also important to point out that other factors were similarly meaningful. The implication of the quote from Gamson is that a collective action frame is necessary to mobilise people to engage in collective action. Throughout the discussion of Corkerhill's opposition however, I highlighted other factors that also appear to be important, specifically, cultural and historical factors.

Cultural factors prevalent within Corkerhill's opposition included the self-help component of the sense of agency that developed. I noted that belief in 'no sitting back and letting others do you dirty work' derives from a working class culture of independence and self-support historically present in Corkerhill, persisting through time and across issues. Consequently, I believe that a 'culture of agency' existed within Corkerhill that assisted the mobilisation of residents in opposition to the M77. Arguably a community with a protest history similar to Corkerhill's, which has previously mobilised on a number of other issues, would mobilise and engage in direct action more readily than one which has never done so. Direct action is quickly perceived as a legitimate and valuable element of that community's strategic repertoire.

In many respects the historical and cultural factors are linked. The development of a 'culture of agency' results in a community with a long history of protest, that produces a body of people experienced in protest who accept the need to engage in direct action. Alongside these historical/cultural factors however I also identified Corkerhill's historic isolation from other communities as important in fostering both a sense of identity and of agency. The fact that Corkerhill has been shunted from constituency to constituency over the past twenty-five years combines with perceptions that they are overlooked because of this and the spatial separation of Corkerhill from surrounding areas. This results in both a strong sense of identity built around the concept of 'community' and a strong sense of agency based on the perception that only Corkerhill has ever or will ever care about Corkerhill. Both of these historical elements facilitate the mobilisation of Corkerhill residents, and thus collective action, whilst not dependent on these factors, is influenced by them.

Furthermore I have suggested that a collective action frame may not simply serve to establish the adversarial 'them' and 'us' involved in protest. It may also work to define what is under threat and what is at stake by highlighting the potential for the contested development to impact upon an existing sense of identity. Thus the collective action frame may not construct a sense of identity but instead concentrate or reform an existing one that the frame identifies as being under threat. I made the point that as currently utilised the concept of framing appears to be more suited to large-scale movements where organisers are required to inform people of their similarity and common identity. In the case of smaller movements such as Corkerhill however a collective action frame may not be necessary to generate a sense of identity. Other factors, again cultural and historical, may also make significant contributions to the development of identity.

Following this it is possible to argue that in Corkerhill's case the collective action frame was important in highlighting the injustice of the M77 particularly in the three areas identified:

spatial; class, and political. With regard to the other elements however it is possible to argue that the development of an identity and agency frame was not the only factor in promoting both a sense of identity and a sense of agency within Corkerhill. Thus it is possible to contend that in small-scale community movements it is perhaps the case that the agency and identity components of a collective action frame do not necessarily need to be constructed from scratch. Instead existing senses of agency and identity can be harnessed and utilised to promote and ensure a collective response to the perceived threat. This certainly appears to be the case in Corkerhill.

Corkerhill's collective action frame successfully united many residents by demonstrating the threat of the M77. The 'alternative message' of injustice, enclosure and segregation overcame media apathy and the 'jobs, jobs, and more jobs' message promulgated by those supporting the road.

The importance of the existence of a critically discursive public sphere in mobilising opinion and action is also apparent. By disseminating information and guidance, holding meetings, producing leaflets, organising demonstrations etc. a group can create a critical public sphere within which public opinion can develop. Habermas noted the importance of communication and discourse for this to occur, but instead of the salons of Paris and London we have instead the houses and community halls of Corkerhill. This does not mean to say that people would not have formed opinions about these issues if the movement had not developed. What can perhaps be said with greater certainty however is that opinion on the solutions to these issues may not have developed to the same extent. It is important nonetheless to remember that, arguably, this discursive public sphere did not only emerge in response to the M77. Corkerhill community has campaigned about many issues during the past 30 years. Consequently, I believe that a culture of critical discourse has developed within the community.

The community possesses a discursive public sphere where issues are discussed and, in particular, local government decisions effecting Corkerhill questioned and challenged.

A public sphere of the type that developed in Corkerhill does not just emerge; it requires opinion leaders and mobilisers to feed information and knowledge in to it and cohesive social networks to facilitate its development and ensure its survival. Consequently public opinion crystallises and forms within an atmosphere of discussion and debate and the collective action that emerges is born out of this communication process.

In the dynamics of Corkerhill's opposition we can witness the evolution of its protest into a wider social movement context. The establishment of The Pollok Free State and the emergence of radical non-violent direct action against the M77 led to Corkerhill's protest merging with that of the anti-roads movement. This merger does not result in a pragmatic division of responsibilities whereby locals organise petitions and Eco-warriors confront the state, instead locals engage in the kind of protest activities usually undertaken by radical environmentalists such as building camps and chaining themselves to trees and equipment. In effect, Corkerhill residents become part of the anti-roads movement.

According to Anderson an imagined community is the result of the fact that people cannot possibly see or communicate with every other person with whom they share a sense of communal identity. This obviously creates a distinction between real and imagined communities such that real communities are those where communication between every member is possible. Following this it is possible that we could consider Corkerhill to be a real community. Throughout the previous chapters I have attempted to demonstrate that Corkerhill could be characterised by its communicative nature, indeed in chapter four it was classified as a 'discursive community' in light of this. With the union between radical and local protest however, an imagined community develops. It is imagined because, again, those within could not possibly communicate with

everyone else, yet they undoubtedly were part of a larger whole and a broader community of those opposed to road construction and the M77. Corkerhill residents do not reject their lifestyles however and do not leave one community for another. They straddle both and are members of both the 'real' community of Corkerhill and the 'imagined' community of the anti-road movement. In this way, the anti-M77 protest builds a bridge between local and global issues. The anti-road movement facilitates this building process but at its heart is, again, notions of communication. Local residents indicate that The Pollok Free State educated them about the environmentally destructive dangers of road building and the strategies and tactics required combating it.

The unison of Eco-warrior and local protester that occurred at Corkerhill bridges the divide between the parochial NIMBY concerns of local residents and the global NOPE concerns of Free State citizens. This is a bridge that some Corkerhill residents have crossed at least partly. As a result of their involvement in radical environmental protest they are now questioning the need for motorway building and local environmental decline. They are now making links between their 'everyday life concerns' of poverty, unemployment and poor housing and global issues such as the environment and the relationship between the state, business, and environmental destruction. Bridges are constructed therefore between local and global issues and between environmental and social issues. Collective action by Corkerhill residents therefore is not merely an event it is a process; a learning process which alters their perception of the world around them. What must be remembered however is that it is the act of protesting itself, not merely the unison of local and environmental protest, which fuels this. Whilst the presence of The Free State was important in raising awareness of broader issues and new strategies it cannot be said that The Free State alone constructed a bridge between local and global issues. This bridge was also constructed by Corkerhill residents whose experience of protesting led to a broadening of perspective and to the incorporation of global concerns into everyday ones. As Joe stated; 'I've had hands on experience so now I can relate to things'.

The history of the M77 and the opposition to it is long and complicated. First proposed as part of the 'Highway Plan for Glasgow' produced in 1965 the first detailed plans of the M77 were drawn up and presented to the public in 1969 and it officially opened in 1996. This represents over 30 years of planning and over 25 years of opposition from local communities. The M77 was designed to ensure quick access to the city from the south whilst connections to the national motorway network would enhance business. It has now been open to traffic for over four years and over 50 000 vehicles a day use it. Ironically, it is now suggested that the M77 is not sufficient to cope with the numbers of vehicles that use it. At busy times tailbacks form at the junction between the M77 and the M8, often stretching back along the road for a distance of 2-3 miles. The effect, especially in the morning, is that a large traffic jam sits on the M77 adjacent to Corkehill. The proposed answer to this is to construct another road, the Glasgow Southern Expressway, which would directly link the A77 to the M8. In addition, another urban motorway in Glasgow, the M74 extension, is the subject of intense discussion and lobbying between Glasgow City Council, The Scottish Executive, the business community and local residents. This discussion presents the same stark options as the M77: jobs or the environment. Meanwhile traffic is returning to the roads that were to be emptied with construction of the M77.

The irony of these calls for new roads is not lost on those who opposed the M77. At the time they argued that construction would only encourage increased car use and that the M77 would very quickly become jammed. In addition, they argued that a limited upgrade to the existing road from the A77 to the M8 and a by-pass around the village of Eaglesham (now upgraded to the Glasgow Southern Expressway) would better serve the traffic needs of south-west Scotland. It would appear that the lessons of the M77 have not been heeded and that protest against motorway construction may be a feature of Glasgow politics in the future.

Appendices

Appendix 1: Three Communities Survey

Section 1: Background Knowledge

1. Have you ever heard of the M77 Ayr Road Route?
- Yes 01
No 02
2. Can you remember when you first heard of the proposals to build the M77?
- 1-2 years ago 01
2-5 years ago 02
5-10 years ago 03
Over 10 years ago 04
Other 05
Don't Know 06
3. Can you remember where you first heard about the construction of the M77?
- Newspaper 01
Television 02
Campaign by local group 03
Talking to friends relatives 04
Other 05
Don't know 06
4. Do you know who is responsible for the decision to build the M77?
- Central government (in London) 01
The Scottish Office 02
Local Government (Strathclyde Regional Council) 03
Other (specify) 04
Don't know 05

Section 2: Opinion

5. What is your opinion of the construction of the M77?
- Strongly Agree 01
Agree 02
Neither agree nor disagree 03
Disagree 04
Strongly Disagree 05
6. If agree at question 5: Why do you agree, what is the most important reason?
- It will reduce travelling time to Glasgow 01

It will reduce traffic in this area 2
 It will be easier to travel from Ayrshire to other parts of Britain 3
 Other (specify) 4

Go to ques 8

7. If disagree – what is the most important reason why?

Because you fear it will damage your health or your family's health 1
 Because it will increase pollution in your area 2
 Because you believe the money would be better spent on improving public transport 3
 Because of the destruction of trees and parkland 4
 Because of its effect on the environment 5
 Other (specify) 6

7b. How concerned are you about the construction of the M77?

Very concerned 1
 Quite concerned 2
 A little concerned 3
 Not concerned 4

7.c Do you feel the M77 will bring any benefits?

Yes (specify) 1
 No 2

7d. The decision to build the road was taken by Strathclyde Regional Council. Do you know why they think it is needed?

To reduce traffic in other areas 1
 To reduce pollution 2
 To assist industry in Glasgow 3
 As part of an overall policy to improve roads 4
 Other 5

7.e. Do you think the road should have been built?

Yes 1
 No 2

If No

7f. What do you think Strathclyde Regional Council should have done instead of building the M77?

Build another road somewhere else 1
 Spend more money on trains and buses 2
 Nothing, the present road is good enough 3
 Upgrade existing roads 4
 Spend more money on social services like schools and housing 5
 Other 6

Go to ques. 9

8. (If agree at 5) The decision to build the road was taken by Strathclyde Regional Council. Do you know why they think it is needed?

- To reduce traffic in other areas 1
- To reduce pollution 2
- To assist industry in Glasgow 3
- As part of an overall policy to improve roads 4
- Other 5

8. Do you think the M77 will make a difference to your day to day life?

- Yes 1
- No – go to ques 10 2

9b. If yes at 9. Do you think it will be improved or made worse?

- Improved 1
- Made worse 2

10. During the recent protest to stop construction can you remember where you got most of your information about it from?

- Newspapers 1
- Television 2
- From a local group 3
- From talking to friends, relatives or neighbours 4
- Other 5

11. Generally speaking how interested would you say are in politics?

- Very interested 1
- Quite interested 2
- Not very interested 3
- Not at all interested 4

Section 3: Protest and Activity

12. Were you involved in any way in trying to stop the construction of the M77.

- Yes 1
- No 2

If no go to ques. 19

12a If yes what action did you take (tick all)

- Sign petition 1
- Write to councillor/MP 2
- Attend public meetings 3
- Direct protest such as a demonstration 4
- Other 5

13. Why did you protest against the M77?

- Because you fear it will damage your health or your family's health 1
- Because it will increase pollution in your area 2
- Because you believe the money would be better spent on improving public transport 3
- Because of its effect on the environment 4
- Because of the destruction of trees and parkland 5
- Other (specify) 6

14. Have you ever protested about an issue you felt strongly about before the M77?

- Yes 1
- No – go to ques 15 2

14a. If yes what did you protest about?

.....

14b. And in what way did you protest?

- Sign petition 1
- Write to councillor/MP 2
- Attend public meetings 3
- Direct protest such as a demonstration 4
- Other 5

15. How did you first get involved in protesting against the M77?

- From going to a meeting or demonstration 1
- Talking to family/friends/neighbours 2
- From talking to member of local group 3
- From talking to member of protest camp 4
- Other 5

16. How much time a week did you spend protesting against the M77?

- Less than 1 hour 1
- Between 1 and 2 hours 2
- Between 2 and 5 hours 3
- Over 5 hours 4

17. How often were you involved in protesting?

- Every day 1
- Once a week 2
- About once a month 3
- Only at big events such as rallies or demonstrations 4
- Rarely 5

18. After your experience of protesting against the M77 are you now more or less inclined to protest about similar issues you feel strongly about in future?

- More 1

Less □2

19. If no at 12. At any time did you think about protesting against the M77?

Yes □1
No □2

19a. If yes. Why, in the end did you not protest?

Because the road doesn't effect me □1
Because you agree with construction □2
Because you didn't have time □3
Because you didn't know how to go about it □4
Because it wouldn't have mattered anyway □5
Other □6

20. Are you or have you ever been a member of any of the following groups or organisations?

Greenpeace □1
Friends of the Earth □2
Transport 2000 □3
Glasgow for People □4
RSPB □5
National Trust □6
Other environmental group □7

20b. Are you or have you ever been a member of any of the following groups or organisations

Trade Union □1
Local community group □2
Political party □3
Other □4

21. In your opinion how successful was the campaign to stop the M77?

Very successful □1
Quite successful □2
Unsuccessful – go to ques 23 □3

22. If successful. In what way was it a success?.....
.....
.....

22b. Who was most responsible for the success of the campaign?

Central government □1
The Scottish Office □2
Strathclyde Regional Council □3
Local residents □4
The protestors □5
The media □6
Other □7

22c. Given that the road is currently being built why do you think the campaign was not more successful?.....

23. If protest was failure. Who was responsible for this failure?

- Central government 1
- The Scottish Office 2
- Strathclyde Regional Council 3
- Local residents 4
- The protestors 5
- The media 6
- Other 7
- Don't know 8

24. What is your opinion of the camp that was set up to stop construction and the people who lived there?

- Strongly Agree 1
- Agree 2
- Neither agree nor disagree 3
- Disagree 4
- Strongly Disagree 5

25. Did the campaign to stop construction change your opinion of the M77?

- Yes 1
- No 2

25b. If yes. In what way?

- I became more opposed to its construction 1
- I became more in favour of its construction 2
- Other

26. Do you feel that anything can be done now to stop construction of the M77?

- Yes 1
- No 2

26b. If yes what?

- Lobbying government 1
- Non-violent direct action (demonstrations, petitions) 2
- Violent direct action 3
- Through the courts 4
- Other 5

27. In the future who do you think would be most likely to be effective in challenging this sort of thing?

- Organised pressure groups 1
- Community groups or community councils 2

Individuals working on their own
Other

3
4

Section 4: Efficacy

28. How much do you feel that the general public can influence this kind of thing in your area?

A great deal 1
A lot 2
Some 3
A little 4
Not at all 5

29. How much do you feel that you personally can influence these things in your area?

A great deal 1
A lot 2
Some 3
A little 4
Not at all 5

30. Which do you think is most influential on policy, an individual working alone or a group of people working together?

Individual 1
Group 2

31. Do you think you received enough information about the M77 from Strathclyde Regional Council?

Yes 1
No 2

32. How much do you feel that the views of the people living close to the M77 were listened to when the decision was taken to build it?

A great deal 1
A lot 2
Some 3
A little 4
Not at all 5

33. Roadbuilding is part of environmental policy. Overall who do you think has most influence over environmental policy decisions like this?

Central government (in London) 1
The Scottish Office 2
Regional Councils (Strathclyde Regional Council) 3
District Councils (like Glasgow) 4
Industry and business 5
The public 6

Other (specify) 7
Don't know 8

Section 5: Voting and Behaviour

34. Is there one political party you support more than others

Yes 1
No 2

If yes which?

Conservative 1
Labour 2
Scottish National 3
Liberal Democrat 4
Militant Labour 5
Green Party 6
Other 7

35. Did you vote in the last General Election in 1992.

Yes 1
No 2

If yes for which party?

Conservative 1
Labour 2
Scottish National 3
Liberal Democrat 4
Militant Labour 5
Green Party 6
Other 7

36. Did you vote in the last Regional Elections in 1994?

Yes 1
No 2
Don't know/cant remember 3

If yes for which party?

Conservative 1
Labour 2
Scottish National 3
Liberal Democrat 4
Militant Labour 5
Green Party 6
Other 7

37. Will the building of the M77 influence the way you vote in future

- Yes □1
- No □2
- Don't know □3

If yes in what way?.....

38. If an election for a new unitary authority (Council) were to be held tomorrow which party do you think you would vote for?

- Conservative □1
- Labour □2
- Scottish National □3
- Liberal Democrat □4
- Militant Labour □5
- Green Party □6
- Other □7

Background/Respondent Details

39. Area of residence

- Corkerhill □1
- Arden □2
- Thornliebank □3

Street name and number

40. Gender

- Male □1
- Female □2

41. How long have you lived in this area?

- 1-5 years □1
- 5-10 years □2
- 10-20 years □3
- over 20 years □4

42. Age

- Under 18 years □1
- 18-25 years □2
- 26-35 □3
- 36-50 □4
- over 50 □5

43. Are you currently working?

Yes

1

No

2

42.b If yes. What is your job. If no what was your previous job?

Thank you very much

Appendix 2: Interview Transcripts

Interview 1: Betty Campbell

Interviewed: Corkerhill Community Shop, 26.10.96

A. Could you just tell me Betty how you first got involved in the M77 protest

B. Well, the first time, the PI I had a house there and I put in to buy and that time we were told not to buy the houses. There was a possibility at that time that they might pull down the houses, but that was quashed and they says that the road would be going ahead and we put in our objections. Now the first thing I had from roads department, they had taken us and shown us a plan of the road and how we would be effected by it. There's a lot of things in it that huvvnae happened. Things that I think..the farm and that is different. I think that was round about 88. Colin was a number of years before he came in to it. We had protests at the golf course which we video'd. We were involved then, at the open days and that; anything that was on we would go and give out leaflets. But there wasnae a lot happened for a while. We'd been up there and up and doon and up and doon and then it went quiet but it was always at the back of our minds that it would come round; and it was just out of the blue one night Walter got a phone call and this guy (Colin) asked to come round. He was talking about doin something with the trees and that is where our friendship with Colin started. He wanted us to go and see the farmer and ask if it was possible if we could go there, but that never happened he went to the Barrhead road. We frequented it practically every day, and didnae have any qualms about it. A lot of time we went to the working group along wi the roads department, but we were involved all through that. Colin was involved in the background one of the meetings we were at they were looking in the windae. I think they thought we told them about the meeting but they found out from different sources. They went round a lot of the Wimpey showhouses and all that. We didnt do that. We went to the, done a protest outside before it was given the go-ahead. Another time we went up and gave them the alternative. Walter went in wi that wi David Spaven, but that wisnae looked at all and yet that could have done a lot more. But wi Colin I dont know whit you would call Colin, he just seemed to come out of the woodwork, he was excellent. He seemed to have a lot of character. As Walter said I though people like that were deid he puts me in mind ae masell when I was age.

He took on up just beyond our houses up the back. First time it was the crane he went up and my son he went down one night about 3 in the morning, they went along wi stuff for him to eat and in the morning we though wed go along and video. And we went along, Thomas was up the crane and he'd fell asleep , but they lifted him.

A. Your son?

B. It was later on after we'd been up speaking to him, I was here in the shop and Walter came in and said thats Thomas been lifted. Walter said don't bother I'll go up they'll probably just let him oot. He went up but said you better go up and explain that this is his dads anniversary and its no nice to think that they're holding him at that time. The way I see it is, if you murder somebody you can get oot on bail but he's done nothing and he's getting held. But the police said "oh were not locking him up" I said but he's getting treated like a criminal he's locked up he cannae get oot. I came back and said to Walter and he couldnae believe it. Monday morning, the whole place, baners fae Pollok, all round bridges and bus stops Free Tommy Campbell. Eh we were getting ready to go to the court on Monday a whole load ah us, we stepped ootside and who's walking along the road but Thomas. Took him tae court but let him go. held him fae Friday to Monday and that was the first time..hed never been in trouble in his life. So that caused a bit of a stir, you've got criminals here breaking into cars and they'd a been oot the next day, whereas Thomas had done nothing yet he got kept in.

From that I think it went to the tree, he (Colin) went up the tree, he was up there quite a long time. And we visited him there I think they tried to prevent stuff going up to him. We'd meet with his mum

and dad and became friendly. It was after that that the meetings started to take place. They had like a caravan up at the Barrhead road and we'd go for meetings. Colin I think he got on with the roads people. Robin Rankin who was head man he says Colin was a gentleman when they met him, he wasn't the person that they thought. But there was a lot of things happened at the camp and in Corkerhill. There was a lot that came from the other side that is no the way to treat human beings. That was about the backae three in the morning..

A. When you say the other side, who do you mean?

B. From the roads people and the contractors, the workers. To come into any place without anybody knowing..I mean my neighbour beside me she was genuinely frightened cause they didnae know what was happening. I just wakened wi somebody talking oot my window but when I looked oot it was just like a yellow carpet and they were just trudging oor the back green. And these cages were put up, it was like caging somebody in. Surely civilised people shouldnae do that to one another. My son who stays near me, William, he came over when they heard Walter going round shouting and they said "your no going in there" he said I'm going in its my mothers. My hoose they came and used it for press contacts and GfP quite a number of folk came up to contact the press. I've never seen anything like it in my life, I thought about it and I think how can they treat people like that and the whole day, I've seen a lot of protests but nothing like that. When we went down the workmen, they're only dain the job fair enough, but they hud an attitude problem, really aggressive and I think it is dangerous when your employing people like that because there were times when we went up there, we went up every day even after the caging and spoke. But the aggression shown by the security guards, one of them was ready to biff Walter, and telling lies you know saying things had happened when they hudnae happened.

A. As far as you were concerned why did you get involved, you've said how, but why?

B. Because I don't think that the road necessarily needed to take the route taken and I think that is there to be seen now. They realise that. I've been told that they'll have to look at ways of taken the traffic away before it gets to Corkerhill. It could have been undercover, we wemaee saying we didnae want roads what we said was it could have went straight across the golf course, it would have been cheaper to do that. In fact just now we've met with the SO last week and I think they've seen for themselves the way its actually come right into Corkerhill. You'd need to be blind no tae see that. We've asked for to investigate the farm because there is something happened, because the reason the roads the way it is is because the farm being there. Noo if they hid sold off the farm, they must have had it in their mind at the time, cause they gave the go ahead for the road then decided to put the farm up for sale. So whit was the reason, why did they no sell the farm and put the road there? So the SO have taken that away with them.; its a haulage contractor thats been brought in, and the farmer had asked for a road and that was refused, so how is it happening now that he's got a private entrance road to the farm.

A. did you see any other issues as being important?

B. I dont see it being right that they stick that motorway right up beside where people are staying, because the fumes from it and the noise is atrocious. You could be sleeping and just wakened up startled at two in the morning eh you've, they must realise that people sleep during the night and the only time they can do this kind of work is during the night, so when they know thats gonnae happen they're no really caring that your hoose is just beside it, or they wouldnae do it. The way I see is, its no in their backyard so its alright and thats the only way I see it.

A. What about.. you've been involved in the CC for some time, what about getting the rest of the community involved. Was there always a lot of people interested or did you have to drum up support?

B. No there was always ones..if there was something on. It had been talked about and brought up so many times that people eventually thought that it just wouldnae happen, it was going through, it was stopped, there wisnae the money, then they had money. There was talk that our houses were supposed to be coming down. There was a lot of support, anytime anything was done and you went out you always had the troops behind you all the time, but I think people in the end thought it wouldnae go ahead. But noo its a reality, and sometimes that puts them off from doing other things, they say it disnae matter whit we dae they'll dae it.

A. Did you feel that you had to convince people?

B. I think we had to get the best out the road, trying to get the best out of it and changing peoples attitudes, there was stuff came out of it cause if it had went ahead in the way they (Wanted) we wouldnae have had access to the park, that had to be fought for and the kids play area had to be fought for, and we managed through the PI, they said now's the time to go for broke and don't accept the pennies.

A. Did you have to say to people to stick together?

B. Oh Aye you've got to stick together, that's what we always done, were great believers in involving everybody, its on our minutes all the time. And yes you've got to involve everybody and I think here I think a lot of people know well know be moved and shoved around. People know were here for them. There was a lot of support when we went to the camp.

A. Did people come to you for advice?

B. Yes a lot of times neighbours came in and asked what was going on. That girl Karen, one of the chaps that was there she ended up marrying him. A lot of goods come out of the camp and I think people realise that all the protesting that was done, they realise that it was needed to let them see that you cannae do this people and get away with it. Cause I've heard it mentioned that that was one of the biggest protests that they had. And the fact that they put up pailings (fences) for two streets that never happened in other places. We had seen protests in other places but they were never used. I couldnae believe it. I thought to myself, its like caging in animals, you know for such a wee place, and needing 500 or 600 people out there, for two streets. It shows you the way they got tuned into Corkerhill that they felt that they should do that.

A. Why do you think they chose the route they did?

B. I think because they know the history of Corkerhill, there was always, we always showed up when things werna right. We were always there. And they werna prepared to allow that.

A... Sorry Betty I worded the question wrong. Why do you think they chose the route of the M77 that they did?

B. There is only one answer to that and that's the golf course. The golf course seem to have benefited the whole way. There must be literally thousands of money over and over again paid to the golf course, and yet were in they houses and still fighting to get windaes. And during the protest, the mess they left behind that was paid back to the golf course. They got a lot of money from that cause they'd dug up their fairways to bring stuff in. The now , all the woods were the kids played, thats on the other side that the golf course is getting as a pay off. So I don't see that they have got anything to complain about, they've benefited a great deal.

A. Why would they choose a route that benefits the golf course?

B. Well there is mair money over there. You'll find that it is planning, some on the board of the golf course were heid yins, judges and justice of the peaces and that. And planning they would have a

lot of influence over ordinary people in Corkerhill. But it is for these people now to say well can we no gie Corkerhill some of it. The money they've spent over there, plus the farm, the farm should have been used for the community rather than being sold..because it is no a lot, 60 000 is no a lot when you consider how much money that golf course got. I you wonder about it. I think that something underhand has went on.

A. And who do you blame for this Betty, if anyone?

B. I would blame Strathclyde, I mean there is no anybody else. I even said to Charlie Gordon, and it is like I dont know, they say it is not as bad you think, I said well If you want to come for a holiday to Corkerhill I'll take your hoose. They think it is no a bad thing, but thats only cause they're no living there. I, m quite sure that if it was a decision for they're area they wouldnae want it. But Walter met him a fortnight ago and he asked him questions. He said if you had to meet Charlie Gordon what would you say. he said If I had to meet the devil I'd speak to him. I think there has been a lot of underhand stuff, I cannae understand how the golf course has all that and yet were sitting with nothing. They've spent thousands of pounds over there. That makes you ask questions like why are you no getting double glazing, and yet I look out my windae and see a man wi all this space hitting a ball. And I think 400 odd weans here all screaming in the play area, looking for space. So there is something in it.

A. How did you keep yerself going and motivated?

B. Well Colin was a great uplift and he got on well wi Walter and that brought it to the boil again, we were at the camp every day. I came round we would let them know what was happenin here. It saved them coming, they could come when they were needed. But there was a lot of wrong done at the camp, cause they were only young. That girl Karen, the rough treatment they got wasnae called for, they went over the top.

A. What about before the camp, within Corkerhill?

B. Well it was never off wir minutes, it was always..came up at our meetings. Normally we rallied people around, said we would meet at certain places and go over, march over back and forward. The police were brought in and said go over and come back but your no going back and forward. And it was to let them see that we were against it when you thought of the way they were benefiting from it.

A. Did you talk to friends and neighbours?

B. They all rallied round, I had there was a lot of my neighbours with us when we did stuff, and Lilly was involved and Ralph. We always used that for taking the children over to the picnic area and it seemed terrible that that was going to be done way with. The way it is just now I just cannae believe that thats there. I get up in the morning and think thats mad. I don't see how they should get away wi doin that to people. And I think we were right to be fighting for what we wanted when you think that the golf course is gaining all that money. Its all been hushed up by the National Trust; we went up to the NT they were embarrassed, they came out to us and said oh it wisnae us, it wisnae us that gave the go ahead. I think there has been a lot of underhand stuff. Dealings went on somewhere. That women at the Trust when she came over and spoke to me said it wasn't us the family was cash strapped and it was them, but they still shouldnae have given the go ahead. They were holding that they shouldane have done what they done. There is something goin on, even with Strathclyde, the whole lot of them. There's been some kind of carve up done. Golfers and Trusts and the whole lot of them, somethings no right. You just see it about. It seems to be all the big heidy ones who have had their influence in it and thats whats happened, and ordinary people have got to except it, but no without a fight.

A. Why, didn't just sit back and let others get on with it.

B. Cause I think everybody's got to stick together in things like this, to try and change attitudes, thats the only way. You'll no get it by sitting back, you've got to involve the whole place. I think thats one of the main reasons why Corkerhill sticks oot fae a lot of other places, because we've always been prepared to stick their neck out and not accept the things that other communities take. I think its appreciated, a lot of the places we go I hear it all the time. At the end of the day the people realise what we're doing. It wasnae for our own gain it was for the community.

A. Has it changed you do you think, your experience?

B. Well all I would say is, people have got to stand together and , yes we've won because its been noted all over about the road, its went ahead but they've had a warning; they thought they had nae....,its changed their attitude towards road building I think Corkerhill made them think that their no gonnae get away..

A. Who do mean 'them' ?

B. Everybody Involved, I think attitudes have changed I see now that the same man that said that was a good thing is now saying we'll need to look at public transport, so thats the man that said you needed roads and now he's telling us we need public transport. But can you believe any of them? It makes you wonder. Charlie Gordon, is that what they do, is he changed or is it just cause his jobs changed. You find that we a lot of people.

A. How do you think it has changed you?

B. Its made me all the more determined that the roads people are no getting away wi it. The SO, they're definitely no getting away fi it, whatever they've said we've tae get I'm looking for that and nothing less, more if possible. What's came out of it is men a re working up the back trying to alleviate the noise and the suffering eh us in the houses. Screening up, the screening..the acoustic barrier has never taken place.

A. In terms of yourself has it made you more determined to fight?

B. I think it does make you more determined because some of the things thats happened wouldnae have happened if wi hadnae fought for them. If you dont fight back they'll just walk over the top of you. I think people have got a lot of power but dont use it to their full capacity. If they stand up in the end they might win.

A. Do you think that's been a consequence of you involvement with CCC?

B. Yes I would say that, but I wouldnae allow anybody to browbeat us. But in the past a never really was involved in stuff, so you didnae see it in the same light. When I came here, the problem was already here, they were talking about it..I think it makes people more determined to see that if we all stick together we can win, you'll win some and lose some, you cant win them all, but I think all over the place it dosnae matter were we go its talked about. We've made a lot of good friends in the process from organisations and even the television.

A. What about..you spent a lot of time at the camp, and mixed with the people like Colin, how did that effect you?

B. I didn't have a problem with them, to me they were very compassionate, when we met them they had great thingmy from Walter. In fact a boy came back from Sweden, we used to get on well. Big Jake comes back to see us. And I didnae see..theyre always tarred and I don't think you can tar people wi what they wear, I think that was the big thing that came across. Mibbae some people

didnae like the way they dressed or done their hair, but at the end of the day I don't think that's how you should look at people. Its what's in their hearts no the colour of their hair.

A Do you think..

B. I think they genuinely cared, some of they kids were crying their eyes out out of frustration.

A. How did their compassion rub off?

B. I got on really well with them and came down a couple of times, we showed them videos and made them soup. They appreciated anything you done for them. They were always helpful.

A. Do you think the camp made you aware of other issues?

B. I think it made you aware that these people were concerned, and yet some people say they're outsiders, but at the end of the day they're ordinary people fighting for the same thing as yerself.

A. Do you think they were fighting about the same thing?

B. Well some of them..it would be unfair to say that they were all..some of them it was the trees we wurnae, I mean at first it was the road I didnae like, the idea of the road going through the wood when it could have taken another route. No really..but I think now when they're saying about the amount of pollution that they kids were right, cause you cannae keep building roads or you'll end up walking on the top of cars. No I would say great on them, some of them are dedicated, its probably the only life they know, they're remarkable. I think they've got to be applauded, everybody knows they'll no get away wi it now.

A. How do you feel now about roads?

B. I don't think we need so many roads. I think the way it is just now that they will soon no be places for people to walk. I think public transport is more an issue now, more so than before. I think there is too many roads, too many cars and it brings in more motors than before. You only have to look at the M77 now. They told us it would cut down traffic there (Corkerhill road) that they'll all use this road (the M77); but in the morning this road is packed and the main road is still busy, so it looks like is if there is a jam up there a lot go back to the main road. This is as busy as ever. Its no done away with the traffic problems here, they said it would take traffic away from here onto the motorway and because it would be faster moving there would be less pollution, what I have found since it opened is that that road is jam packed and their barely moving for about 2 hours in the morning. You can have tailbacks as far back as I can see. And what I've noticed is that a lot of the cars that are passing..buses with two passangers or no passangers, your talking about cars wi one driver and nobody else, which creates, if that was like three or four people in cars and a bus load of people you'd see it working. The way it is just now it has created a problem we never had before.

A. How do you feel, what is your overall feeling about the thing generally?

B. I don't think it has made one bit of difference that road. Its built and there is nothing we can do about it. Its created more problems. I think the protest has made them realise that building roads disnae solve the problem and I thinnk they know that now. I spoke to people and they're talking about looking at ways of taking the traffic away before it reaches Corkerhill, so is that another road they're thinking about?

A. Looking back on all the years you've been involved, do you feel let down?

B. The reason I would say I feel let down is that my father and his father they were all Labour men, and you follow that cause you think that's the right thing to do. Vote Labour and its a Labour council

that.. I mean SRC could have said no but its like your voting for someone who you think is going to be on your side and yet they take that decision. I couldnae understand it at the time. The city council and the Region and the one being against it and the other for it and going and asking the Tories what should they dae.

A. So what's the answer Betty?

B. I think that they've got to know that, I think they know that over and over again. They took a decision that people were unhappy with they got that message from Corkerhill anyway. So I don't see them being so willing the next time because they had a lot of stick to put up with. There was a lot of councillors that was maybe on.. that felt rubbed up because of it..they wernae wanting to be known what they're votes towards it were. They would say to you that they didnae vote for it, but behind the scenes you don't know what happens.

A. So do you vote for a different party, or not vote?

B. No I think let it be known what your feeling are in the hope that it changes their attitudes I think that's the only remedy to it, let it be known, and let them see that if they don't change their attitudes then they'll no be getting your votes. That was seen in the elections when the SNP got in here, I think they saw that people wernae gonnae give them their vote when they go against them, and they'll need to show themselves to get the votes.

A. Thanks very much Betty

Interview 2: Gina and Janet McCrimmon
26.10. 97

Location: McCrimmon household, 51 Hardridge Road, Corkerhill

ANDY. Hello, firstly thanks for taking the time to do this. Could you tell me how long you've lived in Corkerhill?

JANET. 16 years, we've all stayed here 16 years.

ANDY. When did you first hear about the M77?

JANET. Just after we moved in, about 1980, we used to stay in 76 Hardridge road and after the two wee ones were born we moved here. That's when I first got involved. I went to all the meetings and that, the PI but it didnae dae any good.

ANDY. How did you hear about it?

JANET. Walter Morrison,

GINA. We went to meetings, listened to what was happening.

ANDY. Did you do anything to try and get other people involved?

JANET. We done everything

GINA. Put leaflets through doors, went round the doors in Corkerhill.

JANET. The ones nearest to the road, Betty and Margaret and us, we were the only ones that took anything to do wi it, wi the protestors. Gina went down to the camp and stayed there overnight. But I used to go to all the meetings, to the PI before anything was settled. nearly everybody fae Newton Mearns wis at the meetings. And people fae AyRobert. I was saying how would you like to stay next to a road, I've got two boys that are asthmatic. They said it wouldnae bother them.

ANDY. Why did you get involved?

JANET. Cause we didnae want the road there

GINA. For the sake of the children that stay in this scheme we didnae want, cause its a dangeRobert. That's why we fought.

JANET. My weans were brought up wi bein able to go oot the back in the morning and feed the cows, noo they're waking up to motorways rolling by them. I never wanted a motorway. My two youngest were born here, and my two grandaughteRobert.

GINA. Its bad enough wi that

JANET. Well be a lot more isolated than wi ever were, before wi could go right through the Pollok estate, only took you five minutes, noo you cannae dae that. Its a mile walk before you even get tae a path. I hate the thought of going near that road.

ANDY. You got involved cause you were concerned about the community.

JANET. I went to all sorts of meetings with Walter and Betty, we went everywhere, done everything

(at this point Robert McCrimmon enters)

ANDY. Why do you think they chose the route they did?

JANET. I dont know, I think its better for the people of Newton means , its no better for the people of Corkerhill,

G I dont think its good, for us.

JANET. Theyres nae access for us tae it, you've got tae go away up there. You cannae get on tae it fae here.

ROBERT. The golf course got paid money,.. because they are money people their land didnae really get touched. They got money cause eh the motorway. The golf course got some of the farmers land.

ANDY. What do you mean they're money people?

JANET. Its all people wi money that are oor there. Corkerhills poverty stricken.

ROBERT. they are all middle and upper class, they've all got money. In this life the people wi money get wit they want the people without money dont get a say in the matteRobert.

ANDY. Do you think you were consulted?

JANET. No,

ROBERT. I never even heard about it.

J I used to go tae meetings. I took my weans doon tae meetings. Naebody wis consulted about it.

ROBERT. The protest never really started till people actaully seen the bulldozers coming up. I think a lot of people didnae think it would happen. It was oan the agenda for about 20 years. A lot of people thought that.

GINA. I never thought it would happen. Because it was woods and all the kids used to play there. I used to play there myself, it was all woods. We never though they would build the woods doon that the kids played in and build a motorway.

JANET. I think it was about 76 when it was first mentioned, but it kept getting put back and put back, when we went to all the meetings it kept getting put back. So we didnae really believe that it would go ahead. Even when the protestors were doon there some people were saying its no going ahead.

JANET. I think..I mean Walter knew..he fought every way he could to stop that road..But I got involved because its my community as well. Its our community, and we didnae want that road destroying our community. Its right at the back door. we cannae sleep for the noise. And its polluting the environment.

JANET. We got FriendsoftheEarth the involved, people fae Sweden were over here camping oot, but it never done any good. We went to meetings. They telt us it wouldnae be done for another year, then all of a sudden they were oot there at five in the morning

ANDY. What about within Corkerhill?

JANET. Well Betty and Walter, the weans did loads of stuff, putting leaflets through doors and all that.

GINA. The weans done a lot of things as well, drawing pictures, they had a lot to do wi it.

JANET. We got all the kids from the scheme to clean it up doon there. They got certificates, they done that three times. Cause the golf course were complaining that it was full of rubbish and thats how it was alright to build over it. It was a public walkway it should never have been done. Even the kids got fed up. But the kids were coming hame fae school and heading straight doon to that protest and sitting there wi the big ones. They nearly killed them the morning they bulldozed it.

ANDY. If I could talk about the morning the police came in what did you think?

JANET. It was a disgrace...

GINA. It was the sneaky way they done it..nae warning. There was people camping doon there and they just went in and ripped them oot the tent, nearly broke somebody's arm.

JANET. What a disgrace that was..they jumped over my garden fence about 5 in the morning. Fae I moved in there I've been asking them to cut the trees at the back cause they were too high. That morning they jumped over my fence and cut the tree doon that I've been asking them to cut doon for years. It was pandemonium, she was there and I went doon to see if she was aright. But I couldnae get through it was all fenced aff. So I came back up here, he was just going to hes work. The polis wanted to used our gate, they pushed me up against the gate and said they would arrest me for obstructing the police if a didnaae let them.

ROBERT. I said your no going through my gairden, they went another way.

JANET. It was terrible the polis were absolutly unbelievable..

ANDY. Some people of describes as an invasion.

GINA. Yes it was

JANET. Aye, it was like something fae another planet. lights and noise..my boys were screaming, they were terrified of the noise of the chainsaws going at half past four in the morning. They came in to my room screaming. It was a terrible feeling.

GINA. The polis came doon, they were putting fences up in front eh us, and then..they wurnae asking you to move along they just pushed you. And they behaviour of the security guards was a disgrace. They were told to say nothing

JANET. My wee boy was eleven and the way they were speakning to him was a disgrace. And it was wanae they councillors, Nicky says to the polis there is nae need to talk to weans like that.

GINA. He was getting charged wi verbal abuse of the polis and yet they abused him.

ANDY. Why did the police do that?

JANET. I dont know it wasnae like all them in the state, there was nay need for the amount of police here that day. They brought them fae Stewarton and Greenock and they're all on overtime.

GINA. It was terrible..they were all up through the woods in case anybody tried to go up that way. its no as if this is a dodgy scheme.

JANET. Maist of the people doon there were women and weans and they went doon there..it was like a bloody concentration camp..wi the fencing and barbed wire. I'd never seen anything like that in my life. Were all trying to get in and theyre stopping in.

GINA. We felt as though we were caged, trapped, there was hunners eh them, there was thousands.

ROBERT. There was 300 hundred polis that day and 250 security gurads.

GINA. There was too many for that...

JANET. One wee boy touched the fence and got lifted for breach of the peace,,his mother hud tae go up tae the station and get him oot. It was a disgrace.

ANDY. Who was reponsible for that?

ROBERT. The polis. Dan Pollard fae Wimpey...money talks, Wimpey have goat monay, they can get the polis if they need them.

JANET. Wimpey arranged all the security..I was mad I was bruised.

GINA. I didnae approve of the securities at all, the polis and the security. They were the worst it wisnae the protestors. They were spitting on us. I tried to get in and they threw me to the ground, in a puddle. Yet they were told no tae touch anybody at all, and they did. They wrecked the whole place, They were told no to touch anybody. See when they got into the camp they battered hell oot ay all the guys there. They done the opposite.

JANET. They set fire to the caravan. They wouldnae even let them get their personal belongings out. They wouldnae let them. There was nothing they could do, They had radios and stuff and it was all burned. They were pleading wi them, just let us in for were stuff, but no.

GINA. I though the free state was brilliant. Great, great atmosphere, the people were great wi yi. They couldnae be any kinder, they made you tea and soup and all that.

JANET. They were brilliant people, the papers were saying they were all junkies and that but they werna. I think they were brilliant.

GINA. They made a great joab of the camp, they had treehouses. I though a lot of them they were great people.

JANET. The indian restaurants used tae send us doon curries and that.

ANDY. Do you think the peole in the Free State were fighting for the same reasons as you were fighting?

JANET. Aye..to stop the road

ROBERT. They were mare about saving the trees fae getting cut doon, maist people in Corkerhill didnae want the road cause there was gonnnae be nae access to Pollok Park

JANET. And the wildlife.

GINA. Yeah

ANDY. Do you think that effected the way you look at the world?

GINA. Aye.. well it made me aware of things that were going on..like the wildlife. there was some animals that were in danger. The Free Staters found a set and were told that it wouldnae be touched. We had all sorts of wildlife here, soon there'll be nothing

JANET. It made me change my view, years ago I wouldnae care if you built motorway outside my door or no, but now I do. There is naewhere tae take weans. The weans are mair isolated now, there is more trouble. In summertime the weans would just go over to the park, noo they will be all cooped up the gither. Its gonnae isolate us, there will be nothing in the scheme for the weans.

GINA. It seperated the community. It used to be that everybody used to know everybody..see now you dont talk to people. Everydody felt like a big family, we always done things the gither, like take the weans up the estate, get them tae draw things..the mother and toddlers group used to take the weans on nature trails, now they wont be able to cause they'll no be able to get across the road.

ROBERT. since its been built,

GINA. I dont think roads are safe. I cant stand them, I know you need them but their dangerous, for adults and children.

JANET. I dont understand why they built it the way they did, there is plenty of other routes they could have done. They could have went under the golf course, or neareer the golf course. But the golf course objected, and they've got money, they had money people.

ROBERT. They always seem to put motorwyas through communities, it was the same wi the M8, it went through Easterhouse. They never seem to take the roads were its no gonnae bother anybody

ANDY. Why?

ROBERT. All these conservation areas and green belts, people wi money.

ANDY. Why were people so angry about it?

JANET. Because they never got enough information about it..

ROBERT. And because it is right near them.. eventually the fence will get a hole in it and people will go through.

JANET. Its a danger to this whole community.

ANDY. Do you blame anybody?

JANET. I blame the council. It was them that built it..

GINA. The council..they want it.

JANET. We were supposed to be getting all this double glazing and that, when the road started to be built they sent us letters saying well gie yi one bedroom double glazed. We've got nothing, except for a road.

JANET. I feel weve been stabbed in the back, they look for your votes and they were saying well make sure somethings done about it then they go ahead a let them dae it. It was money in their pocket. Somebody must of got money oot it. The people of Corkerhill didnae.

Robert. I dont think anybody in Corkerhills benefited..I suppose that business and that will be benefiting.

JANET. Aye big companieds are making more money oot it while were suffering. It was us and them, we were the poor wans and they were the wans wi money.

ROBERT. If the council took the wishes of the people of Corkerhill they wouldnae have built they road, so they must have been on the side of whoever wanted to build the road.

JANET. I mean when I went tae the PI I says to those that stay at Ayr, I said you give me your hoose and stay here. They wurnae interested in whit our standard of living was as long as theirs was alright.

ANDY. So what do you do.. did you vote Labour again?

JANET. I voted SNP.

GINA. So did I..

JANET. because of what happened. If you dont vote the tories get your vote..I would love to have voted for the green party, when it was just the wee elections for the scheme I voted for the green party, but in the big elections we couldnae. Quite a few people would have. People say a vote for the SNP is a wasted vote, cause they're never gonnae get into power

ROBERT. If there is nae point in voting, whatever governments in power will just stay in power if you dont vote. I dont think you can change the system.

JANET. they should listen to the voice of the people no the the voice of the ones wi the money. If this scheme had stood up more maybe the road wouldnae have went ahead. Yet when the security guards were here the whole scheme was doon. I said how could you know have been here before.

Robert. Its because everybody said it wisnae gonnae go ahead thats why. the day it happened, practically everybody in the scheme was there, some of them were cryinGina. I know it sounds silly, but I was heartbroken, hunners of years they trees have been there. It was the peoples place, the family that owned it, the Maxwell family, left it to the people, That was a public walkway and they took it away.

GINA. I feel the council let us down, the government, everybody that was involved.

ANDY. has it changed you?

JANET. I dont think it has changed me .. I care mair about the environemt noo. I never really though about wildlife, or were birds are gonnae nest or whateve. But I think about that now.

ANDY. Thanks very much for your time.

End

Interview 3: Joe Gallagher

3.11.96

location, 98 Glanmuir Drive Nitshill, Joe's residence.

Andy. Joe, thanks very much for taking the time to talk to me about this, Why don't you begin by telling me a little about yourself

Joe. well I'm 32 years of age, I've lived between here in Nitshill for 9 years but I lived in Corkerhill for 14 years., so I've lived most of life in Corkerhill. When I moved there was a dispute going on about access to Pollok park, a more or less ongoing thing, but at that stage the argument was really raging. Then Corkerhill was a hard scheme to get a house in and although you had your tenants association and your community council they were very united in maintaining that right of way and it culminated then when they dumped a substance on the fairway, I thought it was petrol, there was a big sit down. After that they were more or less granted their right of way. The community then was always very united, we used to have bus runs and summer playschemes and stuff.. You had the Nethercraig games hall which we used in the summer, I've been barred from it a few times as a youngster. It was always good. We always had dogs and we took them up to Pollok park, and even as late as 17 18 years old you ran around up there. In the summer nights that's where you would go, Pollok park, cause it was that close. You always had a bit of hassle wi the golfers cause there was always that wee animosity cause they were better off. There was animosity too wi people fae Mossspark, cause you would go up there stealing apples and stuff, you know, high jinks.

The golfers, it would be a two way thing, we didnae like them they didnae like us, we were young and bold they were older. There was always this thing that they'll build this road but it always seemed years away.

A. Who did you hear about the road from?

J. By that stage I had moved to here and my mates used to go doon the Pollok Free State..

A. Sorry Joe, when you were a youngster in Corkerhill..

J. Maistly then the community council..at various things. But as a young boy your non really interested, then there wisnae..even if there had of been . And then Walter, always in the shop, as the years went by we the Nethercraig hall got burned doon and they built a new neighbourhood hall. after that the tenants mob settled for that, they became the elite then and the scheme which I would have to say..there must have been a decision took in Glasgow district council tae run the scheme doon to break up the unity. Cause if they'd a tried a road in the 70s there had a been absolute outrage. By the time the actual road went through cause the scheme had changed that much and it was no longer united half the folk never bothered. So ..but I stopped by once or twice but never really got involved in it at all, my mates used to go there and there was a few bad press reports aboot drunken parties and all that, blah, blah, blah. But they started, they had large stretches of the road almost built just needing tarred, I'm no sure..it just seemed stalemate. And then just as it really exploded there was a fire in the work..and I was off on the sick for a week. Either that weekend or the next weekend was the ruckus wi Alan Stewart up at Pollok. So I was off sick, the work was damaged badly. and they laid us off until further notice but we still got our wages. So me and a mate were down on the Tuesday cutting some bushes at my maws back garden. And we heard through local folk that they were setting up a camp in Corkerhill that day, so me and the mate went across and it was Jake Hunter, two boys fae Nitshill. So I'd done some camping and that and I said tae them..they had a caravan but the side had been hit so it hud a big gap in it, and bearing in mind this was early February so it was baltic. So I said I'll bring roon a tent and a wee stove and that for you to use. So next day I went roond tae see how they're dain a tent and a wee stove and that for you to use. So next day I went roond tae see how they're dain a tent and a wee stove and that for you to use. So next day I went roond tae see how they're dain a tent and a wee stove and that for you to use. So that night it was really cauld so me and some others stayed, and cause I was local they sort of expected me to be the leader..so we sat roond the fire aw night, in fact four of them slept in

the caravan which was really cauld.. So we sat roond the fire and that was fine. The next night there was naebody to stay again so me and this other guy said well stay. We were really tired and we never knew the difference between green wood and dry wood so if you burn green wood there is smoke in your eyes and everything. It was murder, sitting roond the camp wi five young teenagers, it was dark about 10 o'clock. We looked across and we could see all these guys coming and we though thats the tree cutters coming noo..but it was all the boys fae militant..wee James and that. So I got a few hours sleep and next day we decided to get a rota goin and the camp really started from there. But cause eh the militant boys they wanted to have their ain camp but still wanted locals involved as opposed to the free state camp...and it just went fae there.

A. OK thats how you got involved, but why did you get involved?

J. cause obviously growing up there..see different local got involved for different reasons, mines was to maintain the access to Pollok park for Corkehill. I didnae see why we should have a road going through my scheme, and why they would cut down a forest when there was a golf course there which certainly no one in my pay bracket could afford a membership. Plus I seen it as folk like Gallie and Stewart and them looking to secure their seats in the general election. That was part of why they wanted that road to go through. but primarily to maintain the access to Pollok park for the community.

A. You said Joe that throughout the years, a sense of apathy sets in, did you try and overcome that?

J. See I had moved away, but I lived in Nitshill which would still have been effected by the road, but not as directly as Corkehill, cause really only Arden and Corkehill and certain bits of Darnley could really , would really be effected, and it was as if it was never gonnae happen, and it was just by chance that I got involved. I was involved wi the camp for a month..it got smashed up, we got stuff stolen, in a commando style raid. that happened on the Friday and I got up the hoose and there was a letter saying return to work on Monday so it was just as if the camp and that was meant to be at that time so that I could get involved.

A. Did you go into the community and say to people..

J. Yeah but really the attitude was, fae the wans in the pub and that, the roads gonnae go through anyway. I never for a minute thought that we would stop the road cause I knew what was arrayed against us. And but I says if we make a big enough fuss here they'll maybe think twice about somebody else's scheme or woods or that. I would say now that attitudes have certainly hardened in Corkehill..fae what happened. Even now the golf course has been enlarged..Walter used to go on about this and I use to ignore him but they started a path, a so called right-of-way. They done the first part of it, gravelled it over a year ago and have still no finished it. Noo there starting to fence it aff, the golf course, and probably as an afterthought they'll.. (phone rings)

J Lots of folk on the scheme, folk that were there for..most of the newcomers never knew me. I would say for the likes of Walter and that they were happy to see that someone who had left the scheme had come back in its hour of need. Even if it was ultimately futile it was still valid..it was symbolic

A. In what way?

J. Showing that folk still cared despite everything else. Even though things are bleak that help can come from the strangest sources...it just fell at the right time and certainly even though it was futile we still learned a lot about communal living and stuff, fieldcraft, how to make benders and that.

A. Why that particular form of protest, why a camp?

J. Well I think you would really have to ask...certainly the local camp was like a modern day sit ins..so that you had to manually be removed from it, they would have to get involved. Im glad we set up the camp. Certainly it made you..I certainly felt that it made one with the tress almost, whereas in the past you just seen tress as a wood and stuff like that, know whit I mean. Or at night something you were frightened off, whereas now I see them as shelter. I dont know whose idea it was, certainly it was a focal point, plus it meant you were there 24 hours a day. If you were there from 8 o'clock to five you would soon be outflanked. Ultimately we were outflanked but they had to go to a lot more expense than they perhaps envisaged. Really, after a week or two you realised that it was all about costing as much money as you could and to put the cost of road up as much as you could, even while the road was getting made and the camp was away if you seen the slightest chance of, what might be seen as petty vandalism, well you did it, Especially if you're losing various possessions when your camp was smashed up.

A. You talk Joe about we and they what do mean by those terms?

J. Well I believe that anyone who worked, be it driving a minibus, was pro-road, or as a mercenary or just doing their job ..anyone who was against the road was in my group. Anybody fae . I wulnae get on a stagecoach bus cause they run along that road. They ultimately I mean Wimpey and the then Tory government and the then SRC. Thats who I would envisage as they. But their henchman I view wi just as much contempt, in fact I hud some harebrained schemes at the time, that never got off the ground. Certainly a lot of road protestors had good relationships with the guards and that, especially in the Free State. Certainly a lot of guards at Corkerhill gave us information..and eh. one or two tip offs; but at the time there was always rumours about this place is getting hit next day, or that place. There wis a lot of..there wis a few people it was just did not trust. certainly I mean looking back on the night afore Corkerhill got done there was certainly double agents involved...we actually built, a wire bridge across the river cart, the night afore we got done some local youths were throwing stones at is fae the other side, I think they were dogging school a dain it for a laugh, and when they later started going to Corkerhill camp after it hud been trashed they were made welcome by the militant boys even though they'd done that, I think that was just some rivalry between each other. We had a helicopter buzzing us during the day, there was vans roon the park, eh there was a boy came over, across the bridge, at that stage Nicky Bennett was at the camp, he became sort of leader cause he was a councillor. He was the chef as well, so this boy comes across. Best a gear, Bergahaus waterproofs everything, asked all sorts of strange questions..and then he says anybody smoke hash, we said no. he pulled oot a fag packet wi eight or nine rolled up joints, which is very very strange. That night Nicky said he woke up during the night and someone was stauning outside the caravan, they jumped up. They found oot later that day fae the cops..at got doon the next day and the whole place was fenced aff, wi the guards inside the fence. At the first attack on the Free State the guards were in the front line and the cops werna involved and folk were talking to the guards putting across their point of view, and some guards chucked it, it left them weakened and the cops couldnae show they're hand. Plus there was lots of school weans involved as well..so that time the guards were behind the fence, and the cops werna letting you near the fence, so you couldnae talk to the guards. The cops wanted to show that they were forces of order.

A. tell me how you felt that morning

J. Sickened, scunnered, totally . helpless cause you knew that there was nothing you could do. Plus Colin Macleod s girlfriend got arrested for shouting 'shame'..One of the tree fellers was out of his box on drugs, wanting to fight everybody..plus I walked roond the scheme trying to get folk involved and the just didnae want to know. I stopped this women and she said, I'm for the motorway it'll reduce the traffic on the Corkerhill road. I said it Willie effect the traffic on Corkerhill road, and you knew that you road cause the people that'll use the motorway dont use Corkerhill road, and you knew that you had folk whose parents were openly for the motorway for various stupid reasons, ..but ultimately

I knew that I felt I had truth on my side and they had a reporter there fae radio Scotland dain an interview. They interviewed me but they didnae use it, and they his people saying that protestors were in her garden throwing snowballs at her windae, That wis nonsense cause the cops shut doon everything. It was heavy handed, you couldnae do a thing.

A. Why do you think they used that strategy?

J. I reckon they overestimated the amount of protestors they would actually encounter in Corkerhill, because it was always..obviously they had this attitude and they've said to theresell well whats the potential flashpoints. We always told them Corkerhill..thats your Vietnam. if they has used a wee bit of knowledge and they wanted to give ..they had cops there fae every Strathclyde region, fae every copshop. They just went in heavy handed, they must have used a t least three mile of fences, mabye mair, cause they circled they whole woods. They had folk roond them. Just a massive massive operation. I think..well, in saying they overestimated the protestors you could have huv five thousand there and likely you wouldnae have got through. But ultimately they did get the job done. Even at a terrible cost. Tae us it was a moral victory, in the camp we hud a book The war of the Flea, and thats really what thats all about. Tae make them show their true face, tae flex their muscles and ultimately it the made the camp valid cause if the camp wisane there they wouldnae have used that force, cause the camp was their it worried them, so it made the camp successful although ultimately futile. We went to the pub that night and feelings were running high but I knew myself..

A. Again you talk of them and they, who do you mean?

J. I would ultimately say that an operation of that size must come from government sources. Ultimately they though they would hammer us and get rid of us. Already the free state had abandoned Corkerhill cause they were always more into saving trees and cause British Rail had dumped that much diesel in they woods the trees were dying in large parts. So they were worried, and that show of force was unbelievable..ultimately..obviously, who wants the road the maist, big business to move stuff aboot. If youve got a Tory government its them that are in wi the Tories and they are gonnae apply pressure to get rid of us. Corkerhill was a big stretch of woods..but see if they had used any form of ..even used common sense, see on valentines day when they had their first attack on the free state, all that was left in our camp to my knowledge was one women. So if you had sent a cop walking through there would have been nothing there, and they certainly had the resources to hit both camps at once. All they hud to dae was block off one bridge. Obviously their strategy wisane quite..and they'd hud a few mishaps before. Surely because they underestimated the tactics, or maybe giving us a false sense of security. Plus all the time..there was wan time they tried to cut doon two trees up there, they hud wan jeep full a tree cutters, and aboot 20 stewards, we were aboot 25. Then we had lookouts at they trees. It always seemed a half-hearted attempt on their behalf. We were thinking..then there was other times they tried to survey the woods, they sent up two guys, nae guards or anything, they got chased, no threatened or anything just told to get lost. So you say, is this all they've got. Then you hud the free state, and your sort of, well just let Corkerhill go and go our the free state..were saying no wed rather defend Corkerhill and the free state. Even though we never hud the bodies. After the free state fell right were leaving the M77 to concentrate on the M74. But its no started yet...Ultimately get a wee bit disheartening, certainly during that four week spell up till the free state fell, almost all the trees that they wanted oot were gone, Then it was just a case of cutting fences at night, which we were dain wan night...I would still say they were..there was some lousy characters in the camps right enough and if you lived in the woods you had to be tough and you became accustomed to the cold quickly.

A. How did you get on with the Free Sate People?

J. I got on well wi everybody because I'm no intae groups and that. I was just at Corkerhill camp but I got on well wi Jake and Colin and Jimmy and them. Wi the militant boys. I was always sort

of in the middle. I've nae ulterior motive, I've nothing to gain from it. Maybe some of them were trying to gain votes or credibility for their views. If I meet any of them nowadays we still gab away about it. Obviously when you ultimately lost the battle certain folk will blame others certain groups will blame other groups and certain strategies will get put doon. But that's just human nature..To me it was just a magical time . I might have inwardly thought we were dain thing wrang, and now I dae think we did things wrang, but they were no malicious, they were all well meaning. Just..I dont think in my life I'll ever experience anything like that ever again and certainly if I go doon south and I meet folk they say Joe was involved in the M77 protest, they always like to talk about it. It was a magical time.

A. Do you thinking you were fighting for the same thing?

J. well..see the folk fae Pollok always hud mare sympathy with the PFS, cause that was the woods they knew. The folk fae Corkerhill had mair sympathy wi us, ultimately everybody had the same objectives but maybe different reasons..like militant says if they were cutting doon the trees for a leisure centre for the unemployed we'd have no objection, whereas I would have said, there is plenty of disused factory sights you can use. If you says that to Colin there would have been war. certainly folk were there for political ends, but ultimately every was in it for the same reasons just different reasons. Know whit I mean? Colin I think wanted to save they woods. I worked wi Colin years ago and he was completely different fae whit he is now..hes always hud hunners a energy. Colin was for they woods and a different lifestyle. I was for to stop that road, to maintain access to Pollok park and anything which opposed that I was against, be it Hagg's Castle Golf Course SRC, the government or anything else. As it went on I could appreciate a lot of the militants views and the views of the free state, cause living in they woods did seem to be a very attractive lifestyle. Sitting rood the fire and playing music and that, it was good. We were certainly, towards the end they were wanting to set up land funds and that which all seems very tempting. But that's no for everyone and few folk could think of that let alone dae it. and once old age sets in major problems arise. So it might seem an attractive way of life but its no for everyone.

A. Do you think it has changed you?

J. Certainly..as regards traffic noo. I think..fae being primarily concerned wi maintaining a right of way I'm now very traffic conscious. I see the traffic lights and that. I think whit is Glasgow city council dain to encourage public transport and have to say zilch. Absolutely nothing. They are putting all these traffic lights everywhere. They builds ASDA on Helen St, Paisley road west at Jura St if you go doon there there is a few factories then a fire break. The road is blocked off. They've got this red light there that goes off all the time. It must only be to relieve congestion at ASDA but there is tailbacks up to half a mile..there never used to be jams there. They fumes are really bad. Folk live there. I just think weans and old folk wi breathing problems are in trouble. Its criminal to put the profits of a multimillion pound chain store in front of old folk and young childrens health.

J. Walter has often said and I dont doubt it, that Hardridge road wi its dampness, oor house was damp, has a far higher than average asthma in the weans. To build a motorway in an area which is already has astronomical levels of asthma is ..Had then been in the USA the law suits would have piled up. Cause..when I was in primary school I jumped about wi this boy who had asthma, and then it was almost unknown, he's since died, and nowadays its that common, its almost the norm noo. It seems to me that the traffic..even oor the last five years..its just unbelievable. Plus I run hame fae work to my maws maist night to walk the dug, and Ive got tae cross Dumbreck road..noo you can get the motorway from the M8 to the M77, that road is chock ablock, motorways just attract traffic. All the arguments of folk saying it'll be less motors..this women in work said to me Joe see that Shawlands the traffic is horrendous. I said right is Paisley road west busy? She said Aye. I said well whit runs directly alongside it the M8. so were does the traffic go, do you build another road? If I had my way I would ban all private cars in the city.

There is nae reason to own a car in a city. Glasgow should have an underground going everywhere, it should have a far better bus service to all areas. If you live in an outlying scheme tough luck. It shouldnae be that way. Whats to stop them building undergrounds. Certainly I've become a lot mair aware of that, even though I used to go up your hillwalking and that. I became a lot more aware of nature and that noo, of trees and the effect they have on the environment. I would see the two root causes of it are private land ownership and money. Its greed really, so that folk can make money and I just cannae see any future for the planet, unless there is radical change in attitudes. I think were too much into Thatcher and I'm alright Jack.

A. Do you think concern that has developed through your experiences?

J. I've always felt this but my experiences huv honed it more. I've gained a greater insight into on to it. I've had a hands on experience so now I can relate to things. Certainly I would say that it has left some very deep deep views in my consciousness. I'm just glad that things culminated the way they did and I could take part in the protest. Cause if I hudnae I would have regretted no doing anything.

A. Do you vote?

J Aye

A. Who do you vote for if you dont mind me asking?

J. IN local ones I vote Scottish Militant Labour, in fact even in the election there I vote SML. But I wouldnae have vote Labour cause I'm a nationalist. I used to vote SNP, but as long..a always see myself as being left wing. Power corrupts and probably done a great deal. I would vote them but I would say there disorganised...I vote SML cause they were the only wans involved in the M&7 but ultimately having been involved in the poll tax campaign and that. I knew some of them fae school and that. Militant noo I support them, but best of a bad lot I would say .

A. Alright Joe, thanks very much.

(END)

Interview 4: Lilly and Ralph Harkins

Location: 201 Corkerhill Place

A. if you could just tell me a little bit about yourself first Mrs Harkins

L. I've stayed on this side of the community for 20 years, 14 years in this house. I'm a disabled person and have been nearly all my days. Recently I'm practically confined to a wheelchair. Both my husband and I are registered disabled, my husbands deaf. The reason were here is cause we got beat up in our last house, both of us. I was hospital for quite some time and Ralph never worked again from he was 58 years old.

When we came here I was involved in peoples disabilities. I joined a forum called the GMCC, which is for disabled people. I was the secretary and treasurer for some time. Unfortunately the GMCC had to be given up. The community council hall was no a place for it because there was no toilets. I was elected in to the CC here nearly 7 years ago. When I joined I was interested in the M77 road which was being built, so I was approached by Walter to see how I felt, cause I'm asthmatic and suffer from bronchial asthma. I got very interested in it. Walter asked a few people if they would go to the public inquiry. There was about 11 lawyers there. One of them asked me what did I think of the M77. I replied that it was not going to do us any good whatsoever, it was going to cause an awful lot of children and people in Corkerhill who suffer from asthma in a terrible state. Cause we had the trees, which provide a lot of oxygen for people like us. The lawyer then said, what if we build you a bridge. I said there will still be 40 000 vehicles going past my door which I object to. They then suggested building an underpass. But that would be worse cause people would come and stay in it. So it was thrown out of court. There was another lady whose son suffered from asthma, she gave a statement as well. Walter said stuff, and they put it back.

Since then, as you know the road has gone ahead. Now even before the road went ahead one morning we had a right hassle from the police, about 5 in the morning. I phoned the papers at the time. Telling them that we had been invaded, which we were by the police, who arrested that young man and women at the caravan. That was a disgrace, they protestors are not only protesting for themselves, cause they came here from all different ends of the earth to protest here against them taking down our trees. Unfortunately the road went ahead.

A. You went to the PI, what was the big issue?

L. Noise, pollution, because its terrible. Health reasons. I was one of the people that sat at the camp. I'm totally against it. And the fact that this is just a wee community, there's only two streets, and the people here are either very young or very old. Never have I seen so many deaths in all my life than here. I can tell you, I've been in hospital three times in the last year. They're a liar if they say that road dosnae cause anybody heartache. I cant sleep at night, I was on Temazepam until they took me off them for health reasons. I cant get sleeping, I cant open my windows and its no just me I'm talking about most of the people round here. They say that it doesnae effect you cause the motors go all the time, that is a load of rubbish. Cause its pollution that's causing this place to go downhill. Nobody will take houses across that road. The roads the reason why. Imagine building a childrens playground right next to the motorway, com on! I think that's ridiculous. We've also got children being arrested in the park.

A. How and Why did you get involved in this Lilly?

L. I got involved. I think I did a bit of good, I've had places ramped. Done that myself. This is the reason I got involved, surely somebody, I feel that if you put something into it you might get something back, you cannae just let others get on wi it. No matter how small, to try and go places. I'm involved with the CC, that's were I learned. I learned that this community is going downhill. That's the reason why.

A. What did you do to protest?

R. We done a lot of protesting, the security guards came up in the morning, hunners eh them

L. What we did was, they went wi banners into the city chambers. To protest about the M77. Stand out in the rain and snow to prove to them that it would effect our lives terribly. That day the security guards came in..I was shocked, totally shocked, I heard the rumpus outside and went outside, and it was freezing. I phoned the papers and within about 20 minutes they we here and they televised me here. I was devastated. I couldnae believe that 200 police could come in like that to a small community of 2 streets. There couldn't have been any other crime in the city that day. It took 200 hundred police to arrest 2 people, one pregnant.

A. Why do you think they did that?

L. Because they thought they could come up and go up that hill, we used to have beautiful oak trees. By the time I got through to the camp they came up and the police were holding them back. One councillor came up and he told the people of Corkerhill, this is your place, you've got access, so we all made for the trees, at that time I was in tears. When I thought about how it would effect this community, with no access to the park. We've had no compensation, no nothing. They were talking about giving us help but we've had nothing.

A. Would you have been happier Mrs Harkins if the road had taken another route?

L. Oh yes, there was no need for them to take that road in that way, no need. They could have taken it across the golf course. It would have made more sense to. It would have left the trees. But that would have meant a lot of money and the golf course objected to it cause they didn't want a motorway through there. In my estimation they must have got a lot of money, the golf course, because if they were..ok its quite a famous golf course. We were supposed to be..Sir John Maxwell said Corkerhill would always have access to the park. The children here and the community used to go through there and have picnics, they've taken that away cause we don't have access. You cannae get out, your suffocating, claustrophobic. If that had happened in 1987 we wouldnae be here, its given us 8 years of life. But it wont do todays children any good. That's what I feel.

A. Who are 'they'?

L. Well it was the council. They said they would give jobs. It gave them jobs building it. It takes 7 minutes of the journey, all these people have to suffer because of 7 minutes. Because they're suffocating!

R. It's a constant noise all the time, there isnae any break. I'm deaf so I cannae hear. Just continuous. I cannae understand why there has been so many accidents. Anyway it shouldnae have been built in the first place, people have bad chests, asthma, all that. Now they'll suffer more and their children will suffer. They realise now it shouldnae be there. The only winners out eh it is, no the motorists at a certain point the traffic stops so I cannae see what the good is. The winners is the gold course, they're the only winners, they've got an extra bit of land now and they've taken it offay us, off Corkerhill. I don't see why they should have got it. There was money attached to it.

L. I used to look out the window and could see the fields and trees. What a difference. We walked through there all the time

R. We've been over the bridge but ye cannae, the golf course people chase you away. We were stopped by the golf course who said we'd no access, they said we couldnae come through.

A. How did you get the rest of the community involved?

L. I wanted to help the community, then I heard about this. So I stood for the community council and opposed the road. I wrote to a lot of people, I realised that there was more to it and ye cannae just sit in the house, that's why I joined. I felt that if you were doing something for somebody, for the community that would be good, we don't get paid. I felt that the children listened.

A. But how did you overcome apathy?

L. I took a college course, and I found out then that there were different communities involved. I was able to pick it up and read about it, things like that. I felt there was something for me to do. We held meetings in the hall, and we found out stuff. The main source was the community council. We went wi Walter to meetings. Ralph displayed a lot of the banners, we went to protests.

R. Aye, protested a lot.

L. We held meetings and did leaflets and got people to come and look at it. We had a meeting every so often.

R. To inform people of what was going on. Its amazing how people talk about this and talk about that but trying to get them to come to a meeting, its hard. So you talk to them in the street, or go to their house. Its all done mouth to mouth outside. The ones really involved, the community council, then again its always the same. They came here in a big body, there was lots of people here sometimes. It reminded me of the war, wi all these guys wi their yellow jackets on. I could picture them wi rifles. It was disgraceful, more or less an invasion. They were lined up as far as the eye could see. There was no way you could get by, so many of them.

L. David Spaven came that morning, he took me back home. I was devastated, it was a disgrace.

R. And its all for nothing as far as I'm concerned except for a few motorists who travel a few miles.

A. What should they have done instead of building that road?

R. Forget about it

L. If they wanted better roads they should have upgraded the roads already there. That would have given some people work, they said the trees needed to come down cause they were rotted. That's a load of crap.

A. Did you spend any time down at the camp?

L. Yes..

R. Yes we were there. I thought it was..it took a big heart for these people to remain there in all sorts of weather. We brought them here, gave them coffee, tea and all that.

L. From Australia, America, England..

R. They done a marvellous job and these bampot councillors calling them this and calling them that, they were only fighting for one thing, the earth, they're no hangers on or anything.

L. They didnae want anything of us, I'm no the only wan they came to..Colin was exceptionally good.

R. Colin started it all by sitting up that tree for days..

L. To think those people were over there and they build houses, to think that out of one lad climbing a tree in the Barrhead road and then they built a community, cause that's what they did. Your no gonnae tell me that they were daft, they were very intelligent, and yet people were saying they were tramps.

A. Do you think they were fighting for the same things as you?

L. Yes..

R. Yeah, they were young, they wanted to do it, if I'd been younger I'd have stayed wi them, pity it was all in vain.

L. Aye they were fighting for people to live, they knew the more pollution the more deaths there would be, the camp changed my attitude to health and environments. I saw through they people, the way they were speaking, cause they had experienced it in England. So I think we learned from them about the environment and the effects of roads.

R. We didnae really know about the pollution side or whatever, it didnae dawn on us, we just didnae want them to take away a big chunk ah Corkehill, which is only a wee place. And they golfers got the benefit, they cut the road in towards Corkehill instead of going through the golf course which they should have. But its money and folk wi clout over there. So we will suffer. We learned alright, it was all figured out, backhanders and the like, nae problem.

L. Its made us more environmentally aware.

R. Its amazing how people can be so dim sometimes, we've lost all the birds, but we still get foxes, there's no squirrels any more. You don't hear the birds singing anymore. They've gone. They've killed what we had and the wildlife. Them that's decided, Labour councillors, that's who did it. They know now its wrong. It was all backhanders. That stupid Charlie Gordon.

L. I've never voted Labour. I still vote, but not Labour. They could have stopped it.

A. Do you feel let down?

R. We're being crucified and there's nothing we can do. We'll have to stay shut in. There is no way out of here.

L. The whole community will be closed in, it feels claustrophobic. Its enclosure, think of all the people who have to go all that way to one shop.

R. There's absolutely nothing here, nothing at all.

L. I think everybody's let us down, the council, the men at the top, those that decided they needed the road for to take 7 minutes off the journey. They didnae want to build it for the people, it was for business.

R. Five points were made at the public inquiry, and they'll come true.

L. Why do we need all these roads?

R. We're losers all round. Losers. Somebody wins, people will gain out of it, but no Corkerhill.

A. Thanks very much, I think we'll end it there.

Interview 5: Walter Morrison: 195 Corkerhill Road, March 1996

Andy. Walter, thanks very much for taking the time to talk to me. Perhaps we could begin by telling me about the history of the M77. When did you first become aware of it.

Walter. A document was put out by the then Glasgow corporation, a form of consultation document and we went to a school somewhere round about Shawlands and we were given the details of the plans of the Ayr Road route..As soon as I heard that I started investigating...At that time it was the Community Association, we wanted it to be all the residents included.

About 5 or 6 of us went over. After that we started to look at the thing a bit closer and get as much information as we could. Then what happened round about 1970, the Hags Castle golf course started work on ploughing up what we considered was a right of way from Corkerhill to Pollok Park, that was the issue that we started to hang our hat on, here is an issue here is something we can argue about. We then started to look into the law regarding land usage in order to try and protect our right-of way and use that as the lynchpin for the rest of the arguments we had and demonstrations.

We protested against that. We had a number of very active protests, one was ..where on a Saturday they were having an international golf tournament, and we marked the course with signs saying this is a right of way. The press were called in and done quite a big story on it, our whole idea was to try and get the message across that this was a right-of-way and they were going to have a dispute about it. Then I think The Times came down to Corkerhill and started to pursue the case. Bear in mind that the golf course had doubled its size because the right-of-way was the boundary line of the old golf course. The golf course ploughed up our right-of-way but we were only learning that this was allpart of compensation to the golf club because they were losing land to allow the M77 to be built. We didn't know about this at the time.

A. So the initial issue that the community moved on was an issue surrounding the right-of-way, it wasn't necessarily about fears regarding the motorway?

W. Well what I would have to say is that up front the right of way was the argument, but the health fears definitely because we felt, we called that (Pollok Park) Corkerhill's lung. It was our breathing space and by taking away the right-of-way and denying us this they were taking away Corkerhill's lung. Every time they tried to stop us we always had a demonstration and walked across it. So by mutual consent we learned to live with each other.

62 A How did you go about organising these protests?

What we done initially, we tried to keep it tight, the people of Corkerhill, and anytime we had that type of protest we involved the community itself, and the community council..at that stage we begin to feel that we are going to have to get this message outside because there is more to it than we first realise, it wasnae just a matter of Corkerhill is losing this amenity its going to effect the health of the children..wait a minute there is a wider issue in this and that is the 1939 Maxwell Family Agreement. I joined an organisation and eventually it became Glasgow for People..I'm a founder member of GfP. So in an organised way we started to get the message out to more people.

A. How did you then let the rest of community know what was happening?

W. By about 1975 the whole idea of community councils was starting to evolve and by that time we were becoming more knowledgeable about the laws of the land..and we started to look closely at all the documentation because an important issue in any dispute is how the planners reach the conclusion that they are going to go ahead. So what I done ..we got a hold of the local plan and....later on after the right-of-way has been demolished we then found out that 85000

pounds was given by the old corporation to Haggs Castle to extend their golf course, all at public expense, and when we checked we found that there was no application made for planning permission by the golf course. So we started to push that...I have always tried to avoid allegations of conspiracy discovered that the main man operating as the legal advisor to Haggs Castle golf course was Cllr Ian Dyer, the Tory leader of the planning committee. He is a clever guy and the main legal advisor to the club.

W. Its a slight aside..we had a demonstration at the National Trust for Scotland asking them why they allowed the land to be sold in 1972 in order to promote the road, and only gave their waiver 2 years after. They said we could have done nothing else we were left with absolutely no option, you'll realise that the NT for Scotland was founded by Sir John Maxwell and there was no way we could hold back from giving the waiver because the Maxwell family now were strapped for cash and were trying to diversify. They were unable to carry out the husbandry needed to the woodlands, so it was in their interest to sell off parts of the land and make it the responsibility of the local authority and everything that would be done at public expense would work out to their benefit. So now they are getting three times the rent from the golf course as they were before. Corkerhill still comes within the curtilage of Pollok House and the only reason Corkerhill is now excluded from that is the M77 which forms a new boundary, they have kept the largest part of their estate in one piece and diversified at public cost.

W. Anyway back to what we were doing..we started to educate ourselves. What we done once we seen that there was need for bringing in the people of Glasgow..

A Sorry Walter but what did you do to bring in the people of Corkerhill?

W. Door to door surveys, got a loudhailer and went round the streets, we set up our own objections box in the shop and everybody in Corkerhill was allowed to down and sign objections to the M77..bear in mind that we are dealing now with A) the local plan and we learned that we were allowed to be consulted and to make our protest so anytime we seen any plan or anything we called the community out set up a place in the shop we all the plans so that everybody could see them. We set up two boxes , the official objection box and the other one that we did, and we got 803 individual letters of objection and bear in mind that Corkerhill's only got a voting population of 900-1000.

We had meetings in this community at that time wi almost 300 turning up at every meeting. Most people about the road. Bear in mind that there is nowhere else in Corkerhill you can go in summertime apart from the park. That has been conceded in the public inquiry minutes.If I can put it his way, I don't think there was one stone left unturned in order to let everybody know what was happening, that means the community. And I'm sure we would never have got as far as we got, even to the extent of the public inquiry conceding our case..but in the end we had to be sacrificed for the greater good.

I can assure you that the work we done in this community was so successful that we never had any reason to doubt it. No matter who came in and questioned our community they would get that objection.

(by this point Betty Campbell, the Community Council has come in)

A. How important do you feel the community council was in all this?

W. That's a good question...what I would say is that disorganised communities can find it awfully difficult. And sometimes it takes a smaller body of people to say here's what its all about. Because in the main, and its sad to say, and I don't think its apathy, its lack off....you've been disillusioned and battered doon so much in their lives that everything just seems like a mountain to climb. You cannae win. What we were able to do was argue that there was a possibility that

we could win. The sad thing about is, and bear in mind how long we held that motorway up, it was supposed to be built in the early 80s and because of us and because of arguments we were putting forward we held it up for a very long time. One of the arguments, and its still an argument now..funding is a big thing and if you can effect the funding certain things become prohibitive. So we done a lot in holding that motorway up. The sad thing is having marched the people up to the top of the hill, marched them down again every time..it got to the stage that the people of Corkerhill got to the stage that they didn't know if they were coming or going..Complacency set into Corkerhill. When it came to what I would consider the real action that we might have taken in Corkerhill if we had the level of commitment we had back in they days then I suggest that they would have had some difficulty trying to cut they trees down in Corkerhill. Bear in mind that sometimes you cannae shape events and I believe that if we had a weakness it was because we stopped it so many times and held it up.

A. Do you think you were a victim of your own success?

w. Thats correct.

A. How did you keep that groundswell of opinion going?

W. What we done was, Betty sat outside the shop, we believe in referenda in Corkerhill, there is not an issue, a controversial issue, that we wouldnae do that, you couldnae survive in a small community if you just took decisions of the top of your head. You meet everybody in the street. So we always gave everyone a chance in writing, individually.

Betty. We sat at the shop and got them there, and the addresses we didn'y have we were able to go to, that what we would do in most cases? I dont think there was very many that didnae know about it.

W. Its a small community, I could shout at that end and everybody in Corkerhill would know at night. ..So it is great to be able to go along and I'll produce the bundles of documents. I wouldn't survive if I didn't have the support of the community. at every turn we have tried to involve as many of the community as possible in any decisions. There is absolutely no way you can go to the outside world without that...So to that extent you had to have your community behind you. Anyway that is how we got our community involved, almost on an everyday basis..mountains of leaflets, things in the shop window..anytime someone came out of the shop, hitting them from every angle..public meetings.

Corkerhill was a classic case of a small community be imposed on by big brother. In terms of public transport you couldn't get a better argument than running down a railway line in order to promote a motorway. Now in its centenary year they are running down that railway to build motorways. I did my best to expose, but one of the problems is that we are a small marginalised community, about 800 or 900 votes. Corkerhill is a side issue. Anyway we actually done our best, once we had got our community involved getting the message across to others. Because I believe that's the good politics of it, once you've got your own community solid you have to extend the political argument of it and try and bring in the outside world who will see what it is.

Slowly but surely briefing the people. Bruce Milan was our member of parliament and Bruce Milan was Secretary of State for Scotland. When I went to see him he told us he supported us but he couldn't make public statements. The sad thing is Bruce Milan moved on.

We're talking about the late 70s now. Cause he was involved in the right-of-way argument. But that period...see what we've always argued about Corkerhill is that it has been marginalised, it has been stuck on. It is a community that has been shunted from Pollokshields, when it had a Tory MP. Then it was Pollok, hen Corkerhill became part of Craigton and then later it became part of Govan. So it was once in a Tory area, then Labour, we're stuck on to each of these

constituencies, we have always been poorly represented at the councillor level cause it is such a small community. So you can appreciate when we were only stuck on we were never really properly politically represented.

Bear in mind that when local authorities do their surveys and produce statistics we are the poor relations, we are recognised as a deprived community. Mosspark is a desirable area, if you have an overall statistic we get lost in that.

A. So you feel that you get lost because of the size of the community and the lack of political representation?

W. Bear in mind a lot of the arguments in Corkehill are relative to the risks that people are put at not only from poverty, unemployment, damp houses and that, so we get ourselves involved in the health and safety of the community and produce very well thought out documents to anybody. Start with the city council, then the Scottish Office, in this general move about health and safety. Because of this we attracted the World Health Organisation..of course at the same time, in general terms public transport comes a big issue what with deregulation. We relegated the right-of-way because of this, but if all these things are happening in terms of health, the only place for recreation is over there (the park). It is relegated in that it is not the big issue. We bring in the issue of the road. Corkehill has actually got a worse public transport service now than it did fifty years ago, having said that come the new regulations SRC cut back the railway line.

Anyway, we now have a worse service than fifty years ago and despite all the benefits accruing to certain people from the M77, the M77 has done nothing for us, there is no even a road that leads into Corkehill. There is absolutely nothing in that respect so we havnae gained anything. Bear in mind at this stage were moving towards the public inquiry.

A. Yeah, planning permission was applied for and refused in 1985 wasn't it?

W. It would be them to come up with evidence to prove us wrong and we would be criticised for putting peoples lives in danger. Just to let you see.

A. Can we go back to the mid-80s. At this stage was Corkehill still standing on its own?

W. No, we had another organisation, fairly effective, from Darnley, called the ADC, we were involved in it and collectively we all went up at that stage were the City or the new District Council were considering the Ayr road plans and we had a demonstration between us we had in the region of 3000 signatures. They reckon it was the highest ever protest against the motorway or any enquiry in Scotland. And it was so overwhelming that the City Council had little option but to go against it (the M77)..As members of the Community Council we were able to go up and sit with what they called the are management committee and present our case and they took the decision to oppose the road and it was really they that leaned on all the planning committees and then the full council. So we were actually dealing a good political move that brought, in a nice way, the whole Council, cause its rarely you'll get the full Council opposing something that has been passed by the are involved.

I've got the City Councils objections to the M77, the precognition of the planning committee statement, so now at this stage it puts the councillors in a difficult position, because they are saying that the new council supports it and some old Regional councillors who supported it are now City councillors. Anyway that's how we done it, we started off from the grass roots, getting our community committed by spreading the message, leaning on the politicians in order to get the city council, we worked on that ground. So we got out community in a show of solidarity to involve the politicians, and then gelling with them to make a further consolidation, working all the time towards the decision of the City council in terms of being able to present a united and collective protest. That is how we were successful, in terms of winning the fight about the road.

We maybe didn't win that but the message has still been left behind. A lot of people are beginning to see that building more and more roads doesn't solve the problem, more cars will come on the roads. There is now a political base in the way that we have done it. It was only a short step to the next stage, once the City had declared their opposition to mounting a campaign that was going to bring people into the public inquiry and consolidate again. And that's how I became involved in starting up Glasgow for People.

So bear in mind that we already had the local interest and local opposition, we were now starting to move out and I would suggest that that's what brought the camp here.

A. Who made submissions to the Public Inquiry?

I was involved with the Railway Development Society, I was going out and arguing our case and finding kindred spirits, so other organisations were involved. In many ways, in terms of the scientific and technical side of it I know a lot less than them, but I was able to them about the grass-roots support. A lot of these organisations were a wee bit more middle-class than us, but ye cannae win fights without the middle-class. If ye cannae get the upper echelons to come down and see what your on about.

We should, and we did, organise from the grass-roots so that we have got the ordinary punter on the ground. Now the sad thin about the ordinary punter is its hard to hold him. You know if Rangers are playing Celtic and I'm saying 'Come on we need to do this', you've nae chance. So I've got to say theres times, a climate of opinion, that if we had been able to fight the fight when we were all enthusiastic the ball game might have been a different one. But they (government) play for time and they can do that and get on wi their business. So the way I feel is that you organise yur community and then try and portray and then demonstrate how enthusiastic they are to other people and say there is a link up needed here. So you strengthen the whole basis of it, and I think that is the only way society will take any notice of you..So when you've got a system that is geared ina different way from what you are trying to do, and if they think in general terms that you have to go there then what can you do?

A. How did you approach the Public Inquiry?

W. Right.. I took the view from the beginning that there was absolutley no way that we as a acommunity, wae no having two pennies to rub together were going to be able to challenge the big guns of the system, councillors and all the rest of them. And I was hopeful that Glasgow District Council, as the principal objectors, would be clever enough and fight hard to win. So the only way I can go along with that, and I said it, I said, 'Mr Chairman, there is no way I'm gonnae come here and try to be clever, there is no way I can compete with these people. I'm coming here just to tell you that while they have said in their application that there will be benefits to this and that, I'm coming to say that that it is not so, that that wont happen'. In no other way. Now at the end of the day, we showed two films, one was the general condition of Corckerhill, its poverty, housing and unemployment, and then one on the green belt in terms of its green belt. Now they started to watch them, they last about ten minutes and I can assure you, for at least a couple of minutes after the film had finished, complete silence, not anybody spoke to anybody at all. Queens councillors, all sat looking at one another, the recorder fae the Scottish office got up on the platform and said 'How do I follow that?', and it took the QC for the promotors to give himself a shake and get in to it. To discredit it, to go on about the greater good, so I knew from there on in that there was no way our case was goonae be pushed aside, be not proven. When I went outside, when it was all finished, Mr Housing(??) asked to speak to me, he said 'can I shake your hand, you put up a commendable fight for your community. But I must tell you, this road will go ahead. ' He was the representattive of the Scottish office there, 'This road will go ahead" And from that day on I knew that the road was going ahead, and as soon as I heard that I started investigating the sort of monies, I went immediately to the City Council, I pleaded with them, said please, So I went to them and told them that the money was not enough, and it was doubled.

Please believe me, naebody will ever believe me. It was doubled, we got 600000 pounds for landscaping and the childrens play area. I don't think some of they areas have fought hard enough for their communities, for example, the City Council. Why should they leave it to the tenants to fight for compensation for the houses they (the Council) own. Should it not be them doing the same as the private home owners, because their properties are being devalued.

A. So the PI wasn't successful and you knew the road was going to be built so you changed emphasis, you started fighting for compensation. There's been three changes, first of all the right-of-way, then health and after the PI compensation. So post-PI how are you keeping the community involved?

W. We are trying to get as much support as we could from the community, to get the people involved we had to impress on the people that they should be complaining and that because of the M77 they were losing and one of the big disbenefits to the community would be the M77. So if there was ever any money at all that was gonnae be given we had to show the loss we had..so from that point of view we were getting the community into the mode of mind that if there was a chance of exploiting their poverty then the M77 was central to this.

Again, leaflets round the doors, sitting outside the shop and public meetings. I then begin to learn about overhead slides and all that, I called in experts and we had exhibitions. If there is any monies going we might benefit. And because of that some people were beginning to see the need for saying Corkerhill is deprived..if there is money to be spent please gonnae give us some of it.

A. so after the PI the Community Council is holding public meetings, petitions, running the stall, all that?

W. Yes, and at the same time, bearing in mind the PI, the space from 1989 to 1992, the M77 is on its off its on again. My big argument at that time was if the road was ever gonnae be stopped there was two ways, that was lack of funding and a political change of heart. Now bear in mind that we, the community, had accepted limiting the damages, but during that course of time I had meetings with Malcolm Waugh who was involved in that stage, and every time I met him he would say the roads held up, its no going ahead. I felt he was weakening. I've went through Parnell, Reid, Waugh and Gordon, every one of them had been weakened down. A lot of these guys maybe didn't want to do this. At the same time I'm saying that I've accepted in my mind that the road is going ahead and the only way were gonnae get anything is some form of limited damages, but here is possibilities, here is something that could happen, no matter how remote. I've always argued that if the road was gonnae be stopped it would be because it would be prohibitive in costs. Now bear in mind there was nae love lost between the Scottish Office and SRC and I was always saying that the best thing we could do is push SRC into aposition were monies have got to be spent, and my hope always was..., all you had to do was the change the minds of guys who I thought of as friends. What I'm trying to say to you right, in a period from 89 to 95, I was meeting them all the time, every on of them, they were my friends, all they needed to do was get up one morning from their beds and say we don't want it. That is what my hopes were.

But more pressure was put on them. So I every time I went to the community I was able to say that's it held up for another 18 months. And they were beginning to say ach its never gonnae get built Walter. Walter remember you came to us in 1969 shouting the odds about this, they'll never build it. So the community's becoming complacent. Anyway I'm saying there is still a possibility we could win here, every time monies appear to be slacking there was arm twisting. So I'm gonnae jump a wee bit now to come on to the Colin's of this world. You see it was during that particular time Colin came along here and he had been caught up in the slow gradual build up of spreading the word.

A. You mean Colin McLeod?

W. Yeah, he stayed in Pollok somewhere, from Pollok as a wee boy, he was a freelance ecologist, an arborist or something. Very interested in nature. Anyway it was about 1993, Colin came up here and said to me..oh his idea were great. I'm sitting watching him, and bear in mind I thought the road was gonnae get built but he was so enthusiastic, so charming. I said wait a minute the moulds not broken thers still people out there who can fight and are prepared to. And I've always felt that what would really be needed was a form a civil disobedience in order to focus attention of the nation on our problems. And Colin. It was as if he'd just been planted there..here comes a man that can do that. Colin says to me 'man this road is gonnae be stopped, you've had your chance Walter, wi Public Inquiries and all that, were gonnae stop this road'. There was nae way I was gonnae argue wi someone wi that determination. That's what you need. No matter how knowledgeable you are, when someone is as determined as that then you've got to say how can this be utilised to help the next stage of the contest. And bearing in mind we are now beginning to talk about the trees, their worth, we're beginning to talk about the environment, about roads, about pollution, car reduction, speed reduction. All of these things seemed to falling into place in a kind of scientific way, or as part of a learning process. This is a jigsaw that is all starting to come together.

Colin said to me, would you be against us doing such and such? No way Colin, I like your enthusiasm, pleased to see it. But one thing, I'm gonnae give you a warning. Yes be determined, yes stick by your guns, but always leave yourself an escape route. Cause if you don't succeed your gonnae feel badly hurt. So betty took them up to the farm, the whole intention was setting up a camp at the farm but that didnae happen so there was no other thing to do but to go to the Barrhead road. Now it started to put Corkerhill into a bit of difficulty, the whole thing was, we started to bring people in who were long-term environmentalists, and the focus of the thing was, we were more parochial in our community attitude, was the threat to those woods and involved in that was Pollok park..we couldnae, for the sake of unity start demanding that they notice Corkerhill's problems against the overall protection of the environment of Pollok park, we couldnae, beacause we were saying, if the motorways to go ahead why not straight across the golf course, now that would have been totally alien to the people in the camp, but bear in mind that ours was the stronger argument. Because if they had even given consideration to the motorway going over the golf course then we would have had the golf course on our side.

A. Would you have accepted it if SRC said they would build it across the golf course?

W. What we were suggesting was, if the roads got to go ahead..why not cut and cover, meaning why not do something revolutionary. We want to protect the environment, particularly Pollok estate, what we will do is build the road under the golf course. Despite the talk ..we think small we dont think big. We probably would have gone along wi that cause bear in mind at that time our opposition at that stage wasnae necessarily against roads, our argument was that a community was getting sacrificed for the road and to please other people."

A. So the Pollok free state is set up, how did the rest of the community of Corkerhill respond to that?

W. Very good, Bettys boy was one of the first to be arrested, and the people of Corkerhill supported them. The kids in Corkerhill were involved from the word go. The kids in Corkerhill had had clean-up campaigns every year and they would say Walter why are we cleaning it, look at the men cutting the trees down. The kids knew what was happening and were getting angry. The woods was their play place, kids that know about the woodlands. The main school involved, The Bellarmine, they kids have won environmenatl trophies every year for protecting the environment. The kids were educated about the environment. Their actions, it was just a

continuation of what they did at school, Tommy Sheridan and them were criticised, a lot of it was untrue.

A. What were you doing within the community, you said before that it was difficult to keep people motivated and it looked dead and buried, then along comes the Free State.

W. bear in mind the size of the community, it a small community. Betty and I sat outside that shop every day for months wi big banners that said Children of Corkerhill sacrificed for M77. We sat outside wi our documents and I ran slide shows. There was never any chance during that time that anybody lost sight of the campaign or the camp. The camp became a place for individuals in Corkerhill to go to, almost a therapy for some people..there was always that.

A. Also at this time the strategy appears to change again because STARR had been established.

W. STARR..happened as a result of the camp. It became a focus and people started to come from all walks of life and all organisations. And of course the arguments for the environment were heightened even at national level, what wi Twyford Down and all that and people from around the world got brought in. So what happened, bear in mind we're talking about diverse opinions here. Glasgow for People, fairly middle of the road, conservative, use arguments, direct action if need be but stop and strike up relationships with politicians. Earth First, different attitude, eco-warriors, got to use civil disobedience even to the xtent of sabotage. The at the other end organisations like FoE, right wing but not in a conservative way, The Scottish Wildlife Trust, middle of the road, nice people. And a community council who wether they like it or not are not necessarily operating as a pressure group outside the local authority. So I've got to pull them all together, how do you keep them all going. I think I played a big part in that cause my finger was in every camp. And I used to plead, manys a time I used to think world war three was gonnae break out cause somebody did something. And I used to say look we've got a common ground here lets us learn to turn a blind eye as long as its no really violent, gonnae allow me to condemn ye. So each of us learnt that lesson. I've never seen such diverse organisations moving in the same direction. Anyway we were able to do that for quite a long period but slowly but surely that started to break up because certain things happen that was losing ground. I always felt it wis no very clever for an organisation leading the fight, for all the leaders to get the jail at once.

A. But also at this time Walter, David Spaven is asked to come in and it looks like another change of strategy.

W. I appreciate what you saying but It is no necessarily the campaign that is changing, it is our community. Sometimes we've got to submerge werselves in a lot of the things .It went beyond a community concern and became an environmental concern We went along with it because in general terms we(the CC) were getting involved in environ issues and particularly. We actually were starting to work, in some ways at a higher level than some of the rest of them, the Rio summit, we became involved because of Local Agenda 21. . I'm the environmental spokesamn for Glasgow on the group in the city council. Through my experiences here I'm calling for an environmental ombudsman, because we have learned that there is no-one we can trust. So over and above everything else we have learned that there is a higher level and you learn as you go along..the parochial thing is a miniscule part of all that and if you cannae change higher up you've little chance.

Its been a learning process, everything that has happened, bearing in mind when we start the fight about the right of way that was our first consideration, the first thing we think about. And then the question of course is whats causing it, it's a motorway. There will be 53 000 motors a day along it, how is that gonnae effect us. The community at that stage wernaie thinking about Rio or the environment, sometimes people in out situation, the last thing they think about is the trees in Brazil or the rainforest and stuff, so each time we were going along (to the camp) we

were becoming educated. We begin to learn about the environment in general, we learn that whether a thing happened in Timbuktoo or timbukthree the chances are we would suffer along with it. When we're talking about our immediate plight we wernae really giving too much thought to Tom, Dick or Harry outside. And as I say its educational. You learn that people are gonnae benefit. So you start weighing these up and learning more. You begin to see your position in it.

How best can you utilise this vast amount of people. As the leader of a local community I need to decide the best way to help them. Youve got to tell yir people..You cannae live in isolation youve got to go outside the world rather than looking in on yourselves as a community cos all yi dae in yir ain community is fight wi one another. So that was my job..Ive explained that the reason we have got to do what we ae doing is because the only way we are going to get the feedback or the payback is by doing this. In a civilised society, if you have gained and we have lost, surely we are entitled to say is there any way to alleviate the problems created. There is no way you can imagine that your community will just simply discover this, you've got to go out and tell them. Now its just an educational process for me. All these people are changed people who don't necessarily think just about themselves. It has all been a learning process and I think it has been for the good, and I believe that the fight is lost but a lot of learning went on. People like us will have to in the long term think about how we are going to change the situation.

A. How did you feel when the free state got involved?

W. Great, brilliant..it was a mastermove in terms of the overall arguments about the environment and the educational part of it. Our issue was dead..what happened there was magic ..because it hud tae happen. Colin came along and showed the will was still there. But maybe it distracted from our real arguments, and I think there would have been more chance of the politicians listening if our case had been the one that came to the fore. Our argument about the environment of Corkerhill, the state of the children, the 53 000 vehicles a day, the public enquiries decision that Corkerhill would lose out. All these things were the things that get to politicians. (The protest camp) gave the politicians a get out for their conscience,.....but I honestly believe that the message they gave to the world..was a stronger message than ours. Ours might have has the immediate result locally or to SRC it dosnae mean anything to the general world..in the long term all you would be being is selfish..and I wouldnae like to be a part of a community like that."

A. Do you think the community followed you with that message?

W. .I dont know, I've never met anyone who disnae agree with me about the motorway..sometimes people have got more to think about, but see in the main I know from meetings that in general terms yeah most people say Walters right. I would have to say that our community has followed us.

A. And what about those early months of 1995

W. I woke up at half-past four and police were all over Corkerhill. I jumped out of bed and took my loudhailer and went round the community at half past four, alerting the community, and I thought it was a mistake bit I done it. I heard murmuring against it but they didn't last long. When I looked back the biggest ever show of force in any part of the protest wasnae up at the camp, it was here in Corkerhill, and the reason was because of Corkerhills history. Often I've felt standing alone, but at other times well supported. That community oot there is a good community, they've got all the problems and they are no gonnae all have the commitment I've got. I'll protect my community. They had a new tactic, and that wis to come in at 4.30 wi fencing, 3/4 mile of fencing round Corkerhill. 300 police officers, a similar number of security guards, helicopters, the whole gambit of videos and all that. Because they expected that if they had no fences up the workmen would have been overrun. It has never been done before. Overwhelming power, early in the morning to cut off the people.

A. When you started saying, right we've got to think more globally, we've got look at better public transport, did the community go 'your right Walter its not just about us'?

W. Some groups take the view that direct action is needed but Glasgow for People felt that a positive alternative was needed. And the overall organisation had done things that were rubbing them up the wrang way. There a lot of things I could have said to the people of Corkerhill. Ours has always been the right-of-way, the health. It has always been very much the same the whole way..Anything else that developed was environmental education. In progressing the selfish angle it might have been offputting. We might have felt that if we continue the selfish angle we might have had more sympathy..but the camp was costing them money.

It only took the Labour council to change its mind. In terms of getting the decision reversed that was the only hope we had..that the Labour councillors would change their minds. I think we were more likely to get that with our approach than anyone elses.. But the possibility..it seems to me that in terms of getting the decision reversed that was the only real hope we had. Bearing in mind that SRC had their social strategy . They were saying that the strategy would be a failure if they created two communities instead of one.I was always hopeful that that would get through.

A. What about its effect on voting Walter, people still seem to be voting Labour?

W. This is a real problem, a small marginalised community like Corkerhill, pleading with everybody else outside when other areas also have problems. What choice have we got, what choice of candidates. We all no what calibre of councillors we have. I didnae vote for David Spaven. We had a powerful advocate in Jim Sillars, we voted for Brooks, and he done well here, a green party candidate. In terms of political parties, I've never been a member of a political party in my life. If you were to ask me were my allegiances lie I'd consider myself a socialist. In we regards to voting I've taken the view that any candidate should previously fulfil the request of the community, and then to consider what influence they would have on the city chambers, or in the house of commons. Now we've got a SNP councillor here and the big problem weve got is that he is so much in the minority that he cannae persuade they devils to do a certain thing, as long as they are democratic they are within their rights and that is the problem we face. Jim Sillars was in aminority party, Labour was in opposition. What we needed was a high profile member of parliament that was doing the same things that we were doing at the grassroots level. So in terms of the politics of it we have thought the politics out and we have to go for somebody high powered. I've become a wee bit more astute politically..the best of people get compromised. But that dosnae stop me shouting as loud as I can for the people of Corkerhill, because if we all dae the same thing for our communities then we'll be dain a good service.

A. Walter, it's been excellent talking to you, thanks very much for your time.

end

Further talk (26.10.96). Later that year Walter and I met up while I was out speaking to someone else in Corkerhill, he invited me back to the community shop where we began chatting about, amongst other things, the M77. I took this opportunity to ask him again about the events of March 1995 when the police 'invaded' Corkerhill.

W. What that was was a show of force by the state. I know what a plan is, I know the strategy and the feeling I got when I looked out my window, all I saw was a line of police vehicles stretching as far as the eye could see, and all the communicators going. I thought this is no real, this is how they see Corkerhill. And I'm convinced the reason for it was because of Corkerhill's reputation. This is an organised community. They immediately fanned out round all the houses, they were stopping people in the street. That must have taken a lot of expense. It was done

identical to any military manoeuvre. They've never done that before, they were armed with 3/4 of a mile of metal fences and that fencing was strung right across round the houses to the other side. Which meant, at a stroke, they fenced the whole area they were going to work in and they kept the people of Corkerhill out. The police surrounded the outside of the barriers, the security guards on the inside and at the same time the guys with the saws were doing their work. They had it surrounded, like a fort.

A. So you think it was show of strength by the state?

W. I spoke to Mr Pollard and to the Police and Robin Rankine and I said that was a real strategic move you came up with there, an excellent plan, because previously what had happened was that as soon as the community came up in numbers they could get in to the trees and the men, they had to physically surround the trees, but it was easy enough for people then to jump on a vehicle or on a tree. But because they fenced the area in they isolated us. There was two helicopters. I honestly think this was one time when instructions came from on high. Wimpey couldn't decide to do this, the whole machinery of government was turned on Corkerhill. I think that between the police and the security guards they numbered us man for man.

A. How do you feel about the use of the police in that manner?

W. I always take the view that the police are doing the job they're paid to do and on that day they done a perfect job. I think it would be true to say that with the emotions within the community, and it was displayed around the fences, there was the possibility someone would get hurt. But having said that, the lengths they will go to to impose a motorway on a local community. The point surely, let nobody claim that the people of Corkerhill gladly accepted the M77. They were subdued with an imposition and a strategy that's been organised right from the top, right down with military precision. And the fact that no one was hurt, that doesn't take away from the shame that should be attached to SRC. Cause at the end of the day, I say this even now, that they should be ashamed because they surrendered their own people, the people they were supposed to protect, in terms of promoting positive discrimination. And the fact that it was done with that, it shows you that even a Labour council is prepared to do to its own people. OK some might argue for the greater good but people are saying that something that stinks has happened in Corkerhill.

A. Who do you blame, if anyone?

W. I would have to say SRC..to make you understand, I vote for people who at least I try to find out if they can be trusted, they're asking for my vote and I'm asking them for trust. And they wrote documents like the social strategy for the 90s to promote positive discrimination, so when I go and place my vote that's supposed to help or my children I don't expect them to run away.. They made all the promises, they were making the same promises in every document about how they they were prepared to discriminate in favour of at risk areas. Now at the end of the day when it came to it, it's not as if I didn't sit at the Pi and give them plenty of opportunity to state their case. I gave them it and I stated my case against these people I trusted. We proved we are an area of deprivation even to the extent that it is in the findings. Even when they had that in front of them they were able to look and say here is what's happening in these areas and we've made all these promises and all it takes is us to say well because of what's happening we're not going to do this. At least I could have stood aside and allow somebody else to do it. I never, during the war, expected my mates to change sides. I understand them now but I would have to say that it is a shame on that council.

A. You talk about them and us..

W. Why should it be them and us? The guy who was the leader was a friend of mine since he was a wee boy. Ach I don't know, them could come from anywhere. We talk about them, my son he calls them the invisibles...where do you draw the line. I think in a lot of ways it comes down to

them and us, I talk about social apartheid and it clear over there, if that happened in South Africa, if they cleared the people out and did what they did we'd all be up in arms and we went through that for twenty years. So we've had this battle all the time but if you understood me really I cannae accept that there is an insurmountable barrier between them and us, I dont see it, and I'm prepared to try and find a ways to them. In politics, apart from class, there is still some form of class differences, but I'm not going against the idea of trying to find a way into them, even by compromise and steady approaches.

A. You must feel part of something?

W. I'd have to start from the bottom, politics, seeing the conflict thats going on. I'm a trade unionist and a socialist. I think I'm a humanist, its difficult to categorise yourself.. But more than anything else as soon as the lines are drawn I think I would have to go with us rather than them. If there is going to be a battle. Everything I do, its in my nature. One of the worst things you can do is sit about and wait till something happens so that you can react to it., yuu always try to think ahead. At the same time and ideas that seem to be working try and expand them, bring in other people extend you community outwards. Cause as soon as you turn in you startt battling wi yourself. Thats what I was always worried about wi STARR. I always had the feeling that the worse they can do is sit doon and discuss strategies. The best thin to do is get something going and then bring in other folk. I dont believe you shuld sit about contemplating you own navel. W've got to try and find the best of both worlds.. Thats what annoys me, there was a lot of them councillors there and if I put the blame on them thats why I do it, cause they surrendered their principles. There is times and places for the greayter good, the choices are who to sacrifice. The reason I'm a socialist is because I'm no prepared to sacrifice the wee man. If there's a differencve, who your prepared to sacrifice, and it often come down to that. Who's prepared to sacrifice who, and who's to be sacrificed, the golfers or the people of Corkerhill. The people of Corkerhill are the easiest opponents cause they're only a wee small community. But thats why you vote labour, in order that they protect you..

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